

**EXPLORING A STRATEGIC TEACHERS' BRAIN-
BASED INSTRUCTION FOR SMALL-CLAIMS
COURT INTERPRETATION: A CASE STUDY IN
JORDAN**

**MOHAMMED YAHYA ABDUL RAHMAN ABU
RISHA**

UNIVERSITI SAINS MALAYSIA

2025

**EXPLORING A STRATEGIC TEACHERS' BRAIN-
BASED INSTRUCTION FOR SMALL-CLAIMS
COURT INTERPRETATION: A CASE STUDY IN
JORDAN**

by

**MOHAMMED YAHYA ABDUL RAHMAN ABU
RISHA**

**Thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Interpreting**

June 2025

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This academic journey has traversed several stages of research and investigation in the quest for truth within a knowledge domain closely tied to the just appointment and proper academic training of court interpreters. This endeavour culminated in the development of a model for this field. Such progress would not have been possible without the wise guidance of Dr Paramaswari Jaganathan, the supervisor of this research. Your insightful comments and patient oversight have been instrumental in completing this work. My gratitude extends to Nihad Kanaan for her dedication time in conducting the training under this study. I also thank Taroub Al Aref, Vicky Ayoub, Hamada, Ahmed Magraalneel, Hamidou Saleh, Alaa Ahmad, Zainab Khadouri, and Mohammed Odeh for their illuminating feedback. Sincere thanks go to Lubna Al Thaher for the insightful discussions on scientific research. Heartfelt thanks and recognition go to my family, who supported me throughout these years—my mother, brother, sisters, uncles, and aunts. You have my deepest gratitude and appreciation. Lastly, and by no means least, I extend my profound thanks and love to my life partner and wife, Eman, and to my son Yahya and my daughters Judy and Joanna.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	ii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	iii
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF FIGURES	x
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xii
LIST OF APPENDICES	xiii
ABSTRAK	xiv
ABSTRACT	xvi
CHAPTER 1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.1.1 Jordan’s court system.....	4
1.1.2 Roles and qualities of judges in Jordan.....	4
1.1.3 Court interpreting worldwide.....	5
1.1.4 Court interpreting regulatory framework in Jordan	8
1.1.5 Learning court interpreting in Jordan.....	9
1.2 Problem statement.....	11
1.3 Significance of study.....	16
1.4 Research Objectives	18
1.5 Research Questions	18
1.6 Limitations	19
CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW	21
2.1 Introduction	21
2.2 Historical overview of Interpreting.....	21
2.3 Court interpreting	25
2.3.1 Court interpreting competence.....	29

2.3.2	Court interpreters' knowledge.....	30
2.3.3	Court interpreters' skills.....	36
2.4	Approaches to teaching interpreting	39
2.4.1	The apprenticeship model	39
2.4.2	The discourse analysis approach	40
2.4.3	The error analysis approach	40
2.4.4	The experiential learning approach	41
2.5	Court interpreters' training curricula.....	42
2.6	Defining curriculum	44
2.7	Models of curriculum design.....	46
2.7.1	Tyler's Model.....	46
2.7.2	Taba's model.....	47
2.7.3	Wheeler's model	48
2.8	Defining learning objectives	48
2.9	Bloom's taxonomy of learning objectives	50
2.10	Brain-based education	51
2.10.1	Perspectives from psychology and neuroscience	53
2.10.2	Neuroscience and bilingualism	56
2.10.3	Neuroscience of education	56
2.10.4	Functions of brain regions.....	59
2.10.5	Human memory.....	61
2.10.6	The AGES model	63
	2.10.6(a) Attention	64
	2.10.6(b) Generation.....	67
	2.10.6(c) Emotions.....	68
	2.10.6(d) Spacing	71
2.11	Learning styles	73

2.11.1	The Experiential Learning Style	73
2.11.2	Honey and Mumford's Learning Styles.....	74
2.11.3	Fedler and Silverman's Learning Styles	74
2.11.4	Criticism of learning styles theories.....	75
2.11.5	Research on Jordan students' learning styles.....	76
2.12	Models of Brain Based Learning	77
2.12.1	The Twelve Principles of Brain-Based Learning.....	77
2.12.2	The BRAIN model	80
2.12.3	The Strategic Teachers' Model	81
	2.12.3(a) The Mastery Style.....	82
	2.12.3(b) Understanding Style.....	83
	2.12.3(c) Self-Expressive Style.....	83
	2.12.3(d) The Interpersonal Style.....	83
2.13	Summary	89
2.14	The Conceptual Framework of Study	91
	CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY.....	95
3.1	Introduction	95
3.2	Research design.....	96
	3.2.1 Qualitative research.....	96
	3.2.2 Exploratory case study	98
3.3	Sampling.....	100
3.4	The participants	100
	3.4.1 Roles and responsibilities.....	100
	3.4.2 Inclusion criteria.....	101
3.5	Sample size.....	101
3.6	Recruitment process	102
3.7	Ethical considerations	102

3.8	Data collection.....	104
3.8.1	Semi-structured interviews.....	104
3.8.2	Observation	106
3.9	Instruments of the study	108
3.9.1	Semi-structured interview guide	108
3.9.2	Observation sheet	109
3.9.3	Zoom platform.....	110
3.9.4	Audio and audio-video production software.....	110
3.10	Developing the training material.....	111
3.10.1	Research and Development Model	111
3.10.1(a)	Research and information collection	113
3.10.1(b)	Planning	114
3.10.1(c)	Developing a preliminary form of product.....	114
3.10.1(d)	Developing the visuals and audio-visual components	118
3.10.1(e)	Developing the training material (PowerPoint).....	121
3.10.1(f)	Preliminary field testing (1) and revising main product	125
3.10.1(g)	Preliminary field testing (2) and revising main product	129
3.10.1(h)	Main field testing.....	132
3.10.1(i)	Case study.....	133
3.10.1(j)	Revising the final product.....	133
3.11	Observation	134
3.12	Research bias.....	135
3.13	Results of the pilot study.....	136
3.13.1	Sequencing of learning.....	140
3.13.2	Attention.....	141

3.13.3	Generation	146
3.13.4	Emotions	155
3.13.5	Spacing	166
3.14	Remarks on the material and trainer	172
CHAPTER 4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION		173
4.1	Introduction	173
4.1.1	Situational knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan	176
4.1.2	Procedural knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan	177
4.1.3	Conceptual knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan	181
4.1.3(a)	Domain knowledge	181
4.1.3(b)	Case-specific knowledge	182
4.1.3(c)	Legal knowledge	183
4.2	Discussion of the semi-structured interview results	184
4.2.1(a)	Domain knowledge	185
4.2.1(b)	Legal knowledge	187
4.2.1(c)	Procedural knowledge	190
4.3	Results of case study	193
4.3.1	Overview	193
4.3.2	General impressions of trainees	194
4.3.3	Attention	195
4.3.4	Generation	198
4.3.5	Emotions	200
4.3.5(a)	Reward and self-confidence	200
4.3.5(b)	Frustration and boredom	201
4.3.6	Spacing	203
4.4	Summary of findings	205
4.5	Discussion of case study findings	208

4.5.1	Overview of the findings.....	209
4.5.2	A brain-based SCCI training.....	213
CHAPTER 5 CONCLUSION.....		218
5.1	Introduction.....	218
5.2	Research contribution.....	225
5.2.1	Hypothesized Foundational Pillars of the Adapted AGES-STM Framework.....	226
5.2.2	Hypothesized Role of Emotional Centrality and Neurochemical Regulation.....	226
5.2.3	Hypothesized Role of STM strategies (STM adaptation).....	229
5.3	Implications to policy makers.....	231
5.4	Implications for SCI training institutions.....	233
5.4.1	Venue.....	233
5.4.2	Qualification of trainers.....	234
5.5	Implications for SCCI curriculum designers.....	236
REFERENCES.....		239
APPENDICES		
LIST OF PUBLICATIONS		

LIST OF TABLES

	Page
Table 1.1	Universities offering court interpreting courses..... 10
Table 3.1	Participants recruitment and inclusion criteria..... 101
Table 3.2	Interview questions 108
Table 3.3	Observation Guide 109
Table 3.4	List of activities..... 112
Table 3.5	Alienation and proximity in videos..... 121
Table 3.6	Hedges against bias 136
Table 4.1	Emerging themes..... 175

LIST OF FIGURES

		Page
Figure 2.1	The Strategic Teachers’ Model (Silver, Strong & Perini, 2007).....	82
Figure 2.2	Conceptual framework of study	94
Figure 3.1	Phases of study	95
Figure 3.2	RND Steps adapted from (Borg, Gall & Gall, 2003).....	112
Figure 3.3	Phase (1)- Defining the SCCI knowledge content	113
Figure 3.4	Phase (2)- Defining the hierarchy of knowledge content.....	114
Figure 3.5	A translation into English of a sample page listing TLO1 and its ELOs	115
Figure 3.6	A translation into English of a sample page listing ELO1.3 and its LPs	116
Figure 3.7	Translation of a sample LP (LP 1.6. Small-claims courts)	118
Figure 3.8	Title slide in the training material (the PowerPoint).....	121
Figure 3.9	Examples of hooks used in the training material	122
Figure 3.10	Examples of trainer’s instructions on kindling and bridging	123
Figure 3.11	Using static pictures to reduce words.....	123
Figure 3.12	Three-level videos inserted in a slide.....	123
Figure 3.13	A visual about disputants’ logic using a compare-contrast hook.....	124
Figure 3.14	Sample Journal Entry by ST1	140
Figure 3.15	Graduated difficulty strategy levels	161
Figure 3.16	Levels of difficulty discerned from the Pilot	164
Figure 4.1	Students constructing knowledge.....	209
Figure 5.1	The AGES-STM Hypothesis	227
Figure 5.2	Policy making cycle for SCCI professionalization in Jordan	232

Figure 5.3 Skeleton of the training course.....237

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Attention, Generation, Emotion and Spacing
BBL	Brain-Based Learning
CI	Consecutive Interpreting
CIC	Court Interpreting Curriculum
ELO	Enabling Learning Objective
ExGr	Expert Group
PrGr	Professional Group
SCC	Small Claims Court
SCCI	Small Claims Court Interpreting
ST	Student (enrolled in case-study trainings)
TLO	Terminal Learning Objective

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix A	The four styles of learning as used in this study
Appendix B	Plan for Jordan SCCI training
Appendix C	Brainstorming sessions
Appendix D	Demographics of the participants
Appendix E	Sample observation sheet
Appendix F	Contents of the training material distributed among the lectures
Appendix G	The contents of the training videos used in the case study

**MENEROKAI STRATEGI PENGAJARAN GURU BERASASKAN
OTAK DALAM INTERPRETASI TUNTUTAN KECIL DI MAHKAMAH:
SATU KAJIAN KES DI JORDAN**

ABSTRAK

Peranan jurubahasa mahkamah amat penting dalam memastikan keadilan dalam persekitaran perundangan dwibahasa. Walaupun banyak negara telah menetapkan piawaian profesional dan rangka kerja undang-undang bagi bidang jurubahasa mahkamah, sistem peraturan di Jordan masih kurang berkembang, dan kajian akademik dalam bidang ini masih terhad. Kajian ini meneroka pengetahuan konseptual, prosedural, dan situasional yang diperlukan oleh jurubahasa mahkamah tuntutan kecil (SCCI) di Jordan. Ia turut memperkenalkan modul latihan inovatif yang direka untuk menyampaikan pengetahuan tersebut kepada pelajar jurubahasa. Kajian ini menggunakan reka bentuk kualitatif dan berpaksikan dua rangka kerja teori: model AGES dari bidang neurosains dan Model Guru Strategik (STM) daripada pendidikan berasaskan otak. Data dikumpulkan melalui temu bual separa berstruktur secara mendalam dengan jurubahasa yang sedang berkhidmat serta satu kajian kes yang melibatkan sesi latihan dan penterjemahan. Model AGES digunakan untuk menilai hasil pembelajaran dari perspektif neurosains. Berdasarkan dapatan, kajian ini mencadangkan hipotesis tentang keberkesanan model AGES-STM bersepadu dalam melatih jurubahasa SCCI di Jordan. Pendekatan antara disiplin ini menyumbang kepada pendidikan jurubahasa dengan menyelaraskan sains kognitif dengan strategi pedagogi. Kajian ini memberikan implikasi kepada program latihan jurubahasa, pendidikan tinggi, dan pembangunan dasar, serta menyokong pemerkasaan

profesionalisme dalam bidang jurubahasa mahkamah dan peningkatan mutu keadilan dalam bilik mahkamah pelbagai bahasa.

**EXPLORING A STRATEGIC TEACHERS' BRAIN-BASED INSTRUCTION
FOR SMALL-CLAIMS COURT INTERPRETATION IN JORDAN**

ABSTRACT

The role of court interpreters is crucial in ensuring justice in bilingual legal settings. While many countries have established professional standards and legal frameworks for court interpreting, Jordan's regulatory system remains underdeveloped, and scholarly research in this area is limited. This study explores the conceptual, procedural, and situational knowledge required by small-claims court interpreters (SCCI) in Jordan. It also introduces an innovative training module designed to impart this knowledge to interpreting students. The research adopts a qualitative design and is grounded in two theoretical frameworks: the AGES model from neuroscience and the Strategic Teachers' Model (STM) from brain-based education. Data were collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews with practicing interpreters and observation of a case study that captured training and interpreting sessions. The AGES model was applied to assess learning outcomes from a neuroscience-informed perspective. Based on the findings, the study proposes a hypothetical model regarding the effectiveness of an integrated AGES-STM model in training SCCIs in Jordan. This interdisciplinary approach contributes to interpreter education by aligning cognitive science with pedagogical strategies. The study offers implications for interpreter training programs, higher education, and policy development, supporting the professionalization of court interpreting and advancing the quality of justice in multilingual courtrooms.

CHAPTER 1

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

1.1 Introduction

Deep within the maze of the human brain, the basal ganglia orchestrate our habits (Mullins, 2025), the amygdala pulses with emotional resonance (Lalit & Singh, 2025) and the hippocampus weaves the tapestry of memory—each a cornerstone of how humans learn (Hake, 2024). Yet, sceptics argue that simply mapping these neural territories offers little more than a seductive illusion of understanding, dismissing neuroscience as pseudoscience that leans on brain scans to dazzle rather than enlighten. They warn of the "seductive allure effect," where glossy fMRI images overshadow flawed arguments, reducing complex learning to mere biological buzzwords (Nuccio & Wesselmann, 2024). But to discard neuroscience's insights is to ignore a revolution: learning is no longer seen as behavioural conditioning but as the dynamic remodelling or 'changing' of the brain itself (Sousa, 2022). The real challenge lies not in debating its validity but in translating these discoveries into classrooms where instruction aligns with the brain's natural rhythms—transforming pedagogy from guesswork into a science of possibility (Amran & Sommer, 2024). How, then, do we bridge the gap between the promise of neuroscience and the pragmatism of education? The answer may redefine what it means to truly teach, and to truly learn.

The goal of this study is to explore the implications of neuroscience and brain-based learning in the design and delivery of training for small-claims court interpreting for Jordanian students. However, the title of this thesis prompts numerous inquiries spanning various academic disciplines, each of which could serve as a distinct focus for scholarly exploration. These disciplines—law, neuroscience, and education—are interwoven in this study to provide

a framework for the design of court interpreting instruction. This chapter, therefore, aims to establish the context and rationale for the study, laying the groundwork for a focused investigation into the teaching of court interpreting in Jordan, using it as a case study. Specifically, it examines the Jordanian legal system with a focus on court interpreting and the role of court interpreters in small claims courts (SCCs). The chapter also reviews existing frameworks for training court interpreters in Jordan, analysing how interpreters are prepared for the labour market. In doing so, this chapter not only situates the study within its broader context but also underscores the need for an innovative approach to training interpreters for court settings.

Court interpreting is a recognized complex cognitive skill, requiring interpreters to dynamically receive, process, encode, and decode information while rendering accurate and neutral interpretations in high-stakes legal settings. Such cognitive demands highlight the critical need for training programs that explicitly address these challenges through pedagogically sound and scientifically grounded approaches. In recent years, brain-based education—a framework informed by neuroscience principles—has emerged as a compelling paradigm for optimizing learning processes by aligning training design with how the brain acquires, retains, and applies knowledge.

However, translating neuroscientific insights into practical pedagogical strategies remains under-investigated. While foundational principles of brain-based learning provide essential guidance, their effective application requires structured models to bridge theory and practice. This study integrates two frameworks to address this gap: the AGES model (Attention, Generation of connections, Emotion regulation and Spacing) and the Strategic Teachers' Model in education. The AGES model, rooted in neuroscience, prioritizes four pillars for enhancing memory retention and skill acquisition: sustaining learner attention, fostering active neural

connection-building, managing emotional states to reduce cognitive interference, and spacing instruction to reinforce long-term retention. Complementing this, the Strategic Teachers' Model (Silver, Strong, & Perini, 2007) emphasizes pedagogical adaptability, advocating for the integration of diverse instructional methods to accommodate learners' varied preferences and needs.

By synthesizing these frameworks, this research proposes a holistic approach to court interpreter education—one that harmonizes insights from neuroscience and pedagogical theory. Such an approach aims to optimize training design by addressing the multidimensional demands of the profession: cognitive (e.g., information processing under pressure), emotional (e.g., feeling of reward, punishment and frustration), and practical (e.g., adaptability to diverse courtroom scenarios). Ultimately, this integration seeks to equip interpreters with the skills and resilience necessary to excel in their critical societal role.

The following sections provide details about the current legal and educational settings of court interpreting in Jordan to highlight the research problem.

1.1. Legal framework

Court interpreting occurs within legal environments, where court interpreters are bound by specific regulations governing the performance of their duties in judicial proceedings. This discussion outlines the structure of Jordan's court system, examines the qualities of judges with whom interpreters must engage, and provides a comparative analysis of court interpreting practices globally, with a particular focus on the context in Jordan.

1.1.1 Jordan's court system

The Jordanian constitution of 1952 classifies courts according to subject-matter jurisdiction and degree. Regular courts consist of civil and criminal courts, whilst Sharia courts and special tribunals treat marriage and other religiously based family issues. Courts are divided into two tiers of litigation: first instance and second instance, with the court of cassation acting as the review court of last resort. The lower courts are either conciliation or courts of first instance, whereas the supreme courts are the Appeals Court and the Cassation Court. Each court has its subject-matter, geographical coverage and value jurisdiction defined by the law. A case where the claimed amount is less than 10,000 Jordanian Dinars is heard at the Reconciliation Court. In 2018, Jordan's legislature adopted the small-claims arrangements, which adjudicates claims of up to 3,000 Jordanian Dinars utilizing streamlined procedures to reduce the duration of litigation. Small claims are also heard by civil courts of conciliation (MoJ, 2019).

1.1.2 Roles and qualities of judges in Jordan

Court interpreters communicate directly with judges during legal proceedings, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of the judicial role (Markic & Gersak, 2017). A judge in Jordan presides over the proceeding, hears the case, establishes the legal relationship between the litigants and applies the law to reach a decision. The qualities of judges are provided by the Code of Judicial Practice of 2021, issued in accordance with Article 43(d) of the Judicial Independence Law No. 29 of 2014. Professional judicial practices include independence and neutrality, even in daily life, avoidance of conflict of interests, refraining from leaning to their personal or subjective tendencies, coping with judicial and scientific developments, and putting on professional attire. In civil cases, Judges apply the applicable law on each case and follow the Civil Procedural Law No. 16 of 2006, as amended. When hearing a civil case, the judge applies the Civil Code of 1976 to consider which source of rights applies

to establish a legal relationship between a plaintiff and a defendant: (i) the law, (ii) contract, (iii) beneficial act (undue enrichment), (iv) harmful act (tort) and (v) unilateral will.

1.1.3 Court interpreting worldwide

The legal framework governing court interpreting in Jordan may be more comprehensively understood when analysed within a comparative framework, considering relevant practices in other Arab countries and beyond.

In the United States, the US Act of Interpreters of 1978 provides for interpreters to litigants who do not speak English to put them on an equal footing with English speakers (Baker & Saldanha, 2019). In Arizona, the Code of Conduct for Court interpreters provides for the professional standards including competence, impartiality, confidentiality, professionalism and continuing education. Generally, US courts recognise the complexity of court interpreting, thus requiring rigid certification exams to test their knowledge, skills and abilities (United States Courts, n.d.). Recently, the Maricopa County Superior Court in Arizona appointed Zainab Khadouri, a certified and professional Arabic court interpreter, as a staff interpreter in a U.S. court (Casey, 2023). This is the first time that an interpreter is appointed for a fulltime job at US courts. US courts consider the interpreter as a language conduit where interpreters interpret in an objective mechanic way (Morris, 1995), though confrontation with interpreters has been long debated especially after Crawford v. Washington (Benoit, 2014) and United States v. Yurofsky (Klubok, 2015).

In the United Kingdom, courts outsource interpreters from the Big Word. Interpreters working for the Criminal Justice System, however, must be enrolled in the National Register of Public Service Interpreters (NRPSI). Interpreters in the United Kingdom can be confronted at

court, should a defendant contest to the accuracy of interpreting (The Crown Prosecution Service, 2019).

In Oman, the Civil and Trade Procedural Law No. 101 of 1996 provides that “courts may hear the statements of litigants or testimonies of witness who do not speak Arabic through an interpreter after taking the statutory oath” (Article 27). Oman has a pool of interpreters employed by the court system as full-time employees. Their roles include both written translation and interpreting. There is no code of conduct for court interpreters nor a certification program to ensure the qualification of candidates for this job. The role of court interpreter is unclear (Issaei, 2007). Translators who perform translation under oath will be subject to imprisonment penalties under the ‘false witness’ provisions, if they intentionally distort truth in translation (Criminal Procedure Law No 97/99). It is not clear in the law whether an interpreter is a language conduit or a witness, though. Noteworthy is that the Omani Supreme Court allowed for the confrontation of an interpreter to make a testimony related to the accused as per Decision No. 304 on Appeal 282/2004.

In Tunisia, the interpreters’ profession is regulated by the Law of Regulating the Profession of Sworn Translators No 80 of 1994. The law provides for the qualification and certification requirements of sworn translators and interpreters to be enrolled in the registry and designates them as ‘para-public servants’. There is also the *Handbook for the Sworn Translator Procedures* issued by Minister of Justice’s Decree on 27/11/1998 that details the professional aspects of the career, including wages and disciplinary measures. The handbook mandates that registered translators/interpreters may not decline an assignment, except with a legally accepted excuse, such as conflict of interest. It also provides for civil liability if they commit an error

that causes harm to a third party, and criminal liability should they knowingly present a false translation or interpretation that does not match the original text.

In Algeria, the legislature regulates the profession of translators and interpreters under Presidential Decree No. 95 of 1995. The decree details the responsibilities and rights of translators and interpreters, designating them as ‘public officers’. Regulated aspects include the certification of translators and interpreters, their business attire, neutrality, confidentiality, and wages. In addition, the decree states that the translator or interpreter will be subject to criminal liability of perjury should the translation or interpretation they render proves to be intentionally false.

In Morocco, Law by decree No. 50 of 2001 on Translators and Interpreters Admitted to Courts regulates the profession, certification, rights and responsibilities as well as disciplinary measures of court translators and interpreters, designating them as ‘judicial assistants’. In contrast, a written translator of a contract is deemed as a witness ("Decision on civil file No. 2016/9/1/4276," 2016).

In Syria, Law No. 22 of 2014 on Sworn Translators regulates the certification of sworn translators, who, upon satisfying the requirements are entered into the registry of sworn translators. The law allows, though, courts to seek assistance from unregistered interpreters in case of necessity and it allows the court as well to use relay-translation through more than one interpreter. The law also prescribes an imprisonment penalty combined with a fine to be imposed on any sworn translator who deliberately ‘changed the truth’ or disclosed a secret brought to his attention while performing translation or interpreting.

1.1.4 Court interpreting regulatory framework in Jordan

Unlike the jurisdictions reviewed above, there is no standalone regulation for interpreters in Jordan. Interpreters are assigned to cases where any of the parties do not speak Arabic (The Mecella, Article 1825) and what the interpreter relays is deemed representative of what the original speaker has said (The Mecella, Article 71) so long as he takes the oath (Civil Code of Jordan, Article 84). The role of the court interpreter is that of a language conduit, following the Hanafi jurisprudence, meaning that a single interpreter, male or female, may be appointed (Al Zuhaili, 2006). This contrasts with the Shafiite school, deeming interpreter a witness (Al Mawardi, 1999). If an interpreter is considered a witness following the Shafiite school, then some rules apply including, for example, the prohibition of an interpreter (being a witness) to interpret for a first-degree relative (Al Mawardi, 1999). Invoking different schools of jurisdictions can cause controversies even at court (such as in Aqaba Appeal No. 211/2018 where the appellant objected to the application of principles from the Shafiite and Hanbali schools), but it is yet not clearly debated in research in Jordan. In relation to small claims, Jordan's legislator intended the small-claims arrangements at courts to expedite adjudication. The use of non-professional interpreters has already proven to cause delays in adjudication (Tampubolon, 2024), which implies that the lack of a professional interpreter at a small-claim hearing can be counter to the reason why such arrangements have been created in the first place.

In a broad scope, translation and interpreting firms are regulated and licensed by the Publication and Press Law of 1998, requiring the incorporators to produce identification cards and certificates of non-conviction, qualification proofs, experience, and payment of fees. If a written document is to be official, it must be notarised by the notary public as per the Notary Public Law No. 11 of 1952, in which case the translator is required to be of sound mind and

legal age. However, legislation uses the terms *translator* and *interpreter* interchangeably, unless the context explicitly differentiates between the two. Consequently, there is no specific law or regulation that could otherwise outline the role, qualifications, certification, or appointment procedures for interpreters, especially those serving in court settings.

The only legal framework governing court interpreters is found in the Bylaws of Experts Appearing before Regular Courts No. 35 of 2018. Interpreters appointed for court proceedings are conduits, so interpreting errors, even when detected, cannot be contested or cited as grounds of appeal, and cannot be confronted (Abu-Risha & Jaganathan, 2021). Interpreters, in their capacities as experts, rather than sworn or accredited interpreters, are subject to generalised expert recruitment requirements. The minimum requirements, per the bylaws, are no prior convictions, good morals, an academic qualification or experience, and neutrality. Education is not required, but conflicts of interest must be disclosed at court. The bylaws do not specify the consequences of court interpreting mistakes. There are no guidelines that specify whether the interpreter's rendering at court may be contested if the interpreter has violated any interpreter's code of conduct. In line with the bylaws, the Ministry of Justice offers the service of pooling experts including interpreters. The portal shows the requirements, which are educational background, proof of experience and a certificate of non-conviction. Since educational background is not required for court interpreters in Jordan, it is worthwhile to review possible local avenues for learning the profession.

1.1.5 Learning court interpreting in Jordan

In the absence of primary sources, the study conducted preliminary research, in the websites of ministries, revealing three potential sources of learning court interpreting: higher educational institutions, vocational training schools and Ministry of Labor's employment

programs. The Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE) and the Accreditation and Quality Assurance Commission for Higher Education Institutions (HEAC) oversee higher education institutions and approve university offerings. HEAC decides on new programs according to several factors, including justification, solvency, efficient infrastructure and the appointment of teaching staff with different ranks. A university’s request may be denied if the proposed program is either stagnant or saturated in the labour market (MoHE, 2022). Foreign languages and translation in Jordan are among the ‘saturated’ jobs (MoHE, 2023), as Jordanian authorities encourage school graduates to pursue high-demand vocations instead.

As of 2024, there are 34 universities in Jordan (MoHE 2024), out of which 11 offer degrees in translation (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1 Universities offering court interpreting courses

University	Does it offer court interpreting courses?	Name of course
Muta University	Yes	Simultaneous conference and court interpreting
Yarmouk University	Yes	Court interpreting
Amman Arab University	No	
Jadara University		
Amman Ahliyya University		
Petra University		
Isra University		
Applied Sciences University		
Irbid University		
Jarash University		
The American University		

Vocational education is another possible venue to provide learners with specialized skills and knowledge aligned with the labour market (UNESCO, 2022). Vocational training is offered by the Vocational Training Corporation (VTC) in fields, in accordance with the Law No. 11 of 1985. VTC, however, does not offer any translation/interpreting training. In contrast, the Ministry of Labour through the National Employment Program of 2021 (MoL, 2023), subsidized wages for on-the-job training of employees in the age group of 18-40. It allows for translators/interpreters internships but no statistics are available on that issue.

1.2 Problem statement

In Jordan, the primary requirement for court interpreters is the ability to speak Arabic and a foreign language. This criterion, however, fails to capture the full scope of competencies needed for effective court interpreting. Moreover, there is a significant gap in empirical research concerning the knowledge of court interpreters in Jordan, and a lack of a scientifically grounded instructional framework to align interpreter training with real-life court settings. While bilingualism is undeniably essential for court interpreting, the mere ability to speak languages does not guarantee an accurate and reliable interpreting (Mulwa & Mabule, 2023). This concern is already echoed in research. Internationally, the scarcity of trained interpreters often leads to the recognition of interpreters as "qualified" as long as they are punctual and capable of basic communication in the courtroom (Romberger, 2007). However, a judge's confidence in an interpreter's performance is often undisturbed if the judge does not speak the foreign language, potentially leading to over-reliance on interpreters without assessing their competence (Bestue and Raigal-Aran (2023); Pym (2025)). This highlights a critical issue: the professionalization of court interpreters is inextricably linked to specialized professional knowledge, not confined to linguistic proficiency but involving an understanding of legal language and courtroom

pragmatics (Kadric & Stempkowski, 2024). Interpreters must demonstrate cognitive abilities, as interpreting under fast-paced conditions can challenge note-taking practices and interfere with effective listening (González, Vásquez, & Mikkelson, 1991). Errors in interpreting can lead to misinterpretations, mislead juries and distort justice (Hovland, 1992). Historical examples, such as the case of a man allegedly marrying the wrong woman due to an interpreter's incompetence ("Keystone Vignettes," 1894), or the disastrous misinterpretation of "blouse" as "brief blouse" in a rape trial (Shepard, 2007), underscore the profound consequences of poor interpretation.

The professionalization of court interpreters demands the ability to mitigate errors, which, if left unaddressed, can affect the outcomes of thousands of cases (Bowcott, 2016). This professional competence can only be achieved through systematic training that emphasizes both language skills and real-world court experience, along with an understanding of grammar, semantics, pragmatics, and the cognitive processes involved in interpreting (Yi, 2024). Recent advances in neuroscience also suggest that brain-related skills, such as attention, focus, and memory, are crucial for interpreting training (Díaz-Galaz & Winston, 2025). These findings highlight the growing need for educational approaches that incorporate brain-based insights into interpreting practice. The adoption of a brain-based learning (BBL) approach is particularly salient in this context, as it aligns with neuroscientific principles that optimize the cognitive, emotional, and procedural demands of court interpreting. Traditional pedagogical methods, which prioritize passive knowledge transfer (Brown, Roediger, & McDaniel, 2014), inadequately equip learners with critical thinking and adaptive skills required in real-world contexts. As Hale (2004) and Mikkelson (2017) emphasize, courtroom discourse demands rapid decision-making, cultural competence, and adaptability to unpredictable interactions—skills

that are best cultivated through immersive, context-driven training rather than static, theory-heavy approaches. BBL leverages evidence-based strategies—such as spaced repetition (Brown, Roediger, & McDaniel, 2014), multimodal engagement (R. Mayer, 2009) and metacognitive reflection (Pratama, Lustyantje, & Murtadho, 2024)—to enhance neurocognitive adaptability and long-term retention by aligning with the brain’s natural learning mechanisms. This is critical for mastering the linguistic, cultural, and procedural complexities of court interpreting, which require rapid bilingual lexical retrieval, simultaneous information processing, and ethical decision-making under pressure—skills inherently tied to neural plasticity and executive functioning (Pliatsikas, 2020). By integrating BBL, interpreter training can address Jordan’s systemic gaps in specialized education while aligning with broader educational reforms aimed at fostering 21st-century competencies. Furthermore, BBL’s emphasis on sociocultural and cognitive inclusivity resonates with Jordan’s bilingual legal environment, where interpreters mediate between Arabic/English frameworks and ensure equitable access to justice. Yet, scholarly work in Jordan lacks focus on a BBL instructional design for court interpreters.

Scholarly consensus indicates that interpreters should continuously enhance their proficiency, with a particular focus on authentic interpreting activities (Setton & Dawrant, 2016). A thorough understanding of legal terminology, grammar, idioms, and formal writing styles is essential (Berk-Seligson, 2017), as well as a foundational knowledge of court procedures (UK Ministry of Justice, 2018). Extensive legal knowledge can also be necessary in some cases (Orozco-Jutorán, 2023) to effectively convey legal concepts, thus necessitating court interpreters to possess, among other things, a comprehensive grasp of courtroom procedures (Berk-Seligson, 2017). The significant number of appeals arising from inadequate

interpreter performance further emphasizes the necessity of specialized training for court interpreters (Hayes & Hale, 2010). To bridge the gap in competency, interpreters must adhere to codes of ethics that stress accuracy, professionalism, and integrity (Salimbene, 1996). In many countries, including the United States, Oman, Poland, and Australia, court interpreters are subject to certification and regulation (Palma, 2023).

Against this backdrop, Jordan falls short, with no specific regulations governing court interpreters or their qualifications. The legal ambiguity surrounding the role and qualifications of court interpreters in Jordan is exacerbated by the absence of defined standards for their training. While the Bylaws on Experts Appearing before Regular Courts (2018) specify certain fields of expertise, including translators and interpreters, they do not elaborate on the qualifications necessary for these roles. Historically, Jordan's laws, such as the Notary Public Law of 1946 and the current Notary Public Law of 1952, have allowed for the appointment of illiterate interpreters, further illustrating the lack of regulatory oversight.

Moreover, educational institutions in Jordan provide limited attention to the training of court interpreters. Translation departments at universities often lack a structured curriculum for court interpreting, with instructors not required to use specific teaching materials (Suleiman Al Abbas, personal communication, 2023). Authentic, real-life materials—essential for effective court interpreting instruction—are rarely incorporated (Hunt-Gómez, 2015). Apprenticeship models could offer an alternative approach, where novices learn by mimicking experienced professionals (Stern & Liu, 2019b). The Ministry of Labor's apprenticeship program (MoL, 2023) may serve as a useful framework, yet statistics on court interpreting training are scarce, and the Ministry of Higher Education discourages programs that do not meet market needs (MoHE, 2022). Despite the growing need for specialized court interpreters in Jordan, graduates

from translation programs are often ill-equipped to meet market demands (Khoury (2017); Mahasneh (2012); Abu-Risha (2005, 2006))

From a cognitive perspective, interpreting is a task that demands an understanding of how the brain processes language, memory, and cognitive load (Al-Suhaim, 2024). The integration of brain-based learning strategies into interpreter training could significantly enhance the effectiveness of training programs (Dubinsky (2024); Luk and Christodoulou (2024)). However, there is a scarcity of research on how to adapt instructional designs to the cognitive and learning needs of interpreting students. This issue is relevant to learning styles, in particular. Despite the recognition of diverse cognitive processes in interpreter training, learning styles—distinct ways individuals absorb, process, and retain information—play a crucial role in skill acquisition. According to the Strategic Teachers Model (Silver, Strong, & Perini, 2007), learners engage with new material through mastery (analytical and structured learning), interpersonal (social and collaborative learning), self-expressive (creative and intuitive learning), and understanding (conceptual and reflective learning) approaches. In an interpreting context, these styles can influence how trainees develop essential competencies such as memory retention, cognitive flexibility, and decision-making under pressure.

However, interpreter training programs in Jordan do not systematically incorporate learning styles into instructional design. Traditional methods focus primarily on linguistic proficiency and legal terminology, often neglecting the cognitive and experiential aspects of learning that could enhance interpreters' adaptability and performance. This gap suggests that current training approaches may not fully align with the cognitive demands of interpreting, potentially limiting the effectiveness of skill acquisition and real-world application in SCCs.

The current landscape in Jordan underscores the urgent need for reform. Unlike in many other countries, Jordan lacks a standardized framework for the qualification and training of court interpreters. This gap in professional and educational infrastructure raises concerns about the potential negative impact of interpreting errors on the outcomes of legal cases. The lack of research on court interpreting in Jordan further exacerbates this problem, as interpreters are left without the guidance needed to navigate the complexities of their roles.

Therefore, this study aims fill this critical gap by conducting a qualitative investigation into the knowledge and skills of court interpreters in Jordan. The findings will inform the development of a brain-based instructional design for court interpreting training, which will address both the cognitive demands of the profession and the practical needs of the court system. Ultimately, this research sought to advance the professionalization of court interpreters in Jordan and contribute to the development of more effective training programs that align with international standards of competence.

1.3 Significance of study

This study aims to make three significant contributions to the legislative, educational, and research landscapes of court interpreting, with a particular emphasis on SCCs in Jordan.

First, from a legislative perspective, the study seeks to inform policymakers about the importance of professionalizing the role of court interpreters. By examining the knowledge and competencies of professional interpreters, this research provides evidence that may guide legislative reforms aimed at establishing clear qualifications and standards for court interpreters. The choice of SCCs for this study is particularly relevant, as these courts are designed for swift adjudication, a process that can be severely compromised by the involvement

of incompetent interpreters. Therefore, the study will underscore the need for an effective regulatory framework that ensures interpreters are adequately qualified to contribute to the efficient functioning of these courts.

Second, at the educational level, the study aims to offer valuable insights to university educators and apprenticeship trainers by identifying the essential knowledge areas for training court interpreters, specifically those serving in SCCs. By aligning interpreter training outcomes with the practical needs of the legal system, this research will help ensure that educational programs produce competent interpreters who are capable of meeting the demands of the job market and functioning effectively within the legal environment. This confluence of theoretical knowledge and practical application is critical for fostering interpreters who can navigate the complexities of court proceedings and contribute to the delivery of justice.

Third, the study introduces a brain-based approach to instructional design, which focuses on adapting teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles. By developing a model that maximizes learning efficiency, this approach aims to enhance students' understanding of the cognitive demands of court interpreting. This method will ensure that students not only grasp the linguistic complexities of interpreting but also develop the cognitive skills necessary to handle the speed, accuracy, and attention required in high-pressure court environments.

This research represents the first study in Jordan that explores the role of court interpreters through this integrated legislative, educational, and cognitive lens. It paves the way for further investigations into the professionalization of court interpreters, exploring their dual role as language conduits and cultural mediators, as well as the challenges in developing effective instructional models and training curricula. While the study focuses on SCCs, its

findings will have broader implications for other legal contexts in Jordan, offering a foundation for enhancing court interpreting practices across the judiciary.

In summary, the significance of this research lies in its potential to influence legislative policy, improve educational practices for court interpreters, and ensure a more effective and equitable judicial system. By addressing the gaps in interpreter training and professional standards, the study will contribute to a more robust framework for court interpreting in Jordan, fostering a system that upholds justice through accurate and reliable interpretation.

1.4 Research Objectives

The goal of this study is to conceptualize a model for guiding the professional development of training materials that can produce competent interpreters for SCCs in Jordan. To achieve this, the study's primary objectives are to: first, explore the knowledge and skills currently applied by practicing SCC interpreters in Jordan; and second, investigate the learning outcomes when these competencies are taught in brain-compatible environments. In summary, the study objectives are:

RO1. To define the relevant situational knowledge content of SCCI in Jordan

RO2. To elucidate the relevant conceptual knowledge content of SCCI in Jordan

RO3. To identify the relevant procedural knowledge content of SCCI in Jordan

RO4. To explore a brain-based strategic teachers' instruction of SCCI in Jordan

1.5 Research Questions

The study aims to answer the following questions:

RQ1. To what extent does situational knowledge affect interpreters' renderings at small-claim courts in Jordan?

RQ2. What is the required conceptual knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan?

RQ3. How do professional interpreters perform interpreting in small claims cases in Jordans?

RQ4. Why is a brain-based training instruction needed in teaching SCCI in Jordan?

1.6 Limitations

Given the lack of primary sources of information, this exploratory study is based on interviews, observation and feedback of students undertaking the case study. Since English is not an official language in Jordan, the number of lawyer interviewee who speak English and interpret at courts were limited. The selected student respondents cannot be held as representative of learning styles of students, thereby necessitating more studies on that aspect.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. First, the research focuses specifically on small claims court interpreting (SCCI) in Jordan, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other legal settings or interpreting contexts. Court interpreting varies across jurisdictions, and training programs in different regions may incorporate different methodologies that are not reflected in this study.

Second, while the study integrates brain-based learning principles and a brain-based instructional approach to explore interpreter training, the practical implementation of these frameworks remains largely theoretical. The extent to which such cognitive-based instructional approaches can be fully applied within the constraints of existing court interpreting training programs requires further empirical investigation.

Third, data collection primarily relies on interviews with SCC interpreters and observations of brain-based learning in practice. While these methods provide valuable insights into real-world training experiences, they may be influenced by participants' subjective perceptions and variations in interpreting environments. Additionally, the sample size is limited to a specific group of interpreters, which may not capture the full diversity of learning needs and styles among court interpreters in Jordan.

Lastly, the study does not assess long-term learning outcomes or the direct impact of brain-based learning on interpreter performance. Future research could benefit from longitudinal studies that track the effectiveness of brain-based training interventions over time, as well as comparative studies that evaluate different instructional methods.

Despite these limitations, this research contributes to the growing discourse on cognitive-based interpreter training and highlights the need for more structured, learner-centred approaches in court interpreting education.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a review of studies pertinent to two key dimensions of this research: court interpreting and brain-based learning. It commences with a historical overview of interpreting, tracing its evolution and development. Subsequently, it delves into the complexities of legal systems, including the nuances of terminology and conceptual frameworks, thereby establishing a foundation for exploring the educational dimensions of instructional design. In doing so, this literature review draws on theories from the neuroscience of education and curriculum design, which together form the theoretical framework underpinning this study. These perspectives not only inform the analysis of interpreter competencies but also guide the development of training content and instructional strategies. The chapter also presents and analyses various models that highlight the diverse and sophisticated skill set required of interpreters. Furthermore, it evaluates the implications of recent neuroscience research and the brain-based learning approach, offering insights into effective teaching strategies for their application in court interpreting training.

2.2 Historical overview of Interpreting

Since antiquity, interpreters have facilitated cross-language interactions, from the early days of Haremhab's reign (reigned 1323-1309 BCE) (Gardiner, 1953) or even from the Akkadians' around 1900 BCE (Pöchhacker, 2016). In medieval times, interpreters flourished with the constant contact between the Christian world and the Western Muslim World (Salicru Lluç, 2009). In modern times, the interpreter's role has increasingly received recognition in

such areas as war and politics (Baigorri-Jalon, 2010), achievement of justice at court (Morris, 1999) and healthcare systems (Hadziabdic, 2011).

Interpreting was ordained during the early days of Islam with Zaid bin Thabet assigned to be the first interpreter for Prophet Muhammad (Bukhari, 2002, No. 1779), though a ruler was recommended to recruit two interpreters (Bukhari, 2002, No. 7891). The appointment of Zaid is reported to have been an order from God to His Messenger through the *wahi* (Al Zuhaili, 2006), with different interpretations of that order. For the Shafiites, an interpreter is a witness, therefore requiring two male interpreters or one male and two female interpreters (Al Zuhaili, 2006), while the Hanafis consider an interpreter to be a language mediator who can be male or female except in certain circumstances. The Hanafis also hold that if a ruler speaks the languages of the litigants, an interpreter will not be required (Al Mawardi, 1999).

During the Ottoman reign, dragomans (the Turkish word for interpreters) were recruited to interpret between high-ranking figures, including the Sultan, and foreign diplomats or delegates (Eşiyok & Yağcı, 2023). Some were appointed by Turkish courts (Hallaq, 2009). It is speculated that graduates from Istanbul-based Western vocational schools served as interpreters mediating diplomatic and trade interactions (Delibas, 2023). The same language mediation role is reported in 10th century Andalusia (Adams, 2016) , 17th century China (Tormsen, 2015), and far East Asia (Ibrahim, 2007). In the 19th century, interpreters were indigenous intermediaries between French colonists and Africans in Senegal (M'bayo, 2016).

In the 1920s, the telephonic interpreting equipment was invented, a precursor to simultaneous interpreting equipment (Ball, 2021). The first interpretation system was experimented by the International Labor Organisation (2015) then used at the Nuremberg Trial against Nazi war criminals between 1945 and 1946 (Islamova & Xolmurodova, 2024). In 1946,

the United Nations General Assembly adopted a resolution the official languages of the organisation (UN General Assembly Resolution 2/1, 1 February 1946), recommending the use of interpreting through the telephonic systems.

In less than a decade afterwards, standardization efforts and codes of ethics emerged. The International Association of Conference Interpreters (AIIC) was established in 1956 to promote interpreting standards, liaising with international agencies for the working conditions of interpreters. More recently in 1998, the International Standardization Organization introduced new standards on the booth and interpreting systems. The updated versions of the ISOs cover general recommendations (ISO18841:2018), guidelines for community interpreting (ISO13611:2014), legal interpreting (ISO/FDIS20228) and interpreting technology (ISO/DIS 20539). In 2002, the California Healthcare Interpreters Association published its standards for healthcare interpreters, and in 2013, the Judicial Council of California released its code of ethics for court interpreters (Judicial Council of California, 2013).

In the practice of interpreting, technology, such as video-communication devices, allowed for remote interpreting (Böcker & Anderson, 1993), sound systems enabled interpreters in their sound-proof booths to hear the speaker (van Rooy, 2005) and mobile interpreting devices that reduce technical problems and ensure a mobile service (Pienaar, 2006).

On the professional level, a distinction is made between untrained interpreters (just bilinguals), those with general skills (generalist interpreters) and others with special skills (professional interpreters). Community Interpreters (Al-Zahran (2007); Cerezo (2014)) offer services in such settings as police stations, schools, public safety, employment interviews and healthcare. Shuttleworth (2014) argues that an interpreter working in all those fields is a generalist interpreter, who knows something of everything and can handle assignments up to a

specific level of sophistication. On the other hand, there is a specialist interpreter, a linguist experienced, for example, in medical matters, or a practitioner trained in language interpreting (Hlavac, 2013).

Compared to translators, interpreters tend to be generalists as they accept assignments in a variety of disciplines (Schweda-Nicholson, 1986). On this generalist-specialist contention, though in the field of written translation, Martin (2011) justifies his criticism of specialisation by stating that every field of knowledge expands from time to time and that the term ‘specialisation’ and its derivatives are abused by both commercial companies and translators themselves. On the other hand, Lai and Gonzalez (2025) contends the implementability of specialised training for even untrained interpreters in the specific area of court interpreting.

The generalist-specialist controversy goes on, but linguists may find in laws and regulations a leverage tool to their specialisation. The Syrian Sworn Translators Law of 2014 (Ministry of Justice, 2014) regulates the affairs of ‘sworn’ translators and interpreters, with some provisions governing the use of interpreters by court. The State of California (California Courts, n.d) has a program for court interpreters, which seeks to ensure access to courts for people not proficient in English. To that end, it develops programs to improve the quality of interpreting and provide for a pool of qualified court interpreters. In the 1980s, Washington introduced a healthcare interpreter certification program, with the purpose of ensuring all people have access to medical services, across language barriers (Chen, Youdelman, & Brooks, 2007). These are just few examples to showcase the fact that interpreters may have a *de jure* status as professionals specialised in certain fields. This brings us to the discussion of court interpreters, as a specialisation that has its own principles, ethics, skills and competencies with specific reference to context of Jordan.

2.3 Court interpreting

The term ‘court interpreting’ includes interpreting in settings in different legal settings including courtroom, asylum application interviews, police interrogation or small claims (Berk-Seligson, 2017), police departments or immigration authorities (Gamal, 2019). A court interpreter is a trained professional, able to interpret oral communication in both the source and target languages with accuracy, impartiality, and confidentiality. Their professionalism decides the delivery or otherwise miscarriage of justice (Kasonde, 2016).

Consecutive interpreting (CI) is commonly used in courtrooms, where an interpreter hears or sees the source text, processes it then interprets it into the target language after the speaker has finished, giving the interpreter an interval to speak (Kadric & Stempkowski, 2024). There is no agreement on how long an interval can last (Russell, 2005). Notes can be taken on paper or through digital devices, ushering into a new mode of simultaneous- consecutive interpreting (SimConsec) (Svoboda, 2020). In addition, court interpreters may be asked to perform whispering interpreting (Du, 2024)

Interpreters at courts face the demand for high-precision renderings. Bowcott (2016) notes that misinterpretation can adversely affect the situation, causing delays in judging thousands of cases, as in the United Kingdom. The scarcity of interpreters, according to Romberger (2007), makes an interpreter ‘qualified’ in the eyes of the court as long as he is punctual and able to communicate with the participants of the court. This scenario needs interpreters to have specialized training in the interpretation of legal discourse before entering the profession. Conducting a needs analysis exercise, Chang (2016) revealed that the training should focus on language competence, actual practice at courts and engagement with several modes of interpreting. On a more general level, other elements of interpreting training are

encouraged to be included, such as knowledge, terminology and grammar. Besides, the function of brain has come to the forefront in analysing and categorizing competence. Brain related skills, such as attention, focus and memory are also pertinent for interpreting training (Alexieva, 1991). Developments in brain technology encouraged scholarly work on interpreting based on inputs from neuroscience and brain research with the aim of improving interpreter brain-compatibility (Gran and Fabbro (1988); Setton and Dawrant (2016)). Interpreting is a mental activity involving the interpreter in a process of encoding, decoding, recollecting memory and production, it makes sense that relevant studies should uncover the interface between neuroscience and language interpreting.

Interpreters should seek to enhance their language and knowledge, particularly in advanced courses that require application of knowledge to do authentic interpreting activities (Setton & Dawrant, 2016). With specific reference to court interpreting, judges in Vienna believe that language skills and cultural competence in court procedures are more important than basic legal knowledge (Kadrić cited in Pöchhacker, 2016). Likewise, Berk-Seligson (2017) expects court interpreters to have a good knowledge of synonyms, vocabulary, formal style of writing, grammar, idioms and sayings. Courts in the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia and European Commission place in their respective handbooks and guides much emphasis on the code of ethics that interpreters should follow and the linguistic criteria for qualification. Those documents do not require the interpreter to have an extensive legal knowledge, other than the basics of legal terminology and court procedures (European Court of Justice (2016); Judicial Council of California (2008); UK Ministry of Justice (2018); Supreme Court of Wisconsin (2004)).

However, in light of the number of cases appealed in Australia on the basis of poor interpreters' performance, Hayes and Hale (2010) call for interpreters to receive a 'specialist training'. Bilingualism is only a prerequisite to interpreters' training, as a court interpreter is expected to possess a comprehensive knowledge of courtroom procedures (Berk-Seligson, 2017). Empirical evidence suggests that court interpreters, even accredited or certified, can still make serious mistakes if they are not aware of the legal implications of court discourse (Hale, 2010). This is why an interpreter should have a broad experience in legal knowledge and an understanding of how legal knowledge is expressed both in the source and target languages (Osiejewicz, Podgórna, & Góra-Poland, 2015).

To establish good competence and skills for court interpreting jobs, according to Salimbene (1996), interpreters can benefit from two sources: codes of ethics and training. Common standards that courts share include accuracy, honesty and professionalism. On the training issue, Salimbene (1996) recommends universities to establish special undergraduate degrees for court interpreters and to develop special curricula, in cooperation with the judicial system, to meet the goals stated in courts' codes of ethics. He, furthermore, stresses the importance of creating a stand-alone programme, which, according to him, should not be equivalent to legal education or language education.

However, a survey of 21 countries (Hlavac, 2013) shows that court interpreter certification programmes do not require a court interpreting degree. The most common requirement is a degree in language or training and experience in the field. Translation programmes do not usually offer a degree to court interpreting, the reason for which, as Moeketsi and Wallmach (2005) suggest, is because many academics believe that court interpreting is a vocation. On the other hand, complicated determinants have made some

countries move forward to a stand-alone programme of court interpreters at the bachelor's degree level, as in South Africa (Moeketsi & Wallmach, 2005).

Proficiency in a foreign language is a common requirement in jurisdictions. However, no prior specialised knowledge and training is required for court interpreters in Malaysia (Ibrahim, 2007) or Russia (Babanina, Zhivaeva, & Babanina, 2015), although experience and qualification are required for interpreting at Malaysian apex courts. This can be compared with the more stringent criteria in Taiwan, where court interpreter candidates with high scores in English tests and proficiency in Mandarin Chinese can obtain a court interpreter certificate by proving residency in the relevant language area for five years. Successful candidates must then enrol in induction sessions. (Chang, 2013). Rwanda is another example where there are no guidelines on the appointment of interpreters. The Rwandan Supreme Court had two staff interpreters with a degree in law, and where the judge encounters litigants who do not speak the official language, he will ask the audience if one can do the interpretation (Ngarambe & Ruvebana, 2023). Training and examination, however, were compulsory for court interpreters serving at International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (Brenda, 2015).

The problem with incompetent interpreters is that they may have conflicting understandings of the very phenomenon of interpreting (Lebese & Ndhlovu, 2024). They may not know how to deal with court professionally, by initiating talk with the witness, for example, or directing the litigant to what should be said in court (Kiguru, 2009). This concern is echoed by Bowcott (2016) voices over issues in interpretation that caused thousands of cases at court to be adjourned. Benmaman (2000) reviews cases involving interpretation problems at court for the period of twenty years and concludes that the majority of relevant appeal cases had to do with errors in interpreters formalities rather than with interpretation errors. Although

disputants can appeal a court's decision on the basis of inaccuracies in interpreting, it is often difficult, as Berk-Seligson (2017) emphasises, to prove such inaccuracies, leading appeals court to decline the appeal. She suggests, therefore, that court interpreters should have a good background about court procedures, legal terminology, cross-cultural awareness, interpreters' roles and pragmatics. Interpreters' competence, knowledge, management of errors in interpretation and relationship with other participants at court is also the focus of the Judicial Council of California (2008), which prescribes rules for interpreters to abide by literally.

Jurisdictions differ in the appointment and requirements of professional court interpreters. The following section provides a comparative review of relevant practices in the United States, Oman, Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco.

2.3.1 Court interpreting competence

Competence refers to the knowledge and skills that a learner acquires and their ability to apply such knowledge and skills in real life (Açıkgöz & Babadoğan, 2021). In broad terms, research on the translation/interpreting training curriculum building is flawed by a deficient understanding of how curricula are developed and the unplanned application of relevant skills, which deprive translation/interpreting courses from their efficiency (Calvo, 2011). According to Schweda-Nicholson (1985), interpreters' competence boils down to language skills. This finds support in early research on translation competence, which relied to a large extent on foreign language (Kaczmarek, 2010). On the other hand, NCIEC (2012) almost confines competence, in the context of court interpreting, to an in-depth knowledge of court systems and detailed functionalities and legal background. Furthermore, Mikkelson (2013) contends that competence is something that accreditation programs test for the purpose of ensuring quality services for the client. In a different vein, Moeketsi and Wallmach (2005) consider court

interpreter competence as an indicator to mastery of languages and possession of interpreting skills, while Kalina (2000) defines interpreting competence as the interpreter's skill in handling bilingual texts, considering constraints like time, interference between production and comprehension, and other factors such as prior knowledge, intentions, and assumptions among participants in a bilingual communicative event. The following lines review court interpreters' competence in terms of knowledge and skills.

2.3.2 Court interpreters' knowledge

Knowledge is an epistemological concept that philosophers are in agreement is valuable, although they disagree about its definition and how it can be acquired (Lehrer, 2018). Plato views it as a justified belief or a recollection of inner beliefs that preceded birth (Ichikaw & Steup, 2018). This is opposed to Aristotle's idea that what humans call knowledge is what they acquire through the senses, then store in memory and accumulate into what he refers to as 'experience' (Hauser, 2019). While both philosophers are essentially referring to objective reality as a source of knowledge (Mulder, n.d.), Descartes places subjective knowledge at the core of epistemological inquiry (Stroud, 2007). Researchers, nonetheless, tried to offer their own definitions of the term in line with their respective field of investigation. The following are some of those definitions:

“the ability to do things, or refrain from doing things, or believe, or want, or doubt things, for reasons that are facts.” (Hyman, 1999)

“the capability to interpret data and information through a process of giving meaning to these data and information” (uit Beijerse, 1999)

“a combination of experience, values, contextual information and expert insight that help evaluate and incorporate new experience and information the sum total of peoples perspectives, processes that help them to draw meaningful conclusion” (Ismail Al-Alawi, Yousif Al-Marzooqi, & Fraidoon Mohammed, 2007)

“understanding gained through either study or experience” (Bhatt, 2019)

“Information and skills acquired through experience or education, the theoretical or practical understanding of a subject.” (Sanni, 2021)

As an epistemological question involving the subjective-vs-objective, Lorca (1995) draws the definition of knowledge from Kantian philosophy, as he divides knowledge into two broad opposite domains, knowledge a priori and knowledge a posteriori, proposing that the first is "correctly justified true belief" while the latter is "justified belief with which we assume that we have obtained truth". Another dichotomy, also based on Kant's philosophy, is about analytical vs synthetic knowledge, where the first is knowledge derived from the analysis of facts (Pyo, 2005), the second is the novel combination of previously available knowledge into a new set of knowledge (Manniche, 2012). Likewise, scientific knowledge produces data and extracts conclusions based on evidence, while professional knowledge, which professionals use to bridge between the needs of policymakers and science (Nugroho, Carden, & Antlov, 2018).

Cognitive psychology tends to define knowledge by answering the questions of what, how and when, resulting into declarative knowledge (knowing what), procedural knowledge (knowing how) and conditional knowledge (knowing when). ‘Knowing what’ refers to structure and goals and includes beliefs about personal abilities; ‘knowing how’, relates to information about how actions can be executed; and ‘knowing when’, refers to knowledge of why and when

an action is to be executed (Paris, Lipson, & Wixson, 1983). Other classifications include: declarative and non-declarative (Haladyna, 1994), implicit and explicit (Brewin, 1996) or declarative and procedural (Binder, 1999).

Anderson (1982) posits that declarative (conceptual) knowledge refers to knowing facts that people can describe to other persons while procedural knowledge refers to how a person can perform a given action. Alexander and Judy (1988) introduce the term 'domain knowledge' and define it as the combination of the declarative, procedural and conditional knowledge that a person uses in respect of a specific field of study. Other researchers, according to (Alexander, 1992), refer to domain knowledge using different terms such as 'subject-matter knowledge' and 'content-specific knowledge'. In this vein, Hayes (2010) makes the distinction between declarative and procedural knowledge, posting that the former type of knowledge is further subdivided into conceptual knowledge and empirical knowledge.

In relation to learning, De Jong and Ferguson-Hessler (1996) emphasise the relationship between students' learning process and the knowledge they possess and suggest four categories of knowledge: conceptual, situational, procedural and strategic. According to them, conceptual knowledge states the principles and rules within a given domain, while procedural knowledge refers to correction actions within such a domain. Romero (2012) further elaborated this concept within the terms of 'declarative knowledge' and 'procedural knowledge' that were first introduced by philosopher Gilbert Ryle, who contended a distinction between 'knowing what' and 'knowing that'. Within the scope of ACT Theory of Cognition (Anderson, 1982), declarative knowledge refers to knowing facts that people can describe to other persons while procedural knowledge refers to how a person can perform a given action. This ability to transfer of the facts within a certain performing of an act is what is termed as domain knowledge

(Alexander & Judy, 1988) whereby the combination of the declarative, procedural and conditional knowledge that a person has and uses in respect to a specific field of study. The concept however has evolved and is used interchangeably with different terms such as ‘subject-matter knowledge’ and ‘content-specific knowledge’ (Alexander, 1992).

In relation to court interpreting, world knowledge—defined as an understanding of how the world functions Weigand (2014); Setton and Dawrant (2016))—is widely regarded as essential for court interpreters. Researchers contend that this knowledge enables interpreters to make inferences (Lee, 2009b), maximize accuracy, and ensure faithful interpretation (Moody, 2014). Furthermore, it facilitates specialization in specific fields, prompting jurisdictions like Germany to mandate familiarity with political, economic, and legal systems (Tosun, Akin, & Simsek, 2015).

Focusing more specifically on court interpreting, Corsellis (2005) asserts that community interpreters, including legal interpreters, must understand the procedures, processes, and systems within their working environment. Gile (2009) similarly argues that evaluating interpreter training programs and developing curricula necessitates an analysis of the knowledge and skills interpreters must possess. Despite the recognized importance of subject knowledge for professionalization, scholars note a persistent lack of systematic identification of essential concepts for training curricula (Ordóñez-López, 2015).

Historically, the interpreting profession relied on an apprenticeship model for knowledge transmission, resulting in textbooks that were more practical than academic (Pöchhacker, 2016). However, later research has advocated for a more scientific approach to interpreter training. The debate over generalist versus specialized training remains unresolved. While some scholars support a generalist approach, allowing interpreters to work in diverse

settings (Schweda-Nicholson, 1986), others stress the necessity of specialized competencies. (Witter-Merithew & Nicodemus, 2010) suggest that interpreters typically begin as generalists before pursuing specialized training, particularly in court interpreting. Berk-Seligson (2017) reinforces the need for specialized training in formal court settings.

Court interpreters face a range of knowledge-related challenges, including background knowledge, pragmatic knowledge, legal knowledge, an understanding of the legal system, and cultural awareness (Issaei, 2007). Many university programs fail to address these areas, as observed in Oman, whereas institutions like the Fachhochschule Magdeburg-Stendal in Germany provide specialized undergraduate degrees in public service that include court interpreting modules covering fundamental legal principles (Niska, 2005).

From a pragmatic standpoint, researchers argue that court interpreters must grasp not only the context but also the intentions of court participants (Záňová, 2013) and the legal implications of utterances (Fournier, 1994). Studies highlight deficiencies in legal terminology, comprehension of the legal system, and language competence (Hofer, 2005). Walker and Shaw (2011) found that many interpreters decline court assignments due to gaps in legal and procedural knowledge. Pragmatic aspects of court interpreting also involve managing face-saving and face-threatening acts, as well as markers of politeness, particularly during witness examinations (Ranosa-Madrugno, 2014).

Regulatory bodies impose strict standards on court interpreters. The Judicial Council of California (2013) mandates verbatim interpretation, prohibiting omissions, additions, and embellishments while ensuring natural English style, syntax, and grammar. However, scholars note that the Code does not explicitly require interpreters to possess legal expertise.

In Australia, Hale and Gonzalez Hale and Gonzalez (2017) analysed a legal interpreting course at the University of New South Wales, which covered contextual legal knowledge and exposure to specialized settings such as police stations, lawyer-client interactions, and administrative tribunals. Despite such initiatives, scholars observe that court interpreting courses remain limited in scope and language offerings (Stern & Liu, 2019a).

Subject matter expertise is widely regarded as crucial for court interpreters to provide accurate interpretations (Seleskovitch, 1992). Volker (1995) contends that interpreters with strong subject knowledge perform significantly better than those without it. Anecdotal evidence suggests that court interpreters often research case-specific information in advance to familiarize themselves with technical terms (Mikkelson, 1999). Martínez-Gómez (2015) argues that familiarity with subject matter enhances recall and note-taking, while its absence can create terminological challenges.

Several scholars emphasize the importance of specialized training for court interpreters. Giambruno (1997) underscores the need for knowledge of legal systems, legal language, and ethics. Mikkelson (1998) and Martínez-Gómez (2018) (Martínez-Gómez, 2018) advocate integrating legal system knowledge and real-life court scenarios into training. Wang (2014) proposes a structured training approach, which includes:

- (1) Fundamental legal terms and concepts,
- (2) Skills for reading and understanding case claims,
- (3) Judges' reasoning and application of law, and
- (4) Knowledge of international laws and conventions.

Osiejewicz, Podgórna and Góra-Poland (2015) argue that court interpreters require legal training to grasp implicit information in court exchanges. Orozco-Jutorán and Sánchez-Gijón (2011) propose an ontology system that provides interpreters with resources for legal

terminology, concepts, documents, and participant roles, enhancing their comprehension and accuracy.

Court interpreters require not only knowledge but also a range of specialized skills to perform effectively. Stromberg and Head (1984) identify concentration, memory, simultaneous interpreting, legal terminology, and managing long sentences as essential abilities. González, Vásquez and Mikkelson (1991) expand this list to include listening, prediction, note-taking, and situational control. Hewitt (1995) highlights the importance of seeking clarification, requesting repetitions, and correcting errors, while Giambruno (1997) emphasizes self-monitoring. Hale (2010) advocates pre-service training, stressing preparation, note-taking, and memory aids.

Although studies rarely specify the minimum legal knowledge required for court interpreting, scholars agree that interpreters must possess a combination of world knowledge, subject matter expertise, legal understanding, and pragmatic skills. Training programs should systematically address these areas, blending theoretical knowledge with practical exposure to court dynamics. By doing so, court interpreters can meet the demands of their profession and ensure accurate, faithful interpretation in legal settings.

2.3.3 Court interpreters' skills

Linguistic skills, cultural knowledge and mental abilities are among the perquisites, but, according to Lambert (1992), they cannot alone make an interpreter. Just as with the definition of interpreting, skills and competences vary when looked at from different perspectives. According to Kalina (2000), translation and interpreting share certain basic skills that can be complemented by such skills specific to each mode. Those basic skills, according to Kalina (2000), include linguistic skills and fluency in the working languages. She also suggests that an interpreter has a procedural knowledge allowing the interpreter to choose the right word in the

respective context. However, she highlights other skills specific to the work of interpreters, including proper performance in the communicative event, with due attention given to knowledge about the participants, interests, goal and assumption. In other words, Kalina (2000) is highlighting here the communicative skills of interpreters as a key skill. Another scholar applying rules of written translation on interpreting is Niska (1999). She studied and analysed interpreters' performance in the English-Finnish language pair at real conferences from a text-linguistics approach. Her study covered such textual linguistic rules such as cohesion, coherence, intertextuality, register, speech acts, among other rules, and found that her approach succeeded in making a better understanding of the simultaneous interpreting event, though she suggests for future research to consider other approaches, such as the cognitive approach, in combination with text-linguistic analysis.

Culture has also been considered as essential for the interpreter's knowledge. Edwards (1995) emphasises, in the context of training court interpreters, that interpreters should be bicultural, suggesting that professionalism in languages alone does not make a good interpreter. She elaborates on specific examples of cultural issues in relation to register (formality) and condescension (level of politeness, for example). However, a broader perspective of culture is suggested by Gerver (2013), where the interpreter's knowledge of culture must be broad enough covering main fields of daily life, political events and economic and scientific developments. He notes that an interpreter's role is to bridge communities not only through languages but also through cultures and worlds of thought. This includes knowledge of the participants' cultural backgrounds, motivations and intentions.

Some researchers opt for discussing very specific issues of interpreters' skills. Ma (2013) analyses the interpreting process into five procedures, namely: perception, decoding,

recording, encoding and expressive. Gerver, Longley, Long and Lambert (1989), in the context of defining objective criteria to test and select successful conference interpreters, group interpreters' skills into: profound linguistic and cultural knowledge, mental agility in quickly understanding an incoming message, confident projection of information, a good voice, broad knowledge base and ability to work in a team of interpreters.

Note-taking is important in CI (Chen, 2017), requiring skills such as: writing main ideas, and drawing logical links, and temporal and negation markers (Ahrens & Orlando, 2022). It is, however, a challenging multitasking skill, a cognitive challenge to attention, comprehension and performance (Jeong S-H, 2016) as it requires splitting brain activities in the prefrontal cortex (Charron & Koechlin, 2010). Students may have difficulty in writing symbols in note-taking (Chmiel, 2010) and may miss a lot of information therefore rendering poor quality of interpreting (Liu, Luo, & Wang, 2023).

Court interpreters practice also management skills. Those are necessary to facilitate communication, including by establishing protocols with the interlocutors, deciding the appropriate interpreting mode, interrupting an interaction flow when needed, asking for clarification, reacting to requests and code-switching (National Accreditation Authority for Translators and Interpreters, 2016). Added to the list is displaying tactics and partiality (Halavac & Orlando, 2015) and following court protocols for seeking clarification and repetitions (Liu & Hale, 2018). The manner of speech at court between the judge and litigants and between the litigants is also an important skill of court interpreters and need to be part of professionalization programs (Yi, 2024).

2.4 Approaches to teaching interpreting

2.4.1 The apprenticeship model

Interpreting can be taught in two settings: formal academic environment and apprenticeship, the latter prioritizing practical skills training over the scholarly acquisition (Sawyer, 2004) and knowledge is passed on from a master to a student by exercises designed in accordance with real-life tasks (Pöchhacker, 2016). Apprenticeship has ever existed based on novices learning from experienced practitioners through observation, imitation and practice (Groth, 2024).

The apprenticeship model does not rely on theories or research, but many researchers contend it is not obsolete (Pöchhacker, 2010) and is still used in the academic environment (Sawyer, 2004). Tolosa-Igualada and Echeverri (2019) suggest that the apprenticeship model has marked a shift from a teacher-centred educational system into one that allows students to take charge of their education and construction of knowledge. They, however, suggest the possibility of changing educational models of interpreting to cope with future developments. In the same vein, Pym (2005) agrees to the usefulness of knowledge and skills to be passed from a professional to a novice in translation, but he equally underscores the necessity to incorporate theories in academic settings. He argues that the absence of theory can lead to a return to the "medieval apprenticeship" model.

While not totally excluding apprenticeship as an acceptable form of training, researchers pointed out to some problems. There is the question of availability of professional interpreters interested in having novices "under their wings", (Harris, 1992). Weaknesses of the model, according to Setton and Dawrant (2016), include underqualified instructors, loose testing procedures, delay in updating training to the needs of market and failure to work on targeted

language enhancement. Research is needed to support the teaching techniques used by early trainers, such as skills progression, the use of shadowing and directionality, which would motivate searching for a scientific basis of training (Setton & Dawrant, 2016). Another suggestion is the introduction of cognitive apprenticeship, which focuses on authentic activities and exposure of learners to feedback.

2.4.2 The discourse analysis approach

The relevance of discourse analysis to the teaching of CI derives from an interest of researchers to look into segments of language that go beyond the sentence level and how those segments relate to each other in the interpretation of sequence, structure and social relations (Đorđević, 2012). Discourse analysis approach is necessary in teaching CI (Russell, Shaw, & Malcolm, 2010), since participants have a role in creating and constructing meaning. Russel et al (2010) divide their model into three stages: typical progression, skills, activities, creating scenarios and role plays. This model proposes the educational mode of consecutive interpreters to start by immersing students in the exploration of relevant research in text and linguistic analysis. Such a stage should precede the translation and interpreting skill components. Wu and Wang (2009), furthermore, argue that discourse should be the working unit in approaching CI, highlighting the macro rules of generalization, construction and deletion. Sayfuldeen (2010) supports the use of discourse analysis in teaching CI, highlighting such cognitive issues as message understanding, analysis and re-expression.

2.4.3 The error analysis approach

In applied linguistics, the error analysis approach was pioneered by Pit Corder, who contends that understanding learners' errors can help in guiding educators in dictating their

practice and designing their syllabus (Corder, 1967). Error analysis, according to Kiraly (1995), helps not only in identifying types of problems facing students but also attempting to resolving them then evaluating students' performance, accordingly.

In the field of CI studies, researchers have studied students' performance to get pedagogical insights. Chang (2016) indicated certain implications on the pedagogy of interpreting, such as the designing of prefabricated chunks in exercises, memorization of expressions, sentence structure drills, skills in interpreting numbers. He further recommends a collaborative effort between interpreting educators and language teachers in the design of the consecutive-interpreting course that would consider common patterns such as vocabulary, standard phrases and structure. He also highlighted the effect of word choices on grammar mistakes in the rendering of students. Wang (2015)'s experiment using the quantitative and qualitative methods found that students of CI are challenged by numbers, nouns and logical relations. He recommended teachers to consider those implications, particularly those of logical relations, in the training of consecutive interpreters.

Error analysis has also been used to indicate special areas of challenges for students of CI. Russell (2005) explored opportunities for incorporating professional practice and research in the legal interpreting classroom. Her findings included that interpreters made more errors when interpreting expert testimony and when direct evidence was given (Russell, 2005). With a more focused approach on interpreting errors, Agustin (2018) found five patterns of errors in interpreting auxiliary verbs, recommending lecturers to review auxiliary verbs with students before the actual interpreting class.

2.4.4 The experiential learning approach

Experiential learning (EL) dates back to the Greek philosopher and playwright Sophocles, who believed that no one can claim he has learnt something unless they tried themselves doing it (Spurgeon, 1971). The idea was particularly popularized in the 20th century through the works of John Dewey, who proposed that knowledge is socially constructed on the basis of experience (Roberts, 2003). In interpreting education, advocates stress learning interpreting through hands-on and interaction (Sassman, 2009), because interpreting is an activity for learners to do (Cox, 2013), requiring practising mock exercises of real-world scenarios (Roberson, 2012). Despite its popularity, EL has drawn criticism over ethical issues including bias, inadequate informed choices of students, poor debriefing, even deception (Bradford, 2018), being resource intensive (Diachun, Dumbrell, Byrne, & Esbaugh, 2006), costly and time-consuming (Rageth, 2024).

2.5 Court interpreters' training curricula

Most jurisdictions do not require formal training or pre-service training to become certified as a court interpreter (Lee, 2015). Literature on interpreting training curricula, in general, is limited (Pöchhacker, 2016) and even existing relevant research is sporadic as scholastic works tend to address aspects of interpreting training in isolation from each other (Sawyer, 2004). There is also no consensus on what the course should include or how it should be taught, as translation researchers have not adequately focused their research on curricula (Calvo, 2011) and that, in Jordanian context, academic offerings of interpreting training lags behind market requirements (Al-Dabbagh & Othman, 2024). This is not to undermine the academic role in training students on standards court interpreting practice, especially because academic institutions are structured for the purpose of teaching and can be at ease in meeting the expectations of courts in terms of interpreters qualifications (Salimbene, 1996). However,

personal correspondence with translation/interpreting academic institutions revealed the inexistence of court interpreting curricula at Jordanian universities (Suleiman Al Abbas, personal communication, June 9, 2019), the Boston University Center for Professional Education (Rose Quan, personal communication, July 30, 2019), University of Geneva (Nicole Stoll, personal communication, July 23, 2019) and the Translation School at University of Saint Joseph (Lena Menhem, personal communication, August 26, 2019).

On the other hand, interpreters who receive training on court interpreting achieve higher in tests (Institute for Court Management, 2007). Paradoxically, little attention is given to the essential elements of designing court interpreting training. This weakness is highlighted by Hale (2006) who states that the majority of relevant research have hastened into making generalisations and assumptions based on small databases, thus questioning their reliability. She concludes that this weakness resulted in a poor understanding of the type of training that would improve interpreter performance.

Schweda-Nicholson (1985) prescribe a curriculum should teach legal terms and concepts, court procedures, interpreter's role and ethics. Conversely, the American Translators Association (de Jongh, 2012) follows a detailed descriptive approach as it introduces readers to the various dynamics of courts and gives them a comprehensive background of the system, in addition to selected reading list of dictionaries and recordings for practice. Similar steps are followed by Edwards (1995), who provide details about the knowledge and skills a court usually expects to find in their interpreters. A needs analysis for court interpreter training (Chang, 2016) concludes with the recommendations for the content of the relevant curriculum to distinguish between types of cases, particularly criminal and civil ones, suggesting a focus to be placed on vocabulary and simulated cases. It also prescribes a teaching methodology based on tasks

involving students in cooperative activities undertaken in a classroom equipped with headsets and recording facilities. Again, this research does not spell out the exact steps that need to be implemented to achieve the goals of graduating competent court interpreters.

2.6 Defining curriculum

To develop effective training material for court interpreters, it is essential to understand how curriculum is defined and structured. This section explores key curriculum theories to identify principles that can guide the proposed training design. It examines how objectives are formulated, content selected and organized, and learning outcomes aligned with professional needs. Without sound curricular foundations, the training content may lack purpose, coherence, and pedagogical effectiveness.

Definitions of ‘curriculum’ vary in relevant studies. Taylor and Richards (2018) simplify it as what educators use to decide what to teach (content) and how to teach it (methodology). The Encyclopaedia of Curriculum Studies describes it as conceiving and configuring experiences that lead to learning (Kridel, 2010). Sawyer (2004), after reviewing many definitions, adopted two that clarify different curriculum aspects for interpreter training. First, a curriculum is a written action plan guiding educators and learners through clear objectives, sequencing components to serve learners’ needs. Second, it relates to learners’ experiences. This aligns with Ellis’s (2014) prescriptive-descriptive approach, viewing curriculum as both a document of pre-set goals and empirical observations of educational settings.

Taylor and Richards (2018) classify definitions as descriptive or perspective, then define curriculum as plans guiding learning, documented and implemented at various levels in the classroom. Their definition highlights learner experience and the role of an observer.

Similarly, Gosper and Ifenthaler (2014) identify curriculum features as producing outcomes, providing space for knowledge application and reflection, and being built on pre-determined goals and planned learning experiences. It connects learners' experiences with practitioner expectations and, from a systems perspective, both influences and is influenced by student learning.

Common among these views is that a curriculum is planned before training to achieve instructor-prescribed goals. Learner experiences during training may reveal unexpected needs, requiring real-time adjustments. A documented plan guides the instructor's techniques to meet pre-set or adapted goals. Ho (2015) adds that interpreter training must align closely with labor market demands, given employer concerns about the applicability of translation/interpreting skills taught at college (Liu, 2015). Thus, curriculum content should be versatile to adapt to changes in interpreters' professional world.

Another concept is the 'hidden curriculum,' introduced by scholars such as Dreeben, Jackson, and Vallance (Kentli, 2009). It refers to values and experiences students absorb indirectly in environments without a planned curriculum (Hubscher-Davidson & Borodo, 2012). This implies that institutions teaching without a defined plan may unintentionally transmit their own values and ideas about trainer experience.

A curriculum is expected to facilitate knowledge and skill transfer to students (Allais & Shalem, 2018). The following section reviews types of court interpreting knowledge, focusing on court interpreters' expertise.

2.7 Models of curriculum design

Bilbao, Lucido, Iringan and Javier (2008) classify curriculum design according to three categories: subject-centred, learner-centred and problem-solving centred. The first type focusses on the content, requiring a distribution of classroom hours at school according to the different subjects that students learn. While this approach is simple for delivery and offer formats familiar to teachers, it does not consider the natural tendencies of students or interests. The learner-centred design puts the learners at the centre of the educational and curriculum development process, and focuses on the cognitive development of learners. The problem-solving centred design derives from social problems and interests of the learners, who are provided with such problems to learn how to deal with them in real life. For that reason, the content of such curricula derives from different subjects as it is based on the needs, abilities and concerns of learners.

There are many other models for curriculum development. The following is a brief of some of them.

2.7.1 Tyler's Model

Tyler's model for curriculum development (Tyler, 1959) proposes three criteria to be addressed in an effective curriculum: continuity (the repetition of major elements), sequencing

(one learnt element is based on the previous one) and integration (giving students a unified view about the curriculum). He proposes four steps to develop a curriculum:

1. Define learning objectives
2. Select learning experiences
3. Organise learning experiences
4. Evaluate the curriculum

Tyler's model received both support and criticism. Fogarty (1976) notes that it has long been adopted for curriculum development, inspiring systematic work on writing behavioural objectives and justifying instruction. Its rationale for sustainable objectives and feedback in evaluation offers essential guidance for curriculum design (Du, 2024). Criticism focuses on its rationale, arguing it lacks guidance on selecting objectives, as behavioural objectives may mislead students about real-world experience. Moreover, not all learning types can be broken into objectives, and objectives cannot always be pre-specified since some evolve during training (Fogarty, 1976). Tyler's focus on predetermined objectives is also said to reinforce strict accountability and hinder critical discussion of social issues in education (Burns, 2024). However, D'Souza and Larik (2024) argue that Tyler's clear objectives facilitate developing curriculum-specific skills and competencies, encouraging instruction that supports these goals and enhances effectiveness and student achievement, depending on implementation and local adaptation.

2.7.2 Taba's model

Hilda Taba offered an inductive bottom-up model of curriculum design (Taba, 1971), based on seven stages: diagnosis of learners' needs formulation of objectives selection of the

content organization of the content selection of learning experiences organization of learning activities evaluation. An important contribution of this model is the active role of teachers in developing the curriculum from the early stages (Bhuttah, Xiaoduan, Ullah, & Javed, 2019) and determines objectives and content in addition to the selection of strategies for teaching and assessment (Adirika & Okolie, 2017). The model, though, received criticism as it is difficult to apply in heterogeneous classrooms, in addition to other concerns over conferring the curriculum design with the teachers, which ignores the interests and concerns of higher authorities and makes learning outcomes unpredictable (Adirika & Okolie, 2017).

2.7.3 Wheeler’s model

Wheeler’s model (Wheeler, 1967) deems the curriculum as a continuous cycle, meaning the curriculum development should make amendments whenever necessity to keep pace with changes. There are five stages in curriculum development, according to this model: setting aims, goals and objectives, selecting learning experiences, selection of content, organization and matching experience with content then evaluation. Its main criticism is that it consumes time for application, since it requires an in-depth situational analysis (Bhuttah et al., 2019).

2.8 Defining learning objectives

A learning objective, according to Mager (1962), is “an intent communicated by a statement describing a proposed change in a learner—a statement of what the learner is to be like after successfully completing a learning experience. It describes the behaviour (performance) the learner should demonstrate.” Another definition states it as “a statement of what educators intend students to learn from educational experiences” (Anderson, 2010). Bloom (1956) sees learning objectives as foundational for curriculum development and

research, with a taxonomy helping teachers plan and evaluate. Objectives must be clear, relatable to students' personalities, and attainable (Sweigert, 1969). Well-written objectives help students align their performance with expectations (Gagné, 1977) and assist in organizing student and teacher activities (El Nil el Fadil, 1985). Predefined objectives provide a framework ensuring logical sequencing of learning (Laurel, 2008). They focus students on skills to master and practice, guiding effective instruction methods (Mitchell & Manzo, 2018; Acevedo, 2014; Chatterjee & Corral, 2017).

However, some researchers question the necessity of defining learning objectives. Eisner (1967) argued that outcomes are too numerous and dynamic, especially in subjects like arts, to be fully predicted. Macdonald (1971) viewed objectives as heuristics, known fully only after instruction, subject to modification. Raths (1971) noted real-world teaching often requires engaging students through comments and experiences that fixed objectives may limit. Hussey and Smith (2002) suggested learning outcomes have been distorted, with teachers sometimes feigning or adapting compliance. Brancalone and O'Brien (2011) criticized learning outcomes as a 'predictive promise' from teacher to student. Mitchell and Manzo (2018) warned objectives, while useful in theory, may constrain instruction by ignoring classroom dynamics.

Mager (1962) emphasized that meaningful objectives communicate instructional intent and include three elements: action (what the student will do), condition (under what circumstances), and criterion (performance level expected). Campbell (1996) distinguishes terminal learning objectives—main job tasks—from enabling objectives, which cover specific knowledge or skills needed to achieve terminal goals.

2.9 Bloom's taxonomy of learning objectives

The model proposed by Benjamin Bloom is considered by some scholars as the most popular educational classification system (Kidd, 2009). The proposed goal of the taxonomy is to help educators in their curriculum development process and address problems with greater precision (Bloom, 1956). It is also proposed to help educators specify the desired learning objectives, defined in a hierarchical order from the low level to the higher levels of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Bloom justifies the sequential nature of the model on the premise that a simple behaviour at a lower level is integrated with another simple behaviour to form a complex behaviour. He also noted that the taxonomy comes to cope with changes that happen in the world by time, alluding to the possibility of amending the taxonomy in the future. The taxonomy is based on one dimension, that is the cognitive dimension and is divided into six categories: knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Bloom maintains that a taxonomy is different from classification in the sense that students should master the lower levels of the taxonomy before moving up to the higher levels. That is to say that a student should first of all master the knowledge of the content before proceeding forward to understanding it, and so forth up to the higher levels.

Bloom (1956) underscored that his proposed taxonomy tried to cope with changes in times, alluding to the idea that this taxonomy can be revised in the future should the need arise. In fact, this is what happened as a team of researchers headed by one of Bloom's student, Lorin Anderson did. The new revised model, (Krathwohl & Anderson, 2009), offers an additional dimension, that is the knowledge dimension. It also rephrases the orders of cognitive learning objectives into remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating and creating. The

knowledge dimension includes factual knowledge, conceptual knowledge, procedural knowledge and meta-cognitive knowledge.

2.10 Brain-based education

Brain-based education brings together insights from education as well as from neuroscience. In the broader scope of education, a strategic ‘brain-based’ approach has been adopted by Silver, Strong and Perini (2007), who elicit from a group of models some strategies of teaching. Those relate to ways governing the presentation of content and new information, helping students in practical application of knowledge, assessing their progress and enabling their reflections. They suggest that since each strategy addresses different goals, an instructor must apply a repertoire of strategies, rather than stick to one strategy for all purposes.

Other insights into the teaching and learning of interpreting come from neuroscience, since interpreting is a mental activity. By looking into the functions of the brain during an interpreting event, Gran and Fabbro (1988) suggest that the brain of a monolingual functions differently from one who is using two languages, such as in translation and interpreting. Their research finds, however, that translation skills are not necessarily the same as those required by an interpreter.

Researchers in interpreting studies have also used technology to design their research projects, according to Yan, Pan, Wu and Wang (2013) who also note an increasing trend among researchers to use empirical neuroscience findings in interpreting studies. Hervais-Adelman and Babcock (2019), for example, used structural and functional brain imagery analysis, in light of whose findings, they concluded that a brain does not have a specific system dedicated for language behaviour, but alternatively, it offers a general networking ability which language

uses whenever the need arises. They, furthermore, find that CI can be as demanding, if not more demanding, than simultaneous interpreting, cognitive-wise.

The process of CI, in simple terms, requires receiving information (an input), understanding what is said (decoding) then passing on the message in the target language (encoding and re-expressing) (Ma, 2013). Science approaches the process in a more detailed manner. The message gets into the brain through the senses, it is decoded with the use of memory, a decision is made on the meaning of the message then an output is rendered. The capability of humans to do all these tasks in a split-second so professionally and accurately has received much attention by neuroscientists. They wanted to know what exactly happens in the brain and neurons while a human is performing such tasks (Setton & Dawrant, 2016) so they worked with linguists to study the neuro-linguistic phenomenon and concluded that the whole of the brain is engaged with this linguistic activity. Experiments on the brain proved that when an individual is in the process of learning something new, the brain looks for all existing networks to determine which part is most appropriate for storing that new piece of information. Wolfe (1998) illustrates her idea through the example of a girl who has learnt that a cat has fur and may, later, call a dog 'cat'. She explains this phenomenon by saying that the girl would have searched in her neural network to find and select the closest match to the dog. This process triggers the question on how exactly the brain manages to store and retrieve information and consolidate new information with old one.

The training of court interpreters ideally considers the expectations of clients, since getting a job should be an axiomatic result of the training. With reference to California Code of Ethics (California Courts, n.d), a court interpreter must meet specific expectations when performing his job. For example, a court interpreter is required to preserve in the target language

not only the ideas of the source message but also the order of such ideas, accurately and without omissions. Such a linear type of interpreting seems to conflict with language interpreting researchers. Ma (2013), for example, challenges linear interpretation saying its output will be awkward. Linear interpretation has implications for such teaching strategies as shadowing, where a trainee immediately repeats an input of a speech verbatim, a practice that has divided scholars into fervent advocates and staunch opponents (Pöchhacker, 2016). Indeed, Judicial Council California (Judicial Council of California, 2008) provides for shadowing as an important part of interpreters training. It further builds on the shadowing exercise another skill, which is “to perform other tasks while shadowing”. On the other hand, Kurz (1992), considering neuroscience findings, doubts the usefulness of shadowing, which misses a crucial element, namely “active analysis of the speech input”. The contention can be eased, if not resolved, by understanding which exercise or training methodology agrees with human brain functionality, which is the proper domain of neuroscience.

2.10.1 Perspectives from psychology and neuroscience

The interaction between psychology and interpreting came as a result of interest that students of interpreting studies as well as psychology showed in their approaches to interpreting. In the area of pedagogy, Pöchhacker (2016) argues that the apprenticeship paradigm of transferring knowledge in the pedagogy of interpreters was viewed by some researchers as lacking a scientific basis. This is supported by Ferreira, Schwieter and Gile (2015) who suggest that translation studies were not based on empirical research, which is a necessary part of cognitive science. Language interpreting researchers, therefore, started look for insights from other disciplines such as cognitive sciences (Pöchhacker, 2016). Likewise, psychologists developed interest in researching interpreting, with the first psychology-based

study of interpreting produced by Henri Barik, in the form of a doctorate dissertation on simultaneous interpreting (Millán & Bartrina, 2013). This was followed by psychological research about interpreting. Examples include the inquiry of the segmentation of information as used by interpreters before encoding a message (Goldman-Eisler, 1972), the decoding process consecutive interpreters use in note-taking (Garretson, 1981), how interpreters use their working memory (Bajo et al., 2001) and how reliance on linear thinking raises educational concerns, because it focusses on only one part of the brain, that is the left hemisphere, while effective learning requires also the use of the right hemisphere, responsible for such tasks as synthesis and processing of context (Merritt, 2008). Psychology also has a role in exploring the interpreting linguistic phenomenon. Relevant psychological considerations derive from the assumptions that interpreting requires mental energy and sometimes requires more mental energy that an individual have, which affects his performance (Gile, 2009). Apart from linguistic knowledge, an interpreter must acquire neuropsychological strategies, especially to deal with short-term memory (Daro, 1994). Specifically, according to Ferreira, Schwieter and Gile (2015), many researchers have discerned the value of cognitive science, a branch of psychology, to professional conference interpreting. Others, such as Bajo et al. (2001), assessed the relevance of cognitive science to interpreting studies, focussing on cognitive processes, including attention and memory. Following the same cognitive approach, Ma (2013) analyses the interpreting cognitive procedures that, according to her, fall into five categories: perception, decoding, recording, encoding and expressing procedures. This preliminary review of the role of psychology and cognitive psychology in giving insights to researchers in understanding mental processes governing the work of interpreters raises, in fact, a question about what neuroscience can add to the literature.

To answer this question, there is a need to first explore the distinctions between cognitive psychology and neuroscience, in terms of definition, areas of interest and approaches.

Firstly, cognitive psychology is defined as a field of psychology that investigates mental functions, including perception, learning, memory and planning (Corsini, 1999). Areas of interest include, according to Braisby and Gellatly (2012), attention, perception, recognition, concepts, language processing, memory, problem solving, decision making and emotion. The approaches that cognitive psychologists use are representation, computation, symbol system and connectionism, according to Braisby and Gellatly (2012), as cognitive psychology studies the mind.

As for neuroscience, Bear, Connors and Paradiso (2007) explain that it is a relatively new term, dating back to the 1970s with the introduction of the positron emission tomography (PET) and later on the development of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) in the 1990s. According to neuroscience studies, human brain and the nervous system with the purpose of answering questions about how humans behave, sense, learn, remember and do other cognitive skills. They further suggest its multidisciplinary approach has offered solutions for some mysteries of the human brain and make tangible conclusions. Breidbach (2001) defines it as the science that addresses the functional organisation of the brain and the resulting behaviours. In addition, Carter and Shieh (2015) make an explicit distinction between the study of the mind and the study of the brain, with the latter field being the subject of neuroscience. Neuroscientists follow in their research methods the techniques of case studies, screening, describing, and manipulation (Carter & Shieh, 2015) through the use of invasive as well as non-invasive technology (Engel, Moll, Fried, & Ojemann, 2005).

2.10.2 Neuroscience and bilingualism

Research in neuroscience addressed some issues of bilingualism and interpretation. Hervais-Adelman, Moser-Mercer, Michel and Golestani (2014) conducted a neuroimaging experiments on bilinguals and simultaneous interpreting, finding that experienced interpreters show higher levels of cognitive flexibility compared with those of bilinguals, with the allusion that being a bilingual does not necessarily qualify a person to work as an interpreter. Elmer and Kühnis (2016) found that compared to multilingual control participants, simultaneous interpreters had their left-dorsal pathway strengthened by training. Using neuroimaging techniques, Van de Putte et al. (2018) found an increase in mental activation, particularly in the right angular gyrus and left superior temporal gyrus, compared with what they observed in a group of translators, undergoing the same longitudinal experiment. They also found significant increment in the interconnectivity of some brain regions in charge of language-specific cognitive control, with the conclusion that such mental mechanisms enable interpreters to manage the highly demanding task of simultaneous interpreting. Another study,

2.10.3 Neuroscience of education

The findings and capabilities of neuroscience studies in enhancing understanding of learning have attracted mainstream educators in several respects. Hart (1983) was among the earliest scholars to advocate for the relevance of neuroscience to education, coining the term “brain-compatible” to describe an educational setting that matches how the brain functions best. In the 1990s, political support for neuroscience studies increased when U.S. President George Bush declared the decade as the “Decade of the Brain” (Myslinski, 2022). However, despite such enthusiasm, the practical application of neuroscience to education was not immediately clear (Willingham & Lloyd, 2007).

Bruer (1997) was a strong critic of the early enthusiasm, warning that introducing neuroscience concepts to teachers could foster misconceptions, such as the “right-brain, left-brain” fallacy, and highlighting the difficulties in applying laboratory-based neuroscience findings to complex classroom environments. Similarly, Bowers (2016) argued that neuroscience in education does not offer explanations beyond those of behavioural psychology, suggesting that proponents are often misguided. Tommerdahl (2010) also cautioned that, while neuroscience may have potential in special education, it cannot yet be directly applied to typical classroom practice.

Concerns were also raised by Fischer, Goswami, Geake and Neuroscience (2010), who pointed to the prevalence of myths among practitioners, while Hruby (2012) noted ethical issues and the lack of coherence among neuroscientists themselves. Brockington et al. (2018) criticised neuroscience research for relying on oversimplified tests and artificial experiments, which hinder generalisability to real-world educational settings. More recently, Amran and Sommer (2024) emphasised the neuroscience literacy gap among teachers, who often struggle to distinguish scientific findings from popular myths.

Despite these criticisms, numerous advocates remained optimistic about the potential of neuroscience in education. Wolfe (1998) theorised how memory is stored during learning, using the example of a child who misidentifies a dog as a cat to illustrate how prior neural networks influence memory retrieval. Winters (2001) maintained that research on memory and brain plasticity offers opportunities to enhance students' memory formation. McGeehan (2001) stressed that understanding brain dynamics could inform instructional changes and discourage “brain-antagonistic” teaching practices, identifying emotion, intelligence, and information storage as critical areas illuminated by brain-based research.

Howard-Jones (2007) surveyed teachers and found that over 90% believed learning about the brain was crucial for developing educational programmes. Nevertheless, he later warned against the oversimplified translation “from brain scan to lesson plan” (Howard-Jones, 2011). Clement and Lovat (2012) similarly cautioned that there is limited evidence supporting the direct application of neuroscience findings to classroom settings. Tommerdahl (2010) proposed a multi-level model whereby analyses move from neuroscience to cognitive neuroscience, psychological mechanisms, educational theory, and finally to classroom practice.

Further studies highlighted the brain’s role in learning. More and Rane (2016) asserted that learning cannot occur if the brain’s natural processes are obstructed. Cercone (2006) demonstrated that brain-based learning theory provides a credible framework, particularly for online learners, by facilitating improved understanding of how students learn. Similarly, Willis (2007) advocated for joyful, motivating classroom environments aligned with neuroscience principles. Jensen (2008) also supported the integration of neuroscience into education, criticising traditional models of schooling, while Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) likened outdated education systems to a “masochist coffee pot” to underscore the need for brain-compatible reform.

Memory research has also contributed to this evolving understanding. Huhtala (2006) recognised the continued relevance of rote memory for mastering factual knowledge, while Yandow (2007) argued that learning should activate as many neural pathways as possible to make information usable. Noureen, Awan and Fatima (2017) observed that rote learning remains dominant in Pakistani education, underscoring the global relevance of brain-based teaching practices.

Newer research reflects a more balanced view of neuroscience's place in education. Tandon and Singh (2016) acknowledged challenges in translating neuroscience research into

classroom practice but contended that the field is evolving and may contribute increasingly over time. Tang (2017) defended neuroscience, arguing that the gap between neuroscience research and educational application stems not from neuroscience itself but from educators' continued reliance on outdated behavioural models.

Recent scholars such as (Cañas, 2024) have argued that understanding key concepts—such as executive functions, brain plasticity, attention, and motivation—can dismantle myths and enhance how teachers view the brain's adaptability. Dubinsky, Roehrig and Varma (2022) confirmed that, although direct application remains challenging, teachers can still draw upon neuroscience to gain insight into students' cognitive processes and guide effective pedagogical strategies. Geake and Cooper (2003) concluded that neuroscience research into brain functioning significantly enhances our understanding of cognitive behaviour, a core concern in education.

2.10.4 Functions of brain regions

Studies about the brain (e.g. Wolfe (2009); Huhtala (2006) and Bear, Connors and Paradiso (2007)) clear up the misconception that memory is stored in specific parts of the body. Instead, once an individual receives information or experience, it is deconstructed in the brain then distributed all over the cortex. Recalling information from memory requires certain parts of the brain to be triggered, which makes Wolfe (2009) conclude that enhancing information retrieval, or reconstruction, requires an individual to have learnt it in different ways. She further explains that when subjects of neuroscience experiments were given a memory task, it was found that all brain regions light up on the monitor, with the conclusion that the brain rewires itself when making or recalling a memory, a suggestion that finds support elsewhere in the literature (Yandow, 2007).

In an invasive experiment (Bear, Connors, & Paradiso, 2007), scientists surgically removed a finger from a monkey after deciding on the part of the brain that responds to sensory input from that finger, with the result of that area changing its behaviour by starting to respond to other stimuli. This so-called ‘synaptic plasticity’ denotes that memory is a reconstruction process, involving the rewiring of neurons. In other words, making a memory through learning leads to constant modifications in the brain system.

Waugh, Grant and Ross (2001) explain in depth the parts of the brain and their functions, which are reduced, in this section, to those of specific significance to memory and other related concerns. The cerebral cortex of the brain has four main lobes: the frontal, temporal, occipital and parietal lobes. They are responsible for executive functions, such as decision, planning, attention, behaviour and emotion, and speech and language, memory and planned movement (the frontal lobe); perception and sensation (the parietal lobe), recognition of visual information, such as colour and shape (occipital lobe) and sound, speech and memory (the temporal lobe).

The frontal lobe is responsible for short memory actions, including executive functions such as decision making, reasoning, learning in addition to creative abilities (Collins & Koechlin, 2012). It monitors a limited number of tasks to three actions happening concurrently, which indicates that multitasking might not be a good strategy for learning. Its Broca’s area is responsible for the production of speech and its prefrontal cortex carries out functions related to working memory (Society for Neuroscience, 2006) and anticipation of likely outcomes of actions (Bear, Connors, & Paradiso, 2007). Other areas of interest are the prefrontal cortex and Wernick’s area. The former is responsible for comprehension of time passage, the ability to make anticipations and management of emotions. The latter is important for language

comprehension and higher mental functions (Waugh, Grant, & Ross, 2001). The insular cortex is located deep below the frontal, parietal and temporal lobes. Little is known about its functionalities (Tamraz, Comair and Tamraz (2004); Gogolla (2017)), but Gogolla (2017) says there are clues supporting the assumptions that this part of the brain is responsible for emotions, motor control, prediction of risk, decision making, awareness and empathy.

Deeper in the subcortical region of the brain, the limbic system plays functions related to emotion, learning and memory (Bear, Connors, & Paradiso, 2007). It is mainly composed of the amygdala (an emotion and partial memory centre), the hippocampus (primary memory centre), the thalamus (coordination of sensory and motor impulses), the hypothalamus (body temperature, blood pressure and hunger), the cingulate (attention), olfactory bulb (smell) (Wright, Tibbetts, & Daigle, 2014).

2.10.5 Human memory

The quality of interpretation, hinges upon the efficiency of the interpreter's memory, since, as Mahmood Yenkimaleki and Heuven (2013) suggest, the interpreter has, first of all, to store the source message in his memory, while finding a suitable equivalence in the target language. Memory, however, is not a physical storage object in human body, but, as Turkington and Harris (2002) explain, it spreads over the brain through a web of synapses, and it has several systems, each relating to a different sort of remembering. According to them, memory begins with perception that comes to one's mind through the senses. An experience can get into the brain through different senses at the same time, with each stimulus going to the hippocampus, whose function is to store all relevant stimuli as one experience. Stimuli trigger changes in the neurons, namely the synapses, and with training, education and learning, a person's brain reconnects its synapses to consolidate memory. The input goes to the hippocampus but also to

the amygdala, the regulator of emotions, and will be stored there if it arouses emotions (Turkington & Harris, 2002). At this point, the newly received information is residing in the short-term memory, a term that neuroscientist use to describe the phenomenon where information is temporarily held and that quickly disappears, unless it undergoes subsequent processing (Turkington & Harris, 2002). Once a new experience or piece of information is adequately strengthened, it gets stored into the long-term memory, through a process known as consolidation (Bear, Connors, & Paradiso, 2007).

Two critical notions are reported to be fundamental to the understanding of memory. Firstly, when exposed to an experience, humans do not literally nor linearly store information, but blend new information with one's prior knowledge about the world then reconstruct the learnt experience, accordingly (Brod, Werkle-Bergner, & Shing, 2013). This reliance leads to the implication that if prior knowledge is weak, errors can happen in understanding a message, which in turns implies that if one develops his own knowledge about the world, the same received experience will be reconstructed differently, possibly adding new meaning to it. Secondly, the brain will be selective in 'attending' to what information or thought is to be stored in the memory, for which reason scholars define attention as a mechanism whereby one's brain selects information in a scale of priority in order to control further action or behaviour (Rueda, Pozuelos, & Cómbita, 2015). Selectiveness occurs when the cognitive load is too high in a situation that requires attention to be directed towards a given goal, by ignoring undesirable interferences and distractors (Lavie, Hirst, De Fockert, & Viding, 2004). In the same vein, lowering the cognitive load can balance released neurotransmitters, such as noradrenaline and cortisol, hence probably leading the learner to more efficient attention and more rapid acquisition of the learning task (Henshall, Randle, Francis, & Freire, 2022). In contrast, a

material that is condensed with texts instead of images can considerably increase the cognitive load (Huang & Chen, 2023)

2.10.6 The AGES model

Davachi, Kiefer, Rock and Rock (2010) proposed the AGES model based on neuroscience findings with the aim of introducing a framework for enhancing learning that ‘sticks’ in learner’s minds. “AGES” is an acronym, which stands for Attention, Generation, Emotions and Spacing. The authors contend that by understanding brain dynamics, the learning experience can be effective. The model has received considerable attention by companies and learning institutes. An example is IBM corporation, which cited the AGES model in corroborating its arguments about accelerating employees’ learning (Cook, Miranda, & Shriver, 2018). In scholastic literature, few references are made the AGES model as summarized below.

Morgan (2004) offered a guide for facilitators, to improve their skills for group and team discussion, and under adult learning styles, she claimed misconceptions about learning are the result of a lack of understanding of neuroscience findings. She elaborates on AGES model's attention, generation, emotions, and spacing elements, to support her arguments.

Diab, Matthews and Gokool (2016) employed the AGES model to explore views of students on using a video in teaching language. By applying the focus-group discussion instrument, they concluded that the benefits that student got through the video were “well-related” to the AGES model. Bahgat, Elsafty, Shaarawy and Said (2018) theorized a framework for effective learning based on previous research in areas of facilitative learning, cooperative learning, psychology and neuroscience, citing AGES model in the theoretical framework of the study. Abu Bakar and Abdul Ghani (2022) cited AGES model in their meta-analysis of articles on neuroscience of education, concluding that literacy in neuroscience has significantly

contributed to effective learning, particularly in mathematics. Abu Bakar, Abdul Ghani, Abdullah, Ismail and Abdul Aziz (2022) used the AGES model in their exploratory study on mathematics students and found that the model can account for students' learning abilities, weaknesses and opportunities for effective learning.

Abu-Bakar, Ab-Ghani and Abdullah (2024) used the AGES model as a bridge between neuroscience and the classroom learning environment. The reported result was that the neuroscience approach can be effective in various uses such as critical subjects and complex skills.

2.10.6(a) Attention

James (1918) defines attention as “the taking possession by the mind, in clear and vivid form, of one out of what seem several simultaneously possible objects or trains of thought. Focalization, concentration, of consciousness are of its essence. It implies withdrawal from some things in order to deal effectively with others, and is a condition which has a real opposite in the confused, dazed, scatter-brained state. According to Lindsay (2020), attention can be described in terms of arousal, alertness and vigilance, in relation to one's ability to engage with surroundings and sustain attention. Attention is necessary also for transferring knowledge from short-term memory into long-term memory, in a process called consolidation (Michael-Titus, Shorland, & Revest, 2010).

Paying attention requires engagement with the learning experience and exclusion of distractors (Jensen, 2005). Under the AGES model, distractors can be multitasking, where one is focusing on several sources of information at the same time, application of counter-productive forms of learning in the classroom or external factors, such as email popping out when one is engaged in a virtual classroom learning (Davachi et al., 2010), and anxiety and

stress (Turkington & Harris, 2002). The maximum time limit (span) to which a person can maintain attention is a source of controversy among scholars, who overwhelmingly indicate it is 20 minutes at maximum (Turkington & Harris, 2002), but could be significantly as low as 8 seconds to 10 minutes, but lack of scientific evidence rules out a definitive answer (Bradbury, 2019).

The AGES model approach to attention is based on neuroscience findings. According to Davachi et al. (2010), effective learning requires the hippocampus to be activated. This cannot happen if an individual's attention is obstructed by distractors, such as multitasking, with the implication that learning activities in the classroom environment should be well directed. Boosting attention, from a neuroscience perspective, requires a good supply of two important brain chemicals: dopamine, which is associated with feelings of reward and relevance, and norepinephrine, responsible for alertness. This finding agrees with those of other scholars, such as Rueda, Pozuelos and Cómbita (2015). Brownson (2016) also suggests that creating a reward feeling is associated with dopamine, which can be safely released in the brain by such simple activities as giving charity or helping needy people. In a similar vein, presenting to students a humorous video at the beginning of the training can increase long-term memory retention, especially if the videos are related to the training (O'day (2007); Steffes and Duverger (2012). Memory formation also relies on co-activation of the amygdala and hippocampus, which can be achieved through positive emotions (Katsumi & Dolcos, 2020).

With this in mind, the AGES model recommends a couple of learning techniques including the use of visuals, storytelling, establishing interest in the topic and engaging learners in the learning experience (Davachi et al., 2010). This finds support in a recent study, where

visuals and kinesthetics in multimedia in training were helpful in reducing cognitive load (Li, 2023).

Relevant to attention discussions is mind wandering, which is a spontaneous activity that an awake person can do without engaging in cognitive tasks (Gruberger, Ben-Simon, Levkovitz, Zangen, & Hendler, 2011). Mind wandering can be useful to students as it can engage them in future-oriented thinking and creative thinking and releases them from boredom; (Smallwood & Schooler, 2015) ; (Pachai, Acai, LoGiudice, & Kim, 2016). In mind wandering, an individual would shift focus from a cognitive task to anything unrelated to it, which triggers the default mode network in the brain (Zhou & Lei, 2018). About the reason why minds wander, Killingsworth and Gilbert (2010) suggest that people go off track of a present topic to indulge themselves into an imagined state of happiness, though this may not necessarily make them happy. This finds support in another research, where mind wandering was evident in schizophrenia patients, who show the trait of decoupling from reality (Yamaoka & Yukawa, 2020). Another explanation is that it happens with an individual who sees little value in what he is presented with or when he tries to find other goals more relevant than the one currently dealt with (Shepherd, 2019). Mind wandering correlates with higher creativity as it activates the grey matter in the brain (Jauk, Neubauer, Dunst, Fink, & Benedek, 2015) The process involves recollection of events in episodic memory, which activates the hippocampus (Kempadoo, Mosharov, Choi, Sulzer, & Kandel, 2016), and higher activation of the hippocampus correlates with the accuracy of events that an individual tries to remember (Prabhakar, Johnson, Nordahl, & Ghetti, 2018).

In the same vein, the Attention Restoration Theory (AR) holds that prolonged engagement of direct attention can lead to attention fatigue, requiring the individual to move into a restorative environment (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Similarly, Mooneyham and Schooler

(2013) found that mind wandering, although happening spontaneously, negatively affects performance in comprehension tests and conversations and can lead to adverse consequences such as medical errors or car accidents. Kohan et al. (2017) reported students expressing frustration as mind wandering caused them to divert from their assignments in self-directed learning.

2.10.6(b) Generation

Generation is defined as ownership of what a person learns by understanding a message, putting it in context, retaining it for future retrieval and applying the learned knowledge in real life (Davachi et al., 2010). Although repetition in a learning experience can have a significant impact on learners of CI, for example, as it improves trainees' accuracy (Yu & van Heuven, 2013), neuroscience finds its effect to be limited, which raises the question of the optimum way of making a learning experience memorable after in the post-attentional stage (Davachi et al., 2010). In order to optimise generation, Davachi et al. (2010) suggest that learning should promote strategies that can activate the hippocampus, thus, leading to more associations in the memory system. Those include allowing the trainee to evaluate the message and make sense of it by associating it with previous knowledge, adding in their own personal experience, be self-directed in the learning process and visualise situations. On the teacher's part, (Davachi et al., 2010) urge teachers to reduce their roles as information presenters. The role of 'generation' in supporting memory formation and retrieval is supported by an experimental neuroscience study (Kim & Johnson, 2013) which finds that the medial prefrontal cortex (responsible for functions related to working memory and decision making (Sheynikhovich, Otani, Bai, & Arleo, 2023)) is more active when individuals try to link up the message they receive with what they already know so that they make it relevant to them.

2.10.6(c) Emotions

Emotions play an important role in making a memory, and messages with emotional contents are easier to remembered than those with neutral emotions (Garrison & Schmeichel, 2019). When a learning experience is triggered by an emotional stimulus, it helps the individual to focus attention (which is the first stage of the AGES model) and engage in further processing (Garrison and Schmeichel (2019); (Davachi et al., 2010) and Phelps (2004)). Technically speaking, while the amygdala and hippocampus are independent systems, the amygdala is fast at responding to emotional stimuli, which can make changes in the hippocampal memory formation by giving priority to emotional events (Phelps, 2004). According to the AGES model, emotions can be negative and positive, with the negative ones being much easier to be fixed in one's memory. Davachi et al. (2010) conclude that if a training programme is heavily reliant on negative emotions, such as fear, then this would affect the trainee's desire to continue in that programme, mainly because negative emotions curb novelty and innovation. They also point out to the importance of allowing individuals to perform positive anticipation, to make the learning experience enjoyable and rewarding and get the trainees more engaged. This is, furthermore, consistent with studies (e.g. Jensen (2005)) showing that the dopamine increases when an individual perceives a reward, which hence, increases attention.

A core emotional element in learning is the feeling of reward. Cambridge Dictionary ("reward," 2022) defines 'reward' as "something given in exchange for good behaviour or good work, etc." Rewards can enhance people's attention, thereby improving memory encoding in the brain (Loftus, 1972), and if the rewards are unpredictable, they can raise the dopamine levels in learners, thereby improving their learning experience (Mirenowicz & Schultz, 1994). Reward anticipation, on the other hand, can activate the amygdala and ventral striatum, according to

(O'Doherty, 2004), so that educators should decide when and where a reward will be given, so as to make decisions on behavioural change. Feeling rewarded also helps in improving semantic processing (van Touw, 2015), modulates information-seeking behaviour and strengthens autonomous knowledge acquisition (Murayama, FitzGibbon, & Sakaki, 2019). Feeling rewarded helps release the dopamine in the midbrain, which further reinforces learning and can enhance declarative memory information (Howard-Jones & Jay, 2016). The release of dopamine in the brain is also associated with strengthening the working memory (Roffman et al., 2016), spatial learning (Kempadoo et al., 2016) and episodic memory (Kamiński et al., 2018). Empirical research suggests ways to release the dopamine for better attention and learning, including by engaging in family games (Estrada-Plana, Esquerda, Mangués, March-Llanes, & Moya-Higueras, 2019), adequate exposure to sunlight (Tsai et al., 2011), getting enough sleep (Volkow et al., 2012), listening to music and meditation (Blood & Zatorre, 2001).

Intrinsic rewards come spontaneously and naturally in the current situation, while extrinsic rewards are not connected with the situation (O'Leary and O'Leary (1972); Guzzo (1979)). In business, recent studies show that extrinsic rewards can have positive impact on the performance of workers (Ifeoma, Chukwuebuka, & Chidinna, 2023), whereas others suggest that financial rewards contingent upon task performance could harm intrinsic rewards (Deci (1972). Recent research also suggests that both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards can boost the acquisition of competence (Ifeoma, Chukwuebuka, & Chidinna, 2023), with the teacher's role evident in enhancing reward by providing for constructive and engaging learning environments (Covelli, 2024).

Frustration and boredom are negative feelings that can interfere in the learning of students, and there can be several causes for those two feelings. Without preparation or organization, students who set unrealistic goals, get disappointed if those are not attained (Shih,

Chen, Chang, & Kao, 2010), and frustration increase as the tasks become more complex (Chen & Law, 2016). Nevertheless, frustration can be significantly reduced if students own their learning (Wahbi, 2018) and if they are given the chance to learn from the errors of colleagues, especially through peer-feedback, instead of being put in a situation where they repeatedly commit mistakes when performing a given task (Wolff, Friedhoff, Schwarzer, & Pucker, 2023).

From a psychological perspective, boredom can be defined as the non-optimal arousal state resulting when the immediate environment does not provide the stimulation necessary to meet a person's arousal needs (Csikszentmihalyi, 1975). Given our limited attention span, humans can get bored if they are unable to focus on tasks perceived as either disengaging or uninteresting (LePera, 2011). This results in a drop in dopamine levels, known to be a reason for losing stamina or creating a state of boredom in the individual (Artaloytia et al., 2006) In learning environments, restoring the dopamine to its balanced levels may require the teacher to introduce something different to students including humour and visuals to prevent boredom (Uden, Sulaiman, Ching, & Juan, 2023). Nevertheless, an earlier empirical study suggest that even when an individual has a negative feelings about something, he can still reframe it through 'reappraisal', turning it into an opportunity (Gross, 1998). In this vein, a student could, through 'punishment', reflect on the consequences of negative behaviour to improve their learning (Harahap & Ginting, 2024).

One final point about emotions relates to mirror neurons. Those are activated when an individual performs a motor act and notices another individual doing a similar act (Kliner & Lemon, 2013). When mirror neurons are activated, an observing learner can be better off in aligning his goals with the goals and intentions of the training (Fogassi L, 2005), improves synapses connectivity, hence improving the observer to repeat the same act (Kosonogov, 2012)

and creates empathy (Sahu, 2023). Another study, however, adds that even imagining an act can fire mirror neurons (ES, AFdC, & ST, 2006). This is relevant to the concept of "proximity" in literary studies (Rorty, 1991), introduced by Aristotle as crucial to engendering an emotional connection between the audience and tragic characters. This emotional closeness fosters empathy, enabling the audience to feel deeply the adversities that befall the tragic protagonist. An interesting parallel can be drawn from neuroscience, where mirror neurons play a crucial role in evoking empathy between viewers and the main character. In contrast, comedic characters are often endowed with a sense of superiority or transgress established norms and expectations in order to elicit humour. This could be called alienation (Carlsten (2023)). While empathy (proximity) finds studies in neuroscience, alienation is not well noted or studied in the area.

2.10.6(d) Spacing

Spacing is a term introduced by German Psychologist Ebbinghaus Hermann, whose experiments on memory led him to believe that by increasing the interval between active recalls, the probability of forgetting information decreases (Hermann, 1998). Spaced learning is juxtaposed by a traditional way of teaching where students have to receive masses of learning blocks in a short period of time (Davachi et al., 2010). The 'spaced-effect' notion has been extensively studied over the decades where many advantages of the technique were recorded. Ausubel (1966) found that delayed intervals between presentation and review motivated students to benefit from the review by reflecting on the effort and attention that needs to be put and the parts of the material that has been forgotten. Jacoby (1978) finds that unlike spaced learning, massed repetitions led students to remember the solution of a problem rather than reconstruct the process of solving it, as a result of what he calls 'automaticity. In order to avoid

this automaticity effect, he suggests providing a delay since the last presentation with the length that is commensurate with the situation at hand. Assignments can best help in retention if spread out in long rather than short intervals (Suydam, 1985), and learning was significantly boosted through spaced presentations ((Dempster, 1987). More recent studies support spacing as a means to improve memory retention, hence learning outcomes such as: Chen, Castro-Alonso, Paas and Sweller (2018); Dabiri, Mohammadi and Mojtahedzadeh (2019) and Namaziandost (2020).

Kornmeier and Sosic-Vasic (2012) contend that spaced learning at intervals that can take between seconds to days is twice better than massed learning, depending on the cognitive load entailed. According to Kelley and Watson (2013), long-term potentiation (LTP) is achieved when repeated stimuli are separated by temporal spaces, leading to better educational outcomes. The influence of spaced learning is supported by Abdi Tabari, Lee and Hanzawa (2025) where amassed learning significantly reduces achievement and increases stress.

The AGES model suggests that while it is difficult to determine an optimum temporal space for learning (such as minutes, hours or days), spacing does, nevertheless, improve retrieval rates. It helps students to understand the context of presented information then apply it. It also gives time to the brain to grasp new content and establish new wire connections. Sleep is also considered as an effective spacing habit, especially if happening shortly after information is encoded in the learning process, since it helps new information to be stored in the long-term memory, as James Maas suggests (Greer, 2004). Following the temporal space, activities for memory consolidation involve priming, reviewing and testing. The strategies that instructors use in delivering an interpreter training should be compatible with the brain.

2.11 Learning styles

The learning styles theory is a concept that suggests that individuals think differently and learn best in different ways (Willingham, Hughes, & Dobolyi, 2015), and learning styles theories try to explore individuals' preferences to suggest ways of reinforcing their learning experience. The theory can be traced back to the works of Carl Jung, a gestalt psychologist who proposed that learners have their own unique cognitive preferences. The Jungian learning styles theory inspired further research in cognitive psychology. Based his theory, studies have found that introverts, extraverts and intuitive students prefer audio-visual presentations and learning alone, collaborate learning and field dependent learning, while sensors prefer hands on (Sharp, 2012). Based on Carl Jung's theory, some models have been developed by time.

2.11.1 The Experiential Learning Style

As the name suggests, the Experiential Learning Style holds that learners learn best through experience. The model was developed by David Kolb in 1984 then revised three times since then. According to Kolb (2015), there are four general experiential styles:

- (1) Accommodating learners best learn through hand on training and taking risks
- (2) Assimilating learners prefer structured environments, listening to lectures, reading, and conceptualizing complex ideas.
- (3) Converging learners learn by connecting the theoretical knowledge they have with practice so that they learn by conceptualization after reflections to solve problems.
- (4) Diverging learners learn through creativity, imagination and idea generation and find themselves best suited in collaborative learning environments and group discussions and are good at introspection to learn by reflecting on their own experience.

2.11.2 Honey and Mumford's Learning Styles

Peter Honey and Alan Mumford expanded on Kolb's model as they identified four learning styles, each representing unique cognitive behaviour (Allioua & Benkouiten, 2023): activists, who learn through hands on and experience; reflectors, who learn by observing and reflecting on their own experience; theorists, who learn by finding associations between concepts, and pragmatists who learn through trial and error. The benefits of this model include its offering of a tailored education (Magdin & Turcáni, 2015), promotes self-awareness (Lang, 2023), and focuses on experience. However, it comes under criticism of oversimplification (Lashley & Barron, 2006), and lack of empirical support (Bedek et al.).

2.11.3 Fedler and Silverman's Learning Styles

This learning style model was developed by Richard M. Felder and Linda K. Silverman, who classify learners into four dimensions (Felder & Silverman, 1988):

Sensing/Intuitive Learning: The Sensing/Intuitive dimension delineates two distinct learning styles. Sensing learners predominantly rely on their five senses to acquire information, demonstrating a preference for tangible, practical, and well-structured learning environments. They adopt a procedural approach, often favoring step-by-step learning. In contrast, intuitive learners gravitate towards the broader perspective, exhibiting a propensity for pattern recognition and a preference for exploring concepts and ideas within a more expansive context.

Visual/Verbal Learning: Visual learners exhibit a predilection for information conveyed through visual media such as images, diagrams, and videos. They excel at perceiving relationships between concepts and often employ visualization to recall information. Verbal learners, conversely, thrive when presented with verbal information, feeling most at ease in contexts such as lectures, discussions, and written materials.

Active/Reflective Learning: The Active/Reflective dimension discerns between learners who prefer active, hands-on engagement and those who favour a more reflective, introspective approach. Active learners excel in practical and empirical learning environments, engaging in activities and interactions. They thrive in group discussions and find learning through real-world applications most effective. Reflective learners, in contrast, gravitate towards introspection and analytical thinking. They require time for deep contemplation and often prefer solitary self-learning over group discussions.

Sequential/Global Learning: The Sequential/Global dimension distinguishes between learners who favour a step-by-step, linear approach and those who adopt a holistic, broad perspective. Sequential learners excel in well-structured, systematic learning environments, where they perceive concepts as interrelated and prefer a precise presentation of information. Global learners, conversely, prefer to grasp the overarching picture before delving into specific details. They excel in making connections between seemingly unrelated pieces of information and thrive in creative and broad-thinking subjects.

2.11.4 Criticism of learning styles theories

Learning Styles Theories, while widely employed in research, have encountered notable criticism within the academic discourse. The very premise of these theories presents challenges for special educators when attempting to tailor the curriculum to the unique needs of individual learners. The act of accommodating one learning style can inadvertently exclude others, as noted by Al-Zahran (2007)

Maccleave and Eghan (2010) reject the inclination of learning styles theories to label or stereotype students. They contend that a student's learning style may exhibit variability over time, thus advocating that discussions pertaining to learning styles should prioritise the broader

concept of learning, rather than succumbing to the pitfalls of oversimplification and overgeneralization inherent in student stereotyping.

Concurrently, Scott (2010) levels criticism at what she perceives as a 'one-size-fits-all approach' perpetuated by learning styles theories. In her view, such an approach not only lacks validity but also holds the potential for causing harm.

Critics further underscore the inadequacy of empirical support for these theories, with scholars like Brown (2023), Joswick, Skultety and Olsen (2023), and Zrudlo (2023) highlighting the conspicuous dearth of empirical validation. Furthermore, they emphasise the dynamic nature of learning styles, positing that learners may transition between styles in response to various factors, such as motivation, cultural background, and prior knowledge, as elucidated by Joswick, Skultety and Olsen (2023).

2.11.5 Research on Jordan students' learning styles

The following is a review of some studies conducted on the learning styles of Jordanian university students.

Abu-Moghli, Khalaf, Halabi and Wardam (2005) explored the learning styles as perceived by nursing students, using quantitative method, and found that the majority of the sampled students showed interest in independent learning and in learning new things. Students also indicated themselves having curiosity to learn, while the vast majority reported lacking the skills necessary for studying, concentration and time management.

In another study on third-year students of nursing at a public university (Alkhasawneh, Mrayyan, Docherty, Alashram, & Yousef, 2008), an intervention based on the VARK model concluded that students preferred reading and writing followed by kinesthetics, in a learning environment where teachers used different learning activities. The study recommended teachers

to use models, debates, role playing, demonstrations and discussions in order to improve active learning.

An investigation into the thinking styles of tenth-grade Jordanian students using Herrmann's Whole Brain Model (Bawaneh, Zain, & Saleh, 2010) showed no significant differences in students' assignment to Herrmann's styles, recommending curriculum designers to observe this model, while observing the different learning styles and differences among students.

Mahasneh, Shoqirat, Singh and Hawks (2021) reported the preferred learning styles of Jordanian third and fourth-year nursing students, using the qualitative method, finding that students preferred a structured one-dimensional instructional strategy. Students also were found to be increasingly interested in simulation videos, especially those displayed on YouTube channel, which made them more willing to learn, recommending students' suggestions to be integrated in the enhancement of the educational setting.

2.12 Models of Brain Based Learning

For the purpose of this study, three models of brain-based learning are explored, as developed by Caine and Caine (1991), Hileman (2006) and Silver, Strong and Perini (2007).

2.12.1 The Twelve Principles of Brain-Based Learning

Caine and Caine (1991) provide a detailed description of traditional teaching, which, according to them, focuses on memorizing, is teacher-centered and is delivered through traditional sources, such as textbooks, lectures, even videos. They also cite a gap in alternative theories postulated as a replacement of traditional teaching, saying those were fragmented and

limited. The brain-based model they espouse seek to make leaning more meaningful for students and is based on 12 principles, which can be paraphrased as follows:

1. The brain is a parallel process: Since mental activities involving thoughts, emotion, imagination and predispositions happen at the same time and interact with other information modes, educators must use different methodologies that help in orchestrating those activities.
2. Learning engages the entire physiology: The brain has its own physiological rules, guiding its functionality. The learning experience must consider whatever affects brain physiology, such as stress, nutrition, exercise, among other things.
3. The search for meaning is innate: The brain spontaneously searches for meaning by looking into familiar ideas and responding to new information, and the learning environment must promote both types of information. This principle correlates with Silver's principles of thinking (Silver 1995), saying that thought is natural and strategic.
4. The search for meaning occurs through patterning. The brain perceives information in patterns, which means isolated unrelated pieces of information are assimilated. Learners should be given the chance to create their own meaningful patterns.
5. Emotions are critical to patterning. Emotions are an integral part of learning as they attach to what a person learns. Thought and emotions are interconnected, because the "limbic system mediates both emotion and memory" Caine and Caine (1991, p. 57)
6. The brain processes parts and whole simultaneously. The brain is made up of two spheres, left and right, and during the learning experience, both hemispheres

interact separately but complementarily. One looks at the parts, while the other considers the whole.

7. Learning involves both focused attention and peripheral perception. The brain gets information directly through attention, but it also looks beyond that into peripheral stimuli. In other words, it considers the context where an experience is happening.
8. Learning always involves conscious and unconcise process. Learning is not confined to what the learner is aware of, but extends beyond that to the subconscious, where processes in the background are happening. Addressing peripheral context can help in stimulating the subconscious processing.
9. We have at least two different types of memory: a spatial memory system and a set for systems for rote learning. Spatial memory is spontaneous and effortless. It drives the brain's search for meaning and does not need rehearsal or repetition for later recollection. In contrast, there is a set of systems in the brain that address facts and sort out seemingly unrelated information, requiring rote memory and repetition. This distinction correlates with Kahneman's Systems 1 and 2 (Kahneman, 2011).
10. We understand and remember best when facts and skills are remembered in natural spatial memory. Vocabulary gets meaning in the brain when embedded in a person's experience. Spatial memory, in this connection, can be used best when people are engaged in an experiential learning with teachers, citing to their students examples from real life.

11. Learning is enhanced by challenge and inhibited by threat. Human brain performs better when challenges in a relaxing environment and downshifts when faced with threat.
12. Each brain is unique. People do not have different systems of brain, but since learning changes the structure of, it makes people unique. This finding is an agreement with Brownson (2016) and has implications for educators, who need to use multifaceted methods of teaching.

2.12.2 The BRAIN model

Taking BRAIN as an acronym (behaviour modification, routine development, attention training, intellectual stimulation and nutrition and physical health), Hileman (2006) suggests five principles governing brain-based strategies of teaching: brain's time clock, repetition, active learning, images and novelty. She draws the following implications:

The student's brain clock determines the peaks and nadirs of attentional capacity, which calls upon teachers to appropriately 'space' instructional activities in the classroom. This agrees with findings in other research such as Kelley and Whatson (2013).

Repetition, as a technique, agrees with the plasticity of neurons and enables the learner to be faster in retrieving stored knowledge or skills. However, too much repetition makes students has a boring effect on learners. To solve this problem, Hileman suggests that when using repetition, educators should apply approaches that make learning of interest to the learners.

Active movement in the classroom can consolidate memory retrieval, learning and self-confidence, because most of the brain cells are in charge of controlling movement. She suggests

teachers to set the goals while they are on the move and engage students in physical stretching exercises.

Based on the brain finding that human eyes can register around 36,000 messages every hour, Hileman recommends instructors to use visual aids, such as computers, cameras graphs, charts and bullet boards. Once humans are familiar with their surroundings, their brains work.

2.12.3 The Strategic Teachers' Model

Harvey Silver, Richard Strong and Matthew Perini (Silver, Strong, & Perini, 2007) developed the Strategic Teachers' Model, in light of brain based learning, particularly memory, to illustrate their view that the role of education is to bring together different types of individuals around a common area of learning through the application of different teaching strategies. Lamenting the fact that teachers often used limited sets of strategies in teaching, the authors bring together a variety of strategies under the umbrella of four core models: mastery, understanding, self-expressive and interpersonal strategies. According to them, those strategies, originally devised by other scholars, help in the design of thoughtful lessons, motivating students, implementing teaching plans at classroom, building skills for success, improving student achievements and addressing different kinds of knowledge. According to Silver, Strong and Perini (2007), each of those styles address different types of learners, and hence require different categories of sub-strategies of teaching.

The following diagram shows how the four styles of learning are meant to be used simultaneously in the classroom to assist students in developing their balanced and dynamic approach to their learning:

Figure 2.1 The Strategic Teachers' Model (Silver, Strong & Perini, 2007)

2.12.3(a) The Mastery Style

Originally proposed as 'learning for mastery' by Benjamin Bloom in 1968 (Guskey, 2007), the term was meant to refer an instructional strategy through which a tutor helps students 'master' certain skills and information through corrective feedback. After detecting areas of weaknesses, a tutor works out a corrective assignment, with the ultimate goal of having a student mastering a given unit before moving to the next (Guskey, 2007).

Under this style, Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) suggest four strategies. The New American Lecture seeks to make learning memorable; direct instruction enhances learners' independence; graduated difficulty strategy (based on the work of Mosston (1972)) allows the trainer to account for differences in the abilities of learners; and, teams-games-tournaments, where students learn under a cooperative environment.

2.12.3(b) Understanding Style

The understanding style was first introduced by researchers at Harvard Graduate School of Education led by David Perkins and Tina Blythe (Perkins & Blythe, 1994). Formally named ‘teaching for understanding’, this instructional style address students’ weakness in understanding key concepts in such disciplines as mathematics and sciences. In defining the term ‘understanding’, Perkins and Blythe (1994) suggest that it is not confined just to knowing something, as it also involves students’ ability to apply what they know by demonstrating the skills of explaining, citing examples, looking for evidence, making analogies and making generalisations.

In more details, Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) focus, in the understanding style, on students’ ability to reason and use logic. This prompts them to sub-divide the style into the strategies of comparing and contrasting, reading for meaning, concept attainment and mystery.

2.12.3(c) Self-Expressive Style

The key elements of the self-expressive style of learning are imagination, exploration and curiosity. Teachers adhering to this style should use strategies that focus on visualization, imagination and creativity (Rubio (2007); Silver, Strong and Perini (2007)). The main strategies that Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) use to serve this style are: inductive learning to enhance learners’ predictions, metaphorical expression, to compare things that seem to be different, pattern maker, to help learners see the patterns of ideas and texts and mind’s eyes, which learners use in reading to convert words into images that can be memorized.

2.12.3(d) The Interpersonal Style

There is a shortage in the literature about using the interpersonal style in training translation beginners, despite the fact that the emotional reactions of a student towards his peers

in the classroom can negatively affect their work as a group (Eraković, 2010). According to Silver, Strong and Perini (2007), the interpersonal style boosts learners' need to identify with the curriculum and with each other, with the instructor playing the role of a motivator. Under the interpersonal style, Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) devise four strategies: reciprocal learning (with students learning as partners), decision making (with students using their own criteria to make decisions), jigsaw strategy (with students forming an expert group to research a given topic) and community circle (a group discussion where students make a group understanding of the class).

Before closing this section, it is worthwhile reviewing the role of students in constructivist classrooms, which are aligned to brain-based education (Caine and Caine, 1991).

Constructivism is a learning theory influenced by cognitive psychology (Hausfather (2001); Karagiorgi and Symeou (2005)) that offers a model for learning that views knowledge as being actively constructed in the minds of learners (Bodner, 1986) and through their interpersonal interactions (Murphy, 2013). In this sense, constructivists argue that students interpret new information by associating it with that they know already (Lord, 1997). From a constructivist perspective, students relate to their individual subjective experience through which they interpret reality (Karagiorgi & Symeou, 2005) based on the assumption that humans create meaning rather than acquire it from the external world (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). Constructivist thought differs from other forms of learning where knowledge is presumed to be acquired through response strengthening or is instilled in students' long-term memory (R. E. Mayer, 2009). Constructivist learning happens in a flexible environment that allows students to set their learning objectives (Chen, 2014). An instructional design that follows this line of thought seeks to offer students with tool kits that facilitate student construction of knowledge

(Jonassen, 1991). It enables a shift from expecting students to learn the same thing to permitting different things by allowing them to decide what and how they learn (Karagiorgi & Symeou, 2005) and by supporting multiple interpretations reality (Jonassen, 1991). Constructive learning also facilitates learning through authentic tasks that simulate what learners should expect to encounter in real life (Cooperstein and Kocevar-Weidinger (2004); Splitter (2009)).

Mager (1961) conducted a preliminary investigation on six students who met the criterion of having the desire to learn about electronics. None of the students had had any experience in the subject matter, and the study found that a learner-generated sequence of learning is different from that of an instructor. He suggested this form of leaning to be promoted as a standard classroom procedure and contended that the instructional systems theory strips concepts and strategies from their meaning and suggest the application of other learning theories, such as constructivism, in the design of instructional materials (Bednar, Cunningham, Duffy, & Perry, 1992)

In the same vein, Roth (1994)described how students engaged in experimenting and problem solving on a constructivist laboratory environment, where she finds that students could learn how to investigate phenomena of interest to them and develop complex problem-solving skills.

Kim (2005)investigated the effectiveness of a constructivist teaching model on the academic achievement of students. His study involved 76 six grade students and found that from a statistical point of view, the experimental group preferred the constructivist approach more than the control group. The usefulness of constructivism has also been stressed in instruction design by Eksi (2007) whose study on 26 students and 41 teachers revealed that both students and teachers have had a positive attitude. Karakitsiou et al. (2012) studied the roles of students in medical education, suggesting a value for adapting student-defined learning goals

in producing a teacher-student cooperation environment. The study has found that the perspectives of students regarding curriculum can relieve them from stress and make learning enjoyable.

Gunckel and Moore (2005) discussed two strategies for an effective teacher-student partnership in codesigning the curriculum, based on the assumption that teachers and students are more than recipients or implementers of the material but are in a place to offer valued criticism of it. Interviews with the informants show that students can offer teachers and curriculum designers insight on the motivational and engagement aspects of lessons.

Investigating the effectiveness of constructivist instructional design, Booyse and Chetty (2016) conducted a study based on empirical research using focus group discussions involving 287 practicing teachers in South Africa. They found that a constructivist assessment offered students a self-development environment making them self-motivated and responsible for their own learning.

Gordon (2017) explored the participation of students and co-designers in a linguistics course, in which two students joined the designing team. Their role was to assist the instructor, offer feedback and create own blogs about the experience. They also assisted in writing the pre and post-test surveys. The study concluded that students ended the course with a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction, and that the experience was as much rewarding to the students as challenging.

According to Healey and Healey (2018), partnership between teachers and students go beyond getting feedback of students into recognising the agency of students who could be co-researchers, consultants to the staff and co-designers of the curriculum.

Nahar and Cross (2019) investigated the student-staff partnership (SSP) approach through which first-year students were involved in evaluating a module curriculum then

redesigning it, accordingly, before it is taught in the next semester. The study also involved those students in the co-creation of that curriculum. Through a focus group, the researchers found that SSP was effective in the evaluation and redesigning of the module and recommended the same action research to be conducted on the same module in the next semester. They also found students preferred a radical approach whereby they codesign the curriculum rather than teachers to experiment a prototype of a course and test it on them.

Stacey and Chan (2021) carried out a study in which they involved students in the design of a rhetoric course. The underpinning principle was that students should be involved in the design of their curriculum from the very beginning “to produce a student-centred liberal arts curriculum with deep educational connections to the local context”. The findings included an improvement in shared decisions, backstage conversations, shared cognition and mutual trust. Other researchers, in contrast, indicated some challenges to the application of constructivism in education. Fosnot (2013) argues that although constructivism is a theory of knowledge it is not documented as a teaching theory and that any use of it in instructional design requires a leap in education to meet the theory’s requirements. In the area of teaching of scientific courses, Osborne (1996) criticizes constructivism saying that it ignores important pedagogical practices such as telling or sowing scientific ideas to children.

Karagiorgi and Symeou (2005) point out to such areas of concern as the pre-specification of knowledge, the claim that defining learning outcomes in advance is not possible and the unlimited discretion and control given to students on the instructional design. Lai-Chong and Ka-ming (1996) suggest, however, that the prescriptive approach boils down to the traditional approach which is mainly based on predictability, where pre-defined behavioural responses can be predetermined and reductionism, where knowledge and skills can be broken down into its constituent parts. Kirschner, Sweller and Clark (2006) criticise the constructivist

learning theory arguing that minimally-guided approaches are heedless to empirical studies that find unguided instructions ineffective in learning environments. Wise and O'Neill (2009) contend the absence of empirical research that would otherwise prove the amount of guidance per se as the sole decisive factor in the quality of instruction, which should take into consideration other factors such as context and timing of instruction.

Researchers also explore the role of students in a constructivist learning environment and curriculum planning. According to Brown (1992), students should take the roles of coinvestigators and consultants of their own learning.

Huppatz (1996) explained how she was a student involved in the planning of the Graduate Entry Curriculum for a medical college in Australia. Suggesting that only students are aware of their needs and abilities, she pointed out that involving students in the process would give educators a unique perspective for a curriculum that better serve the staff and students. Since learners construct their own knowledge, the instructional designer should collect reliable data about the prerequisites of learners and their personal characteristics, set general learning goals, plan activities to help students achieve those goals, develop assessment instruments then revise the instructional plan paying specific attention to the perspectives of students (Isman, 2011).

The Board of European Students of Technology (BEST) involved students in curriculum development considering them as major actors in educational development and engages them in conferences and other events where they meet with relevant stakeholders (Campogiani, Czahajda, Mazur, & Stanojevic, 2014).

The role of students is highlighted further by Könings, Brand-Gruwel, and Van Merriënboer (2010) who contend that students should be involved in the instructional design 'from start to finish' including "accounting for learning needs, the use of appropriate teaching

methods and training materials, the planning of lessons, and choosing the best way for implementing learning activities in the lessons” (Könings et al., 2010). In a study by Bishop and Ishikawa (2021), master’s students were engaged in tackling the redesign of their curriculum, with the researchers revealing areas of frustration from the part of students regarding the learning environments and the relevant contribution they could make to the instructional design in their capacity as co-designers. Contending that students should have a role in the design of the training they receive, Silver et al. (2007) devise a model of teaching strategies that they believe encompasses a variety of strategies that address students’ needs.

2.13 Summary

The reviewed literature underscores several key issues related to court interpreter training. First, there is broad consensus that court interpreters require thorough and specialized training to communicate effectively in legal contexts. Given the high stakes of courtroom proceedings, the accuracy and clarity of interpretation are paramount to ensuring justice and fair trials. Second, the literature increasingly highlights the contribution of neuroscience to learning theories, particularly in the areas of memory, attention, and information processing. By integrating brain-based insights into interpreter education, educators can cultivate more effective training approaches that align with the natural cognitive processes of learners.

A third significant strand in the literature addresses the importance of accommodating diverse learning styles and brain-based principles in instructional design. This perspective argues that training programs should not only incorporate strategies compatible with how the brain processes and retains information but also tailor learning activities to individual preferences and styles. Finally, the literature emphasizes the necessity of grounding court

interpreter training in authentic, field-based demands. By aligning instructional objectives and content with real-world practices, interpreter education can more directly meet the practical requirements of the legal environment.

Despite these insights, notable gaps remain. In Jordan, there is a particular lack of systematic scholarship on the professional needs of court interpreters, exacerbated by limited regulation of the field. This scarcity of clear guidelines leaves educators uncertain of the specific knowledge and skills they should impart, increasing the risk that existing programs fail to equip interpreters with the necessary competencies. Another challenge involves the relatively undeveloped application of neuroscience and educational research to court interpreter training. Although extensive literature attests to the relevance of neuroscientific findings to education, their concrete implementation in interpreter curricula—especially those that cater to individual learning styles—remains limited. Addressing these shortcomings serves as the primary motivation for this study.

By addressing content gaps and leveraging principles drawn from neuroscience, education, and court interpreting research, this study seeks to create a systematic instructional model tailored to the demands of SCCI in Jordan. The goal is to enhance both cognitive and practical competencies, ultimately producing interpreters capable of delivering high-quality, accurate interpretations that uphold justice for all litigants, regardless of language proficiency. In providing this interdisciplinary framework, the study not only contributes to the scholarly discourse but also offers pragmatic solutions aimed at strengthening court interpreter training and, by extension, the integrity of judicial proceedings.

A pertinent, unresolved issue in the literature concerns the precise role of the court interpreter: whether interpreters should act strictly as linguistic conduits, function as language

experts, or be considered witnesses. This debate gains particular complexity in the context of Jordan, where the legal framework may draw on different schools of Islamic jurisprudence (e.g., Hanafi or Shafi'i). The Shafi'i school mandates the presence of two male interpreters or one male interpreter and two female interpreters per case, so the appointment of multiple interpreters—potentially with specific gender requirements—could alter the interpreter's responsibilities, including peer-monitoring for mistakes. Additionally, they may be subject to direct questioning and cross-examination regarding their interpretative choices. This situation underscores the need for further theoretical and empirical inquiry into the court interpreter's role, both in Jordan and globally.

2.14 The Conceptual Framework of Study

This research adopts an interdisciplinary conceptual framework that integrates insights from court interpreting, legal studies, neuroscience, and curriculum design. Its aim is to guide the development of a structured, brain-compatible training program tailored for small claims court interpreters (SCCI) in Jordan. The framework supports both the construction of the training content and the methodology for its delivery, ensuring that each component of the training is informed by real-world professional practice and grounded in educational theory.

At the foundation of the framework is the identification of the knowledge types required by interpreters in SCC settings—namely, conceptual, procedural, and situational knowledge. These three dimensions are extracted directly from the professional field through interviews and observations involving legal practitioners, working court interpreters, and other stakeholders. This process ensures that the training is authentically aligned with the realities of the courtroom and meets the professional expectations of those involved in the judicial process. This component addresses Research Questions 1, 2, and 3, which seek to explore the extent to

which situational knowledge affects interpreter performance (RQ1), define the conceptual knowledge required (RQ2), and examine how professional interpreters actually perform in Jordanian small claims courtrooms (RQ3).

Once these knowledge requirements are identified and categorized, they are organized into a hierarchical learning structure modeled as a training pyramid. At the top of the pyramid are the ultimate training goals, which represent the overall competencies interpreters are expected to achieve by the end of the program. These goals are supported by terminal learning objectives, each tied to a specific knowledge domain (conceptual, procedural, or situational). Underneath these are the enabling objectives, which break down each terminal objective into more manageable components. At the base are the learning steps, which represent the step-by-step instructional actions that guide learners progressively toward achieving the enabling and terminal objectives.

Informed by the curriculum design literature reviewed in Chapter 2, the framework emphasizes the importance of explicitly stating learning objectives at every level. Each training module begins with clearly defined objectives, helping learners understand what is expected of them, monitor their own progress, and link each activity to a broader professional outcome. This clarity also supports instructors in ensuring alignment between objectives, content, assessment, and pedagogy.

The training content, including audio-visual exercises and narratives, is constructed around the knowledge gathered from the professional community. These materials are not generic but context-specific, developed to reflect the unique linguistic, legal, and procedural realities of small claims courtrooms in Jordan. Once the learning steps are determined, training scenarios, role plays, and exercises are designed to help learners practice and internalize the knowledge. These tasks are carefully crafted to be compliant with the AGES Model and the

Strategic Teachers' Model (STM), ensuring the delivery method is aligned with how the brain learns best.

The AGES Model informs the structure of the training activities by ensuring that learners are able to: attend to key content and interpret through focused, distraction-free engagement; generate their own understanding through active participation; engage emotionally with the material to improve memory retention; and, learn over time through spaced repetition and distributed practice.

Meanwhile, the Strategic Teachers' Model (STM) guides the instructional strategy, supporting a variety of learning styles—mastery, interpersonal, self-expressive, and understanding. In this model, the instructor is not a transmitter of information but a facilitator working within the learner's Zone of Approximate Development (ZAD). Students are viewed as active agents in their own learning, and the teaching approach is designed to stimulate their cognitive and emotional engagement using diverse, brain-based strategies.

This comprehensive conceptual framework also directly responds to Research Question 4, which asks why a brain-based instructional approach is needed in interpreter training. The integration of AGES and STM demonstrates that interpreter training, particularly in the high-pressure and cognitively demanding context of courtrooms, must go beyond traditional rote learning. Instead, it must leverage what neuroscience tells us about memory, attention, motivation, and learning variability to create instruction that is not only informative but transformative.

Finally, the outcome of this framework is a full set of training materials that will be delivered through a third-party instructor. While the researcher's role is to develop the content and design, the actual delivery will be done by another professional, allowing for an objective evaluation of the materials' effectiveness. During delivery, the AGES Model will also serve as

an analytical tool to assess how well the training engages learners and supports knowledge retention—providing feedback that links pedagogical theory to practical implementation. The conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure (2.2).

A strategic teachers' brain-based instruction for small-claims court interpretation in Jordan
 -A conceptual framework-

Figure 2.2 Conceptual framework of study

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a detailed description of the research methodology, starting from diagnosing SCCI in Jordan, through the initial planning of the training material up to the analysis of the results of the case study. There are four phases in this research, each playing a role in achieving the research objectives (Figure 3.1).

In Phase 1, the study diagnoses SCCI in Jordan, considers its broader context, and assesses the relevant training needs. The second phase elicits the necessary knowledge content for the SCCI training material, a process that requires the collection and organization of data. As the study progresses into Phase 3, its focus shifts to planning the training material, designed to address the needs identified in the preliminary diagnosis, in accordance with the brain-based model of instruction. In Phase 4, the training material is deployed for field testing by teaching it to a cohort of students to evaluate its effectiveness and determine whether brain-based instructional materials were effective.

Figure 3.1 Phases of study

This methodology chapter is organized to address the methodological components of the research, commencing with defining the research design that guides

the study in Section 3.2. Subsequently, Section 3.3 elucidates the sampling method, offering comprehensive insights into the recruitment procedures for participants and the prescribed inclusion criteria. Section 3.4 is about the participant groups recruited in the study. In Section 3.5, the study refers to the sampling size of the study participants, then the recruitment process is described in Section 3.6. Further in Section 3.7, ethical considerations are stated. Section 3.8 explains the data collection method followed by the instruments of study in Section 3.9. In Section 3.10 the training material design is explained. Then Section 3.11 reports the findings of the mock and pilot studies.

In a nutshell, RQs 1, 2 and 3 will be answered by eliciting knowledge content from interviewed interpreters, lawyers and dual professionals. The output of the interviews will be the ‘knowledge content for a SCCI training’. Afterwards, a training material will be developed, using the techniques of the SMT hooks, kindles and bridges with the aim of achieving the AGES model effects on learning. This will be followed by answering RQ4 by conducting, observing and exploring a case study in which a brain-based training was given to translation students and fresh graduates. A Reference Book will finally be produced as a biproduct (not to be confused with the training material).

3.2 Research design

3.2.1 Qualitative research

This study employs a qualitative research approach because it explores a complex phenomenon (Creswell & Poth, 2018) and relies on non-numerical data to generate rich, detailed insights that are often lacking in quantitative research (Babbie, 2008). It also incorporates a theme exploration and an in-depth examination of a phenomenon, whether in relation to small-claims court interpreting practice in Jordan

or in a brain-based learning of it, through participants' perspectives (Holly, 2013), particularly in classroom environments (Pöchhacker, 2010).

A key focus of this study is the instructional design of small-claims court interpreting in a real-life context, emphasizing concepts, views, opinions, and the implementability of results (Hancock, Ockleford, & Windridge, 2009). The qualitative approach is particularly suitable because it does not begin with a predefined hypothesis to be tested (Nicholls, 2009); instead, it seeks insights from lawyers and interpreters while also considering students' interpretations of their experiences in natural settings (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). To achieve this, the researcher applies interviews and observations as primary instruments of study (Mohajan, 2018).

In line with qualitative research, this study challenges presupposed conceptions about the existence of a structured court interpreting system and the possibility of appealing court interpreting errors, among other such misconceptions. As Barone (2008) argues, qualitative research is valuable for disrupting conventional understandings, challenging established assumptions, and embracing the uncertainties inherent in social phenomena. By adopting this perspective, the study aims to problematize existing structures and norms within court interpreting, uncovering systemic gaps and overlooked complexities. This methodological choice ensures a deeper, more nuanced understanding of the lived experiences that define the field of court interpreting, aligning closely with the study's exploratory and interpretive research objectives.

The qualitative research design is particularly suitable for investigating BBL in the context of court interpreter training, as it allows for an in-depth exploration of cognitive and pedagogical processes that are not easily quantifiable (Fam, 2018). BBL is deeply rooted in the complexity of human cognition, requiring an interpretative

approach that considers individual learning experiences, instructional methodologies, and contextual factors (Rasmitadila et al., 2021). A qualitative framework facilitates the examination of how students engage with BBL principles, process information, and apply learned skills in real-world interpreting scenarios. Furthermore, BBL emphasizes experiential and situational learning, which necessitates direct observation and participant narratives to capture the depth of students' cognitive engagement and adaptability (Caine & Caine, 2011).

3.2.2 Exploratory case study

Case studies play a crucial role in policy research, offering valuable insights into best practices for the delivery of specific programs or policies (Keddie, 2006). This case study involves an in-depth examination of a specific phenomenon: learning through a brain-based learning approach (Blatter, 2008). According to Eisenhardt (1989), the focus of a case study as a research strategy is to understand the dynamics within a single setting. In this study, all participants are at the same educational level—either fresh graduates or fourth-year students—who have prior interpreting experience in Jordan. As such, the case study serves as “an in-depth description of a bounded system” ” (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016), where a small number of participants are closely examined (Gerring, 2007).

This case study aims to deepen our understanding of a complex issue (Feagin, Orum, & Sjoberg, 1991) concerning how small-claims court interpreting can be taught in a way that engages students' brains and learning styles. Additionally, the case study provides an opportunity to explore unknown situations, as the real-world setting of court interpreting instruction allows for a more comprehensive investigation of the social context and the challenges involved (Yin, 2003).

The main criticism of case study method is lack of ability to generalise results (Keddie, 2006) as information it provides is not reliable when applied to a broader class (Abercrombie, Hill, & Turner, 2006). The issue of generalisation is debated in research as in (Flyvbjerg, 2006), who dismisses the possibility of social sciences in producing general predictive theory. Blatter (2008) frames criticism and advocacy of case studies in a comparison between the positions of naturalists, positivists and constructivism. Naturalists do not generalise beyond the cases under study and positivists rely on statistical generalisation to apply to a specific population while constructivists. Both naturalists and positivists assume the existence of an objective reality. Constructivism, however, use multiple theories to interpret a phenomenon Blatter (2008). In this vein, Flyvbjerg (2006) cites Karl Popper's falsification principle, which in lieu of generalisation, can act as a test to render a theory invalid or subject to revision.

The adoption of a case study methodology is particularly appropriate for this research due to its objective of observing a brain-based training session within a classroom setting and getting students' feedback (Maxwell, 2013), specifically tailored to interpretation students and fresh graduates in Jordan. The rationale for employing this method is substantiated by the limited existing research concerning the broader phenomenon of training court interpreters and, more specifically, the utilization of brain-based educational strategies, especially in Jordan. The case study approach offers a viable means to address this research gap by systematically investigating and elucidating the intricacies of brain-based training methods within the specialized context of SCCI. This approach, by design, enables an in-depth exploration of the dynamics involved in brain-based training, shedding light on areas that may have been otherwise overlooked or understudied. The findings derived from this case study are

suggested to provide valuable insights, which can, in turn, inform and enhance the efforts aimed at refining court interpreting training practices for students in Jordan.

3.3 Sampling

Sampling is defined as the process of selecting individuals or a group of people to participate in a research study, with the aim of representing a specific population (Futane & Tech, 2021). In qualitative studies, researchers often employ purposive sampling, which involves deliberately choosing participants based on certain criteria. These studies typically involve smaller sample sizes, and the selection criteria can evolve as the research progresses, rather than being rigidly determined from the outset (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Purposive sampling is particularly useful when researchers are intimately familiar with the population, its components, and the research objectives, and when predefined criteria are applicable (Babbie, 2008). As Creswell and Poth (2018) point out, purposive sampling aligns with qualitative research that prioritizes the richness of information over generalization. In such research, the goal is not to make broad generalizations but to gain a profound understanding of the specific phenomena under investigation, such as SCCI knowledge content and the impact of STM-brain-based education on SCCI students. To achieve this, purposive sampling is employed to select individuals who are best suited to serve the study's objectives.

3.4 The participants

3.4.1 Roles and responsibilities

The participants will be divided into five groups: (1) the expert groups and (2) professional group (for the semi-structured interviews), (3) trainers' group, (4) students

(for the pilot study) and (5) students (for the case study) (Appendix D). Different selection criteria apply to each group.

3.4.2 Inclusion criteria

The participants recruited in this study represented the three groups involved: the trainers' group, the interviewees' group and the students' group.

Table 3.1 Participants recruitment and inclusion criteria

RQ	Participants group	Education	Occupation	Special inclusion requirements	Geography
1, 2 and 3	Professional group	BA+	Interpreter	Interpreted at least 1 SCC case	Jordan
1, 2 and 3	Expert group		Lawyer	Attended at least 1 bilingual case	Jordan
4	Students' groups (for the Pilot and Case Study)	4 th year student	-	-	Jordan
		Fresh graduate	-	-	Jordan
	Trainers' group	BA+	Interpreter	-	Worldwide
		BA+	-	-	
		4 th -year student	-		

3.5 Sample size

Qualitative studies tend to focus on small samples of participants in their own context (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Since this study is a qualitative study, sample size was of less importance than in quantitative research, as long as it lead the researcher into the saturation point, at which gathering new information does not add to the themes (Charmaz & Bryant, 2008) or new information would not be attained (Kumar, 2019). When the effects of the variables under a qualitative study are strong and the changes they entail are significant, then smaller samples are adequate (Boncz, 2015). In addition, the more relevant information a sample yields, the less number is needed for

participants (Malterud, Siersma, & Guassora, 2015). This meets with the design of the study in several ways.

The learning environment envisaged in the training is a cooperative one, since neuroscience shows that humans learn better if they interact among themselves (Jacobs & Renandya, 2019). A small classroom size is recommended to keep students engaged (Davidson, Major, & Michaelsen, 2014), in a lighter environment (Wang & Finn, 2000) that significantly reduces student anxiety (Harfitt, 2012). Recommended student group sizes vary from 3-5 (Cuseo, 1992) to 6 (Thousand (1994) and Slavin (1985)) and 4-8 (Byren, 1987).

Appendix D displays the demographics and numbers of the participants in this study.

3.6 Recruitment process

Invitations to volunteer in the study are sent to Jordan based platforms in the social media, including Facebook and WhatsApp. This includes Jordanian translators and lawyers gatherings including the Facebook groups of: JATAL, Mutarjimo Al Ordon (Translators in Jordan) and the Jordanian Bar association group. Personal communication will also be made with instructors at local universities to nominate candidates who are willing to participate. A form of consent will be sent along with the invitation to responding members, stating their voluntary nature of participation and right to withdraw from the study. It will also be agreed that all participants may speak in accordance with the Chatham house rule.

3.7 Ethical considerations

All participants will be fully informed of the study and assured to the use of Chatham House rules, where participants would be anonymously cited in the study. In

addition, due to the spike of COVID-19 cases in Jordan, the study is conducted virtually. All participants will have the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Approval of the Human Research Ethics Committee of USM (JEPeM) has been obtained (No. USM/JEPeM/21040300 dated 27 July 2021). Participants will be fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before the interviews, and confidentiality was upheld by anonymizing their identities in transcripts and analyses. The use of member checking further will serve an ethical function by allowing participants to confirm or clarify their statements, thereby respecting their autonomy and perspectives. These measures will ensure that the research is conducted with integrity, respect, and transparency, safeguarding the rights and well-being of all participants.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the interview-based data in this qualitative study, the research follows the four criteria outlined by Lincoln and Guba (1985): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility is supported by designing the interview questions to directly align with the research questions and by allowing participants to elaborate, clarify, or revisit their answers during and after the interview process. This helps ensure that their perspectives are accurately captured. Transferability is enhanced by providing detailed descriptions of the interview context, participant backgrounds, and selection criteria, allowing future researchers to assess whether the findings are applicable to similar contexts. Dependability is achieved by maintaining consistency in how all interviews are conducted and by documenting the interview procedures, including a peer-review of questions and use of a semi-structured format. Finally, confirmability is addressed by keeping reflexive notes and audio records, helping ensure that interpretations remain grounded in the data rather than

influenced by researcher bias. These measures collectively will contribute to the rigor and transparency of the interview process.

3.8 Data collection

The data collection process for this study involves two primary methods: interviews and observations. Interviews will be conducted to elicit the knowledge and experiences of small-claims court interpreters, providing valuable insights into their perspectives on interpreting practices and their understanding of the role of brain-based learning in their work. Observations will then be employed to examine a specific instance of brain-based learning within the context of small-claims court interpreting, offering a real-time view of how these instructional strategies are applied in practice. These methods are selected to capture both the theoretical knowledge of interpreters and the practical application of brain-based learning principles, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation. This section provides a detailed overview of the data collection procedures, including participant selection, the interview process, and the observation process.

3.8.1 Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews are used to answer RQs 1, 2 and 3. A qualitative interview, according to Rubin and Rubin (2005), is a conversation that seeks to explore the complexity of real world and where the interviewer engages with the interviewee in an extended discussion about the research topic. A semi-structured interview is a qualitative data collection strategy, where the interviewer asks interviews open-ended questions and is useful when the participants are fieldworkers with full understanding of a given community from the insider's perspective (Ayres, 2008). Topics in this type

of interviews tend to be participant-driven and can pursue a phenomenological approach focussing on the experience that the participants have in the interviewed topic (Roulston & Choi, 2018).

Semi-structured interviews, however, have disadvantages. Among them are doubts on the validity of interview data, inconvenience of interviewers writing notes in front of the interview, providing too much information and poor reliability (Walsh, 2001). Semi-structured interviews also can lead to biases if the interviewees are incompetent (Bless, Higson-Smith, & Kagee, 2007), they require on the part of the interviewer good knowledge of the topic and ability to prevent digress from the aims of the interview (Flin, O Connor, & Crichton, 2013).

The study employs thematic analysis to explore patterns in the knowledge types—conceptual, procedural, and situational—demonstrated or perceived by small-claims court interpreters in Jordan. As outlined by Braun, Clarke and Weate (2017), thematic analysis provides “a method for identifying patterns (‘themes’) in a dataset for describing and interpreting the meaning and importance of those.” A five-phase approach is adopted to systematically analyse the qualitative data derived from semi-structured interviews with interpreters and lawyers:

(1) Familiarization and coding: Interview recordings are transcribed verbatim. Segments relevant to the three knowledge types are highlighted and coded using qualitative labels. The coded excerpts are organized in a Word document table, with columns identifying the participant type, interview date, and knowledge domain.

(2) Theme development: Codes are examined in light of the study’s research questions to identify recurring themes across responses.

(3) Refinement: Themes are reviewed against the full interview transcripts in Arabic to ensure consistency and accuracy. Re-coding is conducted where initial

interpretations require adjustment, and outlier comments are revisited for contextual relevance.

(4) Naming and categorization: Themes are grouped under overarching categories aligned with the three knowledge types. Each theme is clearly defined to reflect both the form and function of knowledge as described by participants.

(5) Writing up: Thematic findings are integrated into the results and discussion sections. Selected quotations are translated into English and contextualized, ensuring that the thematic analysis remains grounded in the lived experiences and professional insights of the participants.

3.8.2 Observation

Observation is one of the oldest tools of data collection, where an observer watches attentively a given phenomenon to determine its status (Connaway & Radford, 2021). Observational studies have the advantage of being inexpensive and easy to carry out but can also explore rare outcomes (Gilmartin-Thomas, Liew, & Hopper, 2018). According to Rosenbaum (2002), observation has some similarities with experimental tools, as it observes either a treatment or an intervention, with the main difference being that in observations, treatment is not controlled by the researcher for ethical or other reasons. There are different types of observations.

Kumar (2008) classifies observation in three types: unstructured, uncontrolled, controlled and participant observations. The first type is conducted without a predetermined plan, the second happens in natural settings without using standardized techniques, the third is conducted according to predefined arrangements using mechanical instruments to achieve accuracy while the fourth is conducted with the researcher immersed in the observed setting without revealing his identity in cases where data could have not been obtained through other data collection methods.

Angrosino (2007) suggests a typology of observations based on the observer's role. According to him, an observer can be non-reactive, where he avoids interfering in the observed setting. He could be a reactive, who intervenes in the event or a participant who tries to actively engage with the other participants under study.

As used in scientific research, observation should meet systematic conditions and validity and reliability criteria and should serve a research purpose (Kothari, 2004). Therefore, it has some disadvantages. In general, observation lacks randomization, an important criterion to prevent bias (Cochran & Rubin, 1973). As in the case with qualitative research, observational studies do not use control groups (Busetto, Wick, & Gumbinger, 2020), while a randomized control group is deemed essential for treatment assessment (Boyko, 2013). Participant observation is most appropriate for observers who need to have first-hand experience with real situations in life and the data it gives can be significantly valid (Robson, 1998). However, Cohen and Manion suspect its validity arguing it has a considerable degree of bias. Non-participant observation has the value of reporting behaviours as they are happening in their settings, but the presence of the observer may disturb the respondents (Cohen & Manion, 1989). Another source of bias that may flaw an observational study can derive from a biased selection of subjects, though can be avoided through the proper design of the study (Ellenberg, 1994). Another concern relates to comparison, since testing several hypotheses at once can result in multiple comparison bias, as it increases the possibility of haphazard correlation between factors and data output (Benjamini, 2010)

Nevertheless, there are some mitigating measures that can help the observer make a quality observation. Wästerfors (2018) recommends observers to adhere to the qualities of good observation: details, sequencing and atmosphere. Accordingly, an observer should attend to the minute details of what the observed subjects do and how

actions are made in a chain of practices in an atmosphere that can be contrasted with others. An observational study can also be strengthened with the use of matching methods, where a randomized experiment is replicated using samples well matched to the original control and experimental groups (Stuart, 2010). Differentiated comparison is another method, where treatment is given at two levels, then one treated group can be compared in lieu of the other (Rosenbaum, 2013). **Section 3.9.2** elaborates the instrument used in observation.

3.9 Instruments of the study

3.9.1 Semi-structured interview guide

The interview guide is developed then reviewed by an assistant professor at a local university in Jordan (Table 3.2). He had been an assistant professor for four universities in Jordan since 1997. He worked as a translator, instructor of translation courses and chairman of translation departments in several universities. His experience included serving as the director of Atlas Centre for Studies, that produced dictionaries and held international conferences in translation.

Table 3.2 Interview questions

Interview questions for the interpreters (professional group)	
As drafted	After review
What is the conceptual knowledge that interpreters should have about court interpreting?	What knowledge did you use in the small-claim cases you interpreted for?
What is the procedural knowledge that interpreters should have about court interpreting?	What skills did you apply when you interpreted in small claims cases?

What is the situational knowledge that interpreters should have about court interpreting?	What situational knowledge helped you perform better as a SCC interpreter in the cases you interpreted for?
Interview questions for the lawyers (expert group)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) What conceptual knowledge do you expect the small-claims court interpreter should have? (2) What situational knowledge do you expect the small-claims court interpreter should have? (3) What situational knowledge do you expect the small-claims court interpreter should have? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Have you been in a court room at least once with an interpreter doing court interpreting in a small claim? (2) What kind of (a) general and (b) situational and (c) specialized knowledge and (d) skills do you think an interpreter should have in a small claim? (3) To what extent should a SCC interpreter be specialized in or knowledgeable of the law? (4) If an interpreter in a small-claims court makes a mistake, what happens? How can it be corrected?

The interviews will be held through phone and zoom platform, depending on respondents' convenience from 30/10/2021 to 19/12/2021.

3.9.2 Observation sheet

The observation sheet will be developed to note how the trainer uses the STM hooks and their effect on students' attention, generation and emotions (Table 3.3).

Table 3.3 Observation Guide

Slide #	Hook	Style	Basic result	Main result	Notes

The observation will be carried out after reviewing the recording of each video, filing in the blanks the hooks that were used, the style of learning that was invoked by each hook, the immediate result (if any) that comes out from the hook and the overall effect (main result) of the hook/learning style on the students. Notes will be recorded to point out important implications.

3.9.3 Zoom platform

The Zoom platform has been deemed convenient at the post-covid time with its features, such as screen and audio sharing being suitable for training interpreting courses to students.

3.9.4 Audio and audio-video production software

Technology will be used to produce both explainers and video exercises. Spoken scenarios will be created using different voices offered by text-to-speech technology, from speechor.com, speechelo.com and synthesia.io. Using those platforms are meant to facilitate the production and amendment of high-quality voices. As a next step, around 100 videos will be produced, covering the situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge, using those generated voices into 3-D videos through the Plotagon technology. Plotagon allows for the use of many scenes and unlimited characters. Generated voices will be imported to the videos and Plotagon will synch them to the lips movement. The content of the videos will be based on the knowledge content that the study derives from available sources in addition to the input of the participants of study.

Combining visuals and auditory material in instruction is supported by educational research. It improves learning and memory retention (Clark & Paivio,

1991), enhances working memory and learning efficiency (Kalyuga, 2000) and enhances learning in general (R. Mayer, 2009). The use of cartoon animated videos is supported by the AGES model which states that visuals and asking students to visualise situations can generate neural associations in the brain, hence improve memory dynamics and increase learning. (Davachi et al., 2010). Using animated cartoon videos can enhance motivation and effectiveness of learning (Yunita, 2017), improve learning outcomes (Ramadhan, Rohana, & Pada, 2021) and prevent boredom of students to learn (Aulia & Sari, 2022). Plotagon also had a positive effect on increasing students' interest and reducing feelings of boredom (Siregar, 2023).

3.10 Developing the training material

This section explains in detail how the training material is developed. The training material consisted of PowerPoint explainer slides and audio-video material, covering the SCCI situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge. The design is guided by the Research and Development Model.

The following sections describe the details of this designing process.

3.10.1 Research and Development Model

The Research and Development Model (RND) was proposed by Gall and Borg in 1963, based on the industry, using research findings in the designing of new products and procedures. Those products are then be subjected to field testing, evaluation and refining until such findings meet the set standards of quality and effectiveness (Borg, Gall, & Gall, 2003). Instead of aiming at discovering new knowledge, the researchers contemplate bringing educational research together with educational practices. Ten steps are involved (Figure 3.2.)

Figure 3.2 RND Steps adapted from (Borg, Gall & Gall, 2003)

Since the Research and Development Model is product-oriented, it is suitable for this study for the production of a training material for SCC interpreters in Jordan. According to Gustiani (2019), this model has been widely used in educational research though some researchers preferred to use simplified versions.

The activities involved in the RND process are in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4 List of activities

Activity	RQs	From	To
Semi-structured interviews	1, 2 and 3	30/10/2021	19/12/2021
Brainstorming	4	14/2/2022	13/3/2022
Pilot study	4	4/6/2022	29/6/2022
Case study	4	9/2/2023	3/3/2023

3.10.1(a) Research and information collection

The objective of this phase is to answer research questions 1, 2, and 3 by probing into SCCI situational, conceptual, and procedural knowledge. This information is provided through the review of related literature, review of relevant regulations in Jordan and interviews with lawyers and interpreters as Figure 3.3 illustrates:

Figure 3.3 Phase (1)- Defining the SCCI knowledge content

This aspect of the present study uses the grounded theory introduced by Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss. In qualitative research, the grounded theory is a method of inductive inquiry that aims at theory construction based on analysis and coding of collected experimental data (Charmaz & Bryant, 2008). The application of this theory involves researchers in a coding process of collected data to reach a better understanding of theoretical meaning through exploration of informants' perspectives and thoughts (Williams & Moser, 2019). A coding process ensues beginning with the open coding where data in raw material is tuned into concepts by attaching labels to words or objects (Benaquisto, 2008b). Next is axial coding whereby data is reassembled to find connections between ideas (Benaquisto, 2008a), followed by selective coding, where central categories are finally selected to integrate the previous categories and refine the theoretical claim (Benaquisto, 2008c).

3.10.1(b) Planning

The smallest units of content knowledge are called learning steps (LPs), where a learning step is defined as an element of the subject being taught (Stockard, Wood, Coughlin, & Rasplia Khoury, 2018). Each group of LPs will serve one Enabling Learning Objective (ELO). A group of ELOs served one Terminal Learning Objective (TLO), and eventually, TLOS define the overall goal of the training.

Figure 3.4 Phase (2)- Defining the hierarchy of knowledge content

Appendix (B) outlines the contents of the training material.

3.10.1(c) Developing a preliminary form of product

This procedure consists of three steps, beginning with drafting the terminal and enabling learning objectives and learning steps for the Reference Book until the draft training material is ready. The material will be written in Arabic in a Microsoft Word document file, under the name 'Reference Book'. It will eventually reflect on building a PowerPoint presentation file (the Training Material) to facilitate the delivery of

training. At this stage, the situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge components are fleshed out in detail and presented systematically in the training material and reference book.

Step 1: The TLOs and ELOs will be drafted using Robert Mager’s model (Mager, 1962). Each objective will be expressed in terms of Action, Condition and Standard. Figure (3.5) shows a translation of an example of a TLO.

Terminal Learning Objective (1)		
Action	:	Explain the meaning of law and define the types of civil courts and small claims
Condition	:	In a classroom equipped with audio-visual devices, and IAW a written handbook and simulated videos.
Standard	:	IAW the handbook activities

- **Enabling Learning Objectives**
 - Law and courts
 - Dispute, disputants and claim
 - Types and degrees of courts
 - Situational knowledge
 - Summary

Figure 3.5 A translation into English of a sample page listing TLO1 and its ELOs

Step 2: The learning steps will be inserted under their respective ELOs (Figure 3.6)

Enabling Learning Objective 1.3	
ACTION	: IDENTIFY COURT TYPES AND DEGREES
Condition	: In a classroom equipped with audio-visual devices, and IAW a written handbook and simulated videos.
Standard	: IAW the handbook activities
LP1.4 Court types and degrees	
LP1.5. Civil court types and degrees	

Figure 3.6 A translation into English of a sample page listing ELO1.3 and its LPs

Step 3: Seven (or more as needed) brain-storming sessions will be held with the Trainers’ Group to test the responses that an audience would make to the training and get their feedback instantaneously on the content of the training material (Appendix C). For instance, Learning Step 2.2 of TLO2 aims to stimulate discussions among real students regarding various qualities of court interpreters, such as impartiality. The ensuing discussion effectively is expected to align with this objective. The group will assess the proposed material within the Reference Book, both its substantive and presentational aspects, with their overall impressions being positively made. In the actual meeting, the professional interpreters underscored the need for the training material to account for technical precision concerning legal and technical terminologies. Furthermore, they advocated for accuracy in legal terminologies. They commended the instructional video content, imparting knowledge. Concerning video exercises, the interpreters recommended the cases to follow real-life scenarios in Jordan. They also suggested the reference book to explicitly require the trainees not to make judgments on interpreting, such as ‘the interpreting was disastrous, full of errors, etc.’ but to simply explain what happened in the videos. Since the way that jugs adjudicate cases are

different from what a layman would think, the professional interpreters recommended a unit on how the judges think to be appended at the beginning of the book.

The student and fresh graduates conveyed their satisfaction with the overall content of the training, acknowledging at the same time the challenges that faced them in terms of the new content. However, they provided insights into the form. They proposed the incorporation of coloured icons to demarcate learning steps and wishes to see a more coherent articulation of objectives. Linguistically, they commended the material's simplicity and intelligibility while suggesting the simplification of certain phrases that posed comprehension challenges. The inclusion of audio-visual materials was applauded, accompanied by a desire for expressive imagery within the Reference Book, based on their belief that visual representations can boost learning. As for the sequencing of learning, the students questioned why there were no interpreting exercises at the beginning of the training, and asked for more clarify on background information, such as the rationale for Jordan to establish the small-claims arrangements (Figure 3.7). Lastly, they identified typographical and grammatical errors requiring more attention.

LP 1.6. Small-claims courts

The Ministry of Justice adopted an initiative to resolve small disputes (the value of which is less than one thousand dinars). With the aim of simplifying procedures and reducing costs for litigants, this mechanism allows expedient resolution of pending cases within a period ranging from one day to a month. The subject disputes of small claims are not different from those of other civil cases of higher claimed values. Small claims are heard by the Conciliation court. Every dispute is governed by the applicable law. Workers' wages, for example, are subject to the labor law, and bonds and promissory notes are subject to the law commerce, and so on.

Figure 3.7 Translation of a sample LP (LP 1.6. Small-claims courts)

In this step, new information that students were expected to learn was inserted. All new information was obtained from the interviews, the Bylaws of Experts Before Regular Courts before Regular Courts, the Civil Law and the Civil Procedure Law. No examples, exercises or thought-provocative slides had yet been provided.

3.10.1(d) Developing the visuals and audio-visual components

A total number of 104 videos were created. Some of those videos were meant to explain an idea. Others were just exercises. The videos were created using: (i) Speechelo and Speechor (text-to-speech) platforms, (ii) Synthesys, (iii) Adobe Character and (iv) Plotagon. As for the static visuals, they were created through Microsoft Word icon feature and Comica application in addition to other icons found in public domain online. Six steps were involved at this stage.

Step 1. Two types of videos were created. Video explainers were meant to allow students to elicit information in answering given questions in the training. For example, there was a video about an incompetent person expressing desire to be a court interpreter

contrasted with a well-prepared one. Another example was about a judge thinking aloud (SUP1 and SUP10) to enable students to see how the judge logically thinks when hearing a case.

Video exercises, on the other hand, featured cases that invoked the five sources of right according to the Civil Code of Jordan. Those specific videos were created using the graduated difficulty level to allow students to practice CI at different paces. The three levels would be further divided into other levels (lower or higher) depending on the students' abilities. This is in line with the graduated difficulty strategy, where three levels of difficulty are offered to students to choose from, to allow them to determine which level is too simple or too hard for them (Hendel, 2018). Also in line with this strategy, model answers are provided in the videos in case students wanted to check on their performance (Silver, Strong, & Perini, 2007). In terms of content, exercise videos contained a dispute at court. As for the difficulty level, it was decided based on Daniel Giles Efforts Model (Gile, 2009), where the equation between Total Available Capacity and Total Requirements is challenged. In level 1, there are short exchanges at court with no technical or legal terms (Memory Effort), increasing in quantity in the next two levels. As for length, videos ranged between 50 seconds and 4:56 minutes, inclusive of model interpreting. As the results of Phase 1 shows in Chapter 4, there was no specific fixed criterion to use in determining the span of a talk expected at court. A litigant could speak for a long or short time, and an interpreter could ask for repetition, or clarification, may interrupt the speaker (other than the judge) or simply apologise for not being able to interpret. Notwithstanding any controversy on the time span that is most efficient for consecutive interpreter, the videos were intended for students not only to test their levels, but more importantly to practice the procedural knowledge of asking for clarification or repetition, among other skills. It was also left to the discretion of the

trainer to agree with the students on the level they found themselves most comfortable performing at.

All videos used kinesthetics, tone changes and other extralinguistic features to simulate as close as possible what might be expected to happen in real court settings. In addition, there were learning points about non-verbal communications, where students learn that court interpreters do not copy the body movements or tones of the litigants or witness. This is in line with the language conduit theory.

Step 2: The video explainers were created in way that could serve STM. Some were made to enable the compare/contrast exercise under the Understanding Style, while others promoted pattern making (self-expressive style), and so on. All exercises included the correct interpretation, and some explicated the thinking of a judge, as a form of modelling (mastery).

All videos featured a character that always correctly demonstrate understanding of and ability to use situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge. When the videos were intended to warn students of errors in interpreting, another character was used. In this way, the videos aim to establish a sense of proximity of the first character and a sense of alienation of the second one. The reason for that arrangement is to increase students' empathy with the professional character and keep them alienated from mistakes rather than creating in them a sense of fear for committing mistakes. Fear is a negative emotion that can affect the motivation of students (2.31.3), but at the same time, it was important in the training to capture the attention of students to their own mistakes. For that purpose, the study used the concepts of proximity and alienation.

Table 3.5 Alienation and proximity in videos

Video (Video type)	Intended effect	Goal
A character that always makes mistakes is dressed casually	Alienation	Students do not commit these mistakes.
A character that always makes the right action in interpreting, dressed formally	Proximity	Role model for students
Humorous videos about errors in interpreting	Alienation	Students do not commit these mistakes.

3.10.1(e) Developing the training material (PowerPoint)

Step 1: A skeleton was created in a PowerPoint file with title slides only (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8 Title slide in the training material (the PowerPoint)

Step 2: New information was inserted appropriately.

Step 3: STM hooks were added before the new information slides, to provoke the thoughts of students and engage them in brain-based discussions.

Examples of hooks used in the training

Mastery style	Understanding style:	Self-expressive style	Inter-personal style
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch this video and share with the group what you think a professional interpretation is. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Here are two videos about court interpreting. The first is a yes and the second is a no. What are the professional rules of court interpreting? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Say to yourself "I am a successful court interpreter". What made you successful? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch this video, then I need to volunteers to discuss in a pair the qualities of a court interpreter.

Figure 3.9 Examples of hooks used in the training material

Step 4: Instructions were added in the notes sections to guide the trainer into the hook, kindling and bridging. Intended learning styles were specified for the instructor, which were: New American Lecture (Mastery), Compare and Contrast and Reading for Meaning (Understanding), Inductive Learning and Pattern Maker (Self-expressive) and Reciprocal Learning (Interpersonal).

LOOKING FOR PATTERNS

sitting to the lawyer	subject of dispute	technical terms
legal terms	session date	consecutive interpreting
listening	dealing with dialects	interpreter's attire
taking statutory oath	asking for repetition	asking for clarification
taking notes	legal knowledge	verbatim interpreting
summary interpreting	correct phrasing	communication skills
speech etiquette	neutrality	addition and omission
standing place	judge sitting	interpreter's standing
		litigants standing

Conceptual

Procedural

Situational

Slide 11:
Understanding Hook:
As them to figure out through induction what item falls under what category.

Students may use the traditional way of asking you as a source of knowledge to explain them. Tell them "I don't know... try to give your best guess."
Give reinforcements "Great! Good! Nice" to encourage theory thinking, rather than their 'correct' answers.

Figure 3.10 Examples of trainer’s instructions on kindling and bridging

Step 5: Static images were added to reduce the number of words used in the slides. The static pictures in Figure 3.11 summarizes what happens from the time a dispute arises until a decision is made by court.

Figure 3.11 Using static pictures to reduce words

Step 6: The videos and images were placed appropriately. Each image and video were placed under a slide that taught a single learning step.

Figure 3.12 Three-level videos inserted in a slide

Figure 3.13 A visual about disputants' logic using a compare-contrast hook

The presentation of the material observed the principles of the AGES model in four ways. First, to capture the attention of students, hooks under the four styles of learning were used, followed by kindling by the trainer and students then followed by new information presented to them. Generation is observed through asking students to engage in reciprocal learning or self-expression. In this sense, stress was placed that any attempt by students to answer a question would be construed as a hypothesis waiting to be tested, rather than an answer that was to be judged as correct or incorrect. Students were encouraged to adhere to or modify their hypotheses as the course progressed. With regards to emotion, the training material was sensitive to the feelings of curiosity, reward, boredom and frustration. The hook, kindle and bridges were used to raise students' curiosity without fear of being judged to make their hypotheses. The word 'reward' was expressly used in the material to link it with knowledge learnt, and students were encouraged when making reflections to express any reward feeling they had got through the sessions. In this sense, the reward was intrinsic, rather than extrinsic, which is aligned with educational research that values the former as more constructive for student learning (Wang & Hassan, 2024). In order to avoid students feeling bored, there was a break in each session, though the students were told to alert

the trainer at any time they felt they needed other breaks. The material offered learning in different ways, using images, texts and videos, in addition to having students actively engaged in the learning process.

Reducing, even eliminating frustration, was specially emphasized in the PowerPoint Training Material and the Reference Book. Students could give wrong answers, which could embarrass, hence frustrate them (Barker, O'Neill, & Kazim, 2014). As a remedy, the material provided the learning steps, each on a separate slide, but placed hooks to ask students to make hypotheses of the answers. Videos were also of three levels of difficulty, and students were even encouraged to find more convenient levels of difficulty. There is also the sequencing of the material. Students in the needs-assessment stage expressed fears that they could be required to learn lots of legal terms or that they would be asked to interpret complicated cases. This concern was addressed in the training by introducing rules for professional court interpreting in small claims, one by one in a straightforward manner and encourage students to use them in their actual training. Another area of concern was when students in the needs-assessment exercise (before the training) voiced a concern that one word could change the outcome of the case.

3.10.1(f) Preliminary field testing (1) and revising main product

Firstly, the content of PowerPoint slides and the Reference Book were thoroughly reviewed by a professional lawyer to ensure no errors are there in the legal concepts. He cited some mistakes, and the researcher corrected them accordingly. Afterwards, two stages happened simultaneously. The material was discussed and revised with the training group in an activity that lasted from 14 February to 13 March 2022. This stage also included training the trainer who delivered the actual training in the case study.

The trainers' group highlighted elements in the written material that was unclear or that was not well addressed under the learning objectives. They also highlighted issues that could have hampered the sequencing of the learning process. The group was encouraged to challenge the clarity or logic of sequence but were also acting as if they were real students. One result of the discussions was the possibility that actual students could make hasty judgements about how the judge would decide a dispute. The discussions revealed the following issues as highlighted and discussed by the trainers group:

- (1) Since word count was limited to 20-30 in the slides, a brief was necessary to be provided to the trainer. The brief should contain not only steps to follow but also a guiding script to maximise consistency among trainers, should the training be replicated by others.
- (2) Some images were still overcrowded with words, which could challenge students' attention. The slides in question featured the arguments of disputants, which could not be reduced. As a remedy, the group suggested to further clarify the messages of those slides in antecedent slides so that students could check those pictorial slides in their own time, rather than during the training sessions.
- (3) The slides that were about how judges think was not clear, according to the group. They suggested to start the presentation with a module about how the judge thinks and reasons, in contrast with everyday language users. As a remedy, a new part on how the judge thinks was developed and inserted at the beginning of the situational knowledge module.
- (4) The group suggested that the part about legal knowledge could be challenging, because they anticipated that students would think about legal

knowledge as restricted to legal terminology. They could also find it difficult to understand why legal knowledge is important. Two remedies were made. First, preliminary slides were added under the title ‘let us agree on the terms’. These slides were offered using the ‘this is yes/no’ technique.

- (5) To address all issues raised by the trainers’ group, a written representation of the material was developed (other than the PowerPoint file) with actual examples for the trainer to use in introducing the topics or engage students in discussion.
- (6) The PowerPoint had offered in eight slides (representing the eight lessons) breaks. Those breaks were intended for students to go into mind wandering. Mind wandering happens to humans spontaneously and naturally (Smallwood & Schooler, 2015) with an individual’s thinking diverting from the immediate environment to focus instead on internal series of thoughts, thereby promoting future planning and creativity (Schooler et al., 2014). Research warns of the adverse effects of mind wandering on attention, such as in lectures, but since it happens spontaneously, the current training course envisaged a break time where students were encouraged to release their focus and let ‘their minds wander’. In addition, engaging students in mind wandering at the right time encourages them to address learning tasks that require original thoughts (Gericke, Soemer, & Shiefele, 2022). To make students go into mind wandering, each video contained a short cartoon video produced through Plotagon about things not related to interpreting. However, in this RND stage, two members of the trainers’ group felt the videos were adding more load on their cognitive processing abilities and thus suggested replacing the videos with soft music or just to keep the break

void of any activity. For that reason, the eight breaks had two cartoon videos only, one soft music track with forests background and five empty breaks.

- (7) The trainers group also discussed the quality of audio-visual material. They found the machine produced voices clear and the multi-difficulty videos appropriate. As they attempted to interpret the videos, they found that they had different levels of difficulty than the ones presented in the material. For four of the trainers, even the lowest level of difficulty was longer for them to process and interpret. The summary-interpreting video exercises (the third level) was also challenging for all the group except the three experienced interpreters. Suggestions were made to reduce the length of the videos, an opinion that was then refuted by the same group after taking note of the procedural knowledge of court interpreters, which allowed real-life interpreters at court to ask for clarification or repetition. The consensus among the group was therefore to indicate that clearly in the training material so that students would not feel discouraged when attempting a video interpreting. It was also suggested that if the actual intervention students expressed desire to interpret a video, then the trainer would give them a video that is low in cognitive load, while reminding them of the reason why they were not expected to interpret at the early stage of the training.

The result of this stage in RND was an updated PowerPoint file accompanied by written material with guiding scripts, audio-visual videos in different levels of difficulty and a brief to the trainer. The updated PowerPoint file had four modules, a theoretical part about situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge of SCCI in Jordan and a practical part with audio-visual exercises. PowerPoint was used to produce

the training lessons in 282 slides. The number of words in the slides ranged from 10 to 80 words. All slides that had a word count larger than 20 were intended for the ‘reading for meaning’ exercises, but also for self-study. Eight 10-minute breaks were provided to be given to students after 50 minutes of each lesson.

3.10.1(g) Preliminary field testing (2) and revising main product

After the first preliminary field test, several unanswered questions remained. As a result, a second preliminary field test was conducted. The suitability of the participant selection criteria for the case study remained unclear. Furthermore, it was uncertain whether the intended hooks, visuals, and videos would effectively engage and maintain students' attention. Additionally, the trainer sought to observe another individual delivering the training to gain insights into her teaching methods. A fourth important aspect to consider is the potential uncertainties that may arise during this testing phase, which should be addressed prior to advancing to the case study. This second testing took the form of a real training course. The first lesson was delivered by the main trainer, but later discussions between the researcher and the trainer led to agreeing on the researcher to deliver the rest of the lessons in the attendance of the main trainer. Invitation to the training had been announced through social media without requiring attendees to be students. Four translators and three translation graduates who worked as teachers joined the training. None of them had experience in or knowledge of court interpreting.

The group convened eight times, with each session lasting for two hours. All lessons were recorded for further review aim to pinpoint encountered issues and pre-emptively identify potential pitfalls, which could otherwise be avoided, in the forthcoming case study. The underlying educational philosophy guiding these efforts was firmly rooted in the principles of brain-based education, emphasizing the

diversification of instructional methods to facilitate active engagement and collaborative knowledge construction among all trainees. Specifically, the identified issues revolved around three key facets: the selection of trainees, the preparation of training materials, and the training of the trainer. It is noteworthy that the researcher made dedicated efforts to ensure that trainees received precise and valuable information to maximise their benefit.

In terms of trainee selection criteria, this testing revealed that prior knowledge could detrimentally impact the training process. Even though the professional translators in the group had not previously worked in Jordanian courts, they tended to rely on their pre-existing knowledge or perceptions about legal translation when responding to questions. This practice led the trainers to prematurely raise discussions of advanced topics such as contracts at a time where students were supposed to have not yet learnt the concept. Notably, one of the translators answered a terminology question in the slides by affirming awareness but employed inaccurate terminology.

Furthermore, the presence of professional translators occasionally veered the training away from its intended course. For instance, some of them questioned the necessity of understanding the logic of arguments, arguing that the interpreter's role is to translate without regard to coherence. Conversely, the non-expert trainees adhered to the educational philosophy, actively participating in knowledge construction and displaying higher levels of cooperation with the trainer. Instead of making overarching judgments, they critically analysed the content presented on slides and offered objective explanations, highlighting the aspects they deemed essential for comprehension. An illustrative example is the discussion of a judge's characteristics, logical reasoning, and impartial thinking.

Notably, at the outset of the course, all trainees displayed a limited grasp of interpersonal learning, primarily providing unidirectional answers to the trainers. Responses were often dichotomized into right or wrong, precluding discussions. However, as the course progressed, trainees began engaging in more cooperative discourse, particularly regarding topics where they lacked prior knowledge, such as judicial reasoning processes.

Trainees generally did not extensively comment on the training material, primarily responding to the content presented on slides. Some trainees, however, requested changes to the slide titles for enhanced clarity. Incorporating images into the slides stimulated valuable discussions among trainees, exemplified by their comparisons of logical and illogical argumentation in a specific "this is/this is not" understanding style.

As for the trainer, while she effectively managed the dialogue (in the first lesson she delivered), she expressed concerns to the researcher that the training material might not be adequately covered within the allocated time. This apprehension occasionally led her to directly answer some questions, particularly those raised by professional translators, with the aim of expediting the training session. This contradicts a main aspect of the training where answers were presumed to be hypotheses to be tested, rather than unidirectional 'correct' or 'incorrect' answer. Consequently, the researcher reviewed the slides, providing clarified guidelines for the trainer to adhere to, which were subsequently incorporated into the notes for future reference.

In the remaining lessons, the researcher also faced the same problem, as he had to directly correct wrong perceptions voiced by professionals from time to time. He had also to answer some challenging purely legal questions, such as about who should take the oath at court (the plaintiff or the defendant). Although the researcher had the

knowledge to answer these questions, it was not possible to reasonably presume that another trainer could have that knowledge or could be able to cope with the challenges. That also highlights the finding that the ideas of reciprocal learning and brain-based education in general were not yet obvious to the trainees. This also resulted in a mitigating measure, adopted in the pilot study, where students were fully briefed about brain-based education and the roles of the brain-based learner, teacher and researcher.

Originally, 13 students answered the invitation and showed willingness to participate. However, as the pilot training began, 5 students had withdrawn for availability issues. The remaining students' attendance fluctuated over the training between 4 and 8, but those who missed a lesson was given a recording to review to catch up with the rest. None of the participants was absent for more than 1 lesson. Even when the number of participants was relatively low, this did not affect the reciprocal nature of training that the participants engaged in.

3.10.1(h) Main field testing

This is the stage where a pilot study was implemented as detailed in **Section 3.14**. Pilot studies are meant to detect any obstacles before the full implementation of the study (Schreiber, 2008) and may give indications to the practicality of the main study (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The current pilot study aimed at learning about how the brain-based training material can be effective in keeping students engaged in reciprocal learning environment where they generate knowledge. It also aimed at finding whether the video drills are suitable for the students in terms of difficulty level. Amendments to the training material were considered and implemented simultaneously while the pilot was being conducted. The cohort of students (eight students) in the pilot were all translation fresh graduates or fourth-year students, as in the ultimate case study.

3.10.1(i) Case study

One of the trainers' group members gave the training, with the researcher acting as an observer. The trainer is a community interpreter in the United Kingdom and is a holder of the master's degree in translation. This training lasted for one month, with eight lessons given to the students. Each lesson lasted for two hours. The researcher observed the lessons and took notes on the effectiveness of the strategic teachers' devices, in light of the AGES model. Effectiveness was assessed in terms of students' abilities to pay full attention to the training, generate and construct knowledge, improve positive emotions for learning and space out their learning activities. Students were encouraged to discuss the learning styles they preferred and to practice or request exercises they feel most suitable for them, following the recommendations of Dignath, Buettner and Langfeldt (2008) and Clerc, Miller and Cosnefroy (2014).

3.10.1(j) Revising the final product

The product (presentations) was revised after the pilot study. The case study allowed the researcher to observe the benefits and challenges of presenting the training material following the AGES model and the Strategic Teachers' model. The observation led the researcher to have a better understanding of how the material should be prepared and presented, and the material was revisited in light of some challenges that appeared during the pilot study and given the feedback of the students themselves. Those revisions were formalistic in terms of reducing the texts from the slides and relying on static images and animations. Improvement areas related to issues with the sequencing of learning, the content of the training and its presentation and layout. All of these were then considered in producing the final product of the training manual and the teacher's brief, ready for dissemination and implementation. The feedback of students, trainers and lawyers culminated into the revision of the PowerPoint file, totalling 282 slides,

and the written manual totalling 216 pages. The PowerPoint was then used in the case study. It is important to say that the ‘final product’ in this sense does not mean the product that can be produced and disseminated nationwide, but it refers to the product that was ultimately used in the case study.

3.11 Observation

Observational studies elicit the cause-and-effect relations in a given phenomenon, where it is not possible to use a controlled experiment (Cochran and Rubin (1973); Rosenbaum (2002)). It entails gathering perceptions of the world through the utilization of all sensory faculties, with a particular emphasis on observing and hearing, in a methodical and deliberate manner, to acquire knowledge about a subject of interest (McKechnie, 2008). Observational studies are suitable when the researcher studies the participants without forcing change on their conditions (Gilmartin-Thomas, Liew, & Hopper, 2018).

The researcher used observation in the case study, which was an appropriate method of data collection because it allowed the researcher to get contextual insight of the teaching and learning process, and prompt feedback on the effectiveness of the training material in a naturalistic setting. All lessons were given through the Zoom platform and were recorded with the consent of the participants. Then, the recordings were transcribed verbatim for further qualitative analysis.

The transcribed records were read carefully, noting in each reading how the students responded to their learning environment. Interest was on finding out if students, as judged by the AGES model: paid attention, generated their own knowledge, leveraged their learning through emotions and had better reflected on their learning through spacing. Simultaneously, the analysis considered possible relations between the

different learning styles applied in the training and their effects on learning from a neuroscience perspective.

3.12 Research bias

Bias in qualitative research may result from influences that could damage the accuracy of data sampling, collection and interpretation, requiring hedges that can define the role of the researcher and participants in addition to observing clarity and transparency (Ogden, 2008). Protection has been ensured in this research against potential sources of bias beginning with the choice of the theory, up till the case study phase and reporting of results.

Appeal to neuroscience as a theory per se might be a source of bias, given the ‘seductive allure effect’ (Nuccio & Wesselmann, 2024) or its being claimed to be a pseudoscience, defined as a pretentious claim to apply scientific procedures, though failing to do so (Verschuere, 2025), thereby damaging sampling, collection and interpretation of data and reporting of findings. Ogden (2008) suggests that researchers should be aware of their values and assumptions and be open to alternatives.

For transparency and clarity, particularly when reflecting on the findings of this study, it is important to mention the roles that the researcher assumed throughout the study. Those roles are logistic provider, trainer of trainer, designer, modifier, observer and analyser.

The researcher conducted the preliminary research on the knowledge of court interpreters in SCCs in Jordan, based on which he proposed the content of the training material that was taught in the Zoom-based classroom. In the case study, the researcher did not take part in training the students but assumed the role of the observer only. The following table indicates hedges taken to eliminate bias throughout the study:

Table 3.6 Hedges against bias

Potential bias source	Hedges taken
Interviews	The interview protocol was revised by a professor of translation
Selection of participants	The invitation to the study was made public and no exclusion/inclusion was made except in accordance with the criteria applied in the study.
Creating the videos	A lawyer was consulted for the accuracy of the details in the videos
Developing the hooks	Checked by the ‘trainers’ group’
Developing the PowerPoint file	Checked by the ‘trainers’ group’

3.13 Results of the pilot study

In the pilot study, the researcher’s role was that of an observer to follow up on the progress of the course without interfering in the actual training. In light of the AGES model, the students started the training with no knowledge of court interpreting in Jordan. Since the beginning of the pilot, the students cooperated fully with the trainer by answering her prompts. All students paid full attention and remained attentive to the lessons throughout the training. There was no single moment where a student would answer a trainer’s prompt by saying they were distracted or did not pay attention. Active engagement and full participation as a team took some time until the third lesson. At that point, the students got out of the shell and exchanged their thoughts freely with colleagues and the trainer. Students showed independence as they took the liberty to argue for or against the thoughts made by each other. During the training, students, with such freedom, managed to generate knowledge even without them having any prior knowledge of the topic under discussion. On the emotional level, students showed they were comfortable in receiving the training and there was no indication by them that any had felt a sense of frustration or boredom. This was also evident in the fact that they responded to questions and expressed on multiple occasions their happiness to be in the

training. On the spacing dimension, students kept sending the researcher and the trainer their feedback all through the training during the free weekdays. The researcher observed also in the lessons that students came energetic and active.

The researcher's observation about the trainer is that she complied with the plan of training as agreed with her. She did not push students into an answer, and she even shut an eye, on specific occasions, on some of their mistakes to correct them at a later stage. That was agreed upon with her, because a student's thought was intended as a hypothesis to be tested rather than an answer to be verified as correct or false, in line with the instructional sequencing of content. Out of her own initiative, the trainer used reinforcement words and phrases to encourage students either when they gave a correct answer or shared a thought as a hypothesis. Finally, the trainer was friendly and patient with the students and gave them the permission to call her by her name, rather than by an honorific title such as Mrs or Doctor.

On the conclusion of the course, all students said they felt they owned the material. ST4 said 'I now know the material forward and backward'. Another interesting comment by one student was that she felt encouraged to participate because "...this is an environment where students are dominating the learning experience." (ST10)

Throughout the training, many students would answer some questions by saying "as we learnt in the previous lesson(s)." This is despite the fact that the trainees had not had access to the written material to review. Their answers were based on what they had remembered from the lessons. The following quotations come from reflections that students made throughout and after the intervention. They are self-explanatory:

“I always wished to study the MA in translation. I was frightened to hear about interpreting. Translation is ok but interpreting? It gave me the creep. But now after seeing this training I can go ahead with courage. No more afraid. There was a barrier but now I am very courageous and lots of difference happened.” (ST4)

“We have the trust that we can proceed forward. We know the way forward towards professionalism. We have got the background and essentials of court interpreting. I now understand that without knowing the legal effect and source of obligations I might make mistakes shifting rights and obligations in the case. I may mess up with everything.” (ST1)

“Courage increased. I am a student at the fourth year. Theory followed by practice was very useful. We got the theories of obligations and we applied directly what we have learnt in practice.” (ST8)

“On the personal level. This style of learning has built trust and even given me the core element that I can create my own curriculum. This is the level of trust that the teaching instilled in me. This resulted me in ownership that made the course appeal to me better and accept criticism because I am confident that I have trust in me. I can even explain the material to others. I know it forward and backward.” (ST4)

The trainer acted as a facilitator and instructor. She would hook, kindle and bridge information throughout the training. Whenever students felt stuck in answering a question, the trainer would interfere with relevant information according to the Zone of Proximal Development. The trainer all through the training kept her talk to the minimum as the purpose was to help students generate their knowledge by themselves. The trainer's role is more detailed in the next sections.

The results are presented according to the effect of the use of the AGES model in developing and delivering the training material. The AGES model consists of Attention, Generation, Emotion and Spacing. In implementation of the AGES model on the intervention, the hooks, kindles and bridges under Silver's styles of learning were used and assessed both in the written material and presentation. The results show that students' generation was dominant over other elements of the model, followed by emotions, attention then finally spacing.

The following findings are the results of the observation as well as reading through the journals submitted by the eight students. Figure 3.14 shows a sample of the journal of one of the students. The students did not make regular journal entries on all lessons, so the analysis was made in also in light of their feedback and cooperation during the lessons.

Figure 3.14 Sample Journal Entry by ST1

3.13.1 Sequencing of learning

The sequencing of instruction proved to be incongruent with the pre-established plan. Originally, the intention was to impart students with conceptual knowledge, followed by procedural knowledge, and subsequently situational knowledge. However, as students began to grasp the flexibility afforded to them in customizing their learning experience, they expressed a desire to gain insights into the judicial thinking model (reasoning, inference and deductions) and requested guidance on the application of specific procedures related to interpreting, particularly in situations involving omissions and additions.

These specific requests from the students necessitated a reordering of the instructional materials, resulting in modifications to the final training content. To address this, a new introductory module, termed "TLO 0," was introduced before TLO

1 to provide insights into the judge's cognitive processes. Furthermore, the sequencing of procedural skills was adjusted to precede the delivery of conceptual knowledge. The rationale behind this adjustment was to enable students to apply the conceptual understanding they gained to practical exercises in the procedural realm. Consequently, this approach led to a merger of the two domains of knowledge, as opposed to the original plan of introducing conceptual knowledge first, followed by procedural knowledge.

3.13.2 Attention

The AGES model contends that the need for activating the hippocampus for learning requires one's full attention to be placed on the topic being learnt. Divided attention and multitasking can be distracting and can counter the learning attempt. The following paragraphs present the students' management of attention during the intervention. Attention was observed in the design of the training material as well as in the presentation on the PowerPoint slides with the assumption that each slide should address only one point for discussion. Slides had images to better express ideas as well as texts. It is necessary, here, to recall that according to the AGES model, chunking, visuals and storytelling are critical for optimum retrieval of information. In a recent study, segmentation, in particular, was found to activate the pre-frontal cortex, which is part of the rewarding pathway in the brain (Li et al., 2020). This is why all exercises on CI were provided in the form of a story (a statement of claims by the plaintiff or the answer of the defendant) and in cartoon animation through Plotagon software and human simulating synthesis software.

Early on in the first lecture, however, the students, though appreciating the pictorial illustrations and cartoon videos, found it difficult to pay attention to the lecture because the presentation slides were 'overcrowded with pictures and written phrases'

(All students). According to (ST3), that did not give him the chance to capture all information. He said “I found it challenging to focus on what the trainer is saying at the same time as I see the images and read the texts on the slides”. Another student pointed out that “the text on the screen is too long and annoying for me.” (ST5) In fact, all students immediately pointed to this problem. As a result, the trainer asked them to focus only on specific images and skipped those she deemed redundant. Subsequent slides were all amended to reduce the combination of images and texts, and written material on the slides were shortened as much as possible. Any subsequent slide would have a maximum of two images. Texts were shortened and would appear on the screen by a click to reduce the density of those texts. However, students also noted that their attention became better when important ideas were highlighted or changed in colour. This also resulted in another change to the written material of the training where pictures were reduced, and key words or phrases were highlighted and coloured.

Another element of the training that caused the distraction of students was the 5-minute break in the first lectures, where a video was presented to them about something not related to interpreting. The idea of that break was to allow for mind wandering and force students to stop thinking about interpreting for five minutes. After asking students what they were thinking about during such breaks, only one student said “I found it very emotional and touching” (ST3). The remaining students complained that they were still in the mood of interpreting learning and could not make the connection between such breaks and what they have learnt. A student noted in her notebook “the first breaks that had videos of irrelevant stuff got me distracted. I did not know how I should connect them with the learning experience.” (ST2) Students agreed it would be much preferable to have a real break where students would do nothing or listen to soft music to make them more relaxed. The subsequent lessons were amended

accordingly, and the breaks were just void of any activity except for music for those who wished to listen to it.

The use of cartoon videos and synthesis software throughout the training boosted the attention of students. As the training progressed, the cartoon video started to appeal to them. The humorous videos provided in the beginning of the course, in particular, made them even laugh. At the end of the course, students expressed their appreciation of the cartoon videos. ST5 wrote about her feeling saying “the cartoons were amazing!” while ST7 wrote “the presentation of the material in cartoon videos and cartoon pictures was useful for me because they helped me understand better.” ST2 wrote

“I felt the cartoon videos were a simulation of reality. They were beautiful and varied, but also watching them relaxed me and helped me reduced the concentration burden. In addition, it was fun!” (ST2)

Similar appreciation came from ST1, who elaborated on the cartoon videos contrasting them to the experience of reading as she wrote: “I enjoyed the cartoon videos, as they helped in moving us away from fixing our eyes on anything that is written and from stacked information.” The fun part of the cartoon videos and the benefit that they offer in terms of attention was elaborated by ST8 who wrote:

“As for cartoon films, it is a way and method of learning that I have never experienced before, so it was a strange and enjoyable feeling at the same time. They also made me draw more attention and focus because it is something new, and the content in cartoon films was also interesting, and caught my attention. Because of cartoon films, the

strategies became easier to see and applied in this way, so I got the idea more. I mean, it was a very successful method in education, because it achieved the goal directly.” (ST8)

ST6 also wrote

““Very enjoyable and they increase attention. It is not like you are only listening to a recording but also seeing something. I saw interactions in the videos and the court environment, dress of characters and body language all stuck in my memory more than if they had been just audio files.” (ST6)

ST4 elaborated more on the reason why she liked the cartoon videos writing

“Very enjoyable and added a simplification effect. I had thought that court interpreting was impossible for me, but the cartoon plotting made it simpler as we were dealing with cartoon characters rather than real humans [synthesis human simulator]. ” (ST4)

Overall, all students showed support for the use of cartoon animations, except ST5 who, though liked the cartoons, preferred videos with real human characters (human simulating synthesis software).

The AGES model also holds that in order to maximise attention, the dopamine in the brain should be released in good amounts. This can be done, according to the model, through presenting to the individual a material that gives him the feeling of relevance. That was observed in the training by keeping aligned to the authenticity of material in light of actual court interpreting practices in Jordan and the needs of trainees in the intervention.

Feedback of some students in their diaries reflected on what made them pay attention to the lessons. A student noted in his diary the ‘harmony and willingness to learn featuring the learning environment in the course’. He added that from the first lecture he felt ‘as if I was really in a real court’ (ST3). Another student noted the effect of colours, images and videos that “attracted my attention and helped me concentrate better to the extent that I did not feel bored” (ST5). She also attributed her boosted attention to the fact that the subsequent slides presented in the lessons were not condensed in information but ‘contained key points’. She also stressed that her attention was even stronger than distractions to the extent that even when presented with a video that was full of distractions to teach students attention, “it surprised me that I even did not see the distractions but I even understood the message completely.” (ST5) This student was referring, in her diary, to lecture 4, where a video was presented to the students about distractions including body language. Referring to the recording of the lesson, the student was found to have said that she did not see any distraction and showed full understanding of the message, at which point another student interrupted her saying “I disagree with you. The body language was rather distracting.” (ST4) Here, again, the interpersonal interaction has played a role in exchanging views among the students, causing the former student to realise that she was very attentive to the video to the extent that she could not see the distractions.

Videos that contained wrong interpretations and corrections attracted the attention of some students. A student wrote:

“Some interpretations in the videos were inaccurate and contained information irrelevant to the original message. This made me curious to know more about the correct answers, thus increasing my attention.”

(ST7)

The same thought was echoed by another student who wrote “Videos that were assigned to me increased my attention. My attention was also increased when other colleagues were making comments on my interpretation.” Another student said the video exercises gave her the chance to understand what distraction is. She said “I love today’s lesson. Some noise happened in my room, and it distracted me. I now understand what distraction is.”

At the end of the training, students showed appreciation why they had learnt about some basics of the law and the court system. A student said “In the beginning, I wondered why we had to learn something about the law. Now I get it!” (ST7) All students said they paid full attention to the lectures. While directly assessing the authenticity of the students’ feelings regarding attention is not possible, their correct answers to questions in the subsequent lectures and their ability to remember the knowledge and skills of a consecutive interpreter can be an indication.

An important point about trainees is that one student showed preference to keep silence and her participation was not as active as other students were. She nevertheless wrote feedback in her journal and was active in the reflection part of the last lesson. She said she preferred listening to speaking but was attentive to the lessons and liked the interaction. This desire to refrain from active participation has recurred in the second group, as will be discussed.

3.13.3 Generation

Generation derives from the theory that each one’s brain is unique, and that learning can be enhanced if memory retention is strengthened in students’ minds. This is pursued by encouraging students to take ownership of the training material and

motivating them to link new learning with prior information that they have, by personalising information in a way that makes sense to them. One of the student felt ownership of the training as she generated information, saying

“It was an excellent technique that the trainer would first ask for our thoughts before making comments, because when information is elicited from the trainer himself, that would make it clearer much more than if otherwise was presented by the trainer in the beginning.” (ST4)

During the intervention, the trainer used hooks, kindles and bridges under the four styles of learning to encourage students to generate knowledge based on their prior information. The results show that students ‘caught’ the hooks, engaged with the kindles and successfully generated information on their own, with the trainer occasionally adding or correcting information as required. An example is when the trainer wanted to teach the students that interpreters at court are not allowed to add, omit or embellish messages. She introduced a this is/this is not exercise. A student responding to the question expressed what she understood: “The second interpreter added something not mentioned in the source text message.” (ST8) The trainer further kindled this information by asking whether the addition has made any difference. A student said “Sure, there is an effect on the court’s proceedings.” (ST3)

The students engaged actively with the prompts given to them all over the course where generation was intended. The technique of having students generate thoughts relevant to court interpreting on the basis of information that they already know was successful as illustrated through the following examples.

In the first lecture, the students were presented with a mastery-style hook. They were asked to share their thoughts about the qualities of a court interpreter by answering two successive questions:

“Think of a successful person you know. What made them successful?”

“Say to yourself: I am the first choice of courts as an interpreter? What made me successful?” The answers of the students were: persistence, patience, hard work, accurate interpreting, credibility, knowledge of the law, audacity, being continuously informed about cases at courts, updating general knowledge. The trainer ‘kindled’ the information given by students and encouraged them to further reflect on the example. Finally, students gave more detailed answers: listening comprehension, speed, speaking skills, good knowledge of legal terms and ability to interpret them correctly. In another lecture, students were presented with a case and asked what the judge would do (a mastery-style hook). The answer of one student (ST8), which was corroborated by two other students, was “the judge will listen to the parties, look into the evidence, decide if there is a legal relationship between them then decide on the source of obligation.” When asked how she knew that answer, as the material had not been given to them, the student said it was what she learnt in the previous lecture. Similarly, ST3 wrote “when watching a video about the social insurance case, I immediately remembered the judge’s logic, that is to confirm the facts, decide on the legal relation and determine the source of obligation”. Another student (ST7) elaborated by reminding the class of what happens if there is no legal relation, citing the example of gambling, also mentioned in a previous lecture.

The students also positively engaged with the understanding-style hook of “This is/This is not” exercises, where generation of information happens through comparison and contrast. By watching videos about a ‘cat’ that invites children to play in the street

and harm people, students successfully came with the conclusion that the purpose of the law is to regulate people's lives by restricting their freedoms. Two videos about a non-professional interpreter (this is not) and a professional one (this is) successfully led students to conclude that a professional court interpreter is one who has some situational awareness of the court system, declines jobs that pose conflicts of interest, observes a dress code, speaks in a clear accent, gets a 'nodding acquaintance' with the case and its technical and legal terms. The lesson about court interpreters' qualities included a quality of being neutral even in body language, without showing any facial expressions. This was taught to the students also through the 'this is not' technique by showing them a sphinx image. The sphinx shows no expressions of face, and the students were told to express the quality of neutrality in this respect through looking at the sphinx. All students successfully deduced that a court interpreter should maintain neutral facial expressions. The exercises showed that students had by then started to search for patterns (self-expressive style), as intended by the 'this is/this it not' technique. For this reason, the researcher added exercises about patterns at the end of the first terminal learning objective for learning enhancement.

The trainer presented the students with a picture of a soccer game and asked them, using the 'this is/this is not' hook, to think about what could make soccer game similar to court. The exercise successfully elicited from the students many thoughts about the court, using the soccer example. They compared the rules of the games to the laws and rules of court; the referee to the judge; the competitive teams to the disputants; and, referee's decision to the court decision. By considering the role of the referee in the game, students said the judge should be neutral and the judge's role should be to administer justice. After this brainstorm, the trainer presented the situational knowledge of the court and asked them if such description matched their

thoughts, to which all students confirmed. Again, this is an instance where the trainer's role was to reinforce information already stored in the students' minds rather than teaching them something new to them.

Another 'this is not' video was presented to the students, who collaboratively discussed it and came up with the following suggestions about what the court interpreter should not do: add, omit, manipulate for personal benefits, distort the message and offer inaccurate or misleading interpretation. Another student said the interpreter should have asked for clarification when she did not understand something in the message. Amendments, commissions, additions, facial expressions and body language and asking for clarification were precisely the information that was supposed to be bridged in this exercise. The role of the trainer here was just to reinforce the deductions that the students had made.

There was one instant where the students did not give a correct answer to a 'this is not' exercise. They were presented with a cartoon video featuring a court interpreter adding, omitting and embellishing words. The same featured interpreter in another video imitated the tone of the original speaker and mirrored her emotions. All students said both interpretations were 'good' and that it was good that the interpreter imitated the body language of the original speaker. At that point, the trainer interfered, following the Zone of Proximal Development principle, where the trainer is expected to help the students with the correct information. The trainer told them a court interpreter cannot add, omit or embellish and that those ideas would be explained in subsequent lessons. At the end of the course, the students reflected on that video again, but this time they correctly identified the issues in interpreting. During the training, another pair of videos featured two interpreters saying the same thing but one was using body language.

Students successfully concluded that an interpreter would not ‘translate body language’ when interpreting at court.

The generation technique worked even with instances that could be challenging. Cognitive-wise. Consider the following ‘this is/this is not’ exercise:

Students were presented with the following two instances and were asked to express in their own words what they conclude in legal terms in relation to the word ‘dispute’. Both instances are hypothetical answers by a person to another one asking for his money to be repaid.

This is not: “I have taken the money from you as a loan. I will repay it to you certainly. I am not a bad man.”

This is: “I have taken the money from you. It is not a loan. It is to fund our business but we lost the money in that business”

Students successfully noted that the first instance showed a dispute between the parties, while the dispute did not happen in the second one. The trainer further kindled this information by asking “what does make a dispute ‘dispute’?” Several answers came:

“They don’t agree on something.” (ST3)

“Someone wants something from Y but Y does not want to do it or give it over.” (ST11)

“Different perspectives” (ST5)

More interestingly, in another similar instance, where the ‘this is not’ speaker claimed the amount he is owed by his employer Alpha Beta from the Municipality, a student not only recognized the absence of dispute between the speaker and the municipality but she also said ‘the municipality is not responsible for the payment’. The word ‘responsible’ is a legal term that courts in Jordan use to decide if a defendant is

obliged to pay a debt to the plaintiff. Similar successful answers were made by students when presented with ‘this is/this is not’ scenarios on court jurisdiction and judge’s jargons. One of the students built on the information she previously learnt saying the judge’s talk related to lack of court’s jurisdiction. The way in which a judge thinks and talks was not clear to the other students, so the researcher designed a new slide with pictures this time illustrating the ‘this is/this is not’ scenarios and added a chapter (Chapter Zero) at the beginning of the course to facilitate the learning process of students in this regard. The researcher also designed videos where the students can hear what is inside the judge’s mind when hearing the case. Such thinking-aloud videos are along the lines of the modelling under the direct instruction technique of Silver’s mastery style of learning. The picture and videos resulted in a better understanding of some other students, as they answered the question correctly. Further pictures were added to explain the logic of judges and all students successfully deduced on their own the main ideas behind those pictures. On judges’ logic, a student identified the ‘this is not’ and ‘this is’, respectively as

“a random thinking without logic based on what the speaker thinks can be taken for granted, while the other was logic based on the law, without taking things for granted.” (ST13)

On the issue of emotional statements made by litigants, a student said ‘the judge would not judge people based on their emotions. The judge will follow logical arguments only.’ Several pictorial illustrations were added to ensure that all students will have a role in the discussion. Still one student said he could not fully understand the judge’s logic, at which point the trainer presented a video where a judge is hearing a case and students could hear what the judge is saying in her mind, and asked him to

reply. The student answered the question correctly based on the video, then said “now I understand it after seeing this video.”

Students were actively engaged in collective interpersonal discussions. One of the student noticed in his diary that “I felt comfortable to discuss with colleagues and feel that we have a common understanding of the lesson” (ST3), which is also echoed by ST8, who wrote that the discussion among students was comfortable as “we were thinking in the same way”. In the second lecture, students were asked to figure out what ‘small claim’ mean. A discussion ensued among the students (the interpersonal style), with one saying it is about a person who refuses to pay what he allegedly owes another one. Another student jumped in to add that the claimed value is small in such a dispute. At the end of the slides on the concepts of court, interpreter and small claim, the students have already correctly answered the questions, even added more information than was presented to them on the next slide that had the answers. At that slide, the trainer’s role was to reinforce the information students had learnt and bridge them with the next piece of information. The trainer asked them to express what they hoped to learn more about those concepts (self-expressive style). Among the questions of students were “I need to know about the limitations of a court interpreter” (ST4) and “what should an interpreter do to be able to render a faithful interpretation?” (ST12) An interpersonal discussion also ensued about whether an interpreter had the right to interrupt a speaker at court when the speaker talks at length. Answers varied. ST5 said ‘No, he shouldn’t’, another one said “He should” (ST4) then a third one said “He can do that with the permission of the judge.” (ST7) Then, first student (ST5) elaborated “the interpreter would use notes and chunking.” Another student said “I expect the interpreter to tell the judge that he is facing difficulties.” (ST6) The correct answers to those questions were then incorporated into the next chapters.

In a simulator video, a case was presented featuring small claim court interpreter taking the oath before the judge. Students were asked to tell what they could deduce from the video. A student correctly said the judge would confirm that the interpreter was proficient in the English language (ST7) and that then she was trying to figure out what legal relationship existed between the plaintiff and defendant to check on the applicable source of obligation (ST3). The hook used was from the understanding style of learning where students were asked to approach the video as ‘this is’. More students contributed to the discussion with some indicating that the source of obligation was a contract, and the interpreter was accurate in interpreting the talk exchanged in the court room. Student at this instance mentioned for the first time the use of ‘literal interpreting’ as a good quality of a professional interpreter. Another student carried on the discussion saying that the interpreter’s literal interpretation even involved him preserving the same sequencing of ideas. Students also noticed that the interpreter did not use body language.

In order to retain the knowledge learnt in memory, a student, according to the AGES model, should apply it in practice. The theoretical part of the training gave the students rules for CI at small-claims court, and to reinforce this knowledge, the training material provided students with practical audio-visual exercises to interpret between English and Arabic. In the beginning, students did not directly apply the knowledge they learnt, which students explained by saying that it was their first time to do CI. A student said “In the beginning, it was very frightening. Things are becoming increasingly easier”.

As exercises progressed, students started to actively use the skills learnt through the program, such as interrupting, asking for clarification or requesting repetitions. In doing that, they used the formal phrases taught to them, such as ‘the interpreter requests the litigant to repeat...the interpreter requests a clarification’. Discussions about the

videos involved the students, under the interpersonal model, to reflect on the source of obligation and legal relationship exhibited in those videos. A student said “Collective discussion among us encouraged me more to talk and participate. It also gave me the opportunity to know the opinion of other colleagues, which drew my attention to things that I missed.”

In summary, the training succeeded in offering students the chance to generate their own knowledge based on prior knowledge and apply it. Theoretically, generation can strengthen students’ memory. Throughout the intervention as well as at its conclusion, students reflected on their knowledge, individually but also in peer-discussions. One last point is that while the slides had the minimum possible explanations and the trainer relied heavily on eliciting knowledge from the students through discussions and feedback, students, as one said in the fourth lesson, said “the explanations are more than enough and there is no need to add anything to it” (ST9), answering the trainer’s question whether they thought something was missing in the explanation or if they wished to have anything added to the material.

3.13.4 Emotions

The question of emotions relates, here, to what kind of emotion that students have responded with to their specific learning experiences. This can be framed in Gross’s steps (Gross, 2002), which are: situation, aspect, meaning and response. In this analysis, students found themselves in a situation of learning something they have never been exposed to, that is court interpreting. The skills they brought in the training (aspects) were (as they presumed) not enough to study it, which meant to them that becoming an interpreter at court was an unattainable goal. It is at this point that the training material and the trainer assured the students not to hasten a response (in terms of frustration). Therefore, the training in the case study has worked on assuring

emotional regulation among students early on before reaching the response phase, to prevent frustration or other negative feelings. Here, the emphasis is particularly put on increasing the reward feeling and reducing any frustration or boredom during the process of learning.

3.13.4(a)(i) Reward and self-confidence

In their constant discussions about advancing the relationship between neuroscience and education, researchers have identified reward as an area worth considering in educational practices. Research suggests that increasing the dopamine in the brain can be actualised through rewards, which can be divided into intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, both aimed at increasing an individual's motivation to learning. Studies in neuroscience also link reward to self-confidence. When an individual feels rewarded, their self-confidence increases and hence their desire to do a better job. Thinking positively about oneself activates the value part of the brain, which includes the reward system, hence making him more confident. A more recent study reveals that providing students with achievable goals and rewards can activate the pre-frontal cortex, which is part of the reward pathway in the brain (Blood & Zatorre, 2001) and can make the subject more attractive to students in terms of boosting their self-confidence and understanding of concepts.

There are two types of rewards: intrinsic and extrinsic. In this intervention, the extrinsic rewards promised and given to students were: a certificate of attendance from the Association of Jordanian Translators and Applied Linguists, the training material and the videos for their future use. Rummel and Feinberg (1988) suggest that extrinsic rewards can have an undermining effect on intrinsic motivation. Relevant studies on rewards also suggest that financial rewards provided on the condition of performing well on a task can inhibit the very intrinsic motivation to perform that task. This is why

there the participants were not given any financial compensation for their participation in the training. In addition, neither the researcher nor the trainer exaggerated in showing the students the anticipated value of the extrinsic rewards given to them. The extrinsic reward, though, is not expected to harm the motivation of the training as it comes at the end with the only condition of attending the training course. Research suggests a powerful effect of offering extrinsic rewards after intrinsic rewards. In this training, all emphasis was made on the intrinsic rewards as will be presented below.

The trainer observed the reward effect and sought to maximise it. She used positive reinforcement words such as 'excellent' when a good answer was given by students. She showed verbal appreciation of the collective work of students, and on multiple occasions she would say when presenting new information (bridging) "You can see how the information you mentioned earlier is the same as the one I wanted to present to you. You even said more!" The trainer was keen not to disturb the reward that students felt in making discussions, so when ST1 for example suggested that a court in Jordan would have juries (which is not correct), the trainer did not say anything about that. She simply encouraged the discussion and preferred to correct that information in the upcoming lectures. Other phrases of encouragement included "I am happy with your discussion...I am happy that you came up with this correct idea on your own without me telling it to you."

The training material included parts where the trainees were invited to think of a reward that they get from the training, especially if they learnt any new word or phrase or mastered a skill. The students were encouraged to always think of such rewards throughout the intervention. The reason behind this is to prime the feeling of reward to maximise the feeling of pleasure in the students. By lecture 4, students realised that the videos contained words or phrases which were new to them and asked if those could be

explained. They also repeatedly mistook ‘plaintiff’ with ‘defendant’. Students suggested that there could be reminders of those key words in the training, which the researcher complied with and added reminders not only of those but also of other keywords throughout the pages of the handbook. The researcher also sought to maximise the benefit of students by collecting terms from the videos and presenting them in a form of a glossary.

Getting new knowledge was expressed by students as having the reward effect on them. ST8 wrote “I felt rewarded in the training, when there was information, I didn’t know but now I know. It was like a reward that motivated me to learn more knowledge.” She added that the discussion among students and peer-to-peer encouragement “was also a reward that motivated me to participate more, but the final reward overall after the course was that I learnt things I had never known about.” The same feeling was echoed by ST3, a fourth-year student, who wrote:

“The training has been a bright beacon in my academic and practical journey, which all started with this course. I got a large amount of information with my colleagues and through interaction among us.”

(ST3)

ST8 also seconded the attainment of reward writing:

“I felt being rewarded by knowing new things that I never knew. The reward as an incentive for me to learn more. The trainer’s method and the presentation of the material helped a lot. When I discussed something and found out that I said even a small thing correctly, I felt rewarded and getting the incentive to go on. The discussions of my peers were rewarding, but the biggest reward I felt was when I realized

how much benefit and knowledge I got about topics that I have never known anything about before.” (ST8)

ST4 agrees as she writes “the reward was when I felt my ideas and participation were taken as important and seriously. It gave me self-confidence. That was the main incentive.”

Peer support was also seen by students as a reward. In the video exercises, where students were given the opportunity to do CI, a student made a correct and complete interpretation but reflected in her notebook that she did not feel she did well. The trainer asked the students, and two students said simultaneously “excellent”.

Giving correct answers and receiving positive feedback from the trainer was felt as a reward. In the diaries of students, a student felt being rewarded when giving a correct answer and getting positive feedback. She wrote:

“I had the feeling of being rewarded when I gave correct answers to the prompts. In one instance, I interpreted correctly, and the trainer gave me positive feedback. That made me happy. In another instance, I felt rewarded in a discussion about certain points, and after the brainstorm, the trainer showed us the correct answers and they were exactly the same as we said, despite the fact that we had not had any access to the material.” (ST6)

Support from peers and the trainer was also echoed by ST3, who wrote:

“Whenever I express an idea, however simple, it is followed by encouragement by the trainer. They [the trainer and students] would enrich my idea through discussion and encourage innovative ideas.”

Some students contrasted reward with fear that they had at the beginning of the training, ST5 said “Things are getting better. In the beginning, it was very frightening. Things are becoming increasingly easier.” The same juxtaposition was echoed by two other students. ST2 said:

“Concerning breaking the fear barrier, had I not been in such an environment where people will not judge me, I would have not been able to break that barrier because I know I will make mistakes.... This is why I feel courageous to interpret the videos.” (ST2)

In summary, students in the intervention felt many rewards in the training session. Such rewards included in the students’ abilities to understand concepts, learn new vocabulary and perform in the audio-visual interpreting exercises. Other rewards were in the form of acknowledgement from the trainer of their correct answers or good discussions, and support from the other students. All of those rewards were intrinsic.

3.13.4(a)(ii) Frustration and boredom

When students encounter too difficult levels to perform at beyond the Zone of Proximal Development, they can be frustrated (Ness, 2023) hence losing the motivation to learn. Given the fact that the students in the intervention were not experienced, the study aimed at maximizing their benefit at their own paces. Therefore, the audio-visual exercises were designed according to the graduated difficulty strategy. Originally, as the training started without having a clear hypothesis about what makes a video exercise difficult, the researcher designed the video exercises on three levels as shown in the following image:

Figure 3.15 Graduated difficulty strategy levels

The aim of level 1 was to allow students to build some confidence by interpreting short videos that do not have technical or legal terms. Students who feel that they are proficient at level 1 were given the opportunity to try levels 2 and 3, but the trainer told them that level 3 needs more extensive note-taking than levels 1 and 2. In those exercises, the expectation was that students would use the techniques already taught to them in the court, including asking the judge for a repetition, interrupting and asking for clarification. In level 3, where summary interpretation was required, the students were expected to perform the higher skill of noting key words that would remind them while consecutively interpreting the videos of the claims, the legal relationship, and the source of obligation, in addition to the claimed value, in addition to the names of litigants and any relevant numbers that might be mentioned.

The actual video exercises on all three levels were placed in the last chapter of the book with the idea that students would have already studied the relevant theoretical part of the training covering the necessary knowledge and skills and would be then ready to begin interpreting. The first attempts of students to do CI was in Lesson 2, in the context of their learning of the strategies of interpreting at court. Throughout the

subsequent lessons, subsequent trials and errors were attempted by students, giving them a better understanding of their capabilities. In Lesson 5, ST8 said she found note-taking 'difficult' because notetaking distracted her attention and that she would "prefer the interruption technique". Other students agreed, and they showed relief after the subsequent slides in the Lesson stated that notetaking could be challenging and that some court interpreters in Jordan would use the interruption technique.

The graduated-difficulty-strategy exercises of interest in the results relate specifically to the later exercises where students were expected to use their knowledge and skills in court interpreting. Three levels were always given in each exercise. All students in the beginning chose to start at level 1. They made attempts to interpret at levels 2 and 3. At the end of the training, only ST1, ST3 and ST4 managed to give summary interpretation at Level 3 in some videos. Throughout the exercises, even at level 1, students chose to apply the strategies of interruption, asking for repetition and asking for clarification from the hypothetical judge by saying the expression "the interpreter requests the judge to ask the speaker to...". Note-taking was a challenge for all trainees at all these levels. ST8, for example said "I found it challenging to write notes and interpret at the same time." This remark was responded by an answer from the trainer that in actual court interpreting in Jordan, the interpreter would have the option to ask for clarification or repetition or even to interrupt the speaker. Students showed relief to receive this assurance. Note-taking at the level of the current students, therefore, was a multi-tasking effort that severely affected their comprehension, hence interpretation of the exercises.

The performance of the students on the three levels unfolded into three findings. First, note-taking was difficult for them at this stage of learning, except for writing numbers whenever mentioned. Second, summary interpreting at level 3 was

problematic for them, as they felt they were not trained enough to “know what to omit and what to keep in the interpretation” as ST6 said. Technical and legal terms were also a challenge for all students at level 3, compounded by their inability to use notetaking effectively and their lack of vocabulary, despite the fact that the key terms of the videos were given to them earlier. However, it is also necessary to point out that all students preferred in the beginning to perform at level 1. Some (ST5, ST8) chose to listen to the message first and think about it before deciding to interpret. Others at some moments chose to listen even to the model interpretation (ST2, ST6), and still others decided to move up to levels 2 and 3 after they said they felt comfortable at level 1 (ST1, ST3, ST4, ST13).

Some students (ST1, ST3 and ST4, ST12) managed to interpret up to 15 seconds in a row. The specific use of interruption, with the preference of students that they interrupt the speaker after around five seconds to interpret the message, and the overall trend of students to listen to the video interpretation model first, unfolded into three additional segments of the graduated difficulty. Overall, the levels of videos under the graduated difficulty strategy became as in Figure (3.15):

Figure 3.16 Levels of difficulty discerned from the Pilot

Despite the challenges especially the ones posed by level 3, students engaged actively with the exercises at different paces. ST3 attempted a level-3 exercise where he provided a summary. A reinforcement discussion followed by students. ST1 commented on the incorrect commissions that ST3 did, though she highlighted correct interpretations. ST8 commended ST3's correct omission strategy, an idea supported by ST5, which reinforced ST3 and made him feel comfortable, as he said.

Increasing the level of exercises meant the students were challenged in terms of their knowledge and skills and made errors, which could have caused frustration. In the

training, however, students' attempts were followed by a discussion among the students pointing out to points of strength and improvement. Students were comfortable to accept other students, as all agreed that all of them were making mistakes, and they were in a learning process. Interestingly, after hearing one video at the 3rd level, two students (ST4 and ST5) expressed their amazement: "Interesting!" (ST5) and "That was amazing! Full of useful terms and vocabulary to learn!" (ST4).

Being challenged by the second and third levels was not easy to students, but that did not frustrate them, though. In the diaries, students explained that. ST4 did not have the confidence and courage to go up to higher levels, however

"in light of my performance at the lower levels, and after getting feedback from peers and trainer, the very decision on my part to take the courage and attempt the higher levels (2 and 3) was in itself an achievement. This added to my self-confidence." (ST4)

Indeed, in Lesson 8, ST4 said to the trainer that she was encouraged by her peers' feedback to attempt interpreting the higher level. She said that exercising at the suitable levels increased her satisfaction with her abilities, which "made me more eager to learn."

ST8 also noted that even that the higher levels were difficult, they were a source of encouragement for her "They show us where we are going and what goal we will have to achieve at the end." ST1 tried the higher levels because level 1 gave her 'strength' and made her willing to take the initiative. However, as Level 3 had technical and legal terms and was long in time, ST5 felt "disappointed' as she wished she would perform well at that high level. However, she also noted that such disappointment waned after the trainer and colleagues reminded her that she could use the repetition,

clarification and interruption strategies. Those strategies have also been cited in the diaries by ST1, ST2, ST3 and ST8, as a source of empowerment for them.

In sum, the graduated difficulty strategy was successful in giving the students the chance to practice at their own paces without feeling frustration when committing mistakes. They felt comfortable that even if they went down to easier levels, they would have chances to use such skills in actual court rooms, especially with the use of ancillary strategies such as asking for repetition and clarification or interruption. Students' sense of self-confidence and reward was further boosted by the opportunity they had to develop their own paced levels of practising, as long as they kept in sight the highest level of performance required from court interpreters in real life. The students also said their self-confidence increased their willingness to learn and achieve their goals.

3.13.5 Spacing

Spacing is the distribution of learning over time to improve long-term learning. Spaced learning can produce better performance by the learners than if information is amassed without interruptions, with intervals ranging from minutes to days even weeks. Authors of the AGES model believe that spacing enables the brain to 'digest new content' and build and activate neurological connections conducive to long-term memory and retrieval.

The study used spacing in the case study. Based on the request of the students themselves, the training was given over a period of one month, with two lessons a week. There was a consensus among students that they needed this spacing in order for them to reflect on what they have learnt. Some students (6 of them) added that they preferred to write down notes during the intervals. Since each lesson was delivered in a two-hour time, the students showed a consensus that they needed to shorten the session time to one hour and a half. They also asked to have around a seven-minute break after half of

the lesson. The trainer complied with the requests, as they were compatible with the spacing effect in education. In her notebook, one of the students noted “the breaks were relaxing, especially the one where soft music was played.” (ST1)

In the second lecture, the reduced amount of time available to teach the material led the trainer to rush in the teaching, as she felt it necessary to complete the lesson for that day. The students also expressed the same concern. At that point, I sent her a message through WhatsApp and then personally to tell her to go at a slower pace, since amassing information is contrary to the spacing effect principle. She then proceeded at a slower pace as suitable for the students, promising them at the same time that if they could not finish the material in eight lessons, there would be a chance for an extension to the course if they wished.

In the training, one of the students wrote in her diary about the spacing effect. She expressly stated that it was convenient to her because “it gave me some time to revise the lessons, reflect on what I have learnt and most importantly search the internet for relevant material in case I had a problem understanding something.”

A review of the students’ notebooks showed emphasis on this issue. ST(4) said about this specific lesson “the slides were moving at a fast pace. I could not find time to comprehend the information to take notes. I felt I was losing concentration.” After the issue was resolved, students expressed satisfaction with the spacing. A student said spacing helped her organise her thoughts and learning experience: “Spacing was excellent. It gave me the opportunity to reflect on what I have learnt in the right way. Information did not amass in my mind, but was something that I received in an organized manner.” (ST1) Other students gave positive responses as well:

“The space between lessons was reasonable, preventing amassing of information, thus contributing to easing my revision of the information that I learnt” (ST2)

“Spacing allowed me to comprehend what I learnt in the lesson and allowed me to arrange my thoughts, but most importantly it gave me the time to relax my mind.” (ST4)

“That [spacing] was useful for me. Information was not amassed. On the contrary, the space between lessons gave me the opportunity to get deeper into specific topics.” (ST5)

“Spacing between lessons helped me in rearranging information and organizing my thoughts. It gave me time to reflect on the examples shared in the lesson.” (ST6)

“Spacing was suitable. It allowed me to remember information without feeling pressure but also to assess the information that I received and develop myself.” (ST8)

Since spacing by definition relates to a practice where information is not amassed for the trainees, the intervention applied spacing in the sequencing of the audio-visual CI exercises. Instead of asking students to go on interpreting video after video, a space has been always maintained between each two videos. In the intervals, there would be discussions or a break for a minimum of five minutes. According to the diaries of the students, this technique was helpful. According to a student, the spacing between exercises allowed for an interpersonal dialogue between colleagues to share their constructive comments:

“Discussing mistakes and improvements in interpreting with colleagues after each video was useful in making information stick. I benefited from everyone’s notes and comments. That was better than giving intensive direct exercises all at once and then giving the information because some people might get confused and the information overlaps, for example.” (ST8)

Another student noted that the spacing between videos reduced the stress on her:

“I had thought that the video could be longer or complex, which made me reluctant to participate. When I heard the videos, my fear started to wane. The space between videos also gave me time to comprehend a word or a phrase that I may have missed while watching the video.”

(ST5)

The spacing between videos also had an effect on improving performance:

“The spacing between videos was useful as it helped me arrange my thoughts and learn from my mistakes. It helped me improve my performance.” (ST3)

Spacing also allowed, according to ST2, for reducing the cognitive load, “making the mind ready to receive information. Amassed flow of information, otherwise, in such a highly specialized training, could have let the trainee be in a status of boredom, unresponsiveness and lack of interest to what is presented.” It also, according to ST4, “was important to give me space for organizing my ideas and planning for how to interpret the next videos.”

The idea of peer support and interpersonal discussion effect on performance was also supported by ST8:

“The discussion between the videos was a feedback opportunity. The feedback in fact is the most important part of the training, as we take notes and observe the mistakes of each other, which helps us avoid them but also see the positive things they do and follow them.”

The interpersonal interaction among students, however, was contested by one student. She said in her diary that during the space between videos

“students exchanged their views, were making mistakes and were ignorant of what they were doing. I refrained from opposing them lest I made them angry. I accepted their remarks on my performance but was angry with some criticism that they made on me. Should you [the researcher] have been the one who gave the training and made the criticism, I would have accepted it.” (ST5)

Nevertheless, she still strongly suggested the importance of the spacing between videos:

“Spacing between videos was useful, even a necessity. It gave my mind and nerves a chance to have some rest. I badly needed that space because I was keen on paying maximum attention to the lessons. The spacing itself gave me the chance to take notes, which I was not otherwise able to do during the exercise.” (ST5)

Spacing requires repetitions, and according to the AGES model, it can happen in different forms, including testing, priming and reviewing. By the third lecture, students had learnt about the role of court interpreters as language conduits. After three days, in the fourth lecture, the trainer started a slide about coherence, and asked a direct question to test students' understanding:

“What happens if the litigant or witness makes a statement that lacks coherence?
What should the interpreter do?”

The question triggered prior information of another trainer who talked about the pragmatic principles of coherence, cohesion, quantity, quality and relation (ST3). Another student volunteered and gave an answer that is both based on her prior understanding of the previous lectures but also tried to anticipate what other actions could be taken:

“The interpreter as far as I know is a language conduit and should either interpret everything as is. Incoherence may happen, I guess, because of certain problems with the litigant, so it would be better to alert the judge about the incoherence issue... the litigant might be ill or something like this.” (ST8)

As the student tried to make a guess, the trainer used the opportunity to encourage other students to make other guesses this time by asking what rules apply on incoherent statements in American courts, given the fact they have codes of professional ethics for interpreters. The lesson then proceeded as planned.

Last but not least, after four months of the end of the training, ST1, who reported that she kept on studying the material, reverted to the researcher with this question:

“I understand that the court interpreter should take an oath to perform interpreting in a faithful manner. I cannot understand though why being

‘faithful’ in interpreting is equated with literal or verbatim interpreting?

Can’t ‘free translation’ be faithful?” (ST1)

This feedback is in line with Hale (2007) who refutes the assumption that faithful interpreting equates to literalness. This also resonates with the interpreters in the semi-structured interviews who equated faithfulness to an interpretation that is close to the source text. Regardless of the answer (which will be discussed in the subsequent chapter), this question has come after a spacious space from the training course, which again shows the spacing effect in action.

In summary, the students overwhelmingly expressed their satisfaction with the spacing methods used in the training. They considered those techniques useful in terms of allowing for reflection, preventing intensive cognitive load on them, learning from mistakes and offering them an opportunity to comprehend the material better.

3.14 Remarks on the material and trainer

The pilot study was meant to identify potential problems and limitations in the research design and data collection instruments. The findings of the pilot study were used to adjust the research design and procedures before starting the actual case study. This reflected on making changes to the material and giving clearer instructions to the trainer. In terms of the material, students did not feel comfortable with the presentation of graphic slides that were loaded with words. They also showed interest in having a glossary of terms that they could have otherwise studied before doing an interpretation exercise. They also showed difficulty in applying the procedural knowledge skills taught to them in the training, and had difficulty in memorising terms in English and Arabic.

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the data analysis of this study that explore the content knowledge that should be taught in a small-claims court interpreting curriculum and how lessons plans can be devised in a way that is compatible with findings in neuroscience research and brain-based education. In particular, it answers the first three research questions related to situational, conceptual and procedural knowledge.

Situational knowledge, as the following sections reveal, refers to the interpreter's contextual understanding of the courtroom environment, including the rules of appointment, the spatial and procedural setting of small-claims courts, and the interpreter's own professional status within the judicial system. This form of knowledge largely influences the interpreter's conduct, such as the appropriate choice of register, terms of address, and interactional strategies when communicating with judges, litigants, and other court participants. Situational knowledge is found to be essential for both securing the interpreter's appointment and maintaining professional credibility and role boundaries during proceedings. Situational knowledge enables interpreters to navigate institutional expectations and perform with accuracy, neutrality, and authority in the unique communicative setting of small-claims courts.

Conceptual knowledge in the context of small-claims court interpreting refers to the interpreter's understanding of the legal and thematic domains relevant to a dispute, enabling them to grasp and accurately convey the underlying concepts and terminology involved. This includes familiarity with the typical subject matter of cases

(e.g., accountancy, manufacturing, mechanics, etc.), and the ability to anticipate and articulate key legal terms with minimal prior exposure to the specific details of the case. In addition, conceptual knowledge encompasses an interpreter's foundational understanding of legal systems and principles, particularly the five recognized sources of legal obligations and rights in Jordanian law (such as contract, harm, enrichment, etc.). This knowledge allows the interpreter to perceive the pragmatic legal implications of what is being said and to render the message in a manner that maintains its legal effect, accuracy, and contextual appropriateness. It is, therefore, essential for ensuring that the interpretation supports both legal precision and communicative clarity in judicial proceedings.

Procedural knowledge in the context of small-claims court interpreting refers to the interpreter's ability to apply linguistic, cognitive, and management skills in real-time to perform interpreting tasks effectively. It encompasses the "know-how" required to carry out various interpreting modes used in court settings, including CI, summary interpreting, whispered (chuchotage) interpreting, verbatim interpreting, and sight translation of legal documents. Procedural knowledge also involves strategic management of the courtroom interaction, such as knowing when and how to request clarifications, appropriately interrupt proceedings when necessary for accurate interpretation, and maintaining control over the interpreting process to ensure fidelity and professionalism. This type of knowledge integrates memory retention, rapid language processing, and situational judgment, enabling interpreters to navigate the dynamic and often high-pressure environment of small-claims courts.

Taken together, situational knowledge, conceptual knowledge, and procedural knowledge form the core professional competency required of small-claims court interpreters in Jordan. These three knowledge domains are interdependent: situational

knowledge ensures that interpreters understand the courtroom environment and their professional role within it; conceptual knowledge equips them with the legal and thematic understanding necessary to grasp and accurately render the meaning of disputes; and procedural knowledge enables them to apply interpreting techniques and manage real-time courtroom interactions effectively. Collectively, these types of knowledge not only define the competency profile of a small-claims interpreter but also constitute the essential content knowledge that must be embedded in any training program aimed at authentically preparing students for the realities of professional court interpreting in Jordan. A training curriculum that meaningfully integrates these areas bridges academic learning with professional practice, ensuring that graduates are well-equipped to meet the demands of real-world small-claims court interpreting.

Table (4.1) below lists the revealed components of the three types of knowledge.

Table 4.1 Emerging themes

Open codes	Axial codes	Selective codes
outsourcing procedure	Appointment	Situational knowledge
conflict of interest		
taking the oath	Professional status	
language conduit		
attire		
Court officials in the courtroom	Court room	
posture		
official address		
classical Arabic		
subject matter	Domain knowledge	Conceptual knowledge
Technical terms		
case claims	Case-specific knowledge	
litigants	Legal knowledge	
legal linguistic implications		
legal pragmatics		
consecutive interpreting	Mode of interpreting	Procedural knowledge
whispering interpreting		
sight interpreting		
verbatim interpreting		

summary interpreting		
dictating the court reporter		
note-taking	Memory skills	
short-term memory		
concentration		
listening	Language skills	
speaking		
accuracy		
sequencing	Management skills	
editing		
accents		
interrupting		
asking for clarification		
asking for repetition		

4.1.1 Situational knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan

The courtroom, as described by the interviewees, is not spacious. It is typically office-like and consists of a bench where the judge sits and a small desk next to it for the court reporter. There is also a large computer screen visible to everyone entering the room. This screen is used for the disputants or witnesses to review their statements as transcribed by the reporter. They can approve, make amendments, or changes as necessary. Interpreters and lawyers said there was no official rule for the appointment of court interpreters. The primary method is through the court administration office, known as the Diwan, where interpreters can leave their business cards for their service promotion. Alternatively, interpreters can be outsourced by a translation office or a law firm. In this case, they are contacted directly, and the location and fees are negotiated.

According to all in the Professional Group, judges at hearings did not consistently ask the interpreters to produce qualification evidence, such as copies of translation/interpreting certificates, except for DP7, who showed the judge a card of his membership to the Jordanian Translators Association. According to all in the Professional Group, the judge assessed their eligibility by asking questions like: “Do you speak [the foreign language]? Do you personally know any of the case parties or

witnesses?" Once admitted to the courtroom, the formalities of checking on the interpreter's eligibility starts. The judge checks on any conflicts of interest, and swears in the interpreter as required by the law. This typically involves a series of questions and orders answered by the interpreter as in the following dialogue:

Judge: You are the interpreter, correct?

Interpreter: Yes, your honour! I am the interpreter.

Judge: Are you qualified to perform interpretation between Arabic and Language X?"

Interpreter: Yes, your honour! I hold a degree in X language and have experience in it."

Judge: Do you have any prior knowledge of the disputants or witnesses?"

Interpreter: No, your honour!

Judge: Place your hand on the Qur'an and repeat after me: 'I solemnly swear by God Almighty that I will faithfully carry out the task entrusted to me, faithfully and sincerely.'" (in Arabic: أقسم بالله العظیم أن أؤدي المهمة الموكلة إلي بأمانة وإخلاص

4.1.2 Procedural knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan

The interview revealed issues of procedural knowledge which they applied on performing interpreting in their cases. Interpreters unanimously agree that the interpretation should be conducted in classical Arabic to facilitate the court report writing. If an interpreter needs to request a statement repetition from a participant, they do so through the judge. For example, they might say, "The interpreter requests that the plaintiff repeat what he said" or "The interpreter asks the defendant to clarify." When addressing the judge, some interpreters use "Your Honor," while others opt for "Ya Bey."

Court interpreting requires the interpreter to be familiar with what INT3 calls ‘protocols of the court’, to be well prepared (INT1) and to preserve own ‘prestige’ as indicated by INT10. Before taking the job, an interpreter should be prepared by having some knowledge about the case according to all members of the professional group except for INT10 who stated that such information should be kept to the minimum adequate amount to ensure that an interpreter’s neutrality is not compromised by knowing too much about the case litigants. He said “I am a human being and have emotions. I cannot guarantee that my heart inadvertently goes in favour of a litigant against the other.”

All interpreters in the professional group said they were not members of a roster that could otherwise be held by courts or the Ministry of Justice. The absence of such rosters caused one interpreter, INT7, to lose opportunities to work in further cases at court. She said upon visiting the court to inquire why it no longer contacted her for more jobs, the answer from the Administrative Office was that they did not have any idea about her as an interpreter as they did not maintain a list.

Given the reported lack of rigid interpreter eligibility requirements, I asked the interpreters if they were aware of any error they could have made in interpreting. All professional interpreters except INT10 and INT1, said they did not commit errors in interpretation, stating that the discourse at a court room was, according to their experience, simple and the interlocutors would speak in small chunks. All of the professional interpreters denied that their interpretation was contested by any interlocutor at court, whether disputants, witnesses or the judge, or was subject to judicial review at apex courts, to the best of their knowledge. Nevertheless, INT1 said the judge asked her for confirmation on a given interpreting of an utterance, alluding, she suggests, to an error, upon which she said “I am sorry. I made a mistake” and made

the correction accordingly. INT10 indicated that he made a mistake in one of the cases he interpreted for, but once he realized that, he immediately notified the judge of the error and asked a correction in the script. According to INT10, “It turned out that the omitted phrase was indeed the most important element of the criminal charges that would determine the outcome of the case.” He further elaborated that all testimonies, including those made through his interpretation, were shown on three screens, one before the judge, another with the scribe and a third one shown to all participants in the court room. At the end of the proceedings, INT10 said: “the judge asked me to do sight interpretation of the screen to the non-Arabic speaking litigant then I counter-signed the statement”. This procedure has not been cited by any other interpreter of the study.

The participants in the Expert Group agree that there are no rigid legal provisions governing the appointment of interpreters at court, and that the law considers court interpreters as experts under the Bylaws of Experts Before Regular Courts of 2018, which considers interpreters as expert witnesses and does not specifically provide for the rights and responsibilities of court interpreters. According to the expert group, court interpreters can be nominated by the litigant or alternatively can be sought through the Administrative Office (al diwan) of the court, which may happen to have business cards of interpreters. The main qualifications of an interpreter are their ability to speak Arabic and another language and take a statutory oath. They said there is no system for court interpreter rosters and that any person who speaks a foreign language beside Arabic can act as a court interpreter, with the only legal requirement for him being taking the statutory oath to interpret what he hears faithfully and accurately. The Expert Group stressed the absence of a code of conduct of rigid professional qualification system for court interpreter. The implication, according to Exp3, is that an interpreter would “unfortunately interpret what they understand, without understanding that they

could ask for clarification when in doubt, making them at times render a weak interpretation.”

When asked about the eligibility criteria that they would consider when recruiting an interpreter for their own cases, EX2 said “I will never rely on a person just because he speaks Arabic and the foreign language. My criteria will include a degree in translation and knowledge of court procedures and terminology.” DP3 says that if the hearing was related to rent and lease, for example, then “I would expect the interpreter to be familiar with terms used in this field.” EX4, however, said that “the language that litigants and witnesses use is almost free of legal terms; therefore, I would accept any person who speaks Arabic and the foreign language fluently to do interpretation at the hearing.” INT1 supports this idea, saying that “the required skills for court interpreters are nothing more than correct language use and interpretation.”

When asked how they could detect interpretation errors, DP3 stated that even if he did not speak the foreign language, he would assess the quality of interpreting by comparing the emotions expressed by his non-Arabic speaking client with how the message was expressed through the interpreter and would use discretion to decide if the interpretation was not adequate. EXP9 stated that if he spoke the foreign language and detected errors, he would interrupt the proceedings and raise this issue spontaneously, possibly by asking a replacement for the interpreter. DP1 stated that in November 2021, he was representing a non-Arabic speaking client. “The court appointed an interpreter, who made lots of mistakes. I made an insisting objection to the interpretation and asked for a replacement. The judge finally agreed, and the session was adjourned pending the appointment of another interpreter.” DP1 further elaborates that when such errors happen “judges cannot interfere, correct or replace the interpreter on their own motion even if the judges spoke the foreign language.”

In summary, the procedural knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan were found to include: mode of interpreting (consecutive, whispering, sight, verbatim and summary interpreting, dictating the court reporter), memory skills (taking notes, managing short-term memory, and concentrating), language skills (listening, understanding accents, and accuracy) and management skills (sequencing, editing, dealing with accents, interrupting, asking for clarification and repetition).

4.1.3 Conceptual knowledge of SCC interpreters in Jordan

The following sub-sections reveal that there are three types of conceptual knowledge for small-claims court interpreters: domain knowledge, case-specific knowledge and legal knowledge.

4.1.3(a) Domain knowledge

Domain knowledge refers to knowledge needed to perform a task, such as when a legal expert needs to have knowledge of laws to conduct legal analysis (Wenden, 1995). All interpreters, but one, said prior knowledge of the domain of the subject dispute was not required for them. Their explanation was that even if the subject dispute related to a technical field, judges asked litigants and witnesses straightforward questions about the facts pertaining to their claims, rather than about the technicality of a given domain. The only exception was with INT1 who reported having some difficulty with one highly technical case and suggested it would have been helpful if she were given a brief about the subject in advance. INT7 described needing to review the key concepts of a case but “I was denied access to the file because of confidentiality”. Conversely, recognizing his lack of information on the subject matter dispute, INT10 requested the court give him time to read through the case to prepare himself, to which the judge agreed. INT10 said “I wouldn’t see a reason why the judge would refuse.”

The Expert Group suggested that the depth of a court interpreter's domain knowledge varies from case to case. DP6 noted, 'If the case involves only superficial utterances given by witnesses, ... prior knowledge is not needed. If a witness ... deeply elaborates the particulars of the case, prior knowledge will help the interpreter.' However, DP7 said he would recommend the interpreter to have prior domain knowledge to check for any terms that will be used. DP1 explained that some cases require technical knowledge and that the interpreter 'should have prior knowledge of the case to avoid any surprises'.

In summary, interpreters in Jordanian courts need to possess domain knowledge relevant to the field of the dispute. This often requires a thorough understanding of the specific terminology used, especially technical terms that may arise during the case.

4.1.3(b) Case-specific knowledge

Case-specific knowledge for INT5 meant knowing the names of the judge, litigants and witnesses, with all interpreters agreeing that expansive knowledge of the dispute was not needed. INT10 would even avoid accessing such details to protect his neutrality. This concern was echoed by DP4, who said, 'Some judges do not allow the interpreter to peruse the case file, otherwise [they] would dismiss the interpreter and appoint a replacement.' In contrast, DP7 noted 'I asked the judge about the case, and the judge himself gave me the details'. DP1 added, 'Especially in criminal cases where lots of legal terms are used, the interpreter should have prior knowledge of the case to get hold of and correctly interpret those terms.' There is yet a paradox indicated by DP2, who stated that his being a lawyer entails bias towards his client, so giving the interpreter prior information about the case could harm their neutrality. At the same time, without such knowledge, the interpreter may make mistakes hard to be explained to the judge, concluding that 'I would prefer to acquaint the interpreter just with

technical terms, if any.’ The remaining lawyers said they did not know if an interpreter’s prior knowledge was harmful to their cases.

In summary, case specific knowledge includes the names of the disputants and the subject dispute. Since some judges do not admit interpreters who have prior knowledge of the case, the knowledge of the case should be very limited and shallow.

4.1.3(c) Legal knowledge

All the interpreters agreed that a small-claims dispute would not normally require in-depth legal knowledge. INT3 gave examples of the questions judges ask, such as, ‘What do you do for a living?’ and ‘What is your age?’ INT6 said he had never encountered any legal terms. INT4 agreed, saying, ‘In the four cases I interpreted for, I did not need any legal knowledge’. INT4 also added that ‘the words used in the testimonies at court were general, aside from some legal terms that an interpreter could learn to use through self-preparation’. DP5 noted, ‘The interpreting of civil cases is usually easy since they rely heavily on written documentation. [Conversely], criminal cases rely heavily on witnesses’ testimonies to help the court define the crime accordingly’.

DP1 and DP2 underestimated the relevance of legal education to civil case interpreting training, opining that cases were simple, and plain language was used at court¹. INT4 said ‘the judge simplified questions to disputants, who being not legally specialised, used simple language as well’. INT10 pointed out that some cases involved legal jargon, suggesting that ‘a catastrophe would happen if the interpreter misinterpreted such terms in a companies-related case’. Nevertheless, even when INT2

¹ DPI stresses legal knowledge in criminal cases, citing real examples he witnessed. An interpreter’s erroneous rendering of ‘received’ instead of ‘took’ changed the conviction from ‘stealing to ‘breach of trust’.

faced an unfamiliar legal term, the judge clarified to him its meaning. Some interpreters drew a contrast, saying that, unlike small claims, criminal cases require the interpreter to have some legal knowledge. INT3 noted that in a criminal case, he had to exert extra care to ensure that the defendant clearly understood the charges against him.

Nine experts suggested that the language used in small claims in Jordan is simple, with only a few legal terms that may arise. However, three believed that legal language is used in small claims cases to the extent that only professionally experienced interpreters could understand it. Four experts recommended a court interpreter to have legal knowledge for small claims cases. The remaining participants disagreed, believing that small claims are straightforward, thus not requiring legal knowledge. DP1 pointed out that legal education is not as important as understanding the propositional and pragmatic meaning of utterances exchange in court.

In summary, the participants believe that legal knowledge is equivalent to knowledge of legal terms. Therefore, they conclude that small-claims cases rarely involve legal terms, leading them to believe that legal knowledge is not important for a court interpreter.

4.2 Discussion of the semi-structured interview results

Both groups highlighted the importance of getting situational knowledge of the court before appearing there as an interpreter. Some relevant thoughts included a description of the court room, which is office-like, a requirement that interpreters are not allowed to sit down, though they can take notes, and an unwritten attire code for interpreters. In connection with this type of knowledge, interpreters are required to know how to take the oath, how to address the judge properly and refrain from talking directly to any court participant without the permission of the judge. All of this goes

along the line of a code of conduct as in some other countries, with the main difference that those codes of conduct are written in countries like the United States. Such emphasis, though, is found elsewhere, where professional interpreters teaching court interpreting tend to focus considerably on contextual knowledge of the court, in addition to the interpretation skills (Stern, 2018).

Nevertheless, none of the interviewees believed that ignorance of the situational knowledge could lead to errors in interpreting. Since errors committed by interpreters in Jordan are almost impossible to appeal or even detect, it is hard to verify whether indeed lack of this type of knowledge can result in errors. However, experience elsewhere suggests lack of situational knowledge may result in errors (Russel & Takeda, 2015), may affect inexplicit messaging in the courtroom (Lee, 2009a) and should be taught in short courses (Liu & Hale, 2018).

4.2.1(a) Domain knowledge

The professional groups described their cases as generally simple, as were the judge's questions and the litigants' and witnesses' answers. Consequently, some asserted that the basic knowledge they needed was limited to proficiency in Arabic and foreign languages. Others in the expert group agreed, noting that civil cases, in particular small claims cases, depend heavily on written evidence and that communication between interlocutors is simple. They also pointed out that when a judge hears a case involving litigants or witnesses who are unfamiliar with Arabic, they simplify the language of the proceedings to make the interpreter's task easier. If this assumption is correct, it may partially explain the absence of rigid requirements for court interpreters in the Bylaws of Experts Before Regular Courts. These findings align

with the principle of plain language use, whereby a language user opts for the ‘simplest, most straightforward way of expressing an idea’ (Garner 2001) and where Japanese courts use plain Japanese featuring simple sentence structures at hearings (Yamamoto 2019).

Knowledge of the subject dispute area was highlighted by all interpreters except INT10, who believed prior knowledge of the case could harm his neutrality, an idea that was echoed by one lawyer (EXP4). This suggestion is in line with some international practice: courts sometimes make it compulsory to recruit an interpreter without prior knowledge of the subject dispute to prevent ‘contamination’ (Stone 2018). This aligns with Australian practice, where some interpreters have reported being reprimanded by judges for requesting access to case materials for preparation (Wong, 2019). However, the other interpreters and lawyers did not agree: they believed that previous knowledge of the case would allow interpreters to familiarise themselves with the terms to be used in the courtroom. This finding is in line with previous research that has stressed an interpreter’s need for previous knowledge and experience with the subject dispute domain and terminology (González, Vásquez, and Mikkelson 1991). An interpreter’s lack of contextual knowledge in court may also entail an increased risk of misinterpretation (Lee 2007, 109). Hale (2010, 441) suggested that inadequate court interpreting does not solely involve the interpreter’s competence but also their court specialist training and prior preparation. It may also be unrealistic to expect an interpreter to work in court without knowledge of the topic or terminology, notwithstanding judges’ concerns over interpreters’ impartiality (Kenny 2019, 65). González, Vásquez, and Mikkelson (1991, 877) held that knowledge of burglaries is required to interpret real-life cases and that the more experience interpreters have in various subjects, the more readily they can recall information. The authors also found

that previous domain knowledge of the dispute can be invaluable for court interpreters, who may encounter technical terms (891). Similarly, interpreters associations contend that interpreters must have a thorough knowledge of a wide range of subjects (Morgan 2004, 26), which supports Hrehovčik's (2009, 162) proposal that a court interpreter must be competent with the subject area and have research skills to obtain the specific knowledge necessary to interpret in specialised cases. Further, in the absence of 'rehearsing the scenario', a court interpreter may be forced to improvise (Nartowska 2014).

The implications of this finding are twofold. Firstly, professional court interpreters tend to uphold a dilemma fallacy. A false dilemma fallacy is based on an assumption that erroneously restricts a range of possibilities to two options (Van Vleet 2011, 8), in this case, by describing the situation in terms of a simple-complex dichotomy. However, our analysis shows that the complexity of court interpreting is a spectrum spanning between the extremes of simple and difficult, with varying degrees that lie along this continuum. Simplicity and difficulty pertain to how specialised the domain is at a court hearing. Our finding aligns with the degree of restriction in the register theory, in which a continuum extends between maximally restricted registers and open-ended registers (Hatim and Mason 54). This means the degree of complexity of small claims at Jordanian courts can vary depending on the domain knowledge involved, implying varying levels of professionalism among interpreters. In light of the findings, this study supports previous research that calls for allowing interpreters to peruse cases to prepare themselves for hearings.

4.2.1(b) Legal knowledge

The results highlighted conflicting views about the depth of legal knowledge required for court interpreting. The interpreters overwhelmingly stated that the cases

they interpreted did not require legal knowledge since they had only to interpret straightforward questions and answers. Similarly, DP4 said that the court usually tries to make things easy to understand and to help individuals feel relaxed when they make their statements or testimonies and they use plain Arabic. Half of the experts (53.3%) said the language used in court is simple with some legal terms included, while 26.7% claimed simplified language almost void of legal terms is used. Expert DP4 suggested that the litigants and witnesses would not be specialised in the law; thus, they would not use legal language.

However, the study noted a sharp contrast to this view. According to INT3, INT6 and DP1, an interpreter in criminal cases must possess more than a basic understanding of the law as they need to interpret the charges so that the defendant can understand the allegations, as well as noticing and correcting their mistakes (INT10). According to Osiejewicz, Podgórna, and Góra-Poland (2015, 154), an interpreter's professional knowledge is not restricted to linguistic abilities but extends to proficiency in legal English and knowledge of legal systems: 'A legal interpreter and translator cannot understand the information implicit in specialized texts without legal training' (156).

Some interpreters and lawyers claimed that legal training is not required for court interpreters, holding that the language used in court—whether Arabic or the foreign language—is plain. Thus, according to them, the language used is not purely legal, which means that the interpreter does not necessarily need an in-depth understanding of the law. The view in this research is that this is a fallacy based on a misinterpretation of what a legal oral message is. For illustration, the legal aspects of statements made by a plaintiff in an American courtroom (Case Closed TV Warren, 2010, Episode 1) is worth considering, assuming that such a case could also be litigated

in Jordanian courts. The dispute is about unpaid dental bills: the dentist claimed her clinic provided root-canal treatment to a patient (the defendant), who failed to pay the fees. During the hearing, the dentist said, 'We're not going to let you leave our office with an abscess on your tooth'. She also told the judge, 'We did our part; she did not comply with her part'. In both cases, the statements are in plain English, and neither involves any specific legal terms. The use of 'going to + base verb form' indicates an intention rather than a promise, which is otherwise expressed by using 'will + base verb form' (Azar 2002, 52). Thus, what the dentist said should not be construed as a promise that could otherwise be interpreted as a binding unilateral commitment. In the second statement, the dentist asserted that her clinic performed their obligation (i.e. treating the tooth) but that the patient failed to fulfil her obligation by paying. According to the dentist, an oral contract had been entered into, which raised a contract-based dispute based on the patient's default.

The rejection of the argument that the plain language used in court hearings reduces the necessity for an interpreter to possess legal knowledge is supported by previous research. Cao (2014, 108) suggested that even simple words exchanged in court can be filled with hidden complexities that can lead to serious consequences if not handled carefully by interpreters. Additionally, though the language of witness testimonies may be similar to language used outside of the courtroom, it still carries a legal significance and serves a legal purpose under certain circumstances in court (Cao 2010, 81). Grammatical errors made by interpreters 'can have disadvantageous consequences for the witnesses' (Hale 2004, 130), while subtle changes to utterances exchanged could negatively affect the evidence and assessment of a witness's credibility. However, the depth of legal knowledge that court interpreters are required to possess is understudied within the Jordanian context, and no research has investigated

how such knowledge affects the accuracy and efficiency of court interpretation. Nevertheless, the Jordanian Civil Code of 1976 states five sources of personal rights that may be subject to dispute: the law, unilateral voluntary act, undue enrichment, tort and contract. These topics are worthy of further research that investigates the potential impact of understanding them on court interpreters' professionalisation.

4.2.1(c) Procedural knowledge

The skills that both the interpreters and lawyers cited are mainly indisputable and understandable. Prior research has highlighted language proficiency, concentration, attention, memory, listening comprehension and note-taking as important skills for court interpreting (Stromberg and Head 1984; González, Vásquez, and Mikkelson 1991; Mikkelson 1998). However, our results highlight some aspects that might be peculiar to the Jordanian courts, including notetaking, interrupting a speaker, asking for clarification, dictating the court reporter and offering a summary interpretation.

The interpreters explained that their minimal use of notetaking was due to the short chunks of utterances they were expected to interpret. Some interpreters wrote keywords, numbers and symbols to assist their short-term memory, although none wrote everything they heard. This finding is in alignment with Jones (1985, 36), who suggested that neither note-taking nor memory skills are of high importance since community interpreters are not usually expected to interpret lengthy segments of speech. However, one interpreter (INT10) recounted that they managed long talks by interrupting the speaker. O'Barr and Conley (1990) supported the short chunking in litigants' statements, reporting that litigants knew that it was rare that they could narrate a story without being interrupted by the judge. González, Vásquez, and Mikkelson (1991) deduced that the high-accuracy standard restricts a court interpreter's ability to memorise and produce everything that is said, even with the help of note-taking,

suggesting that an interpreter could be justified in occasionally interrupting a speaker or asking for repetitions. However, the authors warned that the overuse of such techniques could indicate that the interpreter needs to improve their sub-skills since a competent interpreter should not be obstructive. If justified, asking for clarification is important for court interpreters to maintain the illocutionary act and to ‘pick up the ambiguity [...] unless the ambiguity can be kept by interpreting semantically’ (Hale 1996). Court institutions may discourage an interpreter from interrupting the flow of speech or asking for clarifications (Lee 2007), although our results show that in Jordan, judges are generally cooperative with interpreters in this respect and allow them to ask for clarifications whenever needed. Note-taking, interruptions and asking for clarifications are, therefore, skills that court interpreters are encouraged to learn through formal training and use at Jordanian court hearings.

Verbatim interpreting was the default preference of both the interpreters and lawyers to the extent that repetitions and the sequential order of ideas were maintained by some interpreters. This agrees with Susanti (2024) and is in line with the conduit language model, which is:

“A common law construction that allows a court to attribute a translated statement to the non-English speaker, rather than the interpreter, when the interpreter acted only as a “language conduit.” (Kracum 2014)

The United States Supreme Court ruled that interpreters are ‘no more than language conduits’ and unless there is evidence that the interpreter intended to misrepresent the facts or that their interpreting was erroneous, an appeal could not be granted under the Confrontation Clause (‘U.S. v. Koskerides,’ 1989). However, language conduit theory has drawn some criticism. According to Benoit (2014), the rationale of the language conduit principle arises from a misunderstanding of the job of

an interpreter, who should not be viewed as making word-for-word renderings of messages but as being more involved in the communicative and pragmatic dynamics of language. Nartowska (2015) foregrounded other issues countering the language conduit theory, such as the degree to which an interpreter can change a lawyer's power and purposes while interpreting their pleas at court and how an interpreter's rendering of the accused can negatively affect a lawyer's assessment of the situation. Our interviewees indicated that some judges in Jordan have allowed interpreters to give summaries of statements rather than make verbatim renderings. This implies the use of a hybrid mode of interpreting that oscillates on the verbatim-summary interpretation pendulum, which should form part of court interpreters' skill set in Jordan.

Finally, one interpreter was asked by the judge to undertake a sight translation of the defendant's statement into her language to verify that what was written in the court report was compatible with what she said. This implies that the judge presumed a court interpreter has the appropriate skills to do so. Sight translation requires the interpreter to skim over a text silently then translate it aloud, a skill that features in certification exams in some jurisdictions (Berk-Seligson 2017). Sight translation may be more difficult in courts than in other settings since it requires the interpreter to have prior knowledge to allow information retrieval (Yaling 2017). Interestingly, none of the remaining interpreters mentioned that they had been asked to conduct sight translation at a court hearing, which raises questions about consistency among judges and the potential outcomes of cases in which a defendant is ignorant of how their statement has been written in the court report. Nevertheless, the findings point to the viability of including sight translation as a sub-skill in court interpreting professionalisation training.

4.3 Results of case study

4.3.1 Overview

To answer this question, the study relied on the findings of the content knowledge elicited from the semi-structured interviews and on neuroscience findings relevant to brain-compatible education learning for the presentation of the learning material. Lesson plans have been drafted and a trainer and students have been recruited. The trainer delivered the training to a group of 8 students in the Pilot phase and up to 10 students in the case study. Those students were either fresh graduates (two years maximum before the intervention) or fourth-year students. None of the students has had any experience in court interpreting, and the trainer assumed the role of a facilitator and instructor. The trainer presented the material to the students in eight lectures and the researchers made observations and changes to the material based on the input of the students. The following findings have arisen from the pilot study and case study respectively.

The training course was held from 9 to 26 February 2023 and included both theoretical and practical exercises (in the form of videos) for interpreting in small disputes courts. Appendix (E) shows the slides that were covered in those lessons. The researcher attended the eight training sessions, and after two weeks he began transcribing the videos verbatim as they were presented. The transcription process ended on April 15, 2023. After leaving the blog until April 30, 2023, the researcher carefully reviewed both the blog and the videos to clarify any ambiguities, then reread the blog, taking notes on important points. The general patterns that were appropriate for analysis and displayed.

This section summarizes the most important findings in this iteration. Generally, the trainees had a positive impression of the methodology and training materials at the

end of the training course, attributing success not only to the training material but more specifically to the trainer's efficient use of hooks, kindling, and bridges. Nevertheless, during the actual translation of visual audio materials, some challenges have emerged, both at the level of attention and at the level of linking theory to practice.

4.3.2 General impressions of trainees

According to neuroscientific research, prior knowledge of a topic can improve trainee comprehension (Bransford and Johnson, 1972), however, prior knowledge can form a schemata in the minds of previous learners and could negatively affect the schemata of new comers to the training, which could even result in perceptual contamination.

The training saw changes in the learning behaviour of students. In the beginning, trainees thought they had to refer to the trainer by her title of Dr. Nihad or Ms. Nihad, but as the lessons progressed to the end, they began to refer to her by her name alone. The paradigm shift surfaced in the gradual yet steady improvement in the social interpersonal interactions through “exchanging and discussing ideas among ourselves.” (ST3). The rule, according to ST5 became that the trainee had “the freedom to speak without fear of making mistakes” in the “one family” atmosphere, which ultimately resulted in “learning a lot of knowledge and obtaining a lot of benefit mixed with pleasure through the method of self-exploration rather than preaching.” More importantly, the trainees felt that they learned the training material easily in a simplified manner that made the new information “more ingrained in their memories”. At the end of the training course, the trainees expressed their positive impressions of the experience, which “made them feel like they were in one family,” (ST6) especially since there was no need to be afraid “of making mistakes.” Rather, the course added “fun with benefit,” bringing the trainees to levels “higher than they expected to reach.” (ST6)

Then, the theoretical information provided by the course was also “of practical benefit in my life to know own duties and rights in society.”

There was a change in the sequencing of learning in this iteration, compared with the previous one. After the first lesson, the participants asked they needed to know more about what happens inside the courtroom, and they wanted to start interpreting drills even before coming to talk about procedural knowledge. As that was a consensus, notwithstanding the perils of students making mistakes in the drills, the trainer complied and started in meeting 2 with situational knowledge and a drill. Therefore, by the end of lesson 1, the students had already developed a sense of inter-dependently and autonomy in learning. That spirit continued with them until the end.

4.3.3 Attention

Attention can be improved when the right amount of dopamine is released in the brain. Studies in neuroscience report that in an educational setting, dopamine can be released if the learning content is relevant and engaging (Shepherd, 2019), when students are curious to learn, and when they feel rewarded. Variability and novelty of stimuli, effective classroom settings and the use of visuals can also improve attention. The training strategies used the hook-kindle-bridge technique, where a trainer ‘hooks’ the attention of the students, enriches (kindles) the discussion about the topic then connects (bridges) it to the correct answer of the question.

As reported by the trainees, their attention was high throughout the training course, and they did not feel distracted at any time. There were limited instances where a student failed to respond to the trainer's prompt or engage in discussion due to distracted or divided attention. This is consistent with the experience reported by a trainee in the Pilot Study, who expressed the feeling of being in an attentive mode all

the time without interruption or distraction. The analysis of the transcripts of the lessons reveals the reasons why attention was preserved throughout the training.

Firstly, the trainer diversified the learning devices used in the training, to keep the students continuously engaged. She established a network of connections between information that she has created and reinforced with students. The network is triggered by hooks, enriched by kindles, and reinforced by bridges. In theory, each hook would represent and invoke a distinct style of learning, as Silver et al. (2007) suggested. The trainer, though, applied a naturalistic approach, that is to apply a learning-style hook that would suit the situation. This is because the learning styles of students cannot be predicted upfront and may change from one group of students to another. The trainer would use a hook that invoked different learning styles and a bridge that served as a new hook, leading to priming the specific learning outcome.

The first hook in the first lesson was a self-expressive one about the qualities of elite court interpreters. It was supposed to lead students to list the qualities individually, but as students started to engage among themselves, the trainer kindled their discussions, and bridged by acknowledging their answers. The trainer provided the bridge, though, to serve as an interpersonal hook as she reinforced the reciprocal style of learning the students were voluntarily engaged. In a similar manner to what happened in Case Study 1, the students in this iteration showed higher attention to the minute details of visual comics, pictures and videos that were based on the ‘This is/ This is not’ device (compare and contrast strategy), which is in the understanding style. A similar level of attention was observed when students were asked to engage with slides that follow the ‘reading for meaning’ device, also in the understanding style but which nonetheless triggered an interpersonal learning style discussion. All students said in

their feedback that the ‘this is/ this is not’ device was the top strategy that kept them attentive to the training.

In some cases, a given hook did not work, causing the trainer to postpone the discussion on the topic. In one example, a student asked about the characteristics of Jordanian courts. First, that question served as a mastery hook, to which students were unable to respond due to their lack of knowledge. Trainer rephrased the question as “What do you envision the characteristics of the court to be? ” but the answers were speculative and unidirectional (from ‘a student who knows not’ to a teacher ‘who knows’) and silence prevailed. She acknowledged any answers she received, but explained that this would be discussed in greater detail later on. Yet, the trainer created another self-expressing hook by reminding them that this course is about SCC. As such, she asked, "Can you explain the meaning of 'small claim' to me?". As soon as this hook was replaced, the students engaged in the discussion in an interpersonal manner (instead of a student-teacher one). Using the correct answers as a bridge, the trainer then transitioned to the next slide. The bridge she provided for them was at the same time a self-expressive hook, namely the pattern maker, which triggered a learning discussion among students, resulting in the majority of items on the slide being classified correctly.

The classroom settings appeared to be effective, as students comfortably engaged with the trainer and among themselves. The internet connection was high and stable, and no technical problem occurred, which could have otherwise distracted their attention. They interacted with all slides and videos, which according to them were clear in terms of presentation and content. Their feedback during and after the training was appreciative of the audio-visual devices. “I felt comfortable with them, and some of them even compelled me to laugh”, said one of the trainees, in an indication that she paid attention during the course. Visuals are known in neuroscience to be useful for

enhancing encoding in the brain, as they activate the primary visual cortex, responsible for processing visuals, before they are further processed by the hippocampus, which is also responsible for processing declarative memory.

The positive impact of the strategic hooks on attention is intertwined with the other elements of the AGES model, as explained below.

4.3.4 Generation

Memories are stored in associations of webs of information in the brain, which indicates that effective learning is one that triggers and deepens more associations of this kind. This is known in neuroscience as ‘what fires together wires together’. So, the more associations a student makes, the more likely he will memorise what he learns and generates knowledge on his own.

Students in this iteration of the training were able to generate knowledge on their own and link it, where appropriate, to their prior knowledge. In theory, this means they have successfully generated associations in their brains during the training course, which helps in consolidating their knowledge. Although none of the students had previous knowledge about courts or court interpreting, they managed to speculate correct aspects of the qualities of interpreters, courts and judges. In this way, when the trainer bridged the exercise, what she was doing was reinforcing information already known to the students, rather than teaching them something new. There were instances where students could not know the correct answer, or that the answer was not complete. In such situations, the trainer applied strategies to reduce any unfavourable disappointment feelings in the students. For example, in lesson, the students were asked to speculate the characteristics of courts. Few comments came from the students, and the trainer decided to tell them “these are correct answers; this topic will be presented

later on in more details.” The effect of this strategy on the part of the trainer is discussed in the next section about emotions.

The pattern maker exercise (self-expressive style) successfully allowed the students to speculate accurately the meanings of conceptual knowledge, situational knowledge and procedural knowledge. What is interesting is that the self-expressive hook resulted in the students talking together and forming their own collective hypotheses about the meaning of the three types of knowledge. Once again, when the trainer discussed the correct answers with them (the bridge), she was actually consolidating memories of the topic they already had, rather than giving them something new to them. By the same token, all other hooks generated knowledge, particularly through the visuals and videos. During and after the training, all trainees emphasized that the exercises made them discover the correct answers on their own without the trainer explaining them beforehand, which according to the students, consolidated their knowledge. Students also stressed that the top strategy that helped them generate and consolidate knowledge (hence generate and thickening associations in the brain) was the ‘compare and contrast’ hook of “this is / this is not”.

There are two exceptions, however, that qualify scrutiny. The mastery hooks in three instances resulted in silence and failure by students to respond. In the first instance, the students were presented with a slide showing the types of knowledge and students were asked to answer what declarative knowledge could mean. In the second instance, students did not answer the question of the difference between المدعي (plaintiff) and المدعى عليه (defendant), since they did not differentiate between the two similar words in Arabic. The third instance of silence was when students were asked what they thought would happen if a case was filed in the wrong court of jurisdiction.

The fourth instance was when students were asked to read and reflect on what they understood from the slide on the source of obligations.

The second exception was a student who said she preferred to be more a listener than a speaker. She said since she had the choice, she would prefer to sit and ‘concentrate’ on the lesson in order not to be distracted.

4.3.5 Emotions

As in the pilot case study, this iteration worked on creating a sense of reward in the students, increasing their self-confidence and reducing negative feelings such as frustration and boredom.

4.3.5(a) Reward and self-confidence

Students of this iteration expressed their feelings of being rewarded throughout the course as they learnt new strategies, knowledge and skills, which they said they could have never imagined obtaining. The type of rewards created for the students in this iteration was overwhelmingly intrinsic, with extrinsic rewards confined to positive feedback and praise the trainer gave to the group. An intrinsic reward comes naturally in the learning experience, and this is what the trainer and the training material highlighted in the training. In contrast, the trainer’s positive feedback or praise were limited and given to the students as a group in appreciation of the good discussions that they had. Under no circumstances was the extrinsic reward given to students based on them giving ‘a correct answer’. Even when students were silent or when they gave wrong or missing answers, they were still rewarded as long as they were actively engaged with the material.

The trainer played a role in instilling in the students’ self-confidence by giving them as a group an extrinsic reward, which she managed at the end to make it felt by the students as an intrinsic reward. This was evident by the students’ comments as many

of them stated they felt rewarded by learning new things in the lessons. The trainer used priming also, as when the bridges were compatible with the hypotheses the students tested, the trainer would say “As you see, you have discovered the answer even without you being told upfront of it.”

4.3.5(b) Frustration and boredom

A salient comment given by one of the students, seconded by all hr colleagues, was “Even when I found a video challenging for interpreting, I still felt self-confident and never felt frustrated.” (ST12)

Both the training material and the trainer’s abidance by the brain-based learning strategies were helpful in maintaining preventing frustration and boredom in the training. Observation shows that students were actively engaged in the discussion and exercises. Their feedback was also positive as they indicated that they neither got frustrated nor bored during the course. In particular, the students said any feeling of frustration would have been offset by their feeling of pride that their ideas were respected, they owned the training and that their suggestions were taken seriously in amending the training. Their names were even included in the acknowledgement of the final product of the training, which served as an extrinsic reward that according to the students motivated them further to focus on their learning.

The students engaged well by answering the prompts and talking to one another to discover the learning steps. The trainer successfully communicated to the students that any answer they give to a question should be treated as ‘a hypothesis to be tested’ rather than a correct or incorrect answer. That was evident when the students started doing the practical exercises, where they felt some challenges in interpreting some of them. However, the observation and the students’ feedback revealed that the students felt relieved as they were still doing things in the correct way, applying what they learnt

in the theoretical part of the training. For example, after a student made a mistake in the interpretation, the trainer quickly reminder her that she had the right to ask for repetition or clarification. That tip was also taken by other students when performing their tasks, hence learning from the mistakes of others, instead of doing mistakes and learning from them. Still as levels of difficulty increased, the trainer decided to reduce the levels of difficulty so they could cope with the task and deliver better results. Some of the students questioned whether that could be feasible in the real market, and the trainer reminded them that “this is just a training today, and we are in lesson 4 yet” thereby sending comfortable messages to the students and lowering their ambitious unrealistic goals.

The trainer also demonstrated an important role in preventing frustration. When the students gave incorrect answers, or when they did not adequately respond to the hooks, the trainer would repeat this comment: “This is just for brainstorming now, and we will cover it in detail later on.” Similarly, when the students did not give adequate answer to the hook of “Put on the hat of the court interpreter and describe your relationship with the judge”, the trainer reinforced the value of talking by saying “Fine that you talked. We will see the answers later”. By doing so, the trainer managed to reframe negative experience and change the negative aspect of not knowing an answer into the positive emotion of curiosity, with students given the chance at a later stage to further dive into the answers.

The students also highlighted the use of technology in the training as a reason for them not to feel bored. In fact, the observation revealed that they always responded to prompts made in relation to audio-visual and visual prompts. In addition, the humorous videos and the song (played to them at the very beginning of the course) were

relaxing. A student said “I could not keep laughing. They were funny!”. Another student said “I never felt bored and could hardly wait for the next training lesson in the week”.

4.3.6 Spacing

The lessons in the iteration were delivered twice a week with three-four days of intervals between the two lessons. This arrangement was made first based on the availability of the trainer, but also in consultation with the students, who agreed. The spaced interval was discussed with the students during the course, but they said it was convenient for them.

It was not possible to determine the effect of spacing on the students’ reception and learning in the training course. The students did not give much feedback about it other than it was convenient, but it was obvious that all of the students spent the time between the lessons on their daily life activities and on rewatching, given the fact that the majority of them were in the vacation between the two semesters at the university. More precisely, they did not practice interpreting, revise their lessons or practice note-taking. Nevertheless, students showed that they did remember some basic ideas that they have learnt in the lessons. For example, a student, when asked about ‘small claims’, responded “We learnt that the value of claims in small claims is from 1 to 3000 but not higher.”

The spacing effect, in terms of the intervals between lessons, cannot as well be determined in the interpretation videos. However, it may be determined if spacing is defined as the space in ‘seconds’ or ‘minutes’ between two cognitive loads. This has considerable implications to the abilities of the students to learn interpreting by doing. There are examples from the exercises. The following is the first one in the training:

The first utterance to be interpreted in the first exercise given to students (Exercise TLO1.1) was made by a man saying “Your honour! On January the first,

twenty twenty-one, Mr. Samir, the defendant rented my house.” The time that lapsed in this utterance was 7 seconds, which should theoretically be convenient to the attention of the listener, since the minimum attention span is defined as 12 second. The display of the video was preceded by a slide displaying the English words and their Arabic equivalents. The trainer gave the students the time they needed to read them carefully and note them down if needed to use them in interpreting. However, the volunteering student asked for a repetition saying “Can you please rewind?” This raised two issues. First, the theoretical part already taught the students that when an interpreter at court cannot understand and needs the participant to repeat what he says, the way to say it is “The interpreter requests the [participant] to repeat what he said.” Second, the time span was only 7 seconds, yet the trainer accepted to repeat and cut shorter the chunks to Your honour / on January the fourth / twenty twenty-one/ Mr. Samir the defendant/ rented a house from me. Through trial and error and group reflection, the students managed to memorise and use the skill of asking for repetition throughout the course, but as for the chunking in this example, the volunteering student still made mistakes in translating ‘on January the fifth’ and the “Mr. Samir the defendant”. The reason as explained by the student and as shared by the rest of students was that they did not know the Arabic names of the months. That was despite the fact that the name of the month was already mentioned in the previous slide.

From a spacing perspective, this can be explained by assuming that the time interval between displaying the slide with the vocabulary and the actual exercise was not enough. It also means, for a cognitive perspective, that the cognitive load between the utterances was too high to be managed, despite the shortened span. Results could have probably been better if the students got ample time ahead of the lessons to memorise the words, and of the chunks had less cognitive loads, such as: Your honour,

Mr. Judge! / On the first day of the month of January / that was in the year twenty twenty-one / The defendant came to me / I mean Mr. Samir / He rented from me one a house. This redistribution of the cognitive load could help the students do better in the exercise.

4.4 Summary of findings

The first two research questions of study were about the conceptual and procedural knowledge of interpreters in small-claims courts in Jordan, which was studied through qualitative semi-structured interviews. The content of a relevant curriculum requires an understanding of the knowledge and skills officially required by courts in Jordan. However, in the absence of a law or a code of conduct for court interpreters, the decision to appoint court interpreters is left to the discretion of the judge on a case-to-case basis. It can be concluded, on the basis of the results, that in bilingual cases, any person with language proficiency can be invited to act as an expert interpreter under the Bylaws of Experts Before Regular Courts. Language proficiency is the main official criterion for the selection, but as the study has shown so far, interpreters at courts in Jordan need to have more knowledge and skills than the mere proficiency in languages. On the conceptual knowledge level, domain knowledge, case-specific knowledge and basic legal knowledge have been highlighted. On the procedural knowledge level, aside from language skills, small-claims cases in Jordan required interpreters to have good memory skills and management skills.

An area of interest is the perceptions of the professional and expert groups, except one from each, that the language used in those cases is simple and it rarely requires legal knowledge. Those are two perceived ideas that were proved wrong under the falsifiability principle, as one lawyer-interpreter contended that an understanding of

contextual meaning could affect the outcome of the case. On the simplicity issue, one interpreter falsified that perception, as she encountered at least one case in court where the small-claims case involved technical terms in the field of industry, hence requiring an interpreter to have some technical domain knowledge. The resulting understanding of conceptual knowledge and procedural knowledge was therefore used to draft the small-claims court interpreting training course for the second phase of the study, the intervention.

The third questions pertained to the effectiveness of a training course given to students of small-claims court interpreting, from a neuroscience perspective.

The constructivist and brain-based education theories place students at the core of the learning process, emphasizing their active engagement, ownership, and alignment with their individual learning styles, contingent upon their genuine motivation to acquire knowledge. This endeavour necessitates two fundamental prerequisites. Firstly, the curriculum must be meticulously designed to ensure students' comprehension of educational content and its practical application. Secondly, the teacher must transition from a didactic role to that of facilitators, aligning their instructional approach with the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) principle, providing information only as students require it.

To attain this objective, this study envisaged an instructional design for small-claims court interpretation utilizing the Strategic Teacher's Model. This curriculum incorporated diverse hooks tailored to accommodate mastery, understanding, self-expressive, and interpersonal learning styles, as advocated by Harvey Silver et al (2007). These hooks were strategically implemented to foster cooperative learning, stimulate students' sense of ownership over the learning material, and prevent feelings of frustration or boredom. Subsequently, this curriculum has been administered through

a qualified trainer to two distinct groups of students to evaluate its effectiveness. Upon course completion, data were collected and analysed through the lens of educational neuroscience, which underscores the importance of crafting educational content that aligns with brain function to enhance memory retention, neuron activation, and the release of neurotransmitters like dopamine, thereby facilitating lasting learning.

In the analysis, the AGES Model was used, predicated on the premise that effective learning captures students' attention (Attention), catalysing the formation of neural networks in their brains (Generation). This process adheres to the principle "what fires together wires together," optimizing memory and eliciting a sense of reward while mitigating negative emotions such as pain, boredom, or frustration (Emotions). In a neuroscience-informed learning environment, the concept of spaced learning is vital for knowledge consolidation (Spacing).

The analysis of results revealed that the training material, including verbal, reading, audio, and audio-visual hooks, successfully empowered students to explore and generate knowledge independently from the trainer's intervention. Moreover, it fostered self-confidence, instilled a sense of reward, and encouraged collaborative learning without evoking boredom or frustration. Participants expressed profound appreciation for the facilitator, who kindled discussions and deferred answers until students had the opportunity to discover them themselves.

Notably, students unanimously reported heightened attentiveness when the hook adopted a 'compare and contrast' approach, within the understanding learning style. Audio-visual elements were also deemed instrumental in stimulating their imagination and solidifying information retention. 'Reading for meaning' encouraged group discussions, elicited reciprocal learning and instilled a sense of reward, as they transformed answers into hypotheses to be tested rather than mere corrections.

Furthermore, students felt rewarded when consulted about the training material, which was modified 75 times based on their feedback.

It was observed that all hook styles, including mastery, self-expressive, and understanding, consistently prompted discussions among students (reciprocal learning), with the understanding style prevailing, followed closely by the interpersonal style. This trend, however, did not apply to two students, each of whom expressed a preference for individual contemplation and imagination over social interaction, aligning their learning preferences more with the hook and self-expressive styles.

Regarding practical exercises, all students said they struggled with combined notetaking and listening or combined reading notes and interpreting tasks. They also found it challenging to interpret videos exceeding 6 seconds in duration. Nevertheless, students welcomed the concept of graduated difficulty and did not perceive their inability to interpret as a source of frustration. Instead, they appreciated the opportunity to acquire new phrases and terms and enjoyed watching videos and comics. As one student aptly stated, "The training course was a combination of benefit and fun." While the effect of spacing in lessons on learning outcomes was not explicitly discernible, spacing within each exercise indicated improved performance (4-7 seconds) when cognitive load, such as numbers, proper nouns, or technical/legal terms, was minimized.

Overall, a striking alignment in responses across most trainees in both groups suggests the potential applicability of this approach to additional student cohorts, with a key emphasis on co-constructing learning objectives in collaboration with students.

4.5 Discussion of case study findings

The case study aimed at answering:

RQ4. What impact can a brain-based training instruction have on the learning of SCCI knowledge among students?

In neuroscience terms, the training allowed students to generate knowledge, in a spaced environment that motivated them and boosted their attention.

4.5.1 Overview of the findings

Consider the following figure (Figure 4.4):

Figure 4.1 Students constructing knowledge

This is Slide 139 of the PowerPoint presentation, featuring an accountant (right) and an employer (left), the latter ordering the accountant to clean tables as a new task of his job. The figure has few words about what happened between the two persons and a question “What does the law say?” This has been a reading for meaning exercise where students would read and figure out the answer. The students initiated a discussion among them, and they successfully but collectively figured out that this is an example of unilateral will. Interestingly, the students used the information they learnt in previous lectures. They explicitly said “this is not a contract, because there is no agreement” and questioned if an employer “can of his own will create an obligation.” The students had already learnt about the contract elements but not the unilateral will, and they figured out that it is ‘unilateral will’ even before reaching the bridge. In neuroscience terms

(Rushton and Juola-Rushton (2008); Bear, Connors and Paradiso (2007) and Preston and Eichenbaum (2013), the construction of knowledge can be explained.

The image goes to the eye then to the occipital lobe, known to be associated with vision and images (Kandel, Schwartz, & Jessell, 2013). The message is decoded then relayed through the thalamus to other parts of the brain. Since the image presents emotions (happy-greedy employer and sad-aggrieved employee), then the message is processed by the amygdala (responsible for emotions), then coordinated with the hippocampus (Katsumi & Dolcos, 2020). Simultaneously, the written words are received by the occipital lobe to be decoded, then go the amygdala and hippocampus. If the input is salient enough, then the hippocampus with the prefrontal cortex assimilates new memory into the existing knowledge network through a selective perceptual filtering mechanism (Squire & Kandel, 2009). Theoretically, this is how the students quickly managed to make the connection between new knowledge and the previous information already known to them. This result may also relate to the fact that the pictures were static. According to Schüller, Scheiter and van Genuchten (2011), static pictures with text can prove useful for the learning of individuals with high visuo-spatial sketchpad capacity. In this sense, the results are consistent with the propositions of the AGES model, which stresses the necessity to include visuals in the training for better memory formation and recall.

The above is an example to contend that the current model of training was a brain-based model. The flow of information, the content, the visuals, videos and organisation were made in a way that adhered to findings in neuroscience about how the brain works. Students were given freedom to learn and exercise in an environment that is free of ‘punishment’ where all students are appraised of their worth as contributors to the construction of knowledge. The material was delivered to them in

accordance with their own learning style and pace. It even allowed them to express their opinion on the sequencing of learning and presentation of the information in the material. The trainer adopted the role of a facilitator, whereby she raised a hook to students, kindled their discussions and then bridged whatever answer they gave with the new information they were expected to learn. The trainer managed to control the flow of the training without students getting offtrack, and the students committed to following up with the material but not at the expense of their imagination and creativity or queries that they may had about given learning points. This freedom has resulted in students feeling comfortable with learning, engaged in learning and able to retain learning in their memories. This result is consistent with the rationale of the Strategic Teachers' Model, as Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) and brain-based educators, such as Hart (1983), Cercone (2006); Hileman (2006); Kaufman, Akers and Wittler (2008); Noureen, Awan and Fatima (2017); Tang (2017); Tompkins (2007). The findings may also answer the question of whether neuroscience can be directly applied to the classroom (Tommerdahl, 2010) as the study suggests the applicability of neuroscience in the classroom through an intermediary model, such as the Strategic Teachers' Model. There are two exceptions, nevertheless.

The results, as previously elucidated, indicated that students in the second group responded to the mastery hook presented in the "Types of Knowledge" slide with silence. This pattern was also observed in relation to three other slides. Upon revisiting the notes from the first group iteration, specifically focusing on the concerning slide, it was apparent that the students did not possess a comprehensive understanding of the content. However, rather than remaining silent, they expressed their uncertainty by stating that they "could not know." An additional noteworthy observation was the presence of two exceptions, one from each group, who exhibited a preference for limited

verbal participation in group discussions. Both students articulated that they believed they could concentrate better by listening to their peers and giving their full attention to the lesson. Notably, the student in the first group even articulated a preference for receiving clear instructions from teachers in order to enhance their learning experience.

This finding aligns with the principles of the Strategic Teachers' Model, which recognizes that every teaching strategy possesses its own set of strengths and limitations. Thus, the concept of employing multiple teaching strategies concurrently is warranted as it increases students' motivation and positive understanding of learning outcomes (Moore & Craciun, 2024). Furthermore, it underscores the importance of valuing individual privacy in the learning process, not only in shared tasks among students but also when individual contemplation is essential and thinking is personal (Lowe, 2023). Those two learners can be characterized as 'assimilating learners' who favour structured learning environments, including activities such as listening to lectures, reading, and conceptualizing complex ideas (Kolb, 1984). However, considering the presence of assimilators among interpersonal learners, this aspect of learning can be described and explained within the realm of psychology. This aligns with Bowers' assertion that for neuroscience to be considered valid, it must extend its scope beyond the domains of psychology and philosophy. In response to this criticism, this study clearly demonstrates that students do not adhere strictly to a single dominant learning style; rather, they exhibit the capacity to respond to various learning styles. From a neuroscientific perspective, this adaptability can be elucidated in terms of neuroplasticity, wherein an individual's brain reorganizes neuronal connections even when confronted with the same stimulus, thereby shaping the learning experience. This phenomenon underscores the ability of neuroscience to provide insights that extend beyond the realm of psychology.

4.5.2 A brain-based SCCI training

According to the AGES model, students get the best of their learning experience if their learning environment allows for them to boost their attention, generate knowledge, regulate their emotions and space their learning. The study shows that all of those principles are interwoven in application. Their relation is neither discrete nor linear, but systematic as Figure (4.3) illustrates.

The study's findings align with the Strategic Teacher's Model as well as AGES model which underscore the pivotal role of emotion in augmenting learning and memory. Particularly noteworthy is both models placing emphasis on the beneficial impact of positive emotions when coupled with a reduction in negative emotions, such as boredom and frustration. Heightened self-confidence played a significant role in bolstering students' motivation to achieve goals, with self-confidence defined by them as a state of assurance during the learning process, characterized by the absence of tension or anxiety related to their mistakes. This observation is notably in line with the principles of the Strategic Teacher's Model, especially regarding its graduated difficulty strategy. It also resonates with constructivist recommendations for students to engage in curriculum changes to address their emerging needs.

Students successfully navigated their initial apprehensions, despite their limited prior experience and knowledge, remained unfazed by errors and did not experience feelings of frustration as they progressed. This aligns with (Gross, 2002), positing that emotion regulation evolves through distinct stages, encompassing situation appraisal, aspect identification, meaning, and subsequent response modulation (reappraisal). The response, under this model, is perceived to be motivation by students as they see the training rewarding and they seek that reward, which is consistent with neuroscience

findings that the anticipation of a reward activates the ventral tegmental area (VTA), which in turn sends dopamine to other regions in the brain reinforcing the rewarding behaviour (Richter & Gruber, 2018).

The hooks in the interpersonal and understanding styles significantly triggered students' curiosity and assisted in boosting their attention and preventing mind wandering. Of special significance are the compare-contrast, pattern maker and reciprocal learning styles, which kept the students engaged in the learning experience. This was coupled simultaneously with an overwhelming feeling of getting a mix of 'benefit and pleasure', highlighting in neuroscience terms the fact that learning is best achieved by the co-activation, through emotions, of the amygdala and hippocampus (Katsumi & Dolcos, 2020).

It is only the New American Lecture (in mastery style) that did not sufficiently enhance the learning experience. In this method, students were required to express what they already know or think about specific topics. This result is consistent with Silver, Strong and Perini (2007) who explained that this strategy is weaker in an environment where student independent practice is promoted. The students often responded with silence or expressed confusion and lack of understanding. The cause of this problem may be attributed to the fact that students lacked prior knowledge. Despite this, it is noteworthy that they provided accurate responses when the Pattern Maker hook was presented to them, when talking about the types of knowledge, for example. Such circumstances highlight the role of the instructor in brain-based education. As opposed to rigidly adhering to a specific hook, it was observed that the trainer transitioned between alternative hooks and, in some instances, formulated a bridge in the form of a different-style hook. This further aligns with the role of instructor in a brain-based environment in facilitating the construction of knowledge where the teacher is not the

sole source of knowledge, as defined by some researchers, such as like (Haas, 2023), who argues against the "sage on the stage" concept.

Thus, at various stages of their training, students expressed their dissatisfaction with what they called "spoon feeding" and their satisfaction with an educational setting that fosters self-esteem. Neuroscience suggests that if the hippocampus is exposed to emotionally charged information from the amygdala, it will actively seek more of the same. Therefore, it becomes challenging for a student with good self-esteem to abruptly transition into a more adventurous mode and provide potentially incorrect information. Surprisingly, and opposite to this direction, the students displayed no hesitation in proposing answers, even if they were erroneous, particularly within the context of social interactions, which were emphasized in the training.

In spite of this, it is not possible to assert with certainty that this social learning style is a fixed characteristic of students, since it may evolve according to the specific task being undertaken. It can be construed that the brain constructs knowledge by forging unique neural connections. The connections made by students are inherently personal, and they may differ not only from individual to individual, but may also vary within an individual over time, depending on the circumstances and the instructor's ability to regulate their emotions. The perspective aligns with the research on learning styles in Jordan and is consistent with Mahasneh et al. (2021), who report that nursing students prefer structured clinical demonstrations, with at least two participants expressing a preference for this type of approach.

Another key factor at play was the cognitive load, which presented both a theoretical and practical challenge for students. A reduction in cognitive load was essential in the theoretical part of the training in order to facilitate the students' effective engagement with the training material. However, the artificial exercises that prompted

trainees to contemplate personal things outside the prescribed material failed to achieve this objective. Instead, students reported that they continued to think more about the training. This finding resonates with studies discussing the phenomenon of thought suppression, in which trainees tend to focus on precisely what instructors advise them not to think about (Bui, Ghafur, Yankulova, & Morsella, 2023). This observation is also consistent with the perspective of Smallwood and Schooler (2015), who assert that mind wandering is a natural and spontaneous occurrence that should not be artificially induced. Simultaneously, it was observed that the students' cognitive load decreased to a degree that enhanced their attentiveness when they watched purposefully crafted and contextually streamlined videos. For instance, humorous cartoons promoting cooperative learning or criticizing students for procrastination. Additionally, reducing the word count on slides, simplifying static images and using kinesthetics in the cartoon videos played a role in enhancing attention. This phenomenon can be elucidated using the AGES model, which posits that selective attention can be achieved through novelty, rendering the training more relevant.

Concerning the concept of spacing, it remains uncertain whether the division of lessons into two sessions per week positively or negatively impacts student achievement. On one hand, students could effectively retain the knowledge from each lesson, with those in the first group reporting that this spacing suited them comfortably. On the other hand, the second group did not engage in journal writing to document their notes and reflections, making it impossible to determine whether they employed spacing in an effective manner. Nonetheless, all students in both groups concurred on two points. Firstly, not accumulating educational material and providing ample time for each step of learning was beneficial to them. Secondly, they expressed a preference for videos of no more than five seconds in duration, containing minimal cognitive load.

This preference aligns with the EFFORTS theory, the AGES Model, and the emphasis placed by other researchers on the judicious distribution of learning material (as detailed in **section 4.4.6**).

Finally, note-taking was challenging for all students, who said they could not focus on listening and writing at the same time. While interpreting research suggests it is possible to take notes while listening, and neuroscience research has not so far contradicted this belief, this area needs more studies in the context of Jordan students. A speculation can be those students (just as they said) have not adequately learnt how to effectively take notes while listening. Considering note-taking and listening as multi-tasking cannot be excluded, though. Notetaking is a personal skill that does not come naturally (Georgakis, 2017), and challenges working memory limitations (McPherson, 2018), though working memory should be improved in listening task to enhance predictability and comprehension (Mekheimer, 2024). Therefore, students' inability to use notes could also be explained by their lack of exposure to professional ways of note-takers who use their own symbols (Al-Suhaim, 2024). It also indicates that previous interpreting training that the students were trained on did was not challenging enough to improve their working memories. Both assumptions have been confirmed by the students in this case study. One area of investigation to solve this issue could be considering the use of technology to optimise attention and memory while taking notes (Gu, 2024).

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

Court interpreting is not new, nor are the intricacies ever perplexing scholars. Throughout history and across the globe, court interpreters have served as vital links between judges and interlocutors who do not speak the official language of the court. Their role in linguistic mediation has been instrumental in the pursuit of justice and redress of grievances. It is not surprising that judicial systems have consistently recognized the importance of establishing criteria, codes or rosters for accrediting court interpreters and admitting them to court proceedings. However, there have been variations in laws and regulations concerning the interpretation of their roles, ranging from the prevalent model worldwide of a language conduit where their statements are attributed to the disputant or the witness, to scenarios where interpreters take on roles akin to witnesses and judicial assistants, as seen in a few countries like Tunisia and Algeria.

Courts in Jordan do not grant appeals based on errors in interpreting, and the decision of whether an interpreter is qualified to perform interpreting at case is left completely to the discretion of the judge. Even when an interpreter, after taking the oath, makes mistakes, the principle of neutrality prevents the judge from interfering in the process. A seemingly innocuous error, perceived as 'simple' by an interpreter, can precipitate a dramatic transformation in a case's trajectory, shifting it from a 'unilateral will' to 'officiousness', thereby significantly influencing the judge's reasoning and, consequently, the final judgment. However, the types of errors are not only those in changing meaning, but also those in which an interpreter deliberately instructs the plaintiff or defendant to say things in a specific way. An obvious reason for this problem

is attributed to under-regulation, but before that, there is also problem in scholarship on court interpreting not only in Jordan but also in other Arabic-speaking countries. The beginning of such research should start up describing and analysing the current legal framework governing court interpreting.

When compared with other countries such as the United States, Australia, Oman, and Algeria, Jordan finds itself at a nascent stage concerning the establishment of a legal framework that could provide for a professional environment for the professionalization and certification of court interpreters. In Jordanian courts, interpreters are experts, rather than professionals or judicial assistants, and are not liable for interpreting errors, simply because whatever they say in the court is construed as ‘expertise giving’ rather than ‘interpreting’. This is particularly striking given the provisions on court interpreting already mentioned in historical legal instruments like the Mecella, which was adopted during the Ottoman reign in the 19th century and remains effective in several Arab countries including Jordan. Such and other comparable legislation have the potential to provide the groundwork for a more advanced and regulated court interpreting profession. In practice, the role of a court interpreter in Jordan is primarily that of a linguistic conduit who possesses a level of ‘adequate’ proficiency in Arabic and another language, enabling him to convey, under oath, the messages exchanged between the judge, the involved disputants, and the witnesses. Anything interpreters say is attributed to the interlocutors, and interpreters are exempt from any civil or criminal liabilities even if they are proven to have committed serious errors in interpreting. In the latter case, there is no mechanism to challenge or contest their interpretations though the same adjudicating court or in the apex courts.

The variances in laws regarding court interpreting have cast their influence on the realm of education, attracting significant attention towards the scholarly discourse aimed at establishing a robust foundation for the pedagogy of court interpreting. That brought in discussions on what knowledge should be incorporated in their education, and whether court interpreting should be a concern for higher education versus non-degree professional development. In any case, the practice of court interpreting, which should bring in insights from legal systems and linguistic proficiency, necessitates an interdisciplinary approach. Nevertheless, practical research endeavours have yielded limited collaboration between legal scholars, linguists, and professional interpreters, precluding advancement of the professional competence of court interpreters. Compounded by the extensive disparities characterizing diverse legal systems, a prevailing consensus remains elusive concerning the essential conceptual, procedural, and contextual knowledge that should be incorporated into the educational framework, facilitating the alignment of interpreters with real-world practices within court settings. Insufficient or inadequate familiarity with fundamental aspects of the legal domain places court interpreters at risk of misconstruing the intricacies of legal language employed in court proceedings.

Of specific note is that Jordanian law does not mandate specialized training in linguistics or translation, nor does it necessitate the completion of legal, linguistic, or translation courses as prerequisites for court interpreter appointment. Consequently, given that adequate language proficiency and taking the oath are the only requirements for engaging court interpreters in Jordan, it is unsurprising that this study reveals some lack of consistency in the actions of interpreters, further complicated by the absence of clear and stringent legislation defining the rights, obligations, civil and criminal

liabilities, and the professional conduct of court interpreters, including aspects like attire, maintaining neutrality, the use of the first person pronoun (hence the language conduit model), adherence to guidelines for requesting clarifications or repetitions, and withdrawal when conflicts of interest or substantial challenges arise in interpretation. A comprehensive code of conduct for Jordan's court interpreters should encompass these and other critical elements.

Against this backdrop, nonetheless, there is an opportunity for progress. Ongoing efforts are being made in judicial reform in Jordan with the aim of establishing a more mature environment that benefits from the experiences of other countries. These efforts should be heedful to the procedures for court interpreters by effecting a paradigm shift, where interpreters are no longer linguistic experts but also certified judicial assistants. Such efforts are needed to formulate a code of professional conduct that serves as a guiding framework for court interpreters while also aiding educators to prepare students for this profession post-graduation. The initial step is therefore a policy-making issue, and it necessitates an institutionalized assessment of conceptual, situational, and procedural knowledge required of court interpreters, which, in turn, will inform the development of a job description tailored to the specific needs of the court and the imperatives of justice.

Questioning the reliability and trustworthiness of court interpreters in the current situation in Jordan, the present study aims to establish a professional scientific framework for the qualification of interpreters, ensuring a close alignment between educational outcomes and the expectations of the labour market, particularly in the context of court interpreters. Presently, the legal system in Jordan falls short of the necessary standards for appointing and certifying court interpreters. The absence of educational curricula, academic programs within Jordanian universities, and a lack of

regulated professional training opportunities exacerbates this issue. To address the standardization of court interpreters' work, an educational framework becomes imperative.

Consequently, the relevant curriculum development effort must first and foremost thoroughly understand what to include in the curriculum, guided by some fundamental questions: the rationale for developing such a curriculum (cause), its intended purpose (effect), its envisaged structure (ontology), and the individuals or entities responsible for its design (agents).

The rationale underpinning the development of an educational curriculum aimed at training court interpreters is multifaceted. Primarily, this initiative seeks to systematically identify and standardise the optimal practices employed by court interpreters. It endeavours to delineate and cultivate the essential competencies requisite for proficient interpretation within the legal context, thereby fostering the advancement of the profession.

The central objective is to realise a unified standardization of qualification and certification prerequisites for all interpreters. Therefore, the effort must first start with a comprehensive and collectively defined document, with the latter adverb indicating inclusiveness of students in the process. This document should be grounded in the findings derived from scientific research conducted in Jordan, enriched with relevant experience in other countries and offering a blueprint of the substantive content of the curriculum and the pedagogical methodologies best suited for its delivery.

In terms of the curriculum's overarching purpose, it is intrinsically tied to the attainment of a specific vision: that of designating qualified interpreters to function as judicial assistants, not experts. This function serves the overarching goal of rendering non-Arabic speakers on par with their Arabic-speaking counterparts in a court of law,

thus fostering the equal-footing principles of justice and expediting just dispute resolution.

The development of the curriculum necessitates a consensus on an underlying educational philosophy and theory. Presently, Jordanian universities, in adherence to directives from the Ministry of Higher Education and their quality assurance departments, employ general standards pertaining to educational outcomes. These standards, however, lack specificity concerning specialized fields of study, such as court interpreting, leaving considerable discretion to individual departments and instructors. Concurrently, efforts within the Ministry of Labor are geared toward enhancing workforce qualifications through an apprenticeship model. This model involves practical training within authentic work settings, where individuals acquire knowledge directly from experienced practitioners, encompassing the intricacies of their profession and administrative intricacies not typically acquired through conventional academic channels.

While there exists potential for curriculum development to draw upon the diverse knowledge streams of academia and practical apprenticeships, it is imperative to first establish the fundamental orientation of the curriculum, whether grounded in behavioural, constructivist, or other educational paradigms. Consequently, debates surrounding the dichotomy between body-mind, subjective-objective perspectives, often underpinned by divergent theoretical frameworks such as neo-positivism, constructivism, cognitivism, and behaviourism, should be transcended. A more productive approach involves converging upon a poly-focal consensus, wherein varied insights coalesce into tangible, real-world value.

This study posits that the curriculum should be rooted in educational neuroscience, emphasizing that any educational approach or technique should account

for its impact on students' memory processes. While brain-based education aligns closely with constructivism, it is unwise to dismiss the contributions of other educational paradigms. Students, however, should not be passive recipients; they must be actively engaged in decision-making, curriculum design, and the co-creation of their learning experiences to ensure not only success but holistic achievement. The absence of clear objectives can impede progress, as students require guidance to assess their own needs and identify suitable learning techniques.

Curriculum development is a collective endeavour, entailing the identification of psychological and neurological learning styles within each training group. Training strategies are subsequently tailored to specific, mutually agreed-upon objectives. Over time, these collective efforts work to bridge gaps and formulate a near-optimal curriculum capable of accommodating diverse needs. In line with this approach, training materials incorporate brain-based education principles, including hooks, kindling, and bridges, designed to address varied learning styles and promote diverse thinking approaches among students.

Crucially, the curriculum must provide a space for students to actively participate, fostering an environment that encourages them to think in a manner that suits their preferences while contributing to knowledge construction. Advance goal-setting within the educational curriculum is paramount, striving to attain as many objectives as possible while affording students the agency to modify, challenge, or adapt these goals. This study underscores the importance of teaching methods that encompass mastery, comprehension, interpersonal communication, and expression, and the training material or educational curriculum should be structured to accommodate these facets, ensuring that no student is left behind.

5.2 Research contribution

This study proposes a model for designing and teaching small-claims court interpreting in a brain-based learning environment by making a hypothesis about the relationships between variables (Creswell & Poth, 2018). These variables emerged from the qualitative findings of this study, suggesting that integrating the AGES model (Attention, Generation, Emotion, Spacing) and the STM model (Strategic Teachers' Model) can enhance the teaching and learning of small-claims court interpreting in Jordan. Rather than a fixed prediction, this hypothesis is an interpretive proposition grounded in the study's emergent insights, reflecting the complex, context-dependent nature of learning (Mahmoudi-Dehaki & Nasr-Esfahani, 2025) in this professional domain.

From a qualitative, interpretivist perspective, knowledge is discovered rather than predetermined (Alanazi, 2016), meaning this hypothesis does not assert an absolute truth but offers a relative, context-sensitive framework shaped by the data. The study adopts an approach, where the researcher, embedded in the educational system, derives meaning from participants' experiences rather than imposing rigid theoretical expectations. Thus, the AGES-STM hypothesis is not a prescriptive model but a flexible, evolving conceptualization of how neuroscience-informed strategies (AGES) and skill-transfer principles (STM) might interact in Jordan's small-claims court interpreting training.

The central assumption is that effectively merging these models—while accounting for local pedagogical and cognitive realities—can improve knowledge acquisition, retention, and real-world application. Importantly, the hypothesis suggests that educators can apply these principles without deep neuroscience expertise, making brain-based learning (BBL) more accessible. However, as with all qualitative research,

this remains an open, reflexive proposition, subject to refinement as new insights emerge from practice.

Based on the findings of this study, this hypothesis is structured around three interrelated components:

- a) Hypothesized foundational pillars of the adapted AGES-STM framework
- b) Hypothesized role of Emotional Centrality and Neurochemical Regulation (AGES adaptation)
- c) Hypothesized impact of Strategic Instructional Hooks (STM adaptation)

5.2.1 Hypothesized Foundational Pillars of the Adapted AGES-STM Framework

The hypothesis identifies four critical pillars presumed essential for effective teaching and learning in small-claims court interpreting contexts:

- (1) **Brain-Compatible Learning Environment:** Creating an instructional setting that aligns with students' natural neural processes will likely enhance the effectiveness of information encoding, long-term retention, and retrieval in practical scenarios.
- (2) **Learner Agency and Active Engagement:** Encouraging learner agency and active engagement in learning processes is hypothesized to result in improved student motivation, self-directed learning, and ongoing curriculum adaptation that meets evolving learner needs.
- (3) **Strategic Role of the Teacher:** A strategically adaptive teacher, observing and responding to student learning styles within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZAD), is hypothesized to facilitate deeper and more meaningful learning outcomes.
- (4) **Responsive and Dynamic Curriculum Designer:** Continuous updating and dynamic curriculum adaptation based on real-world developments and learner feedback are hypothesized to maintain curricular relevancy, enhancing learner success in real-world applications.

5.2.2 Hypothesized Role of Emotional Centrality and Neurochemical Regulation

The AGES-STM hypothesis underscores a complex interplay among various emotional and cognitive variables influencing learning in court interpreting training. At its core is the regulation of emotions, acting as a foundational element impacting attention, engagement, and generation. Figure (5.1) illustrates the causal relationships

and reinforcement loop among these variables, demonstrating that Attention, Generation, Emotions, and Spacing form an interconnected, dynamic learning system. The hypothesis explicitly emphasizes that these variables are interconnected within a dynamic, systemic structure rather than existing independently or in a linear fashion. Each variable causally influences the others through reinforcing (increasing) or balancing (reducing) interactions. Specifically, the hypothesis proposes that these variables interact within a system characterized by causal relationships. Rather than existing independently or linearly, each component influences the others through reinforcing or balancing mechanisms.

Figure 5.1 The AGES-STM Hypothesis

In a brain-based small-claims court interpreting classroom, emotional regulation significantly affects cognitive processes and learning outcomes. Positive emotional experiences, including reward, curiosity, and pleasure, enhance motivation and engagement. Generation, facilitated by engagement and attention, provides intrinsic rewards by allowing students autonomy and control over their learning, which circles back to further reinforce emotional regulation.

Critically, negative emotions—such as fear, frustration, and boredom—are essential for maintaining emotional balance. Fear of underperformance, frustration with challenging tasks, and boredom from insufficiently challenging activities provide crucial feedback, preventing overconfidence and unrealistic self-assessments. Rather than eliminating these emotions, effective instructional design should manage them carefully.

Effective instructional strategies, particularly through spacing, play a pivotal role in balancing emotional experiences. Spacing enables mastery of each learning component at an individualized pace, minimizing cognitive overload and indirectly strengthening attention. Increased attention, enhanced by emotional regulation, fosters greater learner engagement, subsequently improving students' ability to generate knowledge. Recognizing their contributions as hypotheses rather than merely correct or incorrect answers increases students' confidence and encourages active participation in shaping their learning experiences. This active involvement further elevates self-esteem and willingness to learn.

Ultimately, increased willingness to learn directly improves learning efficacy, enhancing the achievement of defined outcomes. Thus, the AGES-STM hypothesis presents a dynamic, cyclical, and self-reinforcing system in which emotional regulation interacts continuously with cognitive and motivational factors. The hypothesis

explicitly posits a systemic and causal relationship among variables, emphasizing their dynamic interdependence rather than linear or isolated interactions. Ultimately, increased willingness to learn directly enhances learning efficacy, thus improving the potential for achieving defined learning outcomes. The critical question that remains is precisely how the reinforcing and balancing effects can be practically achieved and sustained. The forthcoming section explores how the principles and strategies of STM can specifically facilitate and enhance these relationships, reinforcing the beneficial effects and managing inevitable challenges within the training environment.

The key remaining question is identifying which specific educational techniques or strategies can productively influence each variable or loop within this interconnected system. The following section proposes how the principles and strategies of the Strategic Teaching Model (STM) can practically achieve and sustain these beneficial relationships.

5.2.3 Hypothesized Role of STM strategies (STM adaptation)

The STM principles can be summarized in the following concise points relevant to a small-claims court interpreting training classroom:

- (1) Clarify of learning steps and objectives is paramount. In every encounter, students will ask for and need to know what knowledge and skill they are expected to have learnt after each learning encounter and what the standards are. For that reason, it is paramount to indicate very clearly the terminal and enabling objectives in addition to the learning steps.
- (2) Throughout the training course, students will show needs not already planned for in the curriculum. The teacher and designer will need to be ready to design new learning steps and incorporate them to address the learning needs.
- (3) Students can have different learning styles and can share learning styles
- (4) Students can change from one learning style to another. Specifically, when students are asked to answer a question using the New American Lecture (Mastery style), students gradually and spontaneously move towards adapting the interpersonal (reciprocal learning) and understanding (compare and contrast) styles.
- (5) A bridge in a given learning style can serve as a hook for another learning style.

- (6) If the students are open to socializing with each other, a given learning instance using any learning style might convert spontaneously into the understanding style, making it the dominant learning style of the entire classroom.
- (7) In constructing learning, the students engage in both self-expression and the interpersonal cooperative learning in understanding and mastering concepts.
- (8) In constructing learning, students, especially in the beginning, will
- (9) Asking students about their previous knowledge of a learning instance (using the New American Lecture style) can render silence, partial correct answers and/or misconceptions. All of those are dealt with as hypotheses to be tested rather than correct or incorrect answers. The quantity and quality of knowledge reflected by the students will determine the ZAD.
- (10) In actual exercises, students' sense of comfort will increase if the teacher models an exercise by thinking loud while performing a skill. Metacognitive exercises and videos will also be a useful source of modelling.
- (11) The early lessons will see students relying on a more traditional approach, where the 'teacher is sage' on the stage and students are 'passive recipients'. Addressing this issue should begin early on, not by the teacher theorizing the brain-based method, but by presenting them with exercises that promote: self-reflection, hypothesis tested rather than correct-incorrect answers, self-confidence and peer-to-peer cooperative learning.
- (12) Students will lament what they perceive as 'traditional futile learning', to which the teacher should be very careful just to avoid any unjustified and unfair bias towards any previous learning style they were exposed to.

A variety of teaching strategies should inform the design of training materials and instructional methods. Educators should consider these strategies while adapting to students' diverse learning styles.

For example, students may respond more effectively to expressive-style prompts—such as, "You are the top court interpreter in your country. What qualities earned you this title?"—rather than a mastery-style approach (e.g., "What do you know about the qualities of court interpreters?"). The latter may result in silence, as students often lack real-world interpreting experience. That said, mastery-style questioning can still be valuable when the goal is to uncover and address student misconceptions.

A strategic teacher remains attentive to the dominant learning styles in the classroom and adapts accordingly, recognizing overlaps where one learning bridge may serve as a hook for another. In a brain-based classroom, students often transition into a blend of understanding and interpersonal styles, learning collaboratively through

discussion, metaphorical expression, and peer teaching as they compare and contrast concepts.

In conclusion, as we stand at the intersection of neuroscience and interpreter education, the AGES-STM framework challenges us to fundamentally reconsider how professional competence develops in educational settings. This approach does more than suggest new teaching techniques as it requires a paradigm shift in how court interpreter instructor and course designers conceptualize the very nature of knowledge transfer and skill acquisition. The classroom becomes not just a training ground but a dynamic ecosystem where cognitive processes, emotional responses, and social interactions continuously reshape learning pathways. For Jordan's small-claims court interpreters, this may represent the difference between rote memorization and genuine professional readiness that is agile enough to cope with a changing legal system. Therefore, the true test of this framework will come not in controlled academic studies, but in courtrooms where interpreters face the unpredictable realities of live proceedings. There, in the space between theory and practice, we may discover whether brain-based learning can produce not just competent interpreters, but professional ones who can be real contributors to the delivery of justice.

5.3 Implications to policy makers

The envisioned transformation is conceived here as a multifaceted and all-encompassing policy-making endeavour. The milestones of this change initiative should not only provide a comprehensive assessment of the existing legal framework but also propose remedial actions. Moreover, this cycle should be characterized by inclusivity, where diverse stakeholders, encompassing the judiciary, legislators, scholars, and professionals, collaboratively participate. The recommended policy-

making cycle commences with a cost assessment, followed by the solicitation of financial pledges from funding agencies to cover the expenses associated with research activities, workshops, product development, implementation and dissemination phases.

Figure 5.2 Policy making cycle for SCCI professionalization in Jordan

Following the development of the product, whether it takes the form of legislation, regulations, or a code of conduct, the responsible policy makers will face the crucial task of operationalizing this product into an approval mechanism for the appointment or admission of court interpreters into a relevant roster. If the decision is made to institute a testing system, it will be imperative to initially assess the language proficiency of prospective interpreters. This study advocates that accreditation for court interpreters should be contingent on their successful completion of a specialized language assessment of Arabic and the other language they work with. Once candidates have demonstrated linguistic proficiency, they can progress to the practical component of the assessment, which assesses their aptitude in alignment with the established code of conduct or issued instructions. The rubrics of the assessment depend fully on the policy reached, but small-claims court interpreter should be tested in areas of: law of obligations (sources of rights), code of conduct (including attire), skills (including note-

taking) and the language conduit model, in addition to other areas that this research has highlighted.

However, there remains one important limitation to be taken into account. Jordan, like many other nations, may encounter non-Arabic speakers of languages that are seldom encountered or recognized within the kingdom. This situation necessitates the engagement of individuals who can facilitate communication between these languages. Such a scenario may potentially compromise the standard prerequisites for court interpreters, such as higher education, for example. Consequently, it is advisable that the proposed policy change initially focuses on English interpreters exclusively, with the possibility of extending this framework to encompass other language pairs in the future.

5.4 Implications for SCI training institutions

5.4.1 Venue

The venue of the small-claims court interpreting training course holds significant importance in ensuring the effectiveness and quality of the training, and in achieving its objectives. This is because the learning environment profoundly influences students' thought processes and 'provokes' specific styles of thinking. When it comes to the presentation of theoretical material, which encompasses reading materials and audio-visual cartoon scenarios, the ideal approach is to deliver this content through a virtual platform such as Zoom or within a training room that is well-equipped with multimedia resources.

For promoting an interpersonal learning style, the training venue should include movable chairs, as this flexibility enables students to create collaborative learning groups at their discretion. Furthermore, if the organizers of the training program aim to

establish a stronger connection between the theoretical education within the training facility and the practical realities of the field to ensure authentic learning, it becomes essential to incorporate training sessions conducted in moot courts. This approach serves to mirror the actual workings of the court system, lending authenticity to the teaching of situational knowledge in court translation.

Given the limitations on universities, it is unlikely that any of them would be able or interested in opening a program for court interpreting. More likely is that they could introduce new relevant courses inside the syllabus, but the easiest way would be to offer court interpreting courses at the community service centers each university has. Alternatively, professional training of interpreters can be taken as a private venture through private companies or training centre, in which case they can liaise with the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Higher Education or Ministry of Labor, each depending on the applicable regulations.

5.4.2 Qualification of trainers

The selection of instructors for such courses is a matter of utmost importance, necessitating stringent adherence to specific criteria. The following recommends some of the critical qualities that should characterise instructors in Small-Claims Civil Court Interpreting (SCCI) training, transforming their role into one of profound educational significance.

An instructor's foremost teaching skill lies in their capacity to foster SCCI training within a brain-based learning environment. This involves the art of encouraging students to approach their training, engage with exercises, and cultivate cognitive strategies aligned with their unique learning styles. These styles may encompass mastery-driven, understanding-oriented, self-expressive, or interpersonally reciprocal and cooperative learning.

It is pertinent for instructors to possess a substantial background in interpretation, with a specific emphasis on court interpreting. This background serves as a beacon for students to follow, affording them the opportunity to model their interpretation skills. However, it is imperative that instructors transcend mere interpretation expertise and embrace the practice of teaching as a science rather than a transfer of information from a presumed 'know-it-all expert' to passive 'know-it-not' recipients. Knowledge of the AGES model is required so that the instructor can understand the impact of his own teaching and students' learning on the students' brain-based memory network and connection. For example, instructors should avoid using examples that cause pain or fear among students, to reduce the possibilities of unbalanced adrenaline release and the activation of the fight-or-flight situation. An effective instructor should demonstrate an awareness of current educational research, particularly within the realms of language and interpreting pedagogy, and be continuously updated on new trends in learning styles, teaching strategies and legal changes in local systems.

The instructor should adhere steadfastly to the pedagogical approaches delineated in the SCCI training materials, particularly the 'hook-kindle-bridge' methodology. Furthermore, instructors should wholeheartedly embrace the principle of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). In application, this entails withholding the dissemination of information until students reach the bridging phase, where the instructor scaffolds students' discussions with new knowledge. In this context, instructors should treat each student response as a hypothesis to be rigorously tested, transcending the dichotomy of correct and incorrect answers in favor of encouraging critical examination.

In addition to linguistic proficiency, instructors should possess a deep-seated understanding of the intricacies of language and nuances when employed within legal contexts. A firsthand experience in court settings as a court interpreter is invaluable, yet it must be wielded judiciously to ensure that it does not overshadow or hamper students' independent knowledge construction. Legal knowledge, encompassing the subtleties of language in legal settings, is of paramount importance. Instructors should exhibit a wealth of knowledge concerning legal matters pertinent to cases adjudicated within SCCs, encompassing judicial reasoning, deduction processes, legal pragmatics, the fundamentals of legal jurisprudence, and ideally, an advanced grasp of disputes, domains, and specialized terminology within various professional arenas.

While it is not mandatory for instructors to be technologically adept in the creation of plots and multimedia materials, they should collaborate with specialists to fulfill these technological requirements effectively. It is advisable for instructors not to be distracted by the multifaceted tasks of video creation, where a team of instructional assistants can offer support, both during the delivery of training and in the preparatory stages of curriculum development. The setback, though, is the financial burden as this will likely increase the spending on the program. There are no studies on the affordability of such training courses to students in Jordan, but hypothetically, students could themselves help if they have technological skills, to reduce the expenses provided they be given credit in the preparation of the material, following the example of the two case studies of this study.

5.5 Implications for SCCI curriculum designers

Based on the results of the case studies of the research, outlining objectives upfront was useful to guide the students into their training, but arrangements should be

made to give room for any new objective to be introduced should the need arise. In the current study, students wanted to know more about how the judge thinks, so a learning objective was appended to the training course on the qualities of judges and how they think. Therefore, we recommend the objectives to have serial number in hundreds rather than in serial numbers. For example, the first and second objectives would read: TLO100 and TLO200 respectively to allow for new objectives to be added before 100 or between 100 and 200. The basic structure recommended will represent terminal objectives, enabling objectives and learning steps (Figure 5.2)

Figure 5.3 Skeleton of the training course

There is no specific quantitative limit on the learning steps, as long as they serve in presenting knowledge to the students. Additional exercises may be and are encouraged to be developed to cope with the different levels of difficulty that students can deal with. Those levels should be defined based on the content of: terminology, time span and cognitive load. In the final assessment of evaluation, though, students should know from the beginning about the level that is accepted for graduation from the program. As for the rubrics of the training and its length, based on this study, it is

recommended to decide on the training period based on the aptitude of the students, to complete the rubrics of the program, which will be interdisciplinary as in Appendix B.

REFERENCES

- Abdi Tabari, M., Lee, H., & Hanzawa, K. (2025). Effects of massed and spaced task repetitions on L2 writing task performance and task emotions. *Reading and Writing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-024-10628-2>
- Abercrombie, N., Hill, S., & Turner, B. (2006). *Dictionary of sociology* (5th ed.). Penguin.
- Abu-Bakar, M. A., Ab-Ghani, A. T., & Abdullah, M. L. (2024). An intelligent mathematics problem-solving tutoring system framework: A conceptual merging of fuzzy neural networks and neuroscience mechanistics. *International Journal of Biomedical Engineering*, 20(5), 44–65. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v20i05.47793>
- Abu-Moghli, F. A., Khalaf, I. A., Halabi, J. O., & Wardam, L. A. (2005). Jordanian baccalaureate nursing students' perception of their learning styles. *International Nursing Review*, 52(1), 39–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-7657.2004.00235.x>
- Abu-Risha, M. (2005). Towards more efficient courses of translation. *Atlas Journal for Studies and Research*, 1(1).
- Abu-Risha, M. (2006). Resources for self-training translators. *Atlas Journal for Studies and Research*, 1(2).
- Abu-Risha, M., & Jaganathan, P. (2021). An analysis of responses of Jordan courts to objections based on language interpreting issues. *Perspectives*, 29(4), 539–553. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0907676X.2020.1862261>
- Abu Bakar, M., Abdul Ghani, A. T., Abdullah, M. L., Ismail, N., & Abdul Aziz, S. (2022). Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) formulation to predict students' neuroscience mechanistic: A concept of an intelligent model to enhance mathematics learning ability. *TEM Journal*, 11(4), 1942–1951. <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM114-63>
- Abu Bakar, M. A., & Abdul Ghani, A. T. (2022). The impact of neuroscience literacy on sustainability of the students' mathematics learning environment. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 17(9), 148–161. <https://doi.org/10.46754/jssm.2022.09.010>

- Acevedo, M. M. (2014). Collaborating with faculty to compose exemplary learning objectives. *Internet Learning*, 3(1), 5–16.
- Açıkgöz, T., & Babadoğan, M. C. (2021). Competency-based education: Theory and practice. *Psycho-Educational Research Review*, 10(3), 67–95.
- Adams, C. (2016). Looking for Interpreter Zero: (12) Hasday ibn Shaprut and Recemund, intermediaries and interpreters in 10th-century al-Andalus. Retrieved January 18, 2019, from <http://aiic.net/p/7805>
- Adirika, B. N., & Okolie, V. C. (2017). Examining models of curriculum development and processes: Implications for African educational heritage and review. *Social Science and Humanities Journal*, 6, 325–342.
- Agustin, M. (2018). An error analysis of auxiliary verbs found on students' consecutive interpretation. [Unpublished undergraduate thesis, State Institute for Islamic Studies].
- Ahrens, B., & Orlando, M. (2022). Note-taking for consecutive conference interpreting. In M. Albl-Mikasa & E. Tiselius (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of conference interpreting* (pp. 34-48). Routledge.
- Al-Dabbagh, U., & Othman, W. (2024). Gaps in translation technology education: A case study of Jordanian universities. *Training, Language and Culture*, 8(4), 48–63. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2521-442X-2024-8-4-48-63>
- Al-Suhaim, D. S. (2024). Exploring theoretical dimensions in interpreting studies: A comprehensive overview. *AWEJ for Translation & Literary Studies*, 8(1), 15–43. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awejtls/vol8no1.2>
- Al-Zahran, A. (2007). The consecutive conference interpreter as intercultural mediator: A cognitive-pragmatic approach to the interpreter's role [Doctoral dissertation, University of Salford, UK].
- Al Mawardi, A. (1999). *The great collection of Imam Shafii school (الحاوي الكبير في فقه الشافعي الإمام مذهب)*. Islamweb. <https://www.islamweb.net/ar/library/content/94/8662/index.php>
- Al Zuhaili, M. (2006). *Jurist rules and applications according to the four schools (القواعد الفقهية وتطبيقاتها في المذاهب الأربعة)*. Dar Al Fikr.

- Alanazi, A. (2016). A critical review of constructivist theory and the emergence of constructionism. *American Research of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2, 1–8.
- Alexander, P. A. (1992). Domain knowledge: Evolving themes and emerging concerns. *Educational Psychologist*, 27(1), 33–51.
- Alexander, P. A., & Judy, J. E. (1988). The interaction of domain-specific and strategic knowledge in academic performance. *Review of Educational Research*, 58(4), 375–404. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543058004375>
- Alexieva, B. (1991). The optimum text in simultaneous interpreting: A cognitive approach to interpreter training. In *The First Language International Conference: Teaching Translation and Interpreting, Training, Talent and Experience*, Elsinore, Denmark.
- Alkhasawneh, I. M., Mrayyan, M. T., Docherty, C., Alashram, S., & Yousef, H. Y. (2008). Problem-based learning (PBL): Assessing students' learning preferences using VARK. *Nurse Education Today*, 28(5), 572–579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2007.09.012>
- Allais, S., & Shalem, Y. (2018). Introduction. In S. Allais & Y. Shalem (Eds.), *Knowledge, curriculum and preparation for work*. Brill Sense.
- Allioua, W., & Benkouiten, I. (2023). Blended learning: Associating types of learners' learning styles with their preferred in-person and online learning activities: The case of Master 1 EFL students at Mila University Center Abdelhafid Boussouf University – Mila.
- Amran, S., & Sommer, W. (2024). Seen through teachers' eyes: Neuromyths and their application in Malaysian classrooms. *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4975128>
- Anderson, J. R. (1982). Acquisition of cognitive skill. *Psychological Review*, 89(4), 369–406.
- Anderson, L. W. (2010). Taxonomies of objectives and learning. In C. Kridel (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of curriculum studies* (Vol. 1, pp. 839–841). Sage.
- Angrosino, M. V. (2007). *Observational research*. Routledge.

- Artaloytia, J., Arango, C., Lahti, A., Sanz, J., Pascual, A., Cubero, P., Prieto, D., & Palomo, T. (2006). Negative signs and symptoms secondary to antipsychotics: A double-blind, randomized trial of a single dose of placebo, haloperidol, and risperidone in healthy volunteers. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, *163*, 488–493.
- Aulia, N., & Sari, S. (2022). The effect of animated videos on creativity in science learning of class V students about changes in objects in elementary school 067256 Medan Marelan district academic year 2020–2021. *Journal of General Education Science*, *1*(1), 31–40.
- Ausubel, D. P. (1966). Early versus delayed review in meaningful learning. *Psychology in the Schools*, *3*(3), 195–198. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6807\(196607\)3:3<195::aid-pits2310030302>3.0.co;2-x](https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6807(196607)3:3<195::aid-pits2310030302>3.0.co;2-x)
- Ayres, L. (2008). Semi-structured interviews. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods* (Vols. 1 & 2). Sage Publications.
- Babanina, T., Zhivaeva, A., & Babanina, T. (2015, January 1). The emergence of court interpreting in Russia: Qualified interpreters needed. In *Foreign languages and literature in the international educational space: Proceedings of the Fifth International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Ekaterinburg, March 3, 2015).
- Babbie, E. (2008). *The basics of social research*. Thomson Wadsworth.
- Bahgat, M., Elsafty, A., Shaarawy, A., & Said, T. (2018). FIRST framework design and facilitate active deep learner experience. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, *6*(8), 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v6i8.3337>
- Baigorri-Jalon, J. (2010). Wars, languages and the role(s) of interpreters. In *Les liaisons dangereuses: Langues, traduction, interprétation*, Beirut.
- Bajo, M. T., Teresa, M., Padilla, P., Muñoz, R., Padilla, F., Gómez, C., Puerta, M., Gonzalvo, P., & Macizo, P. (2001). Comprehension and memory processes in translation and interpreting. *Quaderns: Revista de Traducció*, *(6)*, 27–31.
- Baker, M., & Saldanha, G. (2019). *Routledge encyclopedia of translation studies* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Ball, M. (2021). Distance interpreting and the risk of alienation. In K. Seeber (Ed.), *100 years of conference interpreting: A legacy* (pp. 262–269). Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

- Barker, L. J., O'Neill, M., & Kazim, N. (2014). Framing classroom climate for student learning and retention in computer science. In *Proceedings of the 45th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (SIGCSE '14)*.
- Barone, T. (2008). Arts informed research. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods* (Vols. 1 & 2, pp. 29–32). Sage Publications.
- Bawaneh, A. K. A., Zain, A. N. M., & Saleh, S. (2010). Investigating tenth grade Jordanian students' thinking styles based on Herrmann's whole brain model for the purpose of developing new teaching method in modifying science misconceptions. *Educational Research, 1*(9), 363–372.
- Bear, M. F., Connors, B. W., & Paradiso, M. A. (2007). *Neuroscience* (2nd ed.). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Bedek, M., Kickmeier-Rust, M., Debus, K., & others. (n.d.). Deliverable D3.5. [Details needed]
- Bednar, A. K., Cunningham, D., Duffy, T. M., & Perry, J. D. (1992). Theory into practice: How do we link? In T. M. Duffy & D. Jonassen (Eds.), *Instructional technology: Past, present, and future* (pp. 17–34). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Benaquisto, L. (2008a). Axial coding. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research* (Vols. 1 & 2, pp. 51–52). Sage Publications.
- Benaquisto, L. (2008b). Open coding. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research* (Vols. 1 & 2, pp. 581–582). Sage Publications.
- Benaquisto, L. (2008c). Selective coding. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research* (Vols. 1 & 2, pp. 805–806). Sage Publications.
- Benjamini, Y. (2010). Simultaneous and selective inference: Current successes and future challenges. *Biometrical Journal, 52*(6), 708–721. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bimj.200900299>
- Benmaman, V. (2000). Interpreter issues in appeal. *PROTEUS: Newsletter of the National Association of Judiciary Interpreters and Translators, 9*(4). <https://public.courts.alaska.gov/web/language/docs/interpreter-issues.pdf>

- Benoit, D. (2014). Constitutional law/evidence—United States v. Charles: A post-Crawford analysis of an interpreter as a declarant: Did the Eleventh Circuit take its decision a bridge too far? *Western New England Law Review*, 37, 301.
- Berk-Seligson, S. (2017). *The bilingual courtroom* [Electronic book]. University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226329329.001.0001>
- Bestue, C., & Raigal-Aran, J. (2023). Applying a sociological perspective to the analysis of court interpreting interactions: Exploring trust and distrust. *The Interpreters' Newsletter*, 28, 131–150. <https://doi.org/10.13137/2421-714X/35554>
- Bhatt, S. (2019). Knowledge portals. In A. Singh & R. Srivastava (Eds.), *Sustainable resource management through innovative management practices* (pp. 106–118). Bharti Publications.
- Bhuttah, T., Xiaoduan, C., Ullah, H., & Javed, S. (2019). Analysis of curriculum development stages from the perspective of Tyler, Taba and Wheeler. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 58(1), 14–22.
- Billbao, P. P., Lucido, P., Iringan, T., & Javier, R. (2008). *Curriculum development*. Lorimar Publishing Inc.
- Binder, J. L. (1999). Issues in teaching and learning time-limited psychodynamic psychotherapy. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 19(6), 405–419. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7358\(98\)00078-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7358(98)00078-6)
- Blatter, J. K. (2008). Case study. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods* (Vols. 1 & 2). Sage Publications.
- Bless, C., Higson-Smith, C., & Kagee, A. (2007). *Fundamentals of social research methods: An African perspective*. Juta and Company Ltd.
- Blood, A. J., & Zatorre, R. J. (2001). Intensely pleasurable responses to music correlate with activity in brain regions implicated in reward and emotion. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(20), 11818–11823. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.191355898>
- Bloom, B. S. (1956). *Taxonomy of educational objectives. Vol. 1: Cognitive domain*. McKay.

- Böcker, M., & Anderson, D. (1993). Remote conference interpreting using ISDN videotelephone: A requirements analysis and feasibility study. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*.
- Bodner, G. M. (1986). Constructivism: A theory of knowledge. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 63(10), 873.
- Boncz, I. (2015). *Introduction to research methodology*. Faculty of Health Sciences of the University of Pécs.
- Booyse, C., & Chetty, R. (2016). The significance of constructivist classroom practice in national curricular design. *Africa Education Review*, 13(1), 135–149.
- Borg, W., Gall, M., & Gall, J. (2003). *Educational research: An introduction*. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Bowcott, O. (2016, May 4). Thousands of court cases adjourned due to failures in interpreting services. *The Guardian*.
<https://www.theguardian.com/law/2016/may/04/thousands-of-court-cases-adjourned-due-to-failures-in-interpreting-services>
- Bowers, J. S. (2016). The practical and principled problems with educational neuroscience. *Psychological Review*, 123(5), 600.
- Boyko, E. J. (2013). Observational research—Opportunities and limitations. *Journal of Diabetes Complications*, 27(6), 642–648.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2013.07.007>
- Bradbury, N. (2019). Attention span during lectures: 8 seconds, 10 minutes, or more? *Advances in Physiology Education*, 40, 509–513.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00109.2016>
- Bradford, D. (2018). Ethical issues in experiential learning. *Journal of Management Education*, 43(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562918807500>
- Braisby, N., & Gellatly, A. (2012). *Cognitive psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Brancaleone, D., & O'Brien, S. (2011). Educational commodification and the (economic) sign value of learning outcomes. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 32(4), 501–519.

- Braun, V., Clarke, V., & Weate, P. (2017). Using thematic analysis in sport and exercise research. In B. Smith & A. C. Sparkes (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of qualitative research in sport and exercise* (pp. 191–205). Routledge.
- Breidbach, O. (2001). The origin and development of the neurosciences. In *Theory and method in the neurosciences* (pp. 7–29). University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Brenda, W. R. (2015). *Training as a minimum requirement to improve court interpretation in Kenya: A case study of Milimani Chief Magistrate's Courts* [Master's thesis, University of Nairobi].
- Brewin, C. R. (1996). Theoretical foundations of cognitive-behavioral therapy for anxiety and depression. *Annual Review of Psychology*, *47*, 33–57. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.47.1.33>
- Brockington, G., Balardin, J. B., Zimeo Morais, G. A., Malheiros, A., Lent, R., Moura, L. M., & Sato, J. R. (2018). From the laboratory to the classroom: The potential of functional near-infrared spectroscopy in educational neuroscience [Perspective]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *9*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01840>
- Brod, G., Werkle-Bergner, M., & Shing, Y. L. (2013). The influence of prior knowledge on memory: A developmental cognitive neuroscience perspective. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, *7*, 139.
- Brown, P. C., Roediger, H. L., & McDaniel, M. A. (2014). *Make it stick: The science of successful learning*. Harvard University Press.
- Brown, S. B. R. E. (2023). The persistence of matching teaching and learning styles: A review of the ubiquity of this neuromyth, predictors of its endorsement, and recommendations to end it [Review]. *Frontiers in Education*, *8*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1147498>
- Brownson, T. (2016). *86 amazing facts about the human brain* [eBook edition].
- Bruer, J. T. (1997). Education and the brain: A bridge too far. *Educational Researcher*, *26*(8), 4–16.
- Bui, N. C. T., Ghafur, R. D., Yankulova, J. K., & Morsella, E. (2023). Stimulus-elicited involuntary insights and syntactic processing. *Psychology of Consciousness: Theory, Research, and Practice*, *10*(2), 115–133. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cns0000208>

- Bukhari, M. (2002). *Sahih Al Bukhari (Al Bukhari's collection of Prophet's traditions)*. Ibn Kathir Publishing House.
- Burns, J. P. (2024). The Tyler rationale: A reappraisal and rereading. *Prospects*, 54(1), 121–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-023-09643-y>
- Busetto, L., Wick, W., & Gumbinger, C. (2020). How to use and assess qualitative research methods. *Neurological Research and Practice*, 2(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42466-020-00059-z>
- Byren, D. (1987). *Techniques for classroom interaction*. Longman.
- Caine, R., & Caine, G. (1991). *Making connections: Teaching and the human brain*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Caine, R., & Caine, G. (2011). *Natural learning for a connected world*. Teachers College Press.
- California Courts. (n.d.). About. Retrieved January 14, 2019, from <http://www.courts.ca.gov/2685.htm>
- Calvo, E. (2011). Translation and/or translator skills as organising principles for curriculum development practice. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, 16, 5–25.
- Campbell, C. (1996). Instructional system development. In C. Campbell (Ed.), *Education and training for work* (Vol. 1, pp. 55–108). Techomic Publishing Company.
- Cañas, L. G. (2024). *Neuroscience applied to education to improve attention and learning* [Unpublished thesis, Universidad Complutense Madrid].
- Carlsten, J. (2023). Feelings and facts: Agency in Northern Irish cinema. *Journal of British Cinema and Television*, 20(3), 345–364. <https://doi.org/10.3366/jbctv.2023.0680>
- Carter, M., & Shieh, J. C. (2015). *Guide to research techniques in neuroscience*. Academic Press.
- Casey, M. (2023). Maricopa County Superior Court hires staff interpreter to help Arabic speakers. *Fronteras*. Retrieved January 1, 2024, from

<https://fronterasdesk.org/content/1854418/maricopa-county-superior-court-hires-staff-interpreter-help-arabic-speakers>

- Cercone, K. (2006). Brain-based learning. In E. K. Sorensen & D. O. Murchu (Eds.), *Enhancing learning through technology* (pp. 292–322). IGI Global.
- Cerezo, L. (2014). Interpreting. In M. Lacorte (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of Hispanic applied linguistics* (pp. 313–331). Routledge.
- Chang, K. C.-c. (2013). Current practices of court interpreting in Taiwan: Challenges and possible solutions. *Compilation and Translation Review*, 6(2), 127–164.
- Chang, K. C.-c. (2016). Needs analysis for the training of court interpreters. *Compilation & Translation Review*, 9(2), 93–136.
- Charmaz, K., & Bryant, A. (2008). The grounded theory. In L. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research* (Vols. 1 & 2, pp. 374–376). SAGE Publications Inc.
- Charron, S., & Koechlin, E. (2010). Divided representation of concurrent goals in the human frontal lobes. *Science*, 328(5976), 360–363. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1183614>
- Chatterjee, D., & Corral, J. (2017). How to write well-defined learning objectives. *The Journal of Education in Perioperative Medicine*, 19(4), 1–4.
- Chen, A. H., Youdelman, M. K., & Brooks, J. (2007). The legal framework for language access in healthcare settings: Title VI and beyond. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 22(2), 362–367.
- Chen, C. H., & Law, V. (2016). Scaffolding individual and collaborative game-based learning in learning performance and intrinsic motivation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, 1201–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.03.010>
- Chen, O., Castro-Alonso, J. C., Paas, F., & Sweller, J. (2018). Extending cognitive load theory to incorporate working memory resource depletion: Evidence from the spacing effect. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(2), 483–501. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-017-9426-2>
- Chen, S.-J. (2014). Instructional design strategies for intensive online courses: An objectivist-constructivist blended approach. *Journal of Interactive Online Learning*, 13(1).

- Chen, S. (2017). Note-taking in consecutive interpreting: New data from pen recording. *Translation & Interpreting*, 9(1), 4–23.
- Chmiel, A. (2010). How effective is teaching note-taking to trainee interpreters? *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 4(2), 233–250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2010.10798805>
- Clark, J., & Paivio, A. (1991). Dual coding theory and education. *Educational Psychology Review*, 3(3), 149–210.
- Clement, N. D., & Lovat, T. (2012). Neuroscience and education: Issues and challenges for curriculum. *Curriculum Inquiry*, 42(4), 534–557.
- Clerc, J., Miller, P. H., & Cosnefroy, L. (2014). Young children's transfer of strategies: Utilization deficiencies, executive function, and metacognition. *Developmental Review*, 34(4), 378–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2014.10.002>
- Cochran, W., & Rubin, D. (1973). Controlling bias in observational studies: A review. *Sankhyā: The Indian Journal of Statistics*, 35(4), 417–446.
- Cohen, L., & Manion, L. (1989). *Research methods in education*. Routledge.
- Collins, A., & Koechlin, E. (2012). Reasoning, learning, and creativity: Frontal lobe function and human decision-making. *PLoS Biology*, 10(3), e1001293.
- Connaway, L. S., & Radford, M. L. (2021). *Research methods in library and information science*. ABC CLIO, LLC.
- Cook, J., Miranda, G., & Shriver, T. (2018). The rise of the digital learning ecosystem. <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/O9ZJ2ZXB>
- Cooperstein, S. E., & Kocevar-Weidinger, E. (2004). Beyond active learning: A constructivist approach to learning. *Reference Services Review*, 32(2), 141–148.
- Corder, P. (1967). The significance of learners' errors. *International Review of Applied Linguistics*, 5(1–4), 160–170.
- Corsellis, A. (2005). Training interpreters to work in the public services. In M. Tennent (Ed.), *Training for the new millennium* (pp. 153–173). John Benjamins B.V.
- Corsini, R. J. (1999). *The dictionary of psychology*. Psychology Press.

- Covelli, A. (2024). The teacher's role in motivating preschool children to learn English as a FL in a classroom environment
- Cox, T. (2013). *Exploring learner-centeredness within an American Sign Language/English interpreter training program* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Texas State University.
- D'Souza, A., & Larik, A. (2024). The perception of educational leaders about the relevance of Tyler's curriculum model in transforming the learning process in karachi. *Journal of Social Signs Review*, 2(4), 129-160.
- Dabiri, S., Mohammadi, A., & Mojtahedzadeh, R. (2019). The effect of test-enhanced spaced learning on the otolaryngology board and annual examination results: A quasi-experimental study. *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism*, 7(3), 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.30476/jamp.2019.74696>
- Daro, V. (1994). Non-linguistic factors influencing simultaneous interpretation. In S. Lambert & B. Moser-Mercer (Eds.), *Bridging the gap: Empirical research in simultaneous interpretation* (Vol. 81, pp. 249–272). John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Davachi, L., Kiefer, T., Rock, D., & Rock, L. (2010). Learning that lasts through AGES. *NeuroLeadership Journal*, 3, 1–11.
- Davidson, N., Major, C. H., & Michaelsen, L. K. (2014). Small-group learning in higher education—Cooperative, collaborative, problem-based, and team-based learning: An introduction by the guest editors. *Journal on Excellence in College Teaching*, 25(3–4), 1–6.
- De Jong, T., & Ferguson-Hessler, M. G. (1996). Types and qualities of knowledge. *Educational Psychologist*, 31(2), 105–113.
- de Jongh, E. M. (2012). *From the classroom to the courtroom: A guide to interpreting in the U.S. justice system*. John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://books.google.jo/books?id=vi8Ti88EikEC>
- Deci, E. L. (1972). The effects of contingent and noncontingent rewards and controls on intrinsic motivation. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 8, 217–229.
- Delibaş, H. (2023). Vocational foreign language teaching and translation activity in the Ottoman Empire: The case of dragomans. *RumeliDE Journal of Language and Literature Studies*, 37, 1484–1493. <https://doi.org/10.29000/rumelide.1406980>

- Dempster, F. N. (1987). Effects of variable encoding and spaced presentations on vocabulary learning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 79(2), 162–170. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.79.2.162>
- Diab, P., Matthews, M., & Gokool, R. (2016). Medical students' views on the use of video technology in the teaching of isiZulu communication, language skills and cultural competence. *African Journal of Health Professions Education*, 8(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.7196/AJHPE.2016.v8i1.402>
- Diachun, L. L., Dumbrell, A. C., Byrne, K., & Esbaugh, J. (2006). ... But does it stick? Evaluating the durability of improved knowledge following an undergraduate experiential geriatrics learning session. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 54(4), 696–701. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-5415.2006.00656.x>
- Díaz-Galaz, S., & Winston, E. A. (2025). Interpreting, training, and education. In C. Mellinger (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of interpreting and cognition* (pp. 417–437). Routledge.
- Dignath, C., Buettner, G., & Langfeldt, H.-P. (2008). How can primary school students learn self-regulated learning strategies most effectively? A meta-analysis on self-regulation training programmes. *Educational Research Review*, 6(2), 101–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2008.02.003>
- Đorđević, J. P. (2012). Discourse analysis in consecutive interpreting—Necessity rather than aid. *Методички видици*, 6(3), 197–213.
- Du, J. (2024). How interpreting influences defendants' participation: A discursive study of zero renditions and non-renditions in court interpreting. *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 286, 185–208. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2023-0054>
- Du, S. (2024). In defense of the Tyler rationale: As a model for curriculum development. *The Educational Review, USA*, 8(6), 837–841. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26855/er.2024.06.009>
- Dubinsky, J. M., & Hamid, A. A. (2024). The neuroscience of active learning and direct instruction. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2024.105737>
- Dubinsky, J. M., Roehrig, G., & Varma, S. (2022). A place for neuroscience in teacher knowledge and education. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 16(4), 267–276.

- Edwards, A. B. (1995). *The practice of court interpreting* (Vol. 6). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Building theories from case study research. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 532–550.
- Eisner, E. W. (1967). Educational objectives: Help or hindrance? *American Journal of Education*, 91(4), 549–560. <https://doi.org/10.1086/443718>
- Eksi, H. (2007). Teacher and student beliefs on constructivist instructional design: A case study. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 7(1), 30–39.
- El Nil el Fadil, H. (1985). Defining learning objectives for ELT. *ELT Journal*, 39(2), 96–100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/39.2.96>
- Ellenberg, J. H. (1994). Selection bias in observational and experimental studies. *Statistics in Medicine*, 13(5–7), 557–567.
- Ellis, A. K. (2014). *Exemplars of curriculum theory*. Routledge.
- Elmer, S., & Kühnis, J. (2016). Functional connectivity in the left dorsal stream facilitates simultaneous language translation: An EEG study. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 10, 60.
- Engel, A. K., Moll, C. K., Fried, I., & Ojemann, G. A. (2005). Invasive recordings from the human brain: Clinical insights and beyond. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 6(1), 35.
- Eraković, B. (2010). Successful communication in a beginner's translation class, or how to help students develop interpersonal sub-competence. *Buletinul Științific al Universității Politehnica din Timișoara, Seria Limbi Moderne*(9), 40–51.
- Ertmer, P. A., & Newby, T. J. (2013). Behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism: Comparing critical features from an instructional design perspective. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 26(2), 43–71.
- ES, C., AFdC, H., & ST, G. (2006). Building a motor simulation de novo: Observation of dance by dancers. *NeuroImage*, 31(3), 1257–1266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2006.01.033>

- Eşiyok, R., & Yağcı, S. E. (2023). Translation and power dynamics: Exploring the role of the Phanariot families in the Ottoman Empire—A case study of the Mavrocordatos family. In M. T. Öncü, A. Akın, & A. S. E. Yağcı (Eds.), *The history of translation and translators in the Ottoman Empire* (pp. 31–48). Logos.
- Estrada-Plana, V., Esquerda, M., Mangues, R., March-Llanes, J., & Moya-Higueras, J. (2019). A pilot study of the efficacy of a cognitive training based on board games in children with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: A randomized controlled trial. *Games for Health Journal*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1089/g4h.2018.0051>
- European Court of Justice. (2016). *Guide for freelance interpreters (ACIS) working at the Court of Justice of the European Union*. https://curia.europa.eu/common/interpret/Webcalendar/pdf/20160629_EN_aci_handbook.pdf
- Fam, M. (2018). *Acquiring higher levels of proficiency in less commonly taught foreign languages: A single case study of the impact of teacher perceptions of cognitive theories for instructional design* [Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University].
- Feagin, J., Orum, A., & Sjoberg, G. (1991). *A case for case study*. University of North Carolina Press.
- Felder, R., & Silverman, M. (1988). Learning and teaching styles in engineering education. *Engineering Education*, 78(7), 674–681.
- Ferreira, A., Schwieter, J. W., & Gile, D. (2015). The position of psycholinguistic and cognitive science in translation and interpreting. In *Psycholinguistic and Cognitive Inquiries into Translation and Interpreting* (Vol. 115, p. 1).
- Fischer, K. W., Goswami, U., Geake, J., & The Task Force on the Future of Educational Neuroscience. (2010). The future of educational neuroscience. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 4(2), 68–80. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-228X.2010.01086.x>
- Flin, R., O'Connor, P., & Crichton, M. (2013). *Safety at the sharp end: A guide to non-technical skills* (pp. 1–317). CRC Press.
- Flyvbjerg, B. (2006). Five misunderstandings about case-study research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12, 219–245. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800405284363>

- Fogarty, J. S. (1976). The Tyler rationale: Support and criticism. *Educational Technology, 16*(3), 28–32. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44418103>
- Fogassi, L., Ferrari, P. F., Gesierich, B., Rozzi, S., Chersi, F., & Rizzolatti, G. (2005). Parietal lobe: From action organization to intention understanding. *Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1106138>
- Fosnot, C. (2013). Constructing constructivism. In *Constructivism and the technology of instruction* (pp. 167–176). Routledge.
- Fournier, C. (1994). Interpreting in criminal cases in France. In H. Lane (Ed.), *Parallel views: Education and access for deaf people in France and the United States* (pp. 80–94). Gallaudet University Press.
- Futane, A. G., & Tech, B. (2021). Sampling technique in research methodology. In W. K. Yadav, G. S. Futane, S. H. S., K. R. Padma, E. Uma, & M. Sudarsha (Eds.), *Contemporary multi-disciplinary research trend* (pp. 228–251). Notion Press.
- Gagné, R. (1977). *The conditions of learning*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Gamal, M. (2019). Court interpreting. In M. Baker & G. Saldanha (Eds.), *Routledge encyclopedia of translation studies* (pp. 63–66). Routledge.
- Gardiner, A. (1953). The Memphite tomb of the General Haremhab. *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology, 39*(1), 3–12.
- Garretson, D. A. (1981). A psychological approach to consecutive interpretation. *Meta, 26*(3), 244–254.
- Garrison, K. E., & Schmeichel, B. J. (2019). Effects of emotional content on working memory capacity. *Cognition and Emotion, 33*(2), 370–377.
- Geake, J., & Cooper, P. (2003). Cognitive neuroscience: Implications for education? *Westminster Studies in Education, 26*(1), 7–20.
- Georgakis, A. (2017). *How to take good notes: The science behind note-taking*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Gericke, C., Soemer, A., & Schiefele, U. (2022). Benefits of mind wandering for learning in school through its positive effects on creativity. *Frontiers in Psychology, 7*, Article 774731. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.774731>

- Gerring, J. (2007). *Case study research*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gerver, D. (2013). *Language interpretation and communication* (Vol. 6). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Gerver, D., Longley, P., Long, J., & Lambert, S. (1989). Selection tests for trainee conference interpreters. *Meta: Translators' Journal*, 34(4), 724–735.
- Giambruno, C. (1997). Language mediation in the judicial system: The role of the court interpreter [Unpublished doctoral thesis]. University of Alicante.
- Gile, D. (2009). *Basic concepts and models for interpreter and translator training*. John Benjamins.
- Gilmartin-Thomas, J. F., Liew, D., & Hopper, I. (2018). Observational studies and their utility for practice. *Australian Prescriber*, 41(3), 82–85. <https://doi.org/10.18773/austprescr.2018.017>
- Gogolla, N. (2017). The insular cortex. *Current Biology*, 27(12), R580–R586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.05.010>
- Goldman-Eisler, F. (1972). Segmentation of input in simultaneous translation. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 1(2), 127–140.
- González, R. D., Vásquez, V. F., & Mikkelsen, H. (1991). *Fundamentals of court interpretation*. Carolina Academic Press.
- Gordon, L. (2017). Students as co-designers: Peer and instructional resources for novice users of ePortfolio. *International Journal of ePortfolio*, 7(2), 113–127.
- Gosper, M., & Ifenthaler, D. (2014). Curriculum design for the twenty-first century. In M. Gosper & D. Ifenthaler (Eds.), *Curriculum models for the 21st century* (pp. 1–14). Springer.
- Gran, L., & Fabbro, F. (1988). The role of neuroscience in the teaching of interpretation. *The Interpreters' Newsletter*, 1, 23–41.
- Greer, M. (2004). Strengthen your brain by resting it. *Monitor on Psychology*, 35(7), 60. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/julaug04/strengthen>

- Gross, J. J. (1998). Antecedent- and response-focused emotion regulation: Divergent consequences for experience, expression, and physiology. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 74(1), 224–237.
- Gross, J. J. (2002). Emotion regulation: Affective, cognitive, and social consequences. *Psychophysiology*, 39(3), 281–291.
- Groth, C. (2024). Apprenticeship as a model for teaching and learning in formal education. In I. T. S. C. Groth (Ed.), *Embodied learning and teaching using the 4E cognition approach* (pp. 103–112). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003341604-15>
- Gruberger, M., Ben-Simon, E., Levkovitz, Y., Zangen, A., & Hendler, T. (2011). Towards a neuroscience of mind-wandering. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2011.00056>
- Gu, J. (2024). Digital tools in language learning: Optimizing memory and attention for college students. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2024.2400384>
- Gunckel, K., & Moore, F. (2005). Including students and teachers in the co-design of the enacted curriculum. *Annual Meeting of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), Dallas*. <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED498676.pdf>
- Guskey, T. R. (2007). Closing achievement gaps: Revisiting Benjamin S. Bloom’s “Learning for mastery”. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 19(1), 8–31.
- Gustiani, S. (2019). Research and development (R&D) method as a model design in educational research and its alternatives. *Holistics Journal*, 11(2), 12–22.
- Guzzo, R. (1979). Types of rewards, cognitions and work motivation. *Academy of Management Review*, 4(1), 75–86.
- Haas, B. (2023). Education: From shame-based to brain-based. *Children’s Voice Magazine*, 32(1), 20–22.
- Hadziabdic, E. (2011). *The use of interpreter in healthcare: Perspectives of individuals, healthcare staff and families* [Doctoral dissertation, Linnaeus University Press].

- Hake, H. (2024). *Speed of forgetting: A computational biomarker and early indicator for memory impairment* (Publication No. 31330536) [Doctoral dissertation, University of Washington].
- Haladyna, T. M. (1994). *Developing and validating multiple-choice test items*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Halavac, J., & Orlando, M. (2015). Capturing and prescribing desirable attributes of community interpreting: Design and implementation of testing systems in four anglophone countries. In C. Zwischenberger & M. Behr (Eds.), *Interpreting quality: A look around and ahead* (pp. 297–324). Frank & Timme.
- Hale, S. (2006). Themes and methodological issues in court interpreting research. *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series—Themes in Translation Studies*, 5, 205–228.
- Hale, S. (2007). The challenges of court interpreting. *Alternative Law Journal*, 32(4), 198–202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1037969X0703200402>
- Hale, S. (2010). Court interpreting. In M. Coulthard & A. Johnson (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of forensic linguistics* (pp. 440–454). Routledge.
- Hale, S., & Gonzalez, E. (2017). Teaching legal interpreting at university level: A research-based approach. In L. Cirillo & N. Niemants (Eds.), *Teaching dialogue interpreting* (Vol. 138, pp. 200–216). John Benjamins.
- Hale, S. B. (2004). *The discourse of court interpreting: Discourse practices of the law, the witness, and the interpreter* (Vol. 52). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Hallaq, W. B. (2009). *Shari'a: Theory, practice, transformations*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hancock, B., Ockleford, E., & Windridge, K. (2009). *An introduction to qualitative research*. The NIHR RDS EM/YH. http://www.rds-yh.nihr.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2013/05/5_Introduction-toqualitative-research-2009.pdf
- Harahap, I. S., & Ginting, S. A. (2024). Teacher's reward and punishment in English learning process. *REGISTER Journal of English Language Teaching of FBS UNIMED*, 13(3), 47–51.
- Harfitt, G. J. (2012). Class size and language learning in Hong Kong: The students' perspective. *Educational Research*, 54(3), 331–342.

- Harris, B. (1992). Teaching interpreting: A Canadian experience. In *Teaching translation and interpreting* (pp. 259). John Benjamins.
- Hart, L. A. (1983). *Human brain and human learning* (Vol. 82283795). Longman.
- Hauser, C. (2019). Aristotle's explanationist epistemology of essence. *Metaphysics*, 2(1), 26–39. <https://doi.org/10.5334/met.24>
- Hausfather, S. (2001). Where's the content? The role of content in constructivist teacher education. *Educational Horizons*, 80(1), 15–19.
- Hayes, A. (2010). *The complete guide to lesson planning and preparation*. Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Hayes, A., & Hale, S. (2010). Appeals on incompetent interpreting. *Journal of Judicial Administration*, 20(2), 119–130.
- Healey, M., & Healey, R. L. (2018). "It depends": Exploring the context-dependent nature of students as partners' practices and policies. *International Journal for Students as Partners*, 2(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.15173/ij sap.v2i1.3472>
- Hendel, R. J. (2018). A new approach to training and software: Good instruction vs. good software. *Systems, Cybernetics and Informatics*, 4(16), 72–79.
- Henshall, C., Randle, H., Francis, N., & Freire, R. (2022). The effect of stress and exercise on the learning performance of horses. *Scientific Reports*, 12. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-03582-4>
- Hermann, E. (1998). *Über das Gedächtnis. Untersuchungen zur experimentellen Psychologie* (H. A. Ruger & C. E. Bussenius, Trans.). Thommes Press.
- Hervais-Adelman, A., & Babcock, L. (2019). The neurobiology of simultaneous interpreting: Where extreme language control and cognitive control intersect. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 1–12.
- Hervais-Adelman, A., Moser-Mercer, B., Michel, C. M., & Golestani, N. (2014). fMRI of simultaneous interpretation reveals the neural basis of extreme language control. *Cerebral Cortex*, 25(12), 4727–4739.
- Hewitt, W. E. (1995). *Court interpretation: Model guides for policy and practice in the state courts*. National Center for State Courts.

- Hileman, S. (2006). Motivating students using brain-based teaching strategies. *Agricultural Education Magazine*, 78(4), 18.
- Hlavac, J. (2013). A cross-national overview of translator and interpreter certification procedures. *Translation & Interpreting*, 5(1), 32–65.
- Ho, G. (2015). Adapting translator and interpreter training to the job market. In *Handbook of research on teaching methods in language translation and interpretation* (pp. 377–396). IGI Global.
- Hofer, G. (2005). Court interpreting: Practical experience and implications for training interpreters. *MuTra – Multidimensional Translation Conference Proceedings, Saarbrücken*.
- Hovland, D. L. (1992). Errors in interpretation: Why plain error is not plain. *Law & Inequality*, 11, 473.
- Howard-Jones, P. (2007). *Neuroscience and education: Issues and opportunities* (Vol. 2). Teaching and Learning Research Programme (TLRP).
- Howard-Jones, P. A. (2011). From brain scan to lesson plan. *Psychologist*, 24, 110–113.
- Howard-Jones, P. A., & Jay, T. (2016). Reward, learning and games. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 10, 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2016.04.015>
- Hruby, G. G. (2012). Three requirements for justifying an educational neuroscience. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8279.2012.02068.x>
- Huang, G., & Chen, Y. (2023). Effects of visual and cognitive load on user interface of electric vehicle—Using eye tracking predictive technology. *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*.
- Hubscher-Davidson, S., & Borodo, M. (2012). *Global trends in translator and interpreter training: Mediation and culture*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Huhtala, J. (2006). Adolescent cognitive development. In S. Feinstein (Ed.), *The Praeger handbook of learning and the brain* (Vols. 1–2, pp. 14–18). Praeger.

- Hunt-Gómez, C. I., & Moreno, P. G. (2015). Reality-based court interpreting didactic material using new technologies. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 9(2), 188–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399x.2015.1051770>
- Hussey, T., & Smith, P. (2002). The trouble with learning outcomes. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 3(3), 220–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787402003003003>
- Hyman, J. (1999). How knowledge works. *The Philosophical Quarterly*, 49(197), 433–451. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9213.00152>
- Ibrahim, N. (2007). Interpreting in Malaysia: An overview. *Puentes*, 7, 89–96.
- Ichikaw, J. J., & Steup, M. (2018). The analysis of knowledge. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy*. Stanford University.
- Ifeoma, I.-O. M., Chukwuebuka, N. E., & Chidinna, O. S. (2023). Effect of extrinsic reward system on employee's productivity in deposit money banks in Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 18(3), 458–469. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1092>
- Institute for Court Management. (2007). *Skills training for foreign language court interpreters: Does it increase the number of qualified interpreters?* National Center for State Courts.
- International Labor Organisation. (2015). Simultaneous interpreting. Retrieved January 18, 2019, from http://www.ilo.org/global/meetings-and-events/practical-information/WCMS_367969/lang--en/index.htm
- Islamova, A. H., & Xolmurodova, D. U. (2024). The history of the development of simultaneous translation in Uzbekistan. *Formation and Development of Pedagogical Creativity: International Scientific-Practical Conference (Belgium)*, 8, 12–17. <https://www.openconference.us/index.php/pedagogy/article/view/1819>
- Ismail Al-Alawi, A., Yousif Al-Marzooqi, N., & Fraidon Mohammed, Y. (2007). Organizational culture and knowledge sharing: Critical success factors. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 11(2), 22–42. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270710738898>
- Issaei, N. S. (2007). *Court interpreting in the Sultanate of Oman* [Unpublished thesis, American University of Sharjah].

- Jacobs, G. M., & Renandya, W. A. (2019). *Student-centered cooperative learning*. Springer.
- Jacoby, L. L. (1978). On interpreting the effects of repetition: Solving a problem versus remembering a solution. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, *17*(6), 649–667. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5371\(78\)90393-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5371(78)90393-6)
- James, W. (1918). *Principles of psychology* (Vol. 1). H. Holt.
- Jauk, E., Neubauer, A. C., Dunst, B., Fink, A., & Benedek, M. (2015). Gray matter correlates of creative potential: A latent variable voxel-based morphometry study. *NeuroImage*, *111*, 312–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.02.002>
- Jensen, E. (2005). *Teaching with the brain in mind*. ASCD.
- Jensen, E. (2008). *Brain-based learning: The new paradigm of teaching*. Corwin Press.
- Jeong, S.-H., & Hwang, Y. (2016). Media multitasking effects on cognitive vs. attitudinal outcomes: A meta-analysis. *Human Communication Research*, *42*(4), 599–618. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hcre.12089>
- Jonassen, D. H. (1991). Objectivism versus constructivism: Do we need a new philosophical paradigm? *Educational Technology Research and Development*, *39*, 5–14.
- Joswick, C., Skultety, L., & Olsen, A. A. (2023). Mathematics, learning disabilities, and learning styles: A review of perspectives published by the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics. *Education Sciences*, *13*(10), 1023. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/13/10/1023>
- Judicial Council of California. (2008). *Professional standards and ethics for California court interpreters*. Administrative Office of the Courts, Court Interpreters Program.
- Judicial Council of California. (2013). *Professional standards and ethics for California court interpreters*.
- Kaczmarek, L. (2010). Modelling competence in community interpreting: Expectancies, impressions and implications for accreditation [Doctoral dissertation, The University of Manchester].

- Kadric, M., & Stempkowski, M. (2024). *Legal interpreting and questioning techniques explained*. Routledge.
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. Macmillan.
- Kalina, S. (2000). Interpreting competences as a basis and a goal for teaching. [Details missing].
- Kalyuga, S. (2000). The interaction of visual and auditory cues in multimedia instruction. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 48(1), 23–41.
- Kamiński, J., Mamelak, A. N., Birch, K., Mosher, C. P., Tagliati, M., & Rutishauser, U. (2018). Novelty-sensitive dopaminergic neurons in the human substantia nigra predict success of declarative memory formation. *Current Biology*, 28(9), 1333–1343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.03.024>
- Kandel, E. R., Schwartz, J. H., & Jessell, T. M. (2013). *Principles of neural science*. McGraw-Hill.
- Kaplan, R., & Kaplan, S. (1989). *The experience of nature: A psychological perspective*. Cambridge University Press.
- Karagiorgi, Y., & Symeou, L. (2005). Translating constructivism into instructional design: Potential and limitations. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 8(1), 17–27.
- Karakitsiou, D. E., Markou, A., Kyriakou, P., Pieri, M., Abuaita, M., Bourousis, E., & Dimoliatis, I. D. K. (2012). The good student is more than a listener – The 12+1 roles of the medical student. *Medical Teacher*, 34(1), e1–e8. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159x.2012.638006>
- Kasonde, A. (2016). The changing role of the court interpreter-translator in Africa: The case of Zambia. *Comparative Legilinguistics*, 27, 21–32.
- Katsumi, Y., & Dolcos, S. (2020). Suppress to feel and remember less: Neural correlates of explicit and implicit emotional suppression on perception and memory. *Neuropsychologia*, 145, 106683.
- Kaufman, E., Akers, C., & Wittler, P. (2008). Engaging students with brain-based learning. *Techniques*, 50–55.

- Keddie, V. (2006). Case study method. In V. Jupp (Ed.), *The Sage dictionary of social research methods*. Sage.
- Kelley, P., & Watson, T. (2013). Making long-term memories in minutes: A spaced learning pattern from memory research in education [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 7(589). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2013.00589>
- Kempadoo, K. A., Mosharov, E. V., Choi, S. J., Sulzer, D., & Kandel, E. R. (2016). Dopamine release from the locus coeruleus to the dorsal hippocampus promotes spatial learning and memory. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, U.S.A.*, 113(51), 14835–14840. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1616515114>
- Kentli, F. D. (2009). Comparison of hidden curriculum theories. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 1(2), 83–88.
- Keystone Vignettes. (1894, November 26). *Scranton Tribune*.
- Khoury, O. (2017). Investigating the translation competence of graduates of bachelor degree programmes in Jordan [Unpublished thesis, Aston University].
- Kidd, T. T. (2009). *Online education and adult learning: New frontiers for teaching practices*. IGI Global.
- Kiguru, G. (2009). Court interpreting in Kenya: The ideal and the practice. *Proteus*, 5–11.
- Killingsworth, M. A., & Gilbert, D. T. (2010). A wandering mind is an unhappy mind. *Science*, 330(6006), 932. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1192439>
- Kim, J. S. (2005). The effects of a constructivist teaching approach on student academic achievement, self-concept, and learning strategies. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 6, 7–19.
- Kim, K., & Johnson, M. K. (2013). Extended self: Spontaneous activation of medial prefrontal cortex by objects that are ‘mine’. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 9(7), 1006–1012.
- Kiraly, D. C. (1995). *Pathways to translation: Pedagogy and process*. Kent State University Press.

- Kirschner, P. A., Sweller, J., & Clark, R. E. (2006). Why minimal guidance during instruction does not work: An analysis of the failure of constructivist, discovery, problem-based, experiential, and inquiry-based teaching. *Educational Psychologist, 41*(2), 75–86.
- Kliner, J. M., & Lemon, R. N. (2013). What we know currently about mirror neurons. *Current Biology, 23*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.10.051>
- Klubok, G. J. (2015). The error in applying the language conduit-agency theory to interpreters under the confrontation clause. *St. John's Law Review, 89*(4), 1399–1427. <https://scholarship.law.stjohns.edu/lawreview/vol89/iss4/10>
- Kohan, N., Soltani Arabshahi, K., Mojtahedzadeh, R., Abbaszadeh, A., Rakhshani, T., & Emami, A. (2017). Self-directed learning barriers in a virtual environment: A qualitative study. *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism, 5*(3), 116–123.
- Kolb, D. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice-Hall.
- Kolb, D. (2015). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Pearson Education.
- Kornmeier, J., & Susic-Vasic, Z. (2012). Parallels between spacing effects during behavioral and cellular learning. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 1–5*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2012.00203>
- Kosonogov, V. (2012). Why the mirror neurons cannot support action understanding. *Neurophysiology, 44*(6), 499–502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11062-012-9327-4>
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Krathwohl, D. R., & Anderson, L. W. (2009). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. Longman.
- Kridel, C. (2010). *Encyclopedia of curriculum studies* (Vol. 1). Sage.
- Kumar, R. (2008). *Research methodology*. APH Publishing Corporation.

- Kumar, R. (2019). *Research methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners*. Sage Publications.
- Kurz, I. (1992). 'Shadowing' exercises in interpreter training. In C. Dollerup & A. Loddegaard (Eds.), *Teaching translation and interpreting* (pp. 245–250). John Benjamins.
- Lai-Chong, L., & Ka-ming, W. (1996). Implications and problems of constructivism for instructional design. *Education Journal*, 23(2), 73–104.
- Lai, M., & Gonzalez, E. (2025). Mentoring interpreters of new and emerging languages for Australian courts and tribunals. *Multilingua*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/multi-2024-0062>
- Lalit, N., & Singh, V. (2025). Neuro Green: Case studies on the power of neuromarketing in promoting eco-investments. In S. Taneja, B. Chahal, A. Johri, E. Ozen, P. Kumar, & P.-I. G. S. P. (Eds.), *Neuromarketing's role in sustainable finance* (pp. 231–244). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-9117-4.ch012>
- Lambert, S. (1992). Shadowing. *Meta: Journal des traducteurs/Meta: Translators' Journal*, 37(2), 263–273.
- Lang, M. (2023). Learning styles and on-line learning analytics: An analysis of student behaviour based on the Honey and Mumford model. *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*.
- Lashley, C., & Barron, P. (2006). The learning style preferences of hospitality and tourism students: Observations from an international and cross-cultural study. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 25(4), 552–569.
- Laurel, D. S. (2008). *Jump-start your learning objectives* (Vol. 25). American Society for Training and Development.
- Lavie, N., Hirst, A., De Fockert, J. W., & Viding, E. (2004). Load theory of selective attention and cognitive control. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 133(3), 339–354.
- Lebese, S. J., & Ndhlovu, K. (2024). South African court interpreters' perceptions of the phenomenon of interpreting. *Southern African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies*, 42(sup1), S239–S257. <https://doi.org/10.2989/16073614.2024.2359960>

- Lee, J. (2009a). Interpreting inexplicit language during courtroom examination. *Applied Linguistics*, 30(1), 93–114. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amn050>
- Lee, J. (2009b). When linguistic and cultural differences are not disclosed in court interpreting. *Multilingua*, 28(4), 379–401. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mult.2009.017>
- Lee, J. (2015). Court interpreting. In H. Mikkelsen & R. Jourdenai (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of interpreting* (pp. 186–201). Taylor & Francis Books.
- Lehrer, K. (2018). *Theory of knowledge*. Routledge.
- LePera, N. (2011). Relationships between boredom proneness, mindfulness, anxiety, depression and substance use. *New Psychology Bulletin*, 8, 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e741452011-003>
- Li, M. (2023). A review of technology-enhanced Chinese character teaching and learning in a digital context. *Language Learning & Technology*, 27(3), 65–82. <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/5687c641-52f2-418f-9fba-aeaaa017b306/content>
- Li, Y., Yang, Y., Tang, A. C., Liu, N., Wang, X., Du, Y., & Hu, W. (2020). English spoken word segmentation activates the prefrontal cortex and temporo-parietal junction in Chinese ESL learners: A functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) study. *Brain Research*, 1733, 146693.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE Publications.
- Lindsay, G. W. (2020). Attention in psychology, neuroscience and machine learning. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2020.00029>
- Liu, B. (2015). A proposed curriculum roadmap for “marketable” undergraduate degrees in translation: It all begins with a digital sciences information session. *Current Trends in Translation Teaching and Learning E*, 2, 31–71.
- Liu, X., & Hale, S. (2018). Achieving accuracy in a bilingual courtroom: The effectiveness of specialised legal interpreter training. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 12(3), 299–321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399X.2018.1501649>

- Liu, Y., Luo, W., & Wang, X. (2023). Exploring the relationship between students' note-taking and interpreting quality: A case study in the Chinese context. *Frontiers in Education*.
- Loftus, G. (1972). Eye fixations and recognition memory for pictures. *Cognitive Psychology*, 3, 525–551.
- Lorca, D. S. (1995). The two definitions of knowledge [Master's thesis, Western Michigan University]. https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/masters_theses/3571/
- Lord, T. R. (1997). A comparison between traditional and constructivist teaching in college biology. *Innovative Higher Education*, 21, 197–216.
- Lowe, P. C. (2023). Mind wandering in daily life: A national experience sampling study of intentional and unintentional mind wandering episodes reported by working adults ages 25–50 [Doctoral dissertation, Antioch University].
- Luk, G., & Christodoulou, J. A. (2024). Cognitive neuroscience and education. In *Handbook of educational psychology* (pp. 383–404). Routledge.
- M'bayo, T. (2016). *Muslim interpreters in colonial Senegal, 1850–1920: Mediations of knowledge and power in the lower and middle Senegal River valley*. Lexington Books.
- Ma, J. (2013). A study of interpreting skills from the perspective of interpreting process. *Journal of Language Teaching & Research*, 4(6).
- Macleave, A., & Eghan, F. (2010). Use of cultural styles or repertoires of experience to guide instruction: What difference does it make? *Interchange*, 41(3), 233–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10780-010-9128-x>
- Macdonald, J. (1971). Needed theory and research. In R. Leeper (Ed.), *Curricular concerns in a revolutionary era* (pp. 105–109). Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Magdin, M., & Turčani, M. (2015). Personalization of student in course management systems on the basis using method of data mining. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology—TOJET*, 14(1), 58–67.
- Mager, R. F. (1961). On the sequencing of instructional content. *Psychological Reports*, 9(2), 405–413.

- Mager, R. F. (1962). *Preparing instructional objectives*. Center for Effective Performance Inc.
- Mahasneh, A. (2012). Translation curriculum evaluation in Jordan: A new perspective [Unpublished thesis, Binghamton University].
- Mahasneh, D., Shoqirat, N., Singh, C., & Hawks, M. (2021). From the classroom to Dr. YouTube: Nursing students' experiences of learning and teaching styles in Jordan. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 16(1), 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teln.2020.09.008>
- Mahmood Yenkimaleki, & Van Heuven, V. (2013). Effect of memory training on the quality of interpreting. *International Journal of English Language, Literature and Translation Studies (IJELR)*, 3(3), 79–86.
- Mahmoudi-Dehaki, M., & Nasr-Esfahani, N. (2025). Rethinking research in higher education: A scholarly exploration. In A. A. Mdikana (Ed.), *Enhancing research output in higher education: Research proposals, profiles, and publishing* (pp. 1–38). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-0806-7.ch001>
- Malterud, K., Siersma, V. D., & Guassora, A. D. (2015). Sample size in qualitative interview studies: Guided by information power. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1753–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>
- Manniche, J. (2012). Combinatorial knowledge dynamics: On the usefulness of the differentiated knowledge bases model. *European Planning Studies*, 20(11), 1823–1841. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2012.723423>
- Markic, J., & Gersak, M. U. (2017). Establishing relationships between judges and court interpreters. In S. Zupan & A. Nuc (Eds.), *Interpreting studies at the crossroads of disciplines* (pp. 157–172). Frank and Timme.
- Martin, C. (2011). Specialization in translation—Myths and realities. *Translation Journal*, 16(2).
- Martínez-Gómez, A. (2015). Non-professional interpreters. In H. Mikkelsen & R. Jourdenais (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of interpreting* (pp. 417–431). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315745381.ch26>
- Martínez-Gómez, A. (2018). Experiential learning in court interpreting education: A pilot internship in New York City courts. *CUADERNOS*, 740(33), 113–142.

- Maxwell, J. A. (2013). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Mayer, R. (2009). *Multimodal learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mayer, R. E. (2009). Constructivism as a theory of learning versus constructivism as a prescription for instruction. In *Constructivist instruction* (pp. 196–212). Routledge.
- McGeehan, J. (2001). Brain-compatible learning. *Green Teacher*, 64(7), 7–12.
- McKechnie, L. E. (2008). Observational research. In L. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods* (Vol. 1, pp. 573–575). Sage.
- McPherson, F. (2018). *Effective notetaking*. Wayz Press.
- Mekheimer, M. A. (2024). Working memory as a predictor of reading and listening comprehension in EFL college students: A reinvestigation. *Australian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.29140/ajal.v7n3.2076>
- Merriam, S., & Tisdell, E. (2016). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Merritt, D. J. (2008). Legal education in the age of cognitive science and advanced classroom technology. *Boston University Journal of Science & Technology Law*, 14, 39.
- Michael-Titus, A., Shorland, P., & Revest, P. (2010). *The nervous system*. Elsevier.
- Mikkelson, H. (1998). Towards a redefinition of the role of the court interpreter. *Interpreting*, 3(1), 21–45. <https://doi.org/10.1075/intp.3.1.02mik>
- Mikkelson, H. (1999). Interpreting is interpreting—or is it? Monterey Institute of International Studies.
- Mikkelson, H. (2013). Universities and interpreter certification. *Translation & Interpreting*, 5(1), 66–78.
- Mikkelson, H. (2017). *Introduction to court interpreting*. Routledge.

- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Millán, C., & Bartrina, F. (2013). *The Routledge handbook of translation studies*. Routledge.
- Ministry of Justice. (2014). *Qanon Al Tarajimaa Al Muhallafeen (Law of sworn translators)*.
http://www.moj.gov.sy/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=34:2014-05-05-13-33-23&catid=16:2013-08-15-09-29-42&Itemid=22
- Mirenowicz, J., & Schultz, W. (1994). Importance of unpredictability for reward responses in primate dopamine neurons. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 72(2), 1024–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.1994.72.2.1024>
- Mitchell, K. M. W., & Manzo, W. R. (2018). The purpose and perception of learning objectives. *Journal of Political Science Education*, 14(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2018.1433542>
- Moeketsi, R., & Wallmach, K. (2005). From sphaza to makoya!: A BA degree for court interpreters in South Africa. *Journal for Speech, Language and the Law: Forensic Linguistics*, 12, 77–108.
- Mohajan, H. K. (2018). Qualitative research methodology in social sciences and related subjects. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 7(1), 23–48.
- MoHE. (2022, June 23). The Higher Education Council makes important decisions related to the unified admission process for the academic year 2022/2023 and stagnant and saturated specializations. MoE. <https://bit.ly/saturated-stagnant>
- MoHE. (2023). Saturated and stagnant majors. MoHE. Retrieved 2023, from <https://www.admhec.gov.jo/mjr2017/OriginalMajorsLocal.aspx>
- MoJ. (2019, July 1). Small claims arrangement launched in Jordan. <https://www.moj.gov.jo/DetailsPage/MOJ/NewsDetails.aspx?ID=1134>
- MoL. (2023). National employment program. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from <http://tinyurl.com/4b9bx45n>
- Moody, B. (2014). What is a faithful interpretation? *Journal of Interpretation*, 21(1), 37–51. <https://digitalcommons.unf.edu/joi/vol21/iss1/4>

- Mooneyham, B. W., & Schooler, J. W. (2013). The costs and benefits of mind-wandering: A review. *Canadian Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 67(1), 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031569>
- Moore, K., & Craciun, G. (2024). Learning styles in the flipped classroom. *Marketing Education Review*, 34(3), 187–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10528008.2024.2319742>
- More, K. M., & Rane, A. R. (2016). Brain based learning: Holistic approach to teaching and learning. *International Journal of Educational Research Studies*, 2(9), 671–677.
- Morgan, C. (2004). The commission's draft proposal for a framework decision on certain procedural rights applying in proceedings in criminal matters throughout the European Union. In H. Keijzer-Lamboony & W. J. Gasille (Eds.), *Instruments for lifting language barriers in intercultural legal proceedings* (pp. 23–33). ITV Hogeschool voor Tolken en Vertalen.
- Morris, R. (1995). The moral dilemmas of court interpreting. *The Translator*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.1995.10798948>
- Morris, R. (1999). The face of justice: Historical aspects of court interpreting. *Interpreting*, 4(1), 97–123.
- Mosston, M. (1972). *Teaching: From command to discovery*. Wadsworth Publishing Company.
- Mulder, D. H. (n.d.). Objectivity. In *Internet encyclopedia of philosophy*.
- Mullins, A. (2025). Analysing the Shema in the light of the neurobiology of virtue. *Religions*, 16(2), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel16020113>
- Mulwa, E., & Mabule, D. (2023). Justice through interpreting in courts: A case of Machakos courts in Machakos county, Kenya. *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education*, 7(4), 821–833.
- Murayama, K., FitzGibbon, L., & Sakaki, M. (2019). Process account of curiosity and interest: A reward-learning perspective. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31, 875–895. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09499-9>

- Murphy, E. (2013). Sustainable development in SMEs. In S. O. Idowu, N. Capaldi, L. Zu, & A. D. Gupta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of corporate social responsibility* (pp. 2435–2442). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28036-8_59
- Myslinski, N. (2022). Why wait? Neuroscience is for everyone! *eNeuro*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.1523/eneuro.0372-20.2022>
- Nahar, N., & Cross, D. (2019). Students as partners in redesigning and delivery of the curriculum. *The 3rd EuroSoTL Conference: Exploring new fields through the scholarship of teaching and learning*, Bilbao.
- Namaziandost, E., Dehkordi, M. K., Alipour, P., & Tilwani, S. A. (2020). The impact of spaced and massed instruction on foreign language reading motivation and reading attitude among pre-intermediate EFL learners. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 22(2), 104–120. <https://doi.org/10.2478/JTES-2020-0019>
- National Accreditation Authority for Translators and Interpreters. (2016). *NAATI interpreter certification: Knowledge, skills and attributes*. <https://www.naati.com.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Interpreter-KSA-Paper.pdf>
- NCIEC. (2012). *Toward effective practice: Specialist competencies of the interpreter practicing within court and legal settings*. National Consortium of Interpreter Education Centers.
- Ness, I. J. (2023). Zone of proximal development. In *The Palgrave encyclopedia of the possible* (pp. 1781–1786). Springer.
- Ngarambe, T., & Ruvebana, E. (2023). Court interpreting practice in Rwanda: Challenges and strategies for fair justice. *The International Journal for Translation & Interpreting Research*, 108–124. <https://doi.org/10.12807/ti.115202.2023.a07>
- Nicholls, D. (2009). Qualitative research: Part two - methodologies. *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation*, 16(11), 586–592. <https://doi.org/10.12968/ijtr.2009.16.11.44939>
- Niska, H. (1999). *Text linguistic models for the study of simultaneous interpreting* (p. 76). Stockholm University.

- Niska, H. (2005). Training interpreters: Programmes, curricula, practices. In M. Tennent (Ed.), *Training for the new millennium: Pedagogies for translation and interpreting* (Vol. 60, pp. 35–64). Benjamins Translation Library.
- Noureen, G., Awan, R.-U.-N., & Fatima, H. (2017). Effect of brain-based learning on academic achievement of VII graders. *Journal of Elementary Education*, 27(2), 85–97.
- Nuccio, D. A., & Wesselmann, E. D. (2024). Impact of the seductive allure effect and trappings of science on perceptions of paranormal and pseudoscientific research. *The Social Science Journal*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03623319.2024.2343491>
- Nugroho, K., Carden, F., & Antlov, H. (2018). Forms of knowledge and policy influence. In *Local knowledge matters*. British University Press. <https://doi.org/10.51952/9781447348085.ch002>
- O'Day, D. H. (2007). The value of animations in biology teaching: A study of long-term memory retention. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 6(3), 217–223.
- O'Leary, K. D., & O'Leary, S. D. (1972). *Classroom management*. Pergamon.
- O'Doherty, J. P. (2004). Reward representations and reward-related learning in the human brain: Insights from neuroimaging. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, 14(6), 769–776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2004.10.016>
- Ogden, R. (2008). Bias. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Sage Publications.
- Ordóñez-López, P. (2015). A critical account of the concept of 'basic legal knowledge': Theory and practice. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 9(2), 156–172.
- Orozco-Jutorán, M. (2023). Dealing with legal terminology in court interpreting. In Ł. Biel & H. J. Kockaert (Eds.), *Handbook of terminology* (Vol. 3, pp. 570–592). John Benjamins Co.
- Orozco-Jutorán, M., & Sánchez-Gijón, P. (2011). New resources for legal translators. *Perspectives: Studies in Translatology*, 19(1), 25–44.
- Osborne, J. F. (1996). Beyond constructivism. *Science Education*, 80(1), 53–82.

- Osiejewicz, J., Podgórna, U., & Góra-Poland, Z. (2015). Legal education of court interpreters and sworn translators upon the Directive 2010/64/EU. *International Journal on New Trends in Education & their Implications (IJONTE)*, 6(1).
- Pachai, A. A., Acai, A., LoGiudice, A. B., & Kim, J. A. (2016). The mind that wanders: Challenges and potential benefits of mind wandering in education. *Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Psychology*, 2(2), 134–146. <https://doi.org/10.1037/stl0000060>
- Palma, J. (2023). When interpreting does not remove the language barrier: Interpreter ethics at odds with due process rights in US courts. *Texas Hispanic Journal of Law & Policy*, 29, 25–45.
- Paris, S. G., Lipson, M. Y., & Wixson, K. K. (1983). Becoming a strategic reader. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 8(3), 293–316.
- Perkins, D., & Blythe, T. (1994). Putting understanding up front. *Educational Leadership*, 51(5), 4–7.
- Phelps, E. A. (2004). Human emotion and memory: Interactions of the amygdala and hippocampal complex. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, 14(2), 198–202.
- Pienaar, M. (2006). Simultaneous interpreting as an aid in parallel-medium tertiary education. *Stellenbosch Papers in Linguistics Plus*, 33, 27–41.
- Pliatsikas, C. (2020). Understanding structural plasticity in the bilingual brain: The dynamic restructuring model. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 23(2), 459–471. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728919000130>
- Pöchhacker, F. (2010). The role of research in interpreter education. *Translation & Interpreting*, 2(1), 1–10.
- Pöchhacker, F. (2016). *Introducing interpreting studies*. Routledge.
- Prabhakar, J., Johnson, E. G., Nordahl, C. W., & Ghetti, S. (2018). Memory-related hippocampal activation in the sleeping toddler. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(25), 6500–6505. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1805572115>

- Pratama, E. Y., Lustyantje, N., & Murtadho, F. (2024). Brain-based project learning: Developing a formative assessment model in English-speaking instruction. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(6), 3041–3048. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i6.5959>
- Preston, A. R., & Eichenbaum, H. (2013). Interplay of hippocampus and prefrontal cortex in memory. *Current Biology*, 23(17), R764–R773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.05.041>
- Pym, A. (2005). Training translators—Ten recurrent naiveties. *Translating Today*, 2(1), 3–6.
- Pym, A. (2025). *Risk management in translation*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009546836>
- Pyo, S. (2005). Tourism analysis. *Analytical knowledge management for tourist destinations*, 10, 187–196.
- Rageth, O. (2024). Exemplified on an Alpine peripheral living lab in rural Switzerland. In B. Grabher & I. R. Lamond (Eds.), *Events as infrastructure and learning experiences*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003369165>
- Ramadhan, G., Rohana, N., & Pada, A. (2021). The effect of use animation media on learning outcomes in science learning of the fourth grade students Telkom Makassar. *International Journal of Elementary School Teacher*, 1(2), 175–183.
- Ranosa-Madrugno, M. (2014). Power and control in Philippine courtroom discourse. *International Journal of Legal English*, 2(1), 4–30.
- Rasmitadila, W., Widyasari, Prasetyo, T., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., & Aliyyah, R. R. (2021). General teachers' experience of the brain's natural learning systems-based instructional approach in inclusive classroom. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(3), 95–116. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2021.1436a>
- Raths, J. (1971). Teaching without specific objectives. In R. Leeper (Ed.), *Curricular concerns in a revolutionary era* (pp. 20–26). Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Reward. (2022). In *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved April 1, 2022, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english-arabic/reward>

- Richter, A., & Gruber, O. (2018). Influence of ventral tegmental area input on cortico-subcortical networks underlying action control and decision making. *Human Brain Mapping, 39*(2), 1004–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.23899>
- Roberson, L., Russell, D., & Shaw, R. (2012). A case for training signed language interpreters for legal specialization. *International Journal of Interpreter Education, 4*(2), 53–75. <http://www.cit-asl.org/new/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/IJIE>
- Roberts, T. G. (2003). An interpretation of Dewey's experiential learning theory.
- Robson, C. (1998). *Real world research*. Blackwell.
- Roffman, J. L., Tanner, A. S., Eryilmaz, H., Rodriguez-Thompson, A., Silverstein, N. J., Ho, N. F., Nitenson, A. Z., Chonde, D. B., Greve, D. N., Abi-Dargham, A., Buckner, R. L., Manoach, D. S., Rosen, B. R., Hooker, J. M., & Catana, C. (2016). Dopamine D1 signaling organizes network dynamics underlying working memory. *Science Advances, 2*(6), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1501672>
- Romberger, W. (2007). Skills training for foreign language court interpreters: Does it increase the number of qualified interpreters? [Study]. Institute for Court Management.
- Romero, G. (2012). Distinguishing the types of knowledge and the relationship to behavioral intentions and referral behavior.
- Rorty, A. (1991). The psychology of Aristotelian tragedy. *Midwest Studies in Philosophy, 16*(1), 53–72. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4975.1991.tb00230.x>
- Rosenbaum, P. R. (2002). Observational studies. In P. R. Rosenbaum (Ed.), *Observational studies* (pp. 1–17). Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-3692-2_1
- Rosenbaum, P. R. (2013). Using differential comparisons in observational studies. *CHANCE: Using data to advance science, education and society*. <https://chance.amstat.org/2013/09/3-rosenbaum/>
- Roth, W. M. (1994). Experimenting in a constructivist high school physics laboratory. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching, 31*(2), 197–223.

- Roulston, K., & Choi, M. (2018). Qualitative interviews. In U. Flick (Ed.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative data collection* (pp. 233–246). SAGE.
- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, I. S. (2005). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data* (2nd ed.). SAGE. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202106.0491.v1>
- Rubio, M. (2007). The impact of learning styles on boys' motivation and its effect on reading performance.
- Rueda, M. R., Pozuelos, J. P., & Cómbita, L. M. (2015). Cognitive neuroscience of attention: From brain mechanisms to individual differences in efficiency. *AIMS Neuroscience*, 2(4), 183–202.
- Rummel, A., & Feinberg, R. (1988). Cognitive evaluation theory: A meta-analytic review of the literature. *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, 16(2), 147–164.
- Rushton, S., & Juola-Rushton, A. (2008). Classroom learning environment, brain research and the no child left behind initiative: 6 years later. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 36, 87–92.
- Russel, D., & Takeda, K. (2015). Consecutive interpreting. In H. Mikkelsen & R. Jourdenais (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of interpreting* (pp. 96–111). Routledge.
- Russell, D. (2005). Consecutive and simultaneous interpreting. *Benjamins Translation Library*, 63, 135.
- Russell, D., Shaw, R., & Malcolm, K. (2010). Effective strategies for teaching consecutive interpreting. *International Journal of Interpreter Education*, 2, 111–119.
- Sahu, S. (2023). Experiencing others: The science of empathy. In S. Chetri, T. Dutta, M. K. Mandal, & P. Patnaik (Eds.), *Understanding happiness* (pp. 249–264). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-3493-5_11
- Salicru Lluçh, R. (2009). Translators, interpreters and cultural mediators in late medieval Eastern Iberia and western Islamic diplomatic relationships.
- Salimbene, F. P. (1996). Court interpreters: Standards of practice and standards for training. *Cornell JL & Pub. Pol'y*, 6, 645.

- Sanni, A. T. (2021). The challenge facing endogenous knowledge, education and research in Africa. In P. Neema-Abooki (Ed.), *Quality assurance in higher education in eastern and southern Africa*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003141235>
- Sassman, J. B. (2009). The experiential learning theory and interpreter education. *The International Journal of Interpreter Education*, 1(1). <https://tigerprints.clemson.edu/ijie/vol1/iss1/4>
- Sawyer, D. B. (2004). *Fundamental aspects of interpreter education: Curriculum and assessment*. John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://books.google.jo/books?id=eVk9AAAAQBAJ>
- Sayfuldeen, A. S. A. M. (2010). Discourse analysis for translation with special reference to the consecutive interpreter's training. *Journal of the College of Arts, University of Basrah*, 51, 25–40.
- Schooler, J. W., Mrazek, M. D., Franklin, M. S., Baird, B., Mooneyham, B. W., Zedelius, C., & Broadway, J. M. (2014). Chapter one—The middle way: Finding the balance between mindfulness and mind-wandering. In B. H. Ross (Ed.), *Psychology of learning and motivation* (Vol. 60, pp. 1–33). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-800090-8.00001-9>
- Schreiber, J. B. (2008). Pilot study. In L. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research* (Vol. 1 & 2, pp. 624–625). SAGE Publications Inc.
- Schüler, A., Scheiter, K., & van Genuchten, E. (2011). The role of working memory in multimedia instruction: Is working memory working during learning from text and pictures? *Educational Psychology Review*, 23, 389–411.
- Schweda-Nicholson, N. (1985). Court interpreting training: A growing need. The Eastern Michigan University Conference on Languages for Business and the Professions, Dearborn, MI.
- Schweda-Nicholson, N. (1986). A United Nations interpreter survey: The specialist/generalist controversy. *Multilingua: Journal of Cross-Cultural and Interlanguage Communication*, 5(2), 67–80.
- Scott, C. (2010). The enduring appeal of ‘learning styles’. *Australian Journal of Education*, 54(1), 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000494411005400102>

- Seleskovitch, D. (1992). Fundamentals of the interpretive theory of translation. In J. Plant-Moeller (Ed.), *Expanding horizons: Proceedings of the Twelfth National Convention of the Registry of Interpreters for the Deaf*. Silver Spring, MD: RID.
- Setton, R., & Dawrant, A. (2016). *Conference interpreting: A trainer's guide* (Vol. 121). John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Sharp, A. (2012). Jungian learning styles. In N. M. Seel (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of the sciences of learning* (pp. 1672–1675). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_368
- Shepard, R. T. (2007). Access to justice for people who do not speak English. *Indiana Law Review*, *40*, 643–657.
- Shepherd, J. (2019). Why does the mind wander? *Neuroscience of Consciousness*, *2019*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/nc/niz014>
- Sheynikhovich, D., Otani, S., Bai, J., & Arleo, A. (2023). Long-term memory, synaptic plasticity and dopamine in rodent medial prefrontal cortex: Role in executive functions. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, *16*, 1068271.
- Shih, K. P., Chen, H. C., Chang, C. Y., & Kao, T. C. (2010). The development and implementation of scaffolding-based self-regulated learning system for e/m-learning. *Educational Technology & Society*, *13*(1), 80–93.
- Shuttleworth, M. (2014). *Dictionary of translation studies*. Routledge.
- Silver, H. F., Strong, R. W., & Perini, M. J. (2007). *The strategic teacher: Selecting the right research-based strategy for every lesson*. ASCD.
- Siregar, N., & Siregar, N. (2023). Innovation Management Arabic Language Learning Based on Multimedia Audio Visual Animation Increase Learning Class VIII MTs N 4 North Padang Lawas. *Tadbir : Jurnal Studi Manajemen Pendidikan*, *7*(2), 369-390. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.29240/jsmp.v7i2.7060>
- Slavin, R. E. (1985). *Learning to cooperate, cooperating to learn*. Plenum.
- Smallwood, J., & Schooler, J. W. (2015). The science of mind wandering: Empirically navigating the stream of consciousness. *Annual Review of Psychology*, *66*, 487–518. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010814-015331>

- Society for Neuroscience. (2006). *Brain facts: A primer on the brain and nervous system*. Society for Neuroscience.
- Sousa, D. A. (2022). *How the brain learns*. Corwin.
- Splitter, L. J. (2009). Authenticity and constructivism in education. *Studies in Philosophy and Education*, 28, 135–151.
- Spurgeon, J. H. (1971). The student teaching experience: Learning by doing. *Journal of Health, Physical Education, Recreation*, 42(6), 51–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00221473.1971.10617119>
- Squire, L. R., & Kandel, E. R. (2009). *Memory: From mind to molecules*. Roberts and Company Publishers.
- Stacey, P., & Chan, K. (2021). Significant conversations at the intersection of co-teaching and student-faculty partnership. *International Journal for Academic Development*, 26(3), 360–372.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2021.1941035>
- Steffes, E. M., & Duverger, P. (2012). Edutainment with videos and its positive effect on long term memory. *Journal for Advancement of Marketing Education*, 20(1), 1–10.
- Stern, L. (2018). Legal interpreting in domestic and international courts. In *The Routledge handbook of language and superdiversity* (pp. 396–410).
- Stern, L., & Liu, X. (2019a). Ensuring interpreting quality in legal and courtroom settings: Australian language service providers' perspectives on their role. *Journal of Specialised Translation*, 32, 90–120.
- Stern, L., & Liu, X. (2019b). See you in court: How do Australian institutions train legal interpreters? *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 13(4), 361–389.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399X.2019.1611012>
- Stockard, J., Wood, T. W., Coughlin, C., & Rasplica Khoury, C. (2018). The effectiveness of direct instruction curricula: A meta-analysis of a half century of research. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 479–507.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654317751919>
- Stromberg, W. H., & Head, G. L. (1984). Court interpreter training in the language laboratory. *IALLT Journal of Language Learning Technologies*, 18(2), 6–20.

- Stroud, B. (2007). Our debt to Descartes. In *A companion to Descartes* (pp. 513–525). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470696439.ch30>
- Stuart, E. A. (2010). Matching methods for causal inference: A review and a look forward. *Statistical Science*, 25(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1214/09-STS313>
- Supreme Court of Wisconsin. (2004). *The Wisconsin court interpreters handbook*. www.wicourts.gov/circuit/courtinterpreter.htm
- Susanti, S. (2024). *English for law: Students handbook*. PT. RajaGrafindo Persada-Rajawali Pers.
- Suydam, M. N. (1985). Research report: The role of review in mathematics instruction. *ERIC/SMEAK Mathematics Educational Digest*, 33(1). <https://doi.org/10.5951/AT.33.1.0026>
- Svoboda, S. (2020). SimConsec: The technology of a smartpen in interpreting.
- Sweigert, R. I. (1969). The first step in educational problem solving: A systematic assessment of student benefits. *Planned leadership for evaluative development of goals for education*, San Dimas.
- Taba, H. (1971). *Curriculum development: Theory and practice*. Harcourt Publishers Ltd.
- Tampubolon, E. C. (2024). Unfair access to justice for non-Indonesian speakers. *Dialogia Iuridica Journal*, 16(1), 112–141. <https://doi.org/10.28932/di.v16i1.10039>
- Tamraz, J. C., Comair, Y. G., & Tamraz, J. (2004). *Atlas of regional anatomy of the brain using MRI*. Springer.
- Tandon, P. N., & Singh, N. C. (2016). Educational neuroscience: Challenges and opportunities. *Annals of Neurosciences*, 23(2), 63–65. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000443560>
- Tang, Y.-Y. (2017). *Brain-based learning and education: Principles and practice*. Academic Press.
- Taylor, P. H., & Richards, C. M. (2018). *An introduction to curriculum studies*. Routledge.

- The Crown Prosecution Service. (2019). Interpreters. Retrieved January 21, 2020, from <https://www.cps.gov.uk/legal-guidance/interpreters>
- Thousand, J. S. (1994). *Creativity and collaborative learning: A practical guide to empowering students and teachers*. Brooks Publishing Co.
- Tolosa-Igualada, M., & Echeverri, Á. (2019). Because something should change: Translator and interpreter training past, present and future. *MonTI: Monografías de Traducción y Interpretación*, (11), 29–46.
- Tommerdahl, J. (2010). A model for bridging the gap between neuroscience and education. *Oxford Review of Education*, 36(1), 97–109.
- Tompkins, A. W. (2007). Brain-based learning theory: An online course design model.
- Tormsen, D. (2015). 10 fascinating interpreters who changed history. Retrieved January 18, 2019, from <https://listverse.com/2015/05/11/10-fascinating-interpreters-who-changed-history/>
- Tosun, M., Akin, A., & Simsek, F. (2015). Courses on specialized field in undergraduate programs of translation & interpretation departments in Turkey: The importance of courses on specialized field in the specialization process of translator candidates. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 192, 4–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.06.001>
- Tsai, H. Y., Chen, K. C., Yang, Y. K., Chen, P. S., Yeh, T. L., Chiu, N. T., & Lee, I. H. (2011). Sunshine-exposure variation of human striatal dopamine D(2)/D(3) receptor availability in healthy volunteers. *Progress in Neuropsychopharmacology & Biological Psychiatry*, 35(1), 107–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2010.09.014>
- Turkington, C., & Harris, J. (2002). *The encyclopedia of memory and memory disorders*. Infobase Publishing.
- Tyler, R. (1959). *Basic principles of curriculum and instruction*. University of Chicago Press.
- Uden, L., Sulaiman, F., Ching, G. S., & Juan, J. (2023). Integrated science, technology, engineering, and mathematics project-based learning for physics learning from neuroscience perspectives. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1136246>

- uit Beijerse, R. P. (1999). Questions in knowledge management: Defining and conceptualising a phenomenon. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 3(2), 94–110. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673279910275512>
- UK Ministry of Justice. (2018). *Guide to language interpreter and translation services in courts and tribunals*. Ministry of Justice. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/764085/language-interpreter-translation-services-statisticsguide.pdf
- UN General Assembly Resolution 2/1. (1946, February 1). Rules of procedure concerning languages, A/RES/2(I).
- UNESCO. (2022). *Transforming technical and vocational education and training for successful and just transitions*. UNESCO. https://unevoc.unesco.org/pub/unesco_strategy_for_tvte_2022-2029.pdf
- United States Courts. (n.d.). Federal court interpreters. Retrieved December 10, 2019, from <https://www.uscourts.gov/services-forms/federal-court-interpreters>
- Van de Putte, E., De Baene, W., García-Pentón, L., Woumans, E., Dijkgraaf, A., & Duyck, W. (2018). Anatomical and functional changes in the brain after simultaneous interpreting training: A longitudinal study. *Cortex*, 99, 243–257.
- van Rooy, B. (2005). The feasibility of simultaneous interpreting in university classrooms. *Southern African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies*, 23(1), 81–90.
- van Touw, S. C. (2015). The effect of anticipation of reward on semantic processing: An N400 study [Master's thesis, Utrecht University].
- Verschuere, B. (2025). Lie detection: Science or pseudoscience? In *Legal and forensic psychology: What is it and what it is not* (pp. 17–28). Springer.
- Volker, C. (1995). Comments on government interpreters and translators in Papua New Guinea. *Bulletin of Gifu College of Education*, 30, 257–267.
- Volkow, N. D., Tomasi, D., Wang, G. J., Telang, F., Fowler, J. S., Logan, J., Benveniste, H., Kim, R., Thanos, P. K., & Ferré, S. (2012). Evidence that sleep deprivation downregulates dopamine D2R in ventral striatum in the human brain. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 32(19), 6711–6717. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0045-12.2012>

- Wahbi, G. (2018). A case study on students' ownership of learning and its effects on students' academic achievements [Master's thesis, The British University in Dubai].
- Walker, J., & Shaw, S. (2011). Interpreter preparedness for specialized settings. *Journal of Interpretation*, 21(1), 8.
- Walsh, M. (2001). *Research made real: A guide for students*. Nelson Thornes Ltd.
- Wang, D. (2014). Examining the challenges for legal interpreters in New Zealand courtroom settings [Master's thesis, Auckland University of Technology]. Unpublished.
- Wang, H. (2015). Error analysis in consecutive interpreting of students with Chinese and English language pairs. *Canadian Social Science*, 11(11), 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.3968/7755>
- Wang, J., & Hassan, H. (2024). Motivation in multimodal classroom learning: An empirical study of business English learners in China. *Global Business and Management Research*, 16(2), 104–113.
- Wang, M., & Finn, J. (2000). How small classes help teachers do their best. Temple University Center for Research in Education.
- Wästerfors, D. (2018). Observations. In U. Flick (Ed.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative data collection* (pp. 314–326). SAGE.
- Waugh, A., Grant, A., & Ross, J. (2001). *Ross and Wilson anatomy and physiology in health and illness*. Churchill Livingstone London.
- Weigand, E. (2014). Rationality of performance. *Philosophia Scientiæ*, 18(3), 247–268. <https://doi.org/10.4000/philosophiascientiae.1023>
- Wenden, A. L. (1995). Learner training in context: A knowledge-based approach. *System*, 23(2), 183–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0346-251X\(95\)00007-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0346-251X(95)00007-7)
- Wheeler, D. K. (1967). *Curriculum process*. Hodder and Stoughton.
- Williams, M., & Moser, T. (2019). The art of coding and thematic exploration in qualitative research. *International Management Review*, 15(1), 45–55.

- Willingham, D., Hughes, E., & Dobolyi, D. (2015). The scientific status of learning styles theory. *The Generalist's Corner*, 42(3), 226–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628315589505>
- Willingham, D., & Lloyd, J. W. (2007). How can brain imaging help education research [Unpublished manuscript]. University of Virginia, Department of Psychology and Curry School of Education.
- Willis, J. (2007). The neuroscience of joyful education. *Educational Leadership*, 64(9).
- Winters, C. (2001). Brain-based teaching: Fad or promising method. *Information Analysis*, 1–26.
- Witter-Merithew, A., & Nicodemus, B. (2010). Intentional development of interpreter specializations: Assumptions and principles for interpreter education. *International Journal of Interpreter Education*, 2(1), 135–147.
- Wolfe, P. (1998). Revisiting effective teaching. *Educational Leadership*, 56(3), 61–64.
- Wolfe, P. (2009). Brain research and education: Fad or foundation? www.PatWolfe.com
- Wolff, K., Friedhoff, R., Schwarzer, F., & Pucker, B. (2023). Data literacy in genome research. *Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202309.0079.v1>
- Wong, W. K. (2019). The role of preparation using case-related materials in court interpreting [Doctoral dissertation, University of New South Wales].
- Wright, J. P., Tibbetts, S. G., & Daigle, L. E. (2014). *Criminals in the making: Criminality across the life course*. Sage Publications.
- Wu, G., & Wang, K. (2009). Consecutive interpretation: A discourse approach. Towards a revision of Gile's effort model. *Meta*, 54(3), 383–642.
- Yamaoka, A., & Yukawa, S. (2020). Mind wandering in creative problem-solving: Relationships with divergent thinking and mental health. *PLOS ONE*, 15(4), e0231946. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231946>
- Yan, J. X., Pan, J., Wu, H., & Wang, Y. (2013). Mapping interpreting studies: The state of the field based on a database of nine major translation and interpreting journals (2000–2010). *Perspectives*, 21(3), 446–473.

- Yandow, R. (2007). Improving pedagogy through brain based learning [Unpublished master's thesis]. St. John Fisher College. https://fisherpub.sjfc.edu/mathcs_etd_masters/56
- Yi, R. (2024). Manner matters: Linguistic equity through a court interpreter in Australia. *International Journal for the Semiotics of Law - Revue internationale de Sémiotique juridique*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11196-023-10090-3>
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Yu, W., & van Heuven, V. J. (2013). Effects of immediate repetition at different stages of consecutive interpreting training: An experimental study. *Linguistics in the Netherlands*, 30(1), 201–213.
- Yunita, L. (2017). The effect of using animated video media on student activities and learning outcomes on digestive system materials at SMP 1 Darussalam, Banda Aceh [Unpublished thesis].
- Záňová, B. S. (2013). The court interpreters' role and the predicaments they might face [Unpublished master's thesis, Masaryk University].
- Zhou, X., & Lei, X. (2018). Wandering minds with wandering brain networks. *Neuroscience Bulletin*, 34(6), 1017–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12264-018-0278-7>
- Zrudlo, I. (2023). Why the learning styles myth appeals and how to persuade believers otherwise. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 132, 104266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104266>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

THE FOUR STYLES OF LEARNING AS USED IN THIS STUDY

*Adapted from Silver, Strong and Perini (2007)

Objective of Strategy Family	Teaching strategy family	Strategy	Objective of strategy	Example of hook
Making learning memorable	Mastery	New American lecture	Make lecturing interactive, brain-compatible and memorable by connecting prior knowledge with new knowledge?	What do you know about courts? What do you know about court interpreters? What makes them qualified?
		Direct instruction	-Learning steps defined -Modelling offered in videos: model answers and thinking aloud	- Learning steps in the written handbook and PowerPoint slides - Thinking aloud in videos (SUP1 and SUP10)
		Graduated-difficulty strategy	“Self-directed students” analyse the requirements of the task then choose the level that suits their own pace of learning.	You have three levels of difficulty of an interpretation task. You can decide which one you need to work on, and if you are looking for easier tasks, the trainer will prepare them for you. Once you feel bored, you can go to the higher level. If you feel frustrated, you go to the lower level. The model answers for all tasks are

				available and you can watch them any time if you wish.
Exercising reasoning and logic, to motivate curiosity and mystery	Understanding	Compare and contrast	Make conclusions and infer knowledge by discerning similarities, differences and patterns.	<p>I have an idea in my mind and am hiding it from you. In this exercise, try to reveal it. This video is what I call ‘This is Not’. Watch it, then discuss among yourselves what I mean by this is not.</p> <p>Second video: Now, this video is what I call “This is”. In comparison with the previous one, discuss the similarities/differences then come up with the idea that I am hiding in my mind.</p>
		Reading for meaning	Students read simple statements or comics to build a thoughtful interpretation about a concept.	I now want someone to read what is in the slide, then tell us what he/she understands and initiate a discussion.
Highlighting students’ abilities to imagine and create	Self-expressive	Inductive learning	Exploring topics and ideas by grouping them under labels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - You have a list of items on this slide. Can you group them into conceptual, situational and procedural knowledge? - You are the first choicer for courts as a court interpreter? Why does this happen?
		Metaphorical expression	Students use the human unique capabilities of linking things that are not alike.	Be like the sphinx. What does that mean as a court interpreter?

**APPENDIX B
PLAN FOR JORDAN SCCI TRAINING**

TLO	ELO	LS
Introduction	Setting expectations	Overview of the training
		Learning styles
		Role of the instructor
		Role of the students
		Types of knowledge
Situational knowledge	Courts in Jordan	Legal system in Jordan
		Court system in Jordan
		Jurisdictions of courts
	In the courtroom	Simple definition of small-claim court
		Settings of a small-claims court
		Participants in the courtroom
		Regulatory framework of court interpreting
		Regulatory framework of court interpreting
		Regulatory framework of court interpreting
	Court protocols for court interpreters	Appointment of court interpreters
		Neutrality
		Taking the oath
		Conflict of interest
		Attire
		Forms of addressing court officials
		Language conduit
		Classical Arabic
		Knowledge
		Knowledge
	Judge's qualities and functions	Personal knowledge
		Reasoning
		Establish facts
		Establish legal relations
		Establish source of obligation
		Issue a decision
		Rephrase testimonies and statements
		Samples of court decisions
Subject matter of disputes in a small claim		
Case claims		
Conceptual knowledge	Domain knowledge	Subject matter

		Technical terms
	Case-specific knowledge	Litigants
		Witnesses
	Legal knowledge	Legal terms
		Legal concepts: the Law, contracts, unilateral will, undue enrichment and tort
		Legal pragmatics
Procedural knowledge	Modes of court interpreting	Consecutive
		Whispering
		Sight translation
		Verbatim translation
		Summary interpreting: upon the judge's order, removing redundancies, false starts and the like.
	Dictation	Dictating court session reporter
	Language skills	Listening
		Speaking
		Reading
		Accuracy
	Memory skills	Note-taking
		Concentrating
	Management skills	Sequencing
		Self-correction
		Dealing with accents
		Asking for clarification
		Asking for repetition
		Interrupting
		Omission
		Addition
Change in meaning		
Opposite meaning		
	Unclear accents	
Drills	Three levels starting with a level where speech is divided into small chunks with no technical or legal terms. The modifier 'small' means less than 10 seconds. More difficult levels can either increase the chunk or add technical and legal terms.	
Glossary of terms		
ELOs can be made more specific depending on the needs and resources. Each ELO should show: Action, Condition and Criterion.		

**APPENDIX C
BRAINSTORMING SESSIONS**

Session No.	Date	Topics of discussion	Video exercises discussed
1	14/2/2022	1-Court interpreting 2-Scientific basis for instructional design 3-Constructivism and neuroscience 4-TLO1	TLO1-0-0; 1-1; 1-2; 1-3
2	20/2/2022	TLO2	TLO 2-1, 2-2, 2-3, 2-4, 2-5, 2-6, 2-6, 2-8, 2-9
3	1/3/2022	TLO3	TLO3-1; 3-2; 3-3; 3-4; 3-5; 3-6; 3-7
4	6/3/2022	TLO3 continued	TLO3-8; 3-9; 3-10; 3-11; 3-12; 3-13; 3-14; 3-15
5	8/3/2022	TLO4	Exercises
6	10/3/2022	TLO4 continued	Exercises
7	13/3/2022	TLO4 continued	Exercises

APPENDIX D
DEMOGRAPHICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS

1. The Professional Group

Category	Informant Code	Education	Years of Experience	Reported number of interpreted cases
Professional Group (interpreters)	INT1	BA	10+	3
	INT2	PhD	10+	4
	INT3	BA	25+	2
	INT4	BA	5+	4
	INT5	MA	5+	2
	INT6	BA	10+	6
	INT7	BA	10+	3
	INT8	BA	20	3
	INT9	BA	10+	3
	INT10	BA	10+	100+

2. The Experts Group

Category	Informant Code	Education	Years of Experience	
Expert Group (Lawyers)	EXP1	BA	10+	
	EXP 2	BA	10+	
	EXP 3	BA	10+	
	EXP 4	BA	10+	
	EXP 5	BA	10+	
	EXP 6	BA	10+	
	EXP 7	BA	10+	
	EXP 8	BA	10+	
	EXP9	BA	10+	
Category	Informant Code	Education	Years of Experience	Reported number of interpreted cases
Dual-Professional Group (lawyer interpreters)	DP1	MA	10+	+30
	DP2	MA	10+	3
	DP3	BA	10+	4
	DP4	BA	10+	3
	DP5	BA	10+	2
	DP6	BA	10+	3
	DP7	BA	10+	3

3. Students Group (Pilot Study)

SN	Level of education at the recruitment time
1	Graduated 2021
2	Graduated 2020
3	Fourth-year student
4	Fourth-year student
5	Graduated 2021
6	Graduated 2022
7	Graduated 2022
8	Fourth-year student

4. Students Group (Case Study)

SN	Level of education at the recruitment time
1	Graduated 2022
2	Graduated 2022
3	Graduated 2022
4	Graduated 2022
6	Graduated 2022
7	Graduated 2022
8	Graduated 2022
9	Graduated 2022
10	Graduated 2022
11	Graduated 2022
12	Graduated 2022
13	4 th year

5. Trainers' group

Qualification	Job
Master's degree	Court interpreter and community interpreter
Bachelor's degree	Court interpreter and community interpreter
Bachelor's degree	Certified court interpreter and community interpreter
Student	4 th year student
Bachelor's degree	Fresh graduate 2020
Master's degree	Former interpreter for an international agency
Bachelor's degree	Fresh graduate 2020

APPENDIX E
SAMPLE OF THE OBSERVATION SHEET

Situational knowledge					
Slide	Hook	Style	Basic result (if applicable)	Main result	Notes
47	What is the difference between dispute and litigation?	Understanding: C&C		STs discussed among themselves. Litigation is not only difference between two people but difference that came to the court.	
49	What similarities can you discern between tennis court and legal court?	Understanding: C&C		Generated knowledge Enthusiastic to answer More intensive cooperative learning	
50	What do you know about how a courtroom looks like? Furniture? Persons?	Mastery/ NAL		Imagined the court Generated knowledge Intensive cooperative learning	Led to a hypothesis to be tested
53	Bridge: A Jordan courtroom.			Correcting a hypothesis The first time to see a real courtroom. Not frustrated.	Ask students to reassess their hypothesis about how courtroom looks like.
54	What do you think the relationship is between the court interpreter and the judge, witness, plaintiff, defendant, scribe etc.?"?	Mastery/ NAL		Made guesses (hypothesis to be tested)	
55	Look at the slide images and explain in your words what it says.	Mastery/ NAL		Managed to explain	
56	Explain in your words the definition of 'situational knowledge' of SCCI	Mastery/ NAL		Answered by mentioning previously learnt information	Time, place, <u>attire</u> . It is important to apply the rules by coming on time, dressing professionally.

APPENDIX F
CONTENTS OF THE TRAINING MATERIAL DISTRIBUTED AMONG THE LECTURES.

Date	Number of attendees	Content discussed
9 February 2023	12	1.Introduction 2.Situational knowledge
12 February 2023	11	1. Situational knowledge continues 2. Preliminary interpreting drills
15 February 2023	12	1. Drills 2. Situational knowledge continues: Judge's job and management skills 3. Little conceptual knowledge
17 February 2023	12	Situational knowledge continues: Management skills
21 February 2023	5	Procedural knowledge
22 February 2023	6	Procedural knowledge
24 February 2023	8	Conceptual knowledge
26 February 2023	9	Conceptual knowledge

APPENDIX G
THE CONTENTS OF THE TRAINING VIDEOS USED IN THE CASE STUDY

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
1	TLO1-0-0	Interpreting for a teacher	-	-	Qualities of interpreters
2	TLO1-0-1	Violating the traffic rules	Why laws exist	-	Court's protocols
3	Drill 1.1	House rental dispute	Subject matter, technical & legal terms	Verbatim interpreting	Court's protocols
4	TLO1.1	House rental dispute	Subject matter, technical & legal terms	Verbatim interpreting	Taking the oath
5	Drill 1-2	Employee's dispute with company	Subject matter, technical & legal terms	Verbatim interpreting	An answer to a plaintiff's claims
6	TLO1-2	Employee's dispute with company	Subject matter, technical & legal terms	Verbatim interpreting	Taking the oath and an answer to a plaintiff's claims
7	TLO1-3	Computer repair	Subject matter, technical & legal terms	Verbatim interpreting	Taking the oath and an answer to a plaintiff's claims
8	TLO2-1	A 'this is not' example of a court interpreter	-	-	Qualities of interpreter and appointment
9	TLO2-2	A 'this is' example of a court interpreter	-	-	Qualities of interpreter and appointment
10	TLO2-3	Tasks of a court interpreter	-	Interpreting and sign-interpreting	Court's protocols
11	TLO2-4	A lawyer makes an objection	Legal terms	Act as a cultural mediator	Follow court instructions
12	TLO2-5	A 'this is not' example of a language conduit	Technical terms	Embellishment and lack of neutrality	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
13	TLO2-6	A 'this is not' example of a language conduit	Technical terms	Asking for permission	Court's protocols
14	TLO2-7	A 'this is' example of a language conduit	Technical terms	Asking for permission	Court's protocols
15	Drill 2-6	Asking for clarification drill			
16	Drill 2-6-B	Asking for repetition			
17	TLO2-8	Dentist's bill dispute	Technical terms and legal effects of omissions	Omissions	Court's protocols
18	TLO2-9	Employee's claim	Technical terms and legal effect	Interpreters' self-correction	Court's protocols
19	TLO2-10	Legal relation	Technical terms and legal effect	Change in meaning	Respecting the due process
20	TLO2-11	Legal relation	Technical terms and legal effect	Change in meaning	Respecting the due process
21	TLO2-12	Legal relation	Technical terms and legal effect	Change in meaning	Respecting the due process
22	TLO2-13	Fraud and deception 'this is'	Technical terms and metaphorical expressions	Verbatim interpreting	Court's protocols
23	TLO2-14	Fraud and deception 'this is not'	Technical terms and metaphorical expressions	Verbatim interpreting	Court's protocols
24	TLO2-15	Fraud and deception	Technical terms and metaphorical expressions	Verbatim interpreting	Court's protocols
25	TLO2-16	Construction work dispute	Technical and legal terms and metaphorical expressions	Verbatim interpreting	Court's protocols
26	TLO2-17	House renovations	Technical terms	Interpreting irrelevant statements	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
27	TLO2-18	Asking for a reward		Asking for a clarification	Court's protocols
28	TLO2-19	Dispute with landlord	Technical and legal terms	Non-verbal communication	Court's protocols
29	TLO2-20	Dispute with landlord	Technical and legal terms	Non-verbal communication	Court's protocols
30	TLO3-01	Spare parts issues	Technical and legal terms	Errors in interpreting	Court's protocols
31	TLO3-02	Spare parts issues	Technical and legal terms	Errors in interpreting	Court's protocols
32	TLO3-03	Officious acts	Technical terms	Embellishment	Court's protocols
33	TLO3-05	Unjustified firing of an employee	Technical terms and metaphorical expressions	Interpreting metaphorical expressions / legal effect of words that change the case outcomes'	Court's protocols
34	TLO3-1	Definition of a contract	Legal terms	Listening and concentration	Distractors of place
35	TLO3-2	Definition of a contract	Legal terms	Listening and concentration	Distractors of place
36	TLO3-3	Dentist bill dispute	Technical terms and legal obligations	Note-taking and conveying the same legal effect	Court's protocols
37	TLO3-4	Dentist bill dispute	Technical terms and legal obligations	Note-taking and conveying the same legal effect	Court's protocols
38	TLO3-5	Dentist bill dispute	Technical terms and legal obligations	Note-taking and conveying the same legal effect	Court's protocols
39	TLO3-6	Renovation works	Technical terms	Note-taking	Court's protocols
40	TLO3-7	Renovation works	Technical terms	Note-taking	Court's protocols
41	TLO3-8	Rental fees dispute	Technical terms	Asking litigant to chunk the statement	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
42	TLO3-9	Rental fees dispute	Technical and legal terms	Interrupting the litigant	Court's protocols
43	TLO3-10	Dispute with landlord	Technical and legal terms	Self-correction	Court's protocols
44	TLO3-11	Rental fees dispute	Technical and legal terms	Sequencing	Court's protocols
45	TLO3-12	Work contract dispute	-	Asking to be released from the interpreting task	Court's protocols
46	TLO3-13	Mobile phone payment	Technical and legal terms	Summary	Court's protocols
47	TLO3-14	Mobile phone payment	Technical and legal terms	Summary	Court's protocols
48	TLO3-15	Mobile phone payment	Technical and legal terms	Summary	Court's protocols
49	TLO3-16	Unfair dismissal	Technical and legal terms	Note-taking	Court's protocols
50	TLO4-1	Elements of a contract (This is not)	Legal concepts	Interpreting using the procedural skills	-
51	TLO4-2	Contract elements (This is)	Legal concepts	Interpreting using the procedural skills	-
52	TLO4-3	Rental contract dispute-price	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
53	TLO4-4	Rental contract dispute-price	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
54	TLO4-5	Contract dispute-price	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
55	TLO4-6	Mutual assent	Legal concept: Dispute based on mutual assent	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
56	TLO4-7	Mutual assent	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
57	TLO4-8	Mutual assent	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
58	TLO4-9	Dispute on computer procurement	Legal concept: Dispute based on object	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
59	TLO4-10	Dispute on computer procurement	Legal concept: Dispute based on object	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
60	TLO4-11	Dispute on computer procurement	Legal concept: Dispute based on object	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
61	TLO4-12	Medical negligence	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
62	TLO4-13	Medical negligence	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
63	TLO4-14	Medical negligence	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
64	TLO4-15	Rental dispute	Legal concept: Dispute based on	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
			unilateral will		
65	TLO4-16	Rental dispute	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
66	TLO4-17	Rental dispute	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
67	TLO4-18	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
68	TLO4-19	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
69	TLO4-20	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
70	TLO4-21	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
71	TLO4-22	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on unilateral will	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
72	TLO4-23	Dispute on a gift	Legal concept: Dispute based on	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
			unilateral will		
73	TLO4-24	Rescinding an obligation	Legal concept: Dispute based on contract price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
74	TLO4-25	Rescinding an obligation	Legal concept: Dispute based on contract price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
75	TLO4-26	Rescinding an obligation	Legal concept: Dispute based on contract price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
76	TLO4-27	Illegal dismissal	Legal concept: law as a source of obligation	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
77	TLO4-28	Illegal dismissal	Legal concept: law as a source of obligation	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
78	TLO4-29	Illegal dismissal	Legal concept: law as a source of obligation	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
79	TLO4-30	Paying medical fees for another person	Legal concept: Dispute based on undue enrichment	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
80	TLO4-31	Undue enrichment	Legal concept: Dispute based on undue enrichment	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
81	TLO4-32	Undue enrichment	Legal concept: Dispute based on undue enrichment	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols

SN	Video number	Content	Conceptual	Procedural	Situational
82	TLO4-33	Damage to a house	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
83	TLO4-34	Damage in a car accident	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
84	TLO4-35	Damage in a car accident	Legal concept: Dispute based on tort	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
85	TLO4-36	Damage in a car accident	Legal concept: Dispute based on contact price	Interpreting using the procedural skills	Court's protocols
86	SUP1	Labor relations	Labor relations	-	Judge's legal inferencing
87	SUP2	Deleted	-	-	-
88	SUP3	Contract	Legal jargon	Self-correction	
89	SUP4	Contract	Legal jargon	Self-correction	
90	SUP5	Tort	Student's contribution		
91	SUP6	Buying a computer	Contract	-	-
92	SUP7	Construction works	Contract	-	-
93	SUP8	Cooperative learning			
94	SUP9	House renovation	-	Summary	Asking for redirecting the oath
95	SUP10	Internet services/ Student's contribution	Contract	Verbatim interpreting	Judge's rephrasing
96	SUP11	Internet services/ Student's contribution	Contract	Summary	-
97	SUP12	Mobile phone repair/ student's contribution	Contract and Tort	Summary	-

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Abu-Risha, M. Y., & Jaganathan, P. (2021). An analysis of responses of Jordan courts to objections based on language interpreting issues. *Perspectives*, 29(4), 539-553. doi:10.1080/0907676X.2020.1862261